

Methods To Preserve Social Networks At Emergency Shelters

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Declaration

This thesis is the result of my own work and includes nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration except as declared in the preface and specified in the text. It is not substantially the same as any work that has already been submitted before for any degree or other qualification except as declared in the preface and specified in the text. It does not exceed the prescribed word limit for the Earth Sciences and Geography Degree Committee.

Abstract

During large-scale disasters, social structures are disrupted. The current focus of emergency management is to ensure that people evacuate safely. Lost in the process is a mechanism for keeping existing social structures intact, despite substantial evidence that maintaining social structures during and after disasters is beneficial. Instead of displaced people self-assembling at emergency shelters, where the social composition may appear somewhat random, this research introduces algorithms incorporating graph and hypergraph partitioning to reunite displaced people with their friends, family, and communities within shelters without unduly prejudicing the speed and efficiency required during evacuations. The research further investigates how to achieve this result dynamically, by assessing real-time information flows and readjusting recommended shelter locations mid-evacuation, all the while maintaining social connections tailored for each individual.

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Chapter 1

Evacuations Reimagined

Social support structures allow people to cope with difficulties in their everyday lives. However, during a disaster, these support structures get disrupted. Emergency management at present takes no account of this, concentrating instead on the physical necessities of clearing people out of disaster zones and hoping that people will deal with the social consequences if they are provided just with physical support. This leads to various problems: older people are left bereft of their extended families or neighbours that they depend upon to survive (Aldrich, 2012), people with long-term medical conditions that were cared for in the community lose their connections (Aldrich & Benson, 2008; Peek & Stough, 2010), families may become separated, friends lost—the social networks that people rely on is no longer accessible.

This research focuses on how to rewire displaced people's latent social networks and support systems at emergency shelters. Instead of strangers congregating at shelters during large-scale evacuations, this research reexamines mobility not as a divisive process but as a catalyst for reorganising people. For example, children from the same school can be directed to the same emergency site. Neighbourhood, religious, and workplace communities can all be kept intact, allowing displaced people to take advantage of longstanding histories and social capital.

With this intention in mind, the research lays a foundation for designing algorithms that recommend to displaced people specific emergency shelters to visit. The underlying shelter assignment problem is understood within this research as a graph or hypergraph partitioning problem. Beginning with displaced people's social network, where nodes represent displaced people and where edges and hyperedges respectively represent individual and communal social affiliations, the basic idea is to construct a k -way partitioning of the original network, i.e., to split this "network" (whether being a graph or hypergraph) roughly equally across k emergency shelters while minimising the number of edges or hyperedges cut. This will effectively preserve as much network structure as possible within shelters. For this algorithm to operate, participants must register their social network, preferably before a disaster occurs, and displaced people must choose to comply with the shelter location recommendation to realise the full benefits. However, one must emphasise that shelter assignments—in contrast to some evacuation orders—are not a mandate but a recommendation.

If reuniting people with friends and family at emergency shelters is indeed beneficial, and the goal is to facilitate this outcome with an algorithm, then success belongs not simply to algorithm performance but to its adoption. A socially oriented shelter assignment algorithm

must contend with, both methodically and objectively, the fact that people physically travel to shelters. Travel may not happen all at once and could be its own hardship. Against this reality, the research first reflects on the appropriateness of facilitating social outcomes by exploring travel time as both a competing and integrative objective. The research then focuses on the challenge of people evacuating at different times by introducing several methods to generate and disseminate shelter assignments to those ready to evacuate (upon request), that is, absent full knowledge of who will eventually require shelter. Lastly, as generating and disseminating shelter assignments in real time is computationally demanding, the research proposes a method to improve algorithm effectiveness when an algorithm does not have time to converge on a best solution.

What constitutes an acceptable travel time to emergency shelters is deeply contextual. In order to create a backdrop for an evacuation—one realistic enough for people to relate with the environmental, infrastructural, and human interactions as well as envision themselves and others making evacuation decisions—this research begins with a simulation of everyday life in the greater Portland, Oregon area. Informed by real-world datasets, the activities and locations of roughly 750,000 people are represented every second of a nominal day. Given the time people spend together during these activities, the research derives a city-wide social network. By simulating the fastest route between activities (based on traffic analysis), the research derives the location of people not only at activities but also between activities at any given time. Furthermore, the research is privy to Red Cross shelter locations and their capacities throughout the greater Portland area and has employed software used by emergency management for hazard risk assessment, namely HAZUS-MH (USEHAZUS, n.d.-b), to simulate and evaluate the repercussions of a magnitude 6.8 earthquake along a reverse-slip fault that runs through the city. Combining this information, one can probabilistically select people who will return home to find their living situation uninhabitable and then, along with their family, depart for either a friend's home, a Red Cross shelter, or a destination outside the city.

While the data collected richly informs a representation of who requires shelter, one cannot further interpret from it the decision-making processes behind why people visit particular shelters, or to posit an overgeneralisation, one cannot easily discredit the premise that all people will choose to visit their nearest shelter (but can speculate that other motives likely exist). The introduction of socially oriented shelters alters the decision-making process, bringing into focus new and potentially conflicting factors that are uniquely personal—social embeddedness, mobility, coping mechanisms, cultural worldview (e.g., “saving face”), etc.—

and a need for greater contextualisation (e.g., specifying the duration of stay at shelters). Acknowledging the limitations of the data collected, this research defines a range of possible evacuation outcomes, bounding what would likely happen in terms of social connections preserved and travel time when people decide for themselves which shelters to visit. This is achieved by simulating three what-if scenarios, where everyone who requires shelter is assigned respectively to “nearest,” “social,” and “random” shelters. Recognising that socially oriented shelter assignments do not account for travel time, and in this respect are no better than random,¹ this research introduces a fourth scenario, “social–nearest” shelters, where social is the primary and nearest is the secondary objective. By simulating this latter scenario, the research not only establishes a reasonable upper bound of what is socially achievable (effectively replacing the purely social scenario) but also reduces the polarity between social and nearest shelters as discrete choices.

For each of the above what-if scenarios, while calculating social connections at Red Cross shelters is straightforward, calculating travel time to shelters requires knowing how typical traffic patterns become disrupted. The research simulates emergent traffic conditions (vehicle-to-vehicle interactions) within which evacuees must navigate using agent-based models (ABMs).² To summarise the results, if people visit nearest shelters, they will travel on average two hours and reunite with 3.69% of their social network. If people visit random shelters, then relative to nearest shelters, they will travel an additional 40 minutes and reunite with less than 1% of their social network. If people visit social–nearest shelters, then relative to nearest shelters, they will travel an additional 16 minutes and reunite with 71.28% of their social network. In the case of social–nearest shelter assignments, due to geospatial proximity between social acquaintances, the research additionally demonstrates that while certain people may not be assigned to their nearest shelter, they are nevertheless assigned to nearby shelters via their social acquaintances. The presented results frame what could happen with and without introducing a social objective. They do not, however, speak to what makes a shelter choice-worthy and, toward future work, the need for designing algorithms with even greater

¹ To qualify the concept of random shelters, this means that families (as units travelling together) are assigned to random shelter locations, irrespective of everyone else. Whether families are assigned to random shelter locations or whether communities are assigned to random shelter locations (i.e., social shelters), the distance travelled to shelters is the same. That said, the time spent travelling to shelters could be different. For example, if people from the same community/neighbourhood are travelling in the same direction toward an assigned shelter, then their collective movement could contribute to traffic congestion either for themselves and/or others travelling to shelters. When calculating average travel time to shelters, this research treats random shelter assignments as a proxy for social shelter assignments.

² For an overview of ABMs, please see Bruch and Atwell (2015) and, with emphasis on ABMs representing real-world places and actors, O’Sullivan (2008).

customisation. Shifting to the perspective of individual displaced people, the research concludes the Portland study by following a family within the simulation and detailing what different shelter choices would mean for them.

Turning to real-time methods, with respect to people deciding for themselves whether to visit emergency shelters and request shelter assignments, one would have to generate and disseminate these assignments within a set timeframe, spanning the moment people communicate their need for shelter to the moment they depart for shelter. If this window of time is different for each person and non-overlapping, then so as to not delay the evacuation, one would necessarily have to generate and disseminate these assignments with incomplete knowledge of who requires shelter. As a means to produce shelter assignments expeditiously, the research proposes to insert early within the evacuation timeline a question for those impacted by a disaster: “Do you require shelter?” For people who respond “yes,” one could generate shelter assignments for them in a streaming manner. Alternatively, one could generate shelter assignments from a prediction of who requires shelters, where a real-time sample of “yes” and “no” responses would serve to validate the prediction, allowing one to continue or discontinue its use and/or serve as data to continuously create the prediction anew. Moreover, the question could become part of an ongoing dialogue, one that dissociates (conceptually and temporally) the *decision* to visit a shelter from the *action* of travelling to a shelter. In practice, this would minimise the amount of time needed to validate predictions and maximise the number of responses that inform shelter assignments.

The literature on graph and hypergraph partitioning offers a wealth of methods, some of which could support different, if not multiple visions, on how to realise socially oriented shelter assignments. As for integrating partitioning methods, the research first examines attributes or “features” of existing partitioners and what purpose they could serve within the given context, bearing in mind that not all features are relevant or suitable. With consideration for the upcoming experiments, the research then proposes a framework that combines specific partitioning features into a highly adaptable/parameterisable shelter assignment algorithm. At the core of this algorithm, the research further identifies a suitable existing graph partitioner, restreaming FENNEL (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013), whose internal parameters are explained, adjusted, and extended for implementation.

Interfacing with the partitioner is data; how this data is interpreted and managed owes to other algorithmic processes. Shifting attention to these processes, the research is positioned to not only fully describe a variety of shelter assignment methods but, with a more peripheral view, the relationships between these methods. Given that hazard risk assessment tools, such

as HAZUS-MH, can output location-based probabilities of people requiring shelter, this research first develops a method to generate shelter assignments where the data passed to the partitioner represents these probabilities. The research refers to this method as the “static prediction strategy.” The research additionally develops two real-time methods that can take over when a prediction is determined inaccurate, either due to the prediction being poorly conceived and/or due to variation in probabilistic outcomes. As for the first of these real-time methods, the research proposes taking the social connections between people who respond “yes” to requiring shelter and directly passing them to the partitioner, a method referred to as the “real-time batch strategy.” Turning to the second real-time method, the research posits an assumption that spatial proximity exists between people who require shelter. Upon collecting real-time “yes” and “no” responses and associating these responses with household locations, the research proposes taking what is now geospatial data and passing it to a generalised additive model (GAM) to continually update a location-based probability map of households that may soon require shelter. These probabilities are then passed to the partitioner, the results of which are disseminated as shelter assignments for those ready to evacuate. This method is referred to as the “dynamic prediction strategy.”

To evaluate the strategies, the research presents an analytical method to showcase the trade-off between conflicting objectives, namely fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance. This is accompanied by a risk assessment of switching between strategies as well as a discussion of the benefits and drawbacks of using each strategy individually and in combination. As pertains to the simulated evacuations, if one can predict who requires shelter with at least 80% accuracy, then one should arguably implement the static prediction strategy and then switch to the real-time batch strategy mid-evacuation. This will produce better results than implementing either strategy alone. On the other hand, if the prediction is less than 80% accurate, then the benefits of switching between strategies is minimal, and implementing the real-time batch strategy from the outset is advantageous. As a standalone strategy, the dynamic prediction strategy outperforms all others tested, including multiple strategies implemented sequentially. In practice, however, the way this strategy generates predictions does not account for response bias, i.e., people are more likely to respond “yes” when they need shelter than “no” when they do not. Toward future work, the research proposes using “yes-only” responses to generate predictions and argues that certain prediction methods found within species distribution models (SDMs) are particularly well-suited (if not better suited) for the presented evacuation context.

As for another dimension of algorithm effectiveness, people might not comply with shelter assignments if receiving these assignments delays their departure. Assuming computational efficiency is already maximised, the research explores whether altering the sequence/order of people could improve outcome measures when restreaming FENNEL does not have time to efficiently converge on a best solution. With people assigned to shelters one at a time, the research asks whether people with certain network characteristics or positions within a network could act as “seeds” to positively (or not negatively) influence subsequent shelter assignments toward a more ideal partitioning. To this end, different interpretations of what makes people important or central within a social network have contributed to what social network analysis (SNA) refers to as *centrality indices*, and from a selection of these indices, the research created 115 different rank-based centrality orderings, which were then passed to restreaming FENNEL. Results obtained through statistical analysis suggest that randomly ordering people is highly effective, relatively speaking, and that ordering people in other ways would primarily benefit partitioning imbalance (as opposed to fraction of edge cut). Furthermore, along a Pareto front that describes the best trade-offs between partitioning imbalance and fraction of edges cut, one can identify multiple ways of ordering people—for example, based on *betweenness centrality*—that would significantly improve partitioning imbalance without consequence to fraction of edges cut. The research further demonstrates that these “beneficial” ways of ordering people would have no significant adverse effect on outcome measures if restreaming FENNEL did in fact have time to converge on a best solution. Against the prevailing literature, where the authors of FENNEL and restreaming FENNEL respectively find no evidence to order data (see Nishimura & Ugander, 2013; Tsourakakis, 2014), this research takes a more expansive look at the topic and finds that rank-based centrality orderings have the potential to improve partitioning results.

Looking strictly at partitioning as it currently exists, one can never ideally solve the problem of preserving displaced people’s social networks. Indeed, partitioning is an NP-complete problem, solved with a heuristic, and in this case, operating on data that is unlikely both accurate and known upfront. That said, perhaps what is ideal is not reconstructing social networks in their entirety but, more precisely, reconstructing subsets of networks, the extent to which differs for each person. Pushing the boundary of partitioning performance (to preserve every social connection possible) will not bring about an idealised social state; better said, this pursuit accommodates for significantly more meaningful connections than would otherwise transpire. As people look around the shelter, do they generally see others as a source of comfort, or are those around them seen as a threat? Are the interactions that occur supportive and

nurturing, perhaps in the same way or perhaps in different ways? Are superficial social connections distracting from more meaningful ones, or are certain *weak links* beneficial in this context? Does a better shelter experience outweigh the extra physical or mental stress of travelling farther from a home that is potentially destroyed or in need of immediate repair?

To advance beyond a simple partitioning problem, one should consider an open-ended question that this research only begins to answer: which social connections should one prioritise, i.e., preserve and/or eliminate, relative to different underlying evacuation conditions? While exploring the meaning behind social connections, individually and collectively, would provide some ground to preserve and/or eliminate social connections, the research initially explores prioritising social connections subject to “external” factors, including counter objectives (specifically, minimising travel time), probability of people requiring shelter, and specific ways of sequencing those being partitioned. The very act of prioritising one person over another, alongside how to acquire and protect the information that allows for this to happen, requires that one reflects deeply on the presented methods. In step with presenting any new socially oriented technology, what one could and should accomplish arises together in the details of this paper.

Preliminaries

Defining Disaster

Disasters occur across a vast range of space and time scales, from small-scale incidents such as the Boston Marathon bombing and single-building fires, to village-scale flash floods, city-wide earthquakes or storm surges, up to country-scale incidents such as tsunamis and hurricanes, international wars, or even conceivably global disasters. In all cases, everyday activities are disrupted, and for larger events, people can be displaced from their homes and need to be accommodated temporarily in emergency shelters, in some cases for extended periods. The degree of warning may vary from essentially none (for a flash flood, for example), through hours (e.g., tsunami early warning systems) to many days (e.g., hurricanes; see Hardy & Wunderlich, 2007). Evacuations may range from just a few people in the vicinity of a small incident to the organised movement of large populations out of a dense urban area.

The term “disaster” is well studied.³ In the context of this research, one can invest within this term additional meaning: disaster is a widespread loss in communication. It entails

³ Perry (2007) dedicates an article to defining the term disaster. The words “emergency” (Rotanz, 2007) and “crisis” (Boin & Hart, 2007; Quarantelli, 2007; Rotanz, 2007) as well as “evacuation” (Drabek & Stephenson, 1971; Perry et al., 1981; Sorensen & Sorensen, 2007) have undergone similar scrutiny. There is also a “hazards”

the metaphorical stripping of language, expressions, and symbols that situate one comfortably within the norms of society and one's individual experience within that society. As communication occurs between people, its loss is also between people. When the magnitude of this loss isolates individuals, leaving them unable to reaffirm their own histories at will, one can define this state as a disaster. While this interpretation of disaster is abstract, the experience is also uniquely quantifiable as a loss in social network structure, i.e., a loss in the number and weight (value) and configuration (context) of network ties that one can access. Although people may act differently during a disaster, these ties represent channels of trust and accountability between individuals, and they can moreover serve as pathways for emotional support and collaboration during times of great need.

Defining Displaced People

In this context, this research refers to *displaced people* as people whose home is no longer habitable. The literature struggles with how to label displaced people. Indeed, labelling reinforces homogenisation; the term “client,” “victim,” “participant,” “refugee” or “displaced person” tends to de-historicize and universalise diverse populations (Rajaram, 2002). As avoiding the label is impossible, Roger Zetter (1985) suggests that policymakers focus on the experience of displaced individuals. Other researchers recommend that displaced individuals play a less passive role and become active participants in their own disaster recovery (Mazur, 1988; Wood, 1985). The focus on a label should not obscure the fact that individuals with separate identities are involved. This paper focuses on keeping these individual identities intact by finding ways to keep communities of individuals together, allowing preexisting relationships and structures to thrive, notwithstanding the displacement.

Defining Community

Community is a human value (Frazer, 2000), which constitutes and draws upon notions of tolerance (Walzer, 1997), reciprocity (Putnam, 2000), and trust (Coleman, 1990). In more general terms, people describe community as networks: “For most of us, our deepest sense of belonging is to our most intimate social networks, especially family and friends. Beyond that

approach to understanding disasters (University of Colorado, Boulder; see Mileti, 1999) as well as a sociological approach (Rodríguez, Quarantelli & Dynes, 2007). Thirty disciplines have an interest in the disaster field (Fordham, 2007, citing Alexander, 1997). In the United States, twenty-seven federal agencies play a role in responding to presidentially declared disasters (Mileti, 1999). At least two comprehensive typologies of disasters have been created (Barton, 2005; Kreps, 1989).

perimeter lie work, church, neighbourhood, civic life, and [an] assortment of other ‘weak ties’” (Putnam, 2000).

The idea that refugee camps, internally displaced people (IDP) camps, or emergency shelters currently have a collective community is a misnomer. In the words of Simon Harris (1999), regarding IDPs in the northern Wanni region of Sri Lanka, “They are, in effect, [‘unimagined’ communities] brought together purely through the dislocating circumstances of displacement.” Vincent and Sørensen’s (2001) book, *Caught Between Borders: Response Strategies for Internally Displaced*, echoes this assertion and documents how cultural continuity is an essential coping strategy.

Social Networks and Experiencing Displacement

When emergency planners focus solely on quickly relocating survivors, their actions could generate an even more traumatic experience, one that may actually qualify as a disaster. Aldrich (2012) writes, “While recovery coordinators may imagine that quick evacuation would somehow save more lives than methodological mass departure plans, their assumptions are often mistaken. Rapid, random evacuation places those citizens most in need of assistance after disasters in temporary housing where their social connections are limited at best and non-existent at worst” (see also Tsuji, 2001). Aldrich (2012) points to the 1995 Kobe earthquake, where “placing many senior citizens in huge, Soviet-style apartment blocks without attempting to resettle them near friends and family resulted in a number of ‘lonely deaths’ (*kodokushi*) where elders died without [anyone] even knowing about it.” The stark juxtaposition of post-disaster experiences, both positive and negative, suggests that problems and solutions are occurring (and if understood, can be capitalised on) independently of traditional relief intervention. What follows is a collage of interviews and literature references compiled by Aldrich (2012), which depict the state of displacement and both the desired and desirable impact that social capital has on people’s lives:

In interviews, survivors of the [Indian Ocean] tsunami describe how they were randomly assigned to temporary shelters and how “people were placed with people of different communities” (Case 7, Tata Institute 2007). As one displaced person told me, “My old neighbors are not nearby; they are in the location but far from my house. It was a lottery to choose locations for houses” (author interview, 20 February 2008). Local residents recognised the benefits of maintaining and strengthening networks after the tsunami. In one study an older woman reported that “many people in this camp are from the same street and village in which I live and we all help each other” (HelpAge

International 2005, 12). Some organized themselves in their evacuation, so that “post tsunami, all members of one village decided to stay together in the temporary sheds in a gesture of unity, especially to support people who have lost their dear ones” (Gomathy 2006a, 218). These tsunami survivors intuitively recognized that “women who were able to access familiar religious sites, markets, hospitals, relatives, friends and other resources will be far less vulnerable to abuse, exploitation and psychological distress.” (Banerjee & Chaudhury 2005)

If keeping communities intact at emergency shelters becomes technically achievable, and if there are demonstrable benefits in doing so, then emergency planners should change their basic design calculus. A random assortment of people convening at emergency shelters is no longer a passive phenomenon and a neutral planning decision; randomness would actively work against the formation and benefits of sustaining community networks at emergency shelters. At the very least, emergency management should consider the social repercussions of existing protocols. As pertains to the Hanshin–Awaji earthquake in Japan, “[o]n the whole, Kobe municipal officials made it difficult for those who actively sought to move together en masse to temporary or permanent housing (Yoshimune, 1999)” (Aldrich, 2012). Indeed, the manner in which society breaks apart, and what remains intact, is subject to human action/inaction.

Social Networks and Disaster Recovery

When levees in New Orleans broke following Hurricane Katrina in August of 2005, one of the neighbourhoods to suffer the greatest loss in property and infrastructure was New Orleans East, better known to its American-Vietnamese residents as Versailles. In the opening scene of the documentary *A Village Called Versailles* (Chiang, 2009), the director depicts Uptown New Orleans after the hurricane, which did not flood and where people quickly resumed their everyday lives, followed by what a local describes as a 30-mile stretch of “flooded-out, gutted homes...[where] maybe 80% of the houses are still unoccupied.” Amidst this “ghost town” is Versailles, which in stark contrast to adjacent neighbourhoods, appears rebuilt and thriving; “[Versailles] came back faster and more robustly than virtually all other neighbourhoods in Orleans Parish, even those with similar levels of flood damage, and those that were considerably more affluent” (Chamlee-Wright & Storr, 2009). Indeed, two years after the hurricane, New Orleans overall experienced a 45% return rate; the American-Vietnamese community, on the other hand, returned at a rate of approximately 90% (Chamlee-Wright &

Storr, 2009). What is unique about Versailles is that its people maintained a strong commitment to each other throughout the evacuation. In the words of a respected community elder:

I've fled three times, this is the third time. When I fled here from Vietnam I had no hope of returning. This hurricane is different...I still had hope as I fled, the hope to return. I figured, after so many decades of living here, we're all emotionally connected. Fathers, sons, mothers, daughters, neighbors. We can't lose each other. (Chiang, 2009)

This commitment to each other was reinforced in a tangible way at emergency shelters. A senior pastor from Versailles, Father Vien Nguyen, travelled from shelter to shelter “to check the status of his parishioners and to convey information about family members” (Chamlee-Wright & Storr, 2009). As Father Vien recounts,

The people evacuated, some to San Antonio, some to Austin, some to Fort Chaffee, Arkansas. That's where the journey began, where I went to all of the centers to visit with my people. They were very fearful. A lot of them really haven't been out there in the wider community, so I told them that I would be there to wait for them, or I'll come to see them. (Chiang, 2009)

Further documenting Father Vien's interactions at shelters, Chamlee-Wright and Storr (2009) write, “[H]e took digital photographs of every member of the community he met to confirm their safety to loved ones in distant cities” (Chamlee-Wright & Storr, 2009). These photographs were by no means a substitute for interpersonal communication at shelters. They served a different role; they shifted the narrative from what was physically destroyed, the built environment, to what was perfectly intact but displaced and scattered, the American-Vietnamese community. As a central figure within the community—a position reinforced through his personal outreach—Father Vien was able to transmit or propagate a message across the social network that he (and, given his network centrality, potentially many others) would return. Others have attributed the exceptional recovery of Versailles not simply to a coordinated return effort but also to the cultural, linguistic and civic services or “club goods” unique to Father Vien's church (Chamlee-Wright & Storr, 2009). Of course, these are not mutually exclusive factors.

What becomes quite clear is that social networks play multiple roles during an evacuation. This research focuses specifically on immediate support at (or beginning at) emergency shelters, which presumably includes support to return home. Assuming that rebuilding is necessary and that future disasters are a manageable concern, people may not want to return and rebuild without some assurance or reasonable expectation that others will do so. In a worst-case scenario, this problem is represented as a single-shot prisoner's dilemma

(PD) game,⁴ where the rational and dominant strategy for those separated across shelters and unable to communicate with each other is to not return home (see Chamlee-Wright & Storr, 2009). To change the outcome of this game, one would want displaced people to communicate with each other, i.e., to share their intentions, prior to deciding what action to take (see Bachi et al., 2010; Sally, 1995). In theory, reuniting people at shelters would present this opportunity. Furthermore, if a community leader, such as Father Vien, wanted to visit his or her community at shelters, then arguably this leader could accomplish the task more simply or more thoroughly (perhaps even without knowing the whereabouts of all constituents) if people were reunited at emergency shelters.

While many forms of support accessed through social networks (including emotional, financial, and logistical support) involve pairwise interactions, the decision to return home if others return home requires the perception of collective action, brought about from multilateral (potentially iterative) social interactions. Additionally, not all social interactions are equal. For example, knowing the intention/strategy of someone like Father Vien, who is recognised as a central figure, and projecting that others in his social orbit also know his intention/strategy, should influence the outcome of a PD game. Unto itself, social infrastructure at emergency shelters does not incentivise people to return home; however, social infrastructure could in theory create a forum more amenable to a collaborative effort to return home, particularly in the absence of a community leader advocating for it.

Although literature juxtaposing the experience of displacement with and without access to social networks more strongly motivates the research (see previous section), one should not overlook this additional vein of support—namely the support to return home—even if the evidence awaits empirical grounding.⁵

⁴ The prisoner's dilemma (PD) game is a metaphor for studying the evolution of cooperation between unrelated individuals (Axelrod, 1984). For a simple description of this metaphor, please see Poundstone (1992). More formally, given the choice to cooperate (*C*) or defect (*D*), where cooperators pay a cost, *c*, for their opponents to receive a benefit, *b* (such that $b > c > 0$), and where defectors incur no costs and distribute no benefits, then a payoff matrix would reveal that mutual defection (*D*) is the only stable evolutionary strategy. As defecting is always the more rational choice, a social dilemma presents itself: rational playing is at odds with the best mean population payoff, achieved if everyone had blindly cooperated. If the game is iterative (IPD), however, individuals can observe an opponent's past behaviour and employ a simple tit-for-tat or Pavlov strategy (Nowak & Sigmund, 1993) to catalyse a cooperative outcome (Axelrod, 1984; Axelrod & Hamilton, 1981; Nowak & Sigmund, 1992, 1993).

⁵ "Disaster recovery represents the least understood aspect of emergency management, from the standpoint of both the research community and its practitioners" (Smith & Wenger, 2012; see also Berke et al., 1993; Rubin, 1991). Also defining the academic void is the lack of emphasis on the role of neighbourhoods and groups during disasters, as the common focus has always been individuals or households (Mileti, 1999). Research is only beginning to shed light on the role social networks play in disaster recovery (e.g., Aldrich, 2012; Beggs et al., 1996; Chamlee-Wright & Haeffele-Balch, 2016; Lee et al., 2022; Rayamajhee & Bohara, 2021). More narrowly,

Language From Network Science, Graph Theory, and Displacement

During a disaster, one might find social networks split needlessly across multiple shelters. This paper offers an alternative process, the *calculated* division of social networks and their effective recombination. While breaking apart a unified network is always a destructive act, the subnetworks that remain may actually function more effectively than the original network. To facilitate more thoughtful subnetworks, the research introduces algorithms, of which graph and hypergraph partitioning play a unique and central role.

By applying graph partitioning to a social network, one is melding together concepts from different academic traditions. Toward understanding the mixed-use language adopted by this research, one can begin with how to represent social affiliations between people. From network science and, more specifically, social network analysis (SNA), the term “social network” is well-suited for this purpose. From graph theory, the term “graph” is also appropriate. One should note, however, that a graph is not oriented toward a particular context. If one were to use only the word “graph,” one would have to specify its social attributes.

Whereas graphs are structurally comprised of vertices and edges, networks are comprised of nodes and links (or ties), albeit the term “edges” is common across disciplines. In the evacuation context, the vertices/nodes could represent people—individuals or groups—and the edges could represent social affiliations. When introducing partitioning, however, one may not want to treat groups as vertices/nodes, i.e., as inseparable entities. In fact, certain groups may not even fit within a single partition. The best tool to represent groups comprised of individuals is neither a social network nor a graph but a generalisation of a graph known as a hypergraph. This delineation between graphs and hypergraphs, which falls within graph theory, does not mean that graphs are more specialised than social networks; they are structurally equivalent. Graph theory simply has additional vernacular in this respect.

Continuity in language is not always appropriate. One cannot singularly endorse the word “network,” for example, by replacing the terms “graph partitioning,” “hypergraphs,” and “induced subgraphs” with “network partitioning,” “hypernetworks,” and “induced subnetworks”—the former are terms of art, and the latter are an abstraction. By the same logic, one cannot exclusively adopt the word “graph,” for example, by replacing the term “network centrality” with “graph centrality.” Some terms, like “community” (as in “community detection” from network science) and “cluster” (as in “clustering” from graph theory) are

the role social networks *within shelters* play in disaster recovery remains largely theoretical and would benefit from dedicated empirical studies.

interchangeable; however, their connotations are different, and depending on the context, one might choose a particular term, for example, to emphasise its social or technical quality.

The research imports terminology from both network science and graph theory. As to not lose sight of the “people behind the nodes,” the research prefers language from network science and, with its more sociological bent, social network analysis (SNA). The research also transitions quite freely between pairs of words that conceptually bridge the simulated model and real world—analogously, “nodes” and “people,” “partitions” and “shelters,” etc.—as a means to inform and critique algorithm design.

Graph Partitioning

Graph partitioning is a well-studied problem in discrete mathematics, specifically in combinatorics, scientific computing, and machine learning. It can be described as the problem of partitioning an undirected graph into k components of roughly equal size while minimising the capacity or weight of edges being cut. This is an NP-complete problem, meaning there is no known efficient decision-making process to locate a solution, even where $k = 2$ (also known as the minimum bisection problem). Pertaining to the challenges of this problem, Andreev and Racke (1994) have demonstrated that there is no approximation for perfectly balanced partitions; however, for the case where the balance constraint is relaxed by a factor of one percent of the number of vertices (Andreev & Racke, 1994) or greater than one percent (Even et al., 1999), approximations are possible. Without the balance constraint, also known as the minimum-weight k -cut problem, Goldschmidt and Hochbaum (1994) proved that, given a fixed k , the problem has an optimal solution. The basic trend is that as the imbalance constraint tightens toward a perfect balance, the problem becomes harder; Wagner and Wagner (1993) have demonstrated this regarding minimal bisections.

While optimal and near-optimal solutions are theoretically important, practically speaking, particularly for large graphs, a number of heuristic algorithms have proven far more valuable. These have appeared in a number of applications, which can be found in recent graph partitioning surveys (Bichot & Siarry, 2011; Buluç et al., 2013; Çatalyürek et al., 2022). The most prolific research on graph partitioning concerns the distribution of computational threads/subtasks over multiple processors running in parallel (Hendrickson & Kolda, 2000; Rajamanickam & Boman, 2012); in these graphs, vertices represent data, and edges represent dependencies between data (Devine et al., 2006). As for physical design, integrated circuits that combine thousands or millions of transistors, aka very-large-scale integration (VLSI), take

advantage of graph partitioning to minimise the weight of connections between subcircuits (i.e., minimise interprocessor communication) and thereby the number of switches a message will be routed through. As Hendrickson and Kolda (2000) point out, the bottleneck for the overall speed of applications is not the length of wires but the number of switches to which the wires are attached. Apart from parallel processing and VLSI design, graph partitioning has been applied to image segmentation (grouping pixels into recognisable objects), route planning (preprocessing spatial searches), power-grid design (splitting apart power grids to prevent cascading failures), and biological networks (data reduction through grouping biologically similar entities; see Buluç et al., 2016, for a more in-depth look at these applications).

Hypergraph Partitioning

While graphs can represent pairwise connections between actors, hypergraphs can represent supra-dyadic transactions (Bonacich et al., 2004). For example, a medical unit or football team, where individuals perform unique tasks, might only consider itself functional or effective through coordinated action. Instead of using multiple edges to represent connections between two or more people, a hypergraph would use a single hyperedge to represent these connections (see Berge, 1989), with a hyperedge being a non-empty subset of vertices (Rajamanickam & Boman, 2012).⁶

A hypergraph is said to be more expressive than a graph. When hyperedges have a cardinality of two, they essentially become edges; however, edges cannot straightforwardly convert into hyperedges (see Hendrickson and Kolda, 2000; Klamt et al., 2009; Zhou & Schölkopf, 2007). Indeed, excluding Levi graphs (bipartite graphs associated with an incidence structure; Gross et al., 2014), hypergraphs have readily useable information that ordinary graphs lack and are a nontrivial extension of them.

A more striking difference between graphs and hypergraphs is that their respective partitioners have different objective functions. Graph partitioners aim to minimise edge cuts while hypergraph partitioners aim to minimise communication volume. In the context of parallel computing, total communication volume (TCV) is “the sum of the number of processors to which each vertex has connections” (Hendrickson & Kolda, 2000). This is accompanied by another measure, maximum communication volume (MCV), which is the worst communication volume of any processor (Glantz et al., 2014).⁷ This latter metric

⁶ As common to VLSI circuit design, hyperedges are called nets and vertices are called pins.

⁷ More precisely, MCV is the number of connections belonging to the processor that contains the greatest number of connections to other processors.

represents the weakest link in parallel processing, i.e., the slowest processor determines the overall speed of an application (Hendrickson, 1998).

MCV has gained considerable attention in a 2012 graph partitioning challenge, the 10th DIMACS Implementation Challenge (Bader et al., 2018). Interestingly, when the objective function was not edges cut but MCV, it was not a hypergraph partitioner that took the prize for best performance but a graph partitioner, KaFFPaE, developed by Peter Sanders and Christian Schulz (Sanders & Schulz, 2013). As Schulz reports (Schulz, 2013), “KaFFPaE outperformed dedicated hypergraph partitioners by just changing the fitness function to prefer solutions with low communication volume—the multilevel algorithm still optimized cuts.” Seemingly, attempting to optimise for MCV from the outset with a hypergraph partitioner may not be as effective as using a graph partitioner outfitted with a post-processing procedure for minimising MCV (Glantz et al., 2014).

Edge Weights and Node Weights

Several parameters are commonplace within the graph partitioning literature, including node weights, edge weights, and target partition weights. While these parameters are not ubiquitous, they are supported by METIS (Karypis, 2013), which is the most well cited graph partitioner. Another parameter worth mentioning is the fixed vertices constraint, which is common to hypergraph partitioners. Other parameters, such as restreaming and batching, are unique to specific partitioners and are introduced later in the research.

In a parallel computing environment, the node weights represent the amount of computation while the edge weights represent the amount of interaction between nodes (Schloegel et al., 1997). From a social perspective, the most straightforward adaptation of these concepts is to have edge weights represent social affinities between people. For example, family members might be assigned a relatively high edge weight while friends are assigned a medium edge weight and other acquaintances a low edge weight. The challenge for edge weights is finding an appropriate scale. This involves determining what relationships are relatively important for displaced people, a topic that deserves considerable attention but is beyond the scope of this research.⁸ As for node weights, one can repurpose this parameter for a situation unique to disasters: it can represent the probability of a person needing an emergency shelter. Using node weights could ensure that everyone is assigned to a shelter without

⁸ For research, surveys can be administered to discover what relationships are important. In practice, people can register their own perceptions of what is important.

needlessly wasting resources by opening an extraneous number of shelters. Or from another perspective, instead of some shelters being full of people and other shelters being nearly empty, node weights could more evenly balance occupancy levels.

Target Partition Weights

Another useful parameter, supported by partitioners such as METIS (Karypis, 2013) and SCOTCH (Pellegrini, 2010), allows one to input target weights for various partitions.⁹ As the METIS user manual states, this allows one “to compute partitioning solutions that are well-suited for parallel architectures with heterogeneous computing capabilities” (Karypis, 2013). From a disaster management perspective, this constraint is vital—it allows one to change the desired occupancies at emergency shelters. By default, METIS will partition a graph into nearly equal parts, or in other words, all shelters have nearly equal occupancy.

Fixed Vertices

Generally speaking, hypergraph partitioners have an extra constraint tailored for VLSI applications, namely the *fixed-vertices* constraint. Other than hypergraph partitioners, such as hMETIS (Selvakkumaran & Karypis, 2006), PaToH (Çatalyürek & Aykanat, 2009), and ZOLTAN (Boman et al., 2012), certain graph partitioners, such as SCOTCH (Pellegrini, 2010), have this constraint as well. This feature allows one to pre-assign vertices to a partition (for an overview of how fixed vertices are useful in VLSI design, see Alpert et al., 2008). Apart from the utility of fixed vertices, Caldwell et al. (1999) demonstrate that when the percentage of fixed vertices increases, runtimes substantially decrease: “[T]his is expected since the partitioner has less freedom and a smaller number of movable vertices.”

For the people who have committed to a specific shelter, their location can be pre-assigned or “fixed” before (re)conducting graph or hypergraph partitioning. In other words, the partitioner could treat people who have yet to commit to a shelter as free or movable and consider those who have already arrived or are arriving at a shelter as fixed, and then optimise in the best interest of everyone. This proposed technique is distinct from what is termed “dynamic” repartitioning, whereby a graph partitioner adapts to network changes while considering the migration cost of rearrangements—there is no cost to changing a

⁹ While this research is concerned with multiple partitions, this capacity is also available for the minimum bisection problem (dividing a graph into two parts). Galbiati (2011) has developed an algorithm to find a minimum cut-weight, where the cardinality of one shore is exactly equal to a given integer k (i.e., partition size can be specified).

recommendation if no one has acted on that recommendation; people would simply be assigned a new recommendation (perhaps not even knowing a change was made). One can think of this approach as static partitioning that occurs over and over again.

Another use for fixed vertices is to connect displaced people to particular shelters. In this case, shelters are represented by “virtual” or “dummy” nodes/vertices, which are fixed within distinct partitions. Edges that connect to these nodes could represent, for example, a relationship between displaced people and their nearest shelter and/or an affinity between displaced people and a specific host community. Whether these edges are preserved or not during partitioning depends largely on how they are weighted relative to social affiliations.

Partitioning Performance

For research purposes, while partitioning performance is important, this research places greater emphasis on other considerations. Indeed, this research seeks to showcase a variety of partitioning methods (including graph and hypergraph partitioning) as well as highlight differences in how data is managed with respect to partitioning (where a single and adaptable partitioner is selected as a control). In practice, however, one should stay apprised of new partitioning algorithms and determine which are most appropriate for the scenario at hand.

Apart from the 10th DIMACS Implementation Challenge, which as mentioned earlier was a competition featuring different graph and hypergraph partitioners, Chris Walshaw (2023) maintains an online public domain resource, *The Graph Partitioning Archive*, which tracks the best balanced and nearly-balanced edge cuts ever performed on 34 real-world benchmark graphs. Out of the 44 algorithms tested, approximately 50% of the top results, defined by minimum cut-weight and largest subdomain weight, are currently achieved with ILP algorithms (Henzinger et al., 2020) and FSMAGP (Fast Memetic Algorithm for Graph Partitioning; Schneider & Dorndorf, 2014). Other algorithms that perform notably well include RatioDCA (Hein & Setzer, 2011), JOSTLE (Walshaw & Cross, 2007), MAHMBCDP (Memetic Algorithm with Hungarian Matching Based Crossover and Diversity Preservation; Ruiz & Segura, 2018), and KaBaPe (Sanders & Schulz, 2013).¹⁰ In practice, as no one

¹⁰ ILP algorithms do not scale well; however, they could play a role when runtime is not a factor (e.g., when implementing the static prediction strategy) or initiated during lulls in an evacuation, i.e., as a post-processing step to an otherwise scalable algorithm. These ILP algorithms are part of a larger family of graph partitioning programs, KaHIP (Schulz, 2020). KaBaPe is included within this family and is highly scalable. One should also note that the second-best performing algorithm, FSMAGP, is not publicly available. Lastly, RatioDCA is particularly interesting as this algorithm is more closely aligned with clustering than partitioning (see citations within Hein & Setzer, 2011). Beyond literature on graph partitioning, one might explore literature on constrained clustering—constraining the upper and potentially lower bound of cluster sizes—to achieve a similar result. This is quite straightforward with spectral clustering (see RatioDCA) or with hierarchical clustering (where clusters

algorithm always performs best, running multiple algorithms and selecting the best results might be a more sensible protocol than selecting a single algorithm with the highest likelihood of success.

As the name communicates, the *Graph Partitioning Archive* does not track the performance of hypergraph partitioners or their objective functions, total or maximum communication volume. Notable hypergraph partitioners include hMETIS (Selvakkumaran & Karypis, 2006) and PaToH (Çatalyürek & Aykanat, 2009), which run in serial, ZOLTAN (Boman et al., 2012), and PAR κ WAY (Trifunovic & Knottenbelt, 2008), which run in parallel, as well as Mondriaan (for sparse matrices; Vastenhouw & Bisseling, 2005) and MLpart (for circuits; Caldwell et al., 2000).

In terms of scalability, software like PuLP can partition a 1.8 billion edge network on a general-purpose distributed memory system in less than a minute (Slota et al., 2014). They report that their approach uses 7.5% less memory and is 16% faster than METIS, producing comparable if not better edge count results. Other partitioners are also exceptionally scalable, for example, algorithms within the graph partitioning framework of KaHIP can partition a web graph with 3.3 billion edges in less than 16 seconds using 512 cores (Meyerhenke et al., 2017). These types of programmes run in parallel and take advantage of label propagation, a near-linear time technique that was originally designed to detect community structures in large-scale networks (Raghavan et al., 2007; see also El Moussawi et al., 2021).¹¹

Understanding the Problem Visually

To examine the upper bound of what is socially achievable—which assumes one is partitioning networks without retrospective knowledge of who requires shelter—the research employs basic static partitioning. To examine what is realistically achievable, the research employs partitioning methods that incorporate predictions (more complex static partitioning) and/or make use of real-time information (streaming partitioning).

Prior to solving what is realistically achievable, one can visualise this intention by streaming assignments generated from a static graph partitioner, which when illustrated capture how partitioning must contend with information about people needing shelter that grows or

are defined by cutting branches off a dendrogram, the level of which is specified). With clustering based on local search optimization (e.g., van Laarhoven & Marchiori, 2013), one could theoretically add an extra penalty term to the objective function and tune the weight of this new term to enforce desired cluster sizes.

¹¹ Many of the more popular graph partitioners also run in parallel, e.g., PT-Scotch (Chevalier & Pellegrini, 2008), ParMETIS (Schloegel et al., 2002), JOSTLE (Walshaw & Cross, 2007), KaPPa (Holtgrewe et al., 2010), and DibaP (Meyerhenke & Gehweiler, 2010).

Figure 1

Evacuation Underway
25% Complete

Note. A movie was produced to visualize displaced people reuniting at emergency shelters over the course of an evacuation. This image is a snapshot taken from this movie. The screen is partitioned into four quadrants, which represent different emergency shelters. At the beginning of an evacuation, many people are alone in the shelters. All the people who have connections are located in the same shelter.

Figure 2

Evacuation Underway 50% Complete

Note. People sharing a shelter are represented by large nodes with the same distinct color. If they are connected, they also share a long edge with this color. Halfway through the evacuation, person 10 (a large, yellow node in quadrant IV) is connected with three people (long, yellow edges) but also separated from three people (short, grey edges). These separated people are located in quadrant III (large, grey nodes), where reciprocally, they are shown separated from someone in quadrant IV (short, yellow edges), i.e., person 10.

Figure 3

Evacuation Underway
75% Complete

Note. Person 18 is assigned to quadrant IV, where she has three connections. At this point in time, the better assignment would be quadrant III, where she would have six connections. That said, eventually she will have eight connections in quadrant IV (see Figure 4), which makes her current assignment the better option in the long run.

Figure 4

Evacuation Underway
100% Complete

Note. The evacuation is complete. This image shows the result of assigning people to shelters using a partitioner, a method that attempts to preserve social connections while ensuring that a roughly equal number of people are assigned to each shelter.

evolves over time (see Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4). This visualisation could represent real-time assignments generated using streaming graph partitioning. It could also represent assignments generated prior to an evacuation, where the streaming component simulates when people commit to assignments. More precisely, the visualisation does not depict a specific method (or combinations of methods); it depicts the formation of well-partitioned assignments by the end of an evacuation. The question remains: what method or methods allow one to generate assignments that become well-partitioned (similar to those visualised here) without perfect, retrospective knowledge of who requires shelter?

The techniques employed during network visualisation or graph drawing—minimising crossed edges, keeping edge lengths short, clustering highly connected nodes, etc.—organise the social network and, both directly and indirectly, make apparent social relationships that could otherwise remain perceptually/visually (and perhaps statistically) obscure. In the wake of partitioning, one should further visualise not only which network structures are preserved, the induced subgraphs, but also which network structures are lost or broken during partitioning. With respect to the latter, the figures presented depict edges cut, which are illustrated as relatively short edges or “whiskers” emanating from nodes. The research has produced these figures by developing software dedicated to the visualisation of streaming graphs into partitions (see Appendix A).

Organisation of Chapters

The research is divided into two parts. Part 1 includes chapters titled “Portland Study” (Chapter 1) and “A Family in Portland” (Chapter 2). Part 2 includes chapters titled “Relevant Partitioning Methods” (Chapter 3), “Three Partitioning Strategies” (Chapter 4), and “Limited Time Partitioning Strategy” (Chapter 5). This is followed by a conclusion and a section on future work.

Part 1 couches socially oriented shelter assignments within the greater evacuation context. In practice, the effectiveness of these assignments depends upon what otherwise would or could occur and, moreover, who interprets the projected results or intervention capabilities. As part of an ongoing discussion of what data is included within and excluded from the Portland simulation, the research identifies who is displaced and reflects upon how their experience would change under different simulated conditions. This perspective on behalf of displaced people, which is developed alongside the construction of the simulation, is arguably as important as the presented methods and results.

Part 2 focuses on advancing real-time methods to preserve displaced people's social networks at shelters. The underlying assumption is that the social objective is warranted and desirable; however, the data used for partitioning—knowing who requires shelter—is not provided upfront and, in this sense, is incomplete (cf., Part 1). The research explores multiple methods, operating alone and in concert, to overcome the problem of incomplete data.

One can read Part 1 and Part 2 independently. If interested in big-picture ideas and large-scale simulation design (with a large focus on data integration and analysis), then one might focus on Part 1. Alternatively, if interested more narrowly in the social objective and more practically in algorithms designed for real-time data, then one might jump to Part 2.

Chapter 2

Portland Case Study

This research contends that pre-disaster social landscapes can be reconstructed to some degree at emergency shelters, laying the groundwork for greater support at emergency shelters and an opportunity for speedier recovery. The stage for such intervention has been set long before any disaster takes place; intervention begins with how cities both shape and are shaped by communities. With respect to each city's distinct social blueprints, a case study becomes a tool that can incorporate and navigate the complex, pre-disaster relationship between the physical and social landscape and how this relationship may devolve or be reimaged in a post-disaster context, where policies, recommendations, and displaced people's decision-making processes guide social outcomes.

The research utilises graph theory and agent-based modelling (ABM) to determine network preservation and travel costs to emergency shelters under three routing scenarios: when displaced people are assigned to (1) random shelters, (2) nearest shelters, or (3) social-nearest shelters. A fourth scenario, social shelter assignments, is implicitly derived. Indeed, the network preserved from social shelter assignments, for all practical purposes, is equivalent to social-nearest shelter assignments. Additionally, as shelter locations associated with k -way partitioning are completely interchangeable, the average travel cost to social shelter assignments is equivalent to random shelter assignments. To make this latter equivalency, the research constrains random shelter assignments in the same way as social shelter assignments; each shelter contains a predetermined as opposed to a random number of displaced people, which means that no one will be rerouted after discovering that a shelter has reached capacity. This is achieved by solving the multiple-knapsack problem (MKP), where the solution is herein referred to as "random shelter assignments." Likewise, for nearest shelter assignments to be constructively juxtaposed, the research solves the capacitated p -median problem (CPMP). This solution is herein referred to as the "nearest shelter assignments." The proposed method for solving "social-nearest shelter assignments" involves taking the output from the CPMP and incorporating it into a hypergraph structure before partitioning. In terms of travel costs, on a spectrum between random shelter assignments, which represent a rational (not theoretical) lower bound, worst-case scenario, and nearest shelters assignments, which represent an upper bound, best-case scenario, one could place social-nearest shelter assignments somewhere in between.

For social-nearest shelter assignments, the research creates a network structure, where people are connected to both their social acquaintances and their nearest shelter. As partitioning

minimises the sum of edges/hyperedges cut, the research prioritises social connections by assigning them a higher weight. With social connections prioritised, one might perceive nearest shelter connections as adding location-based information to the social network. One should keep in mind, however, that social connections contain their own location-based information—their formation is often indicative of spatial proximity between people. Taking this into account, the research posits the following hypothesis: as concerns social–nearest shelter assignments, while many nearest shelter assignments are sacrificed for the primary social objective, those nearest assignments that are preserved geospatially anchor the social network and bolster the results, demonstrated by a reduction in travel cost to emergency shelters markedly better than what would be expected if the social network did not have geospatial attributes.

The case study used in this research features a simulated vehicle-based evacuation of the greater Portland, Oregon area following a magnitude 6.8 earthquake generated from the Portland Hills reverse-slip fault (see Figure 5). If displaced people travel to their nearest shelter location during this evacuation, then these people would likely find 3.69% of their social network present at shelters. In contrast, social–nearest shelter assignments preserve 71.28% of displaced people’s social network during the same evacuation while also sending roughly 43.52% of these people to their nearest shelter location. For those not travelling to their nearest shelter, the vast majority of these displaced people are still travelling to nearby shelters; using an agent-based model to simulate displaced people’s movement patterns, the proposed method results in travel times of approximately 60.3% of the way between random and nearest shelter allocations.

Scope and Limitations

Scope and Limitations of Case Study

Case studies involving people are varied and complex, and not easily reducible (Flyvbjerg, 2006; Taylor, 2013). Are there patterns of displacement, if not recurrent hardships across different regions or countries, then within a single place across different times? Specific to this research, would an analysis of displacement in Portland, Oregon be relevant to others? Perhaps its relevancy ends in the Pacific Northwest of the United States or in “Western” countries, or perhaps in places with similar infrastructure, modes of transportation and/or mobile technology. While a single case study cannot offer generalisable findings so essential to “theorisation” (G. Thomas, 2010; Nadel, 1957), a well-conducted and communicated case study has some degree of inherent sensibility, resonating with and against a reader’s own

Figure 5

Portland Hills Fault

Note. These images depict the inferred location of the Portland Hills fault. The lower-right image is adapted from "The Portland Hills Fault: An Earthquake Generator or Just Another Old Fault," by I. G. Wong, M. A. Hemphill-Haley, L. M. Liberty, and I. P. Madin, 2001, *Oregon Geology*, 63(2), p. 40 (https://people.wou.edu/~taylors/g473/seismic_hazards/wong_etal_2001_pdx_hills_fault.pdf). Copyright 2001 by Oregon Department of Geology and Mineral Industries. In the public domain.

circumstances. After demonstrating that a socially oriented intervention strategy holds merit against a rich backdrop of competing, real-world factors (as pertains to Portland, Oregon within this chapter), the discussion should eventually shift to whether the case study in question is unique and how particularities from other cases might support or work against the findings.

Scope and Limitations of Data Used

Prior to creating new models or adapting this model for cross-cultural or longitudinal studies, one could extend the research by evaluating the model created here from different perspectives. For example, the proposed evacuation model owes realism to the aggregation of multiple data sources. One could catalogue this data—road typologies, disaster types, demographic characteristics, building construction categories, social network compositions, times of day, etc.—with an eye to understanding socially vulnerable geographies during evacuations. In the same vein, one could reinterpret emergency management’s current strategies in terms of social implications as well as reimagine how these strategies might serve a socially oriented goal.

For this chapter, analysis begins after an evacuation model has been constructed; however, one would be remiss not to draw attention to how all the data collected, generated, and/or manipulated along the way speaks to further research, specifically pertaining to social vulnerabilities and opportunities during evacuations. Beginning with an example: do spatial relationships between acquaintances translate into social vulnerabilities at emergency shelters? One might hypothesise that a person with a more geospatially dispersed social network would have more friends unaffected by a disaster (all disasters are to some degree localised) who can be called upon to provide accommodation.¹² On the other hand, if this person were to require emergency shelter accommodation, under the assumption that people are generally visiting their nearest shelter, then this person might find less of his or her social network at the nearest evacuation site.

As another consideration, when a disaster strikes, people are geographically situated somewhere in their social network. How does this initial disaster state influence who is socially vulnerable at shelters? If people were to directly evacuate to their nearest shelter, considering that each person values his or her communities (religious, school, workplace, neighbourhood,

¹² A geospatially dispersed social network entails that one’s social acquaintances are not only separated by distance but, for example, by variability in terrain and exposure to atmospheric conditions. This broader appeal to dispersion encompasses the idea that people living nearby but away from the coastline, forest, or tall buildings, or perhaps living at higher elevations or upwind of potential disaster sites, or even living in newly built neighbourhoods as opposed to older or historically preserved ones, might be less affected by certain disasters.

etc.) differently and each community is experienced at a different location and time of day, then one might hypothesise: (1) each person's social vulnerability at shelters would change throughout the day, (2) different people would likely experience social vulnerability at shelters at different times, and (3) a community's social vulnerability at shelters (as an average across its members) would be exacerbated or allayed depending on the time of day. Setting aside this dimension of social vulnerability, even if people do not travel to their immediate nearest shelter, the initial disaster state would still give rise to social disparity. Given the location of people when a disaster strikes, those with the longest commute to shelters (or the longest commute home and then to shelters) must contend with the possibility that nearby shelters have reached capacity, following which only the more remote shelters (physically and likely socially remote) would be available.

Among real-world factors included in constructing an evacuation model are decisions made by emergency management. Recognising social vulnerabilities at emergency shelters is certainly a call to action; however, recognising that emergency management's own actions impart social vulnerabilities suggests that emergency management is already partially responsible for the current social milieu at shelters. As an example, suppose a given region is well-clustered into two distinct communities, one being located to the east and the other, to the west. Beyond this region are four shelters respectively located in the four cardinal directions. In such a case, if two shelters are selected by emergency management, then all else being equal, selecting the north and south shelters would result in the two communities being split apart to a significant degree.

Alongside selecting destinations among emergency shelters, labelled emergency routes could emphasise improved social composition at emergency shelters instead of functioning to maximise evacuation speed. As yet another example, staggered departure times, which are sometimes implemented during evacuations, could also be geared toward preserving social networks. Indeed, the fact remains that emergency management intervenes in multiple ways, and each intervention likely has unintended social consequences, the effects of which are currently unknown and the opportunities of which are unexplored.

Scope and Limitations of Agent-Based Modelling

Simulating traffic conditions during an evacuation requires that one generate an origin-destination table. For the context at hand, the research defines "origin" as the location of people in Portland during a nominal day when an earthquake strikes and "destination" as the location of people upon reaching a safe harbour. While a traffic model depicting a nominal day is readily

verifiable, a traffic model depicting a disaster with no history of occurrence is not. In other words, the introduction of significant model assumptions is unavoidable when destinations are considered.

Theoretically, emergency management could generate multiple preconceived evacuation scenarios with an ABM, each of which incorporates predictable, micro-level behaviour into deciding emergency shelters for displaced people. One of these preconceived scenarios might approximate the conditions of a future disaster, which if recognised early during an evacuation, could then help guide people to emergency shelters. In practice, however, data acquisition (particularly regarding destinations), not to mention limited foresight into traffic accidents, road closures, localised weather effects, etc., might overwhelmingly prohibit or limit the utility of such a “virtual laboratory” to anything beyond hypothetical insights.

While a preconceived ABM may not be particularly well suited for guiding real-time shelter assignments, such a model is quite capable of *simulating* shelter assignment strategies as if they were employed in real time. As pertains to this research, the ABM presented here is not part of a shelter assignment strategy; rather the ABM is used to *evaluate* each strategy in terms of travel costs.

Scope and Limitations of Static Partitioning

Building on the above logic, while one could design real-time shelter assignment strategies, one could also generate benchmarks to *evaluate* real-time shelter assignment strategies. The latter could utilise a priori (or retrospective) information pertaining to who requires shelter to generate best-case, global optimising shelter assignments using a static graph or hypergraph partitioning. With an emphasis on introducing meaningful evaluation techniques (which can be applied to any case study), this chapter aims to present output—derived from static partitioning—against which future, dynamic solutions can be better understood, both as a function of social preservation and travel costs.

Chapter Overview

This chapter begins by providing background information on the datasets collected and generated for research: synthetic social network data, American Red Cross shelter data, earthquake data, and road network data. Overlapping the data allows for an informed selection of displaced people and, more specifically, determining who among them would require visiting an emergency shelter as opposed to visiting friends or family either within or outside the model’s spatial boundary (a 75-mile radius placed around the centroid of Portland, Oregon).

Figure 6

Note. In order to route displaced households using an agent-base model, having identified each household's probability of being displaced, one must then select individual displaced households and assign them (along with those who are not displaced) to a safe location.

After selecting who is displaced, the chapter progresses by first allocating those not requiring shelter to reasonable destinations. As for those requiring shelter, three allocation scenarios are explained: displaced people assigned to (1) random, (2) nearest, and (3) social–nearest shelters. Regarding the last scenario, instead of explaining the construction of social assignments unto itself, a method is presented to combine nearest and social assignments into a multi-objective function.

Considering not only the destinations of displaced people but also the destinations of non-displaced people as well as everyone’s location when an earthquake strikes, an agent-based model is then introduced to showcase the meaningful difference in travel costs between the above three scenarios (see Figure 6).

Data Sources

Synthetic Social Network Dataset

This research tests theories requiring highly realistic, synthetic social networks with embedded geospatial attributes. The question of whether to generate such social networks or whether to utilise existing datasets that contain this information depends on the research objective. If the goal is to study location-specific disaster scenarios, then the ability to generate social networks tailored for particular sites is appealing. On the other hand, if a specific location is not the motivating factor behind the research, then perhaps constraining the location selection to readily available data is advantageous; indeed, fewer technical hurdles are involved as well as less data processing, both of which make replicating the research findings easier. Given that a geospatially embedded social network of Portland, Oregon is readily available, and considering that this location coincides with other factors important to this research,¹³ what follows is a description of how this Portland dataset is couched within the greater literature, and ultimately, why the dataset is suitable for this research.

Available Data

Generally speaking, two distinct fields have contributed to generating realistic social networks: those studying transportation demand modelling and those studying the spread of infectious disease. Beginning with the former, the most prolific contributions can be traced, both independently and collaboratively, to the Urban Planning Group at Eindhoven University

¹³ For starters, Portland is susceptible to real disasters, such as earthquakes, and American Red Cross shelter data is available for the city.

of Technology as well as to the Institute of Transport Planning and Systems at ETH Zurich. The research produced from these institutions has strong theoretical underpinnings, drawing influence from social network analysis and graph theory (Arentze & Timmermans, 2008) as well as citing investigations into “spatial games” and sociological behaviour (Hackney & Axhausen, 2006). At Eindhoven University, proposed models have incorporated the random-utility-maximisation (RUM) framework, which has a long tradition of use in transportation and land use modelling (Ben-Akiva & Lerman, 1985), as well as take advantage of object-oriented programming languages, initially coding with the open-source, agent-based modelling and simulation toolkit, RePast (Hackney & Axhausen, 2006). At ETH Zurich, in the context of social interactions influencing joint activity scheduling (Ronald, Arentze & Timmermans, 2012), fictional grid-based environments become the landscape for synthetic populations, and social networks are geospatially generated using Hamill and Gilbert’s (2009) social circles, which are then extended (Ronald, Dignum, et al., 2012). All the above research acknowledges a thread of ongoing, empirical literature centred on surveying ego-centric social networks with an eye to understanding how this literature can be incorporated into transportation modelling.

Due to logistical hurdles, a large-scale, complete social network has never been surveyed. Even if such a social network existed, to then geocode this data with any level of precision (at least down to the street level) would raise ethical considerations, requiring careful attention to data protection and/or sophisticated anonymising procedures. In light of these challenges, only small-scale, complete social networks exist, and these are not publicly available. One of the better-known examples is found in the Netville study (Hampton & Wellman, 2003). Despite the intention to generate a wholly inclusive social network of Netville (the primary researcher was equipped with the names and addresses of every resident in the city), a 62% household response rate to survey questions, while enough to draw significant and interesting conclusions regarding the sociability of its residents, still leaves an incomplete understanding of social network structure. Larger socially oriented surveys rely on sampling techniques, which by design result in incomplete, sparse, or porous social networks. These include the Survey of the Social Networks of the Dutch (SSND; Röper et al., 2009) and the Netherlands Longitudinal Lifecourse Study (NELLS; Tubergen & Völker, 2015). In Canada, the Connected Lives project (Wellman et al., 2006) and, more generally, Cycle 17 of the General Social Survey (GSS; Housing, Family, and Social Statistics Division, 2004) track various aspects of social connections. With a focus on adolescents, the National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent to Adult Health (Harris, 2013) and The Project of Human Development in Chicago Neighborhoods (Sampson, 2012) both look at social capital as an indicator for

understanding adolescent health and development. Researchers have also mapped the spread of obesity over a 32-year period (Christakis & Fowler, 2007) and happiness over a 20-year period (Fowler & Christakis, 2008) between friends and family within the *Farmingham Heart Study*.

While empirical data can suggest rules regarding social interactions (with whom do people interact and where), one must also disentangle whether these rules are universally applicable or embedded within specific city or national contexts. This comes to the forefront in a 2012 article, “Distance patterns of personal networks in four countries: a comparative study” (Kowald et al.). The article focuses on the relationship between individuals (egos) and their social contacts (alters),¹⁴ as the title implies, from four independent countries: Canada (Toronto), Netherlands (Eindhoven), Switzerland (whole country), and Chile (Concepcion). Its co-authors include the primary investigators responsible for each of the four study areas. The findings call into question the credibility of using overly generalised models to represent socio-spatial networks, which in turn has motivated new methodologies to reproduce network structures and social distances emulating geographically situated empirical data. Indeed, one result from this cross-cultural comparison is that while spatial distances between acquaintances for all four countries follow a power-law distribution, the scaling exponent is unique to a given place. In other words, as social networks are a proxy for travel behaviour (Illenberger, 2012), the distance people travel to socialise is country/city dependent. With a sensitivity to geographic location, Arentze et al. (2013) demonstrate how to use maximum-likelihood estimation (MLE) to parameterise a random-utility-function and ultimately generate a complete, synthetic friendship network based on incomplete, surveyed personal network data coupled with census data. Their methodology speaks directly to the above-mentioned Switzerland dataset (and the Swiss Micro Census on Mobility and Transport [MZMV]), a methodology that Kowald, Arentze, and Axhausen (2015) later put to practise when generating a country-wide social network of Switzerland to support agent-based travel-demand simulations. The research put forth by Kowald, Arentze, and Axhausen (2015) follows in the footsteps of Illenberger (2012), who uses the same Swiss datasets and similar modelling techniques. These studies also find precedent in Daraganova et al. (2012), where Melbourne, Australia becomes a case study for producing an augmented, complete social network from

¹⁴ The personal networks within this article are more than simply ego networks; the authors ask the egos about the attributes of the alters, thereby rendering a more complete picture of the network relationships. Furthermore, a snowball survey has been implemented in one of the study areas (Switzerland), which can not only lead to a more expressive networks, i.e., the possibility of generating a directed graph, but this methodology also captures a more cohesive network that can be validated vis-à-vis mutual contacts.

surveyed personal network data. Pointing to the operational need for urban planners and policymakers to have access to reliable agent-based models, Zhang et al. (2019) provide a step-by-step guide on how to generate connected synthetic populations for urban simulations using digital records (e.g., cellular records or social media data) of inter-personal communications; the San Francisco Bay Area in California, US, is used to showcase their method.¹⁵

Where transportation modelling requires social networks to simulate joint-trip scheduling and social convergences for leisure activities, infectious disease modelling capitalises on social networks to map the spread of contagion. The social networks used in this research are a (by)product of infectious disease modelling. They were generated using software called EpiSimdemics (Barrett, Bisset, et al., 2008),¹⁶ which has a direct methodological lineage to one of the most widely-cited infectious disease modelling tools, EpiSims (Eubank et al., 2004a). EpiSims was originally designed at Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), along with the transportation modelling software TRANSIMS, which is the massive-scale, multi-agent modelling backbone of EpiSims. According to LANL's Mathematical and Computational Epidemiology (MCEpi) group, EpiSims has been internally rebranded within LANL and is now called OPPIE (Valle, 2021), while another group at the Virginia Bioinformatics Institute's (VBI) Network Dynamics & Simulation Science Laboratory (NDSSL), under the direction of Stephen Eubank (principal investigator), provides the current home of EpiSims as well as its extensions, EpiSimdemics, EpiFast, Indemics, ISIS, DISimS, etc. (Deodhar et al., 2012). Looking specifically at EpiSimdemics, this software has several financial contributors, one being the National Institute of Health (NIH) funded Models of Infectious Disease Agent Study (MIDAS) group. VBI is one of the original research groups under MIDAS.

In order to understand how EpiSimdemics generates a social/contact network, one would benefit from tracing the literature back to TRANSIMS, a program that is not explicitly part of EpiSimdemics but is nevertheless fundamental to EpiSims (its predecessor software) and contains much of the logic needed to understand EpiSimdemics. TRANSIMS has its own history; the primary article featuring EpiSims (Eubank et al., 2004a) has supplemental information on TRANSIMS, including citing 18 published articles spanning the software's theoretical and architectural construction as well as its computational challenges, like

¹⁵ Please note: most literature on generating synthetic populations does not consider the role of social networks (e.g., Huynh et al., 2016). The literature presented here is narrowly selected.

¹⁶ Not to be confused with Simdemics (Barrett, Eubank & Marathe, 2008), which is an earlier version of EpiSimdemics.

parallelisation and algorithm efficiency (Eubank et al., 2004b). The literature pertaining to TRANSIMS' population synthesiser and activity generator is of particular interest to this research.

Operating TRANSIMS requires first collecting demographic information about a given population. TRANSIMS can combine summary tables from the US Census Bureau (SF-3), which contains aggregated demographic values, with the Public Use Microdata Sample (PUMS), which consists of a 5% representative sample of the actual responses to the census questionnaire (designed to represent approximately 100,000 individuals). As these actual responses preserve family structure data, an iterative proportional fitting (IPF) technique (Beckman et al., 1996; Wheaton et al., 2009), is adopted to replicate microdata across all households tied to geographic areas containing SF-3 summary statistics.¹⁷

Regarding subsequent procedures, one of the better descriptions of TRANSIMS is found in the article "Generation and Analysis of Large Synthetic Contact Networks" (Barrett et al., 2009). In summary, the next step involves assigning a list of activities and corresponding locations to each household member. Locations for work, retail, and recreational activities are derived from Dun & Bradstreet data while schools and colleges are located using data from the National Center for Educational Statistics. A list of activities is preliminarily assigned to each person; this "activity sequence" considers several thousand responses to activity or time-use surveys, where responses from individually surveyed households are matched to the synthetic population via a demographic-based decision tree. Activity locations are specifically chosen using a gravity model, statistically fitted with travel-time distributions from the National Household Travel Survey (NHTS). The gravity model additionally incorporates a constant that adjusts for the type of activity performed. TRANSIMS will then read these activity locations and use a traffic assignment function to generate routing instructions on a road network, which are then executed by the TRANSIMS' cellular automata (CA) traffic micro-simulator, which attempts to reach a Nash equilibrium where travel times cannot be further improved by rerouting procedures. In other words, the inherent problem is that people's routing plans depend on traffic congestion and, simultaneously, traffic congestion depends on people's routing plans.

As an analytical solution cannot be determined, TRANSIMS resolves this by relaxing the system, i.e., preliminary plans are run through the traffic simulator, followed by adapting a small percentage of the plans (typically less than 10%), which are then run through the traffic

¹⁷ The developers recognise that IPF may not be a statistically correct procedure; however, they also note that in preliminary studies, IPF performs fairly well compared to maximum likelihood and minimum chi-square, which require a vast number of parameters and computational power (Smith et al., 1995).

simulator, followed by adapting the plans again, etc., until a state of equilibrium is reached (typically 50 iterations; Nagel & Rickert, 2001). TRANSIMS additionally makes use of a feedback mechanism that can identify alternative activities if routing is deemed infeasible. In this way, over the course of many iterations, people's activities and itineraries may be structurally refined so as to be statistically consistent with empirical findings. With the location of every person known on a second-to-second basis, one can then construct a contact/social network, represented as a bipartite graph $G(P, L)$, where P is a set of people, and L is a set of locations. In turn, the collocation or shared space or people can be determined as well as the amount of time people spend in contact.

As the transmission of many infectious diseases occurs between collocated people, EpiSims takes advantage of TRANSIMS' contact/social network to simulate within-host disease progression and between-host disease propagation (Eubank et al., 2004a). The disease model can be viewed as a “networked probabilistic timed finite state machine” (Barrett, Eubank & Marathe, 2008), where the stated transition is probabilistically determined by the duration of contact between individuals as well as their demographic attributes. The primary difference between the EpiSims and the newer EpiSimdemics model is computation time and scalability (Barrett, Bisset, et al., 2008). Without going into technical details as to how EpiSimdemics improves parallel efficiency, EpiSims demonstrates poor scaling with over 10 million individuals (Barrett, Bisset, et al., 2008), whereas the most recent version of EpiSimdemics (using CHARM++ runtime system instead of the original MPI framework) can simulate a 120-day epidemic for the entire population of the United States, which includes 300 million people and 1.5 billion edges, on the 352,000 core NCSA Bluewater system in 12 seconds (Network Dynamics and Simulation Science Laboratory, n.d.). Although articles pertaining to EpiSimdemics (Barrett, Bisset, et al., 2008; Bhatele et al., 2017) focus primarily on improvements in computational performance within disease modelling, the techniques for generating specifically the contact/social networks, which are necessary for EpiSimdemics to operate, have remained nearly static since TRANSIMS was introduced. One might thereby argue that TRANSIMS alone is responsible for generating the complete, synthetic social network datasets publicly available today; however, this would not be entirely correct, for as the methodology belongs to TRANSIMS, the call to action, i.e., why a dataset would be generated in the first place, belongs to the great importance attributed to understanding the spread of infectious disease.

As a result of EpiSims and the 2004 article “Modelling disease outbreaks in realistic urban social networks” (Eubank et al., 2004a), a full bipartite social/contact network of the

Portland, Oregon area is available upon request (at roughly 12GB, the data is not openly hosted). This includes the locations of approximately 1.6 million people every second of a 24-hour day as they navigate through 181,000 activity locations. In 2006 and 2007 respectively, two newer datasets of Portland, Oregon became freely available for download; dataset “1.0” is created with EpiSims and dataset “2.0,” with EpiSimdemics. The latter employs a more rigorous methodology and has been borrowed and modified for use in this research. At the time of writing, these are the largest available contact/social networks publicly available for download.

Without looking at the full spectrum of infectious disease models, one cannot categorically assert that generating social networks for infectious disease modelling is methodologically distinct from that of transportation demand modelling. That said, EpiSimdemics (and all models developed by VBI) specifically embrace a definition of social networks that is more easily justified and likely to emerge in the context of infectious disease.

From the perspective of EpiSimdemics, the concept of social networks is indistinguishable from contact networks—the latter does not exist within transportation literature. One might argue that EpiSimdemics’ interpretation of social networks defies a commonplace understanding of social relations; simply being in contact with others does not imply that a deliberate and conscious social exchange has taken place, i.e., that someone socialised. Furthermore, this conflation between social networks and contact networks upends how empirical researchers typically define and measure social networks. The construction of ego-centric social networks, for example, is often the result of a name-generator survey. A contact network, however, would include connections well beyond those that can be named. This is not necessarily wrong; in fact, this may point to a limitation in the name-generator approach. Indeed, whether social networks are bound by names or recognition, or whether they are defined by the ego (him or herself) or by an outside observer, is unclear or, at the very least, dependent on the purpose of the social network.

As this research makes use of “social networks” created by EpiSimdemics, one should be aware of the unchallenged, liberal usage of the term “social networks” in place of “contact networks,” which is not indefensible but certainly not traditional. This research appeals to the fact that social networks are indisputably contained within contact networks, and if the synthetic social networks are deemed unrepresentative of real social networks (most likely exhibiting an inflated edge count), then the number of connections can be tactically reduced or otherwise modified. One approach would entail removing connections in a social network starting with pairs of people with low contact time until the network structure is closer to

idealised; this approach operates under the assumption that people who spend more time together have a greater probability of becoming social acquaintances (contact time can be represented as edge weights, where greater edge weights are more valuable). Another approach is to use a dedicated graph editor, like the Multiscale Entropic Network Generator (MUSKETEER), to modify the EpiSimdemics network without inadvertently distorting the inherent network structure (Gutfraind et al., 2015). Of course, claiming that a social network is unrealistic and requires modification is difficult to prove.

More fundamentally, in contrast to both travel demand models and other infectious disease models, EpiSimdemics does not treat social networks as an input variable; EpiSimdemics simply does not utilise empirical findings about social networks, either derived from multiple social surveys (to create a generalised social network) or from region-specific social surveys. The underlying philosophy of EpiSimdemics is that social networks are subject to discovery based on *first principles* (Barrett et al., 2009). Social networks might very well be irregular and unstructured, unable to be fitted using traditional statistical techniques;¹⁸ they must be understood as emerging from real-world data coupled with “procedural knowledge about urban mobility” (Barrett et al., 2009). Furthermore, to borrow the language and viewpoint of EpiSims (Eubank et al., 2004a), social networks produced by TRANSIMS are “based on the assumption that the transportation infrastructure constrains people’s choices about where and when to perform activities.” The above-presented literature on travel demand modelling suggests, however, that this “constraint” is only part of the story; looking back at the 2005 Swiss Micro Census on Travel Behavior, leisure activities comprised the highest share of all trip purposes (41%), including the highest share of time (51.5%) and distance travelled per day (44.7%; Kowald et al., 2010). In the book *Mobilities, Networks, Geographies* (Larsen et al., 2006), while the authors associate leisure activities with tourism, they also “de-exoticize” tourism and travel theory, emphasising that the primary incentive for travel is the co-presence between friends and kin: “much tourist travel thus involves a particular combination of places and significant people.” Indeed, leisure activities are a pervasive and socially motivated component of everyday travel. To counterbalance the methodological positioning of EpiSims, one might argue that sociability dictates travel patterns as much or more so than the “constraints” of transportation infrastructure. Even within the early literature on infectious disease modelling (R. Thomas, 2010), many alternative methodologies are juxtaposed against

¹⁸ One of the more popular statistical approaches for modelling social networks is with an Exponential Random Graph Model (ERGM). A first principles approach offers an alternative solution (Xia, 2014).

those advocated by EpiSims, some of which directly question EpiSims' sociological view. Of particular note, the authors of BioWar (Carley et al., 2006) praise EpiSims' accountability to demographic asymmetries while critically asserting that “[t]ransportation networks may constrain but do not define social networks.”

One can ascribe to the EpiSimdemics (and EpiSims) methodology in practical terms while maintaining some principled reservations. A case can be made that social surveys would augment infectious disease models; however, the fact of the matter is that geographic-specific social data is not widely available (although digital records might change this). Even if social data is available, this information would need to be integrated with some computational efficiency. EpiSimdemics is not only scalable, but the methodology allows for easy adaptation and extension to almost anywhere in the world, e.g., Xia (2014) has demonstrated its applicability in Delhi, India. The Portland, Oregon dataset, with all its advancements and caveats, must be viewed in light of a design intended for large-scale implementation without sacrificing the level of detail necessary to map the spread of infectious disease.

In conclusion, utilising the Portland, Oregon dataset satisfies multiple criteria. The dataset is a product of many years of research, supported by a wealth of organisations, and a great deal of technical knowledge has gone into its development. Furthermore, the dataset is publicly available, which allows other researchers to easily access the data and start from a common ground, i.e., circumnavigating the intricacies of independently synthesising a population. Lastly, Portland, Oregon is geographically prone to disasters and thereby of further relevance to this research.

Content of Data. The Portland, Oregon dataset includes time-stamped data of where roughly 750,000 people are located at any given moment of a typical day. Each person is assigned an age, gender, and work status. Additionally, a head of household is defined as well as each household member's relationship with this person. Possible relationships include spouse/partner, child, adult relative, or other. For each household, the number of vehicles is known as well as the household's income range in US dollars (income is binned into one of 14 categories). While people's exact movement patterns are not part of this dataset, the start time (in seconds past midnight) and the duration of daily activities (in seconds), including the real-world coordinates of each activity, are provided for each person. A person's daily activity sequence includes a combination of the following: home, work, shop, visit, social/recreation, other, pick up or drop off a passenger, school, and college. As this dataset ultimately serves to represent and track the diffusion of contagion across large social networks, the data also

contains a pairwise list of who has been in contact with whom as well as the duration of these contacts (in seconds).

The activity locations are aggregated. This means each location represents multiple households or workplaces. The activities are located with respect to the existing roadway infrastructure, which is comprised of roadway junctions connected by roadway links. The dataset specifies two activity locations per roadway link, positioned midway down both sides of the roadway. The roadway links are not provided with the dataset. Furthermore, activity locations can have sub-locations, representing individual households or separate rooms within a building.

Preparation of Data. In order to prepare the data for future integration with other software, specifically Multi-Agent Transportation Simulation (MATSim; Horni et al., 2016), the coordinates for all activities were transformed from Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) coordinates (Zone 10) to WGS 1984 World Mercator using the Environmental Systems Research Institute's (ESRI) geographic information system (GIS) software, ArcGIS 10.2.2. As people can consecutively perform the same activity in different sub-locations (for example, moving from classroom to classroom within a school), and as sub-activities are indistinguishable within the dataset (e.g., the name of different classrooms are unknown) and as the sub-location coordinates are aggregated and thereby also indistinguishable, a choice was made to simplify the dataset by merging consecutively visited sub-activities into a single activity, redefined by the start time of the first activity and the end time of the last activity. Using this data, an evacuation will eventually be simulated. This simulation has been designed such that people do not complete the activity being performed when a disaster strikes but rather evacuate immediately. For this reason, no information is lost by simplifying the dataset in this manner. Depending on the nature of the evacuation, one might forgo this step.

American Red Cross Shelter Dataset

Apart from mapping the typical activity patterns of residents in Portland, Oregon, so too must information be collected about non-typical activities, namely those pertaining to the site selection of American Red Cross (ARC) emergency sites. Within the United States, under the National Response Framework (NRF), the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) is the primary agency responsible for coordinating Emergency Support Function #6 (ESF-6), which includes support for temporary shelter and family reunification (FEMA, 2008a,

2016). In collaboration with the ARC,¹⁹ FEMA has co-developed the National Shelter System (NSS), which is a nationwide database containing information on over 56,000 potential shelter facilities (FEMA, 2011b). This database is a “living document,” which communicates real-time facility preparedness and usage.

The public can view/find open emergency shelters managed by the ARC or their affiliates at the Red Cross website (<https://www.redcross.org/get-help/disaster-relief-and-recovery-services/find-an-open-shelter.html>). Along with a map displaying all open shelters, the address and current population count for each open shelter is provided. A third-party version of this information is available for smart phones (specifically iPhones), found under the name *VisionLink OEM Shelter App*.²⁰ This mobile version disseminates additional shelter information (e.g., shelter capacities) and features a “Get Directions” routing service.

Available Data. The NSS database itself is not accessible to the public. Furthermore, in order to export data from the database, one must register as a Red Cross or FEMA affiliate and subsequently be granted a certain level of security access. One should note that the Red Cross is not obligated to export information, nor is there a transparent protocol for making such a request. On the other hand, one can also look to FEMA to obtain a data export. As FEMA is part of the Federal Government, United States citizens can make a request for information (RFI). For this research, however, the data was provided upon request to Red Cross personnel. The data received and presented here is not considered as a security threat; security measures are in place to prevent individuals from tampering with the NSS data, either submitting management reports or adding/editing shelter information or agency information or, above all, deleting agency information.

The NSS database contains a wealth of shelter information. This includes agency or ARC chapter information, along with reachable contact numbers and emails. Shelters are specified as handicap-accessible, and whether restrooms, showers, cafeterias, and phones are available. Shelters are further categorised as general-purpose or gender specific. Other categories include medical shelters and pet-friendly shelters. There are options to specify

¹⁹ ARC is an ESF-6 Supporting Agency recognised as a subject matter expert in mass care. As ARC is a non-profit, humanitarian organisation chartered by an Act of Congress, ARC does not act on behalf of the Federal Government. Indeed, ARC has a humanitarian mission separate and distinct from the NRF mandate under which FEMA operates. A memorandum of agreement (MOA) sets forth the joint responsibilities of ARC and FEMA (ARC & FEMA, 2010). ARC’s position as the United States’ largest mass care service provider makes this agency a central focus of this research.

²⁰ This application and others can be found in a recent survey of emergency management web and mobile applications (Banerjee, et al., 2016).

limitations of facility use (e.g., only available for a part of the year). Of no less importance, the database provides information concerning whether shelters meet hurricane standards and whether they are located in a storm surge area (SLOSH area). Also known is the number of available blankets and sleeping cots and whether the shelters have self-sufficient power or emergency generators on site. Furthermore, energy usage has implications for yet more input fields concerning heating, cooling, and cooking. More technically, the database contains the exact location of each shelter (longitude and latitude coordinates) as well as each shelter's usable square footage, accompanied by evacuation capacity (based on 20 square feet per person) and post-impact capacity (based on 40 square feet per person). What is above presented is but a sample of the more "static" data available; however, the database also accepts dynamic input such as the day/time shelters become operational as well as the daily population counts. Regarding the latter, population counts are taken at noon and midnight, which denotes whether the counts represent mid-day populations or overnight stays.

Content of Data. As the city of Portland, Oregon borders Washington State, a request was made for shelter data pertaining to both Oregon and Washington. In preparation for a basic simulation, this data request was limited to (1) facility names, (2) locations, and (3) evacuation capacities (not to be confused with post-impact capacities). The difference between "evacuation capacity" and "post-impact capacity" is the duration of stay, where the former is intended for three days or less. As noted above, ARC designates a smaller square footage per person in this scenario, which directly equates to relatively larger short-term hosting capacities. Focusing on evacuation capacity is a logical starting place for evacuation simulations because reallocation, which might be necessary as certain facilities cannot host long-term stays (or because knowing in hindsight who is displaced might lead to even better shelter assignments), should be considered as another layer of research with its own unique solutions. Of course, simply noting and bypassing the reallocation problem by using post-impact capacity is also justifiable and raises different opportunities to extend the research. For example, a longer stay at shelters might place a greater emphasis on social relationships between those in shelters and the host community (an idea currently not explored within this research). Generally speaking, longer durations of displacement require negotiating different and more complex network relationships. At a certain point, networks that foster and take advantage of people's careers and skill sets or networks that best enable self-sustaining communities, with less or "tailored" relationships with host communities, require attention. Keeping in mind that displacement can

take place over a spectrum of durations, this research begins with short-term displacement, where basic social networks play a central role and act as a springboard for future studies.

An evacuation capacity is not a prescribed occupancy for shelters. Indeed, shelters can always hold fewer people than their respective capacities. Likewise, shelters can be selected that have a minimum capacity. Perhaps best-practice occupancies should represent a percentage of shelter capacities, leaving room for contingencies such as an influx of unexpected people. This of course begs some important questions: Given a fixed number of displaced people, what subgroup size can the Red Cross most effectively manage, or alternatively, what subgroup size is socially optimal? The answer to these questions might be contradictory as well as be compounded by other questions and factors of no less significance. For example, if a clustering or community detection algorithm is applied to sparse, disjointed social networks as a means to define the optimal number and size of shelters, then this might lead to a vast number of shelters with the unintended consequence of spreading thin Red Cross' human and provisional resources. Through a slightly different lens, the consequence can be framed not in terms of limited resources but best use of resources: Does it make sense to open shelters for only a handful of people knowing that these shelters are repurposed facilities that can no longer serve their intended use, often to the detriment to the host community? On the other hand, having fewer shelters with many people carries its own set of repercussions. For instance, displaced people on average would have to travel farther to reach shelters.

One might also argue that what is really detrimental to a host community is not the number of repurposed facilities but rather the sheer number of people at facilities, which would concentrate displaced people into certain areas, initially draining the resources not necessarily of the Red Cross but of the local, hosting community. For example, the grocery stores near a stadium occupied by displaced people are likely incapable of supporting both the local community and the displaced population. That said, these negative implications are subject to context. To not dwell on counterpoint, perhaps the Red Cross has ample resources and decides to regulate who enters and leaves shelters. Furthermore, and not without controversy, the size and available resources of hosting communities (augmented by their propensity to provide assistance) could be weighed into a calculation regarding the location and size of emergency shelters. Perhaps facilities can still operate with limited numbers of displaced people, and travelling farther to reach shelters is of minor concern.

Instead of customising each shelter occupancy based on displaced people's "natural" community sizes as well as known shelter capacities (not to mention a host of other factors not captured within the data obtained for this research), another approach is to initially simplify

and generalise the problem by selecting a single occupancy size across all shelters. In other words, select shelters with a given minimum capacity while imposing an additional constraint to not exceed that given capacity. In this case, what fixed shelter occupancy is ideal? Much like the preceding questions, this cannot be easily answered. For example, is the correct occupancy the number of people who can comfortably interact with each other or the number of people who can find each other within shelters and thereby self-organise? Emergency management could potentially facilitate interactions within shelters, so an informed answer is contingent upon whether emergency management adapts to the new social landscape at emergency shelters or whether they maintain current protocols.

Emergency Management's Use of Data. Selecting ideal emergency shelters for displaced people is different from selecting ideal displaced people for emergency shelters. Emergency management currently operates under the assumption that displaced people's movement patterns cannot be influenced, and thereby defining the ideal displaced people for shelters—the best occupancy and social composition—is not a factor of consideration. What follows is a literature review showing the extent to which emergency management caters their response to the number of displaced people, but nevertheless, how they ultimately are unprepared to identify ideal shelter occupancies. This leaves any new approach that takes advantage of controlling shelter occupancies with little to no guidance from the current framework.

To this end, who decides which shelters to open during an evacuation? This requires some insight into the National Incident Management System (NIMS), a program designed by FEMA to coordinate disaster management (FEMA, 2008b, 2019). More specifically, NIMS employs the Incident Command System (ICS), which is an approach to delineate emergency personnel responsibilities. Under the ICS, while the Incident Command Post (ICP) performs on-scene, tactical-level command functions, the Emergency Operation Center (EOC) plays a supportive, off-scene role, coordinating information and resources. In the case of multiple incidents, an Area Command Post (ACP) will take over multiple ICS responsibilities and liaise directly with the EOC (see also Deal, 2010).

When a disaster overwhelms a state's ability to respond, the Governor (or Tribal Chief Executive) from the impacted state can request through their FEMA Regional Office that the President of the United States issue an emergency or major disaster declaration, both of which make available tremendous federal resources and financial support (FEMA, 2023). When this happens, FEMA establishes a Joint Field Office (JFO) that coordinates with the EOC (or for

multiple incidents, the Area Command Post). The JFO has representation from agencies like the Department of Health and Human Services as well as the Environmental Protection Agency and the Army Corps of Engineers. Until the JFO is operational, FEMA's Regional Response Coordination Centers (RRCC), located within each of the Regional Offices, maintain situational awareness and later provide the JFO with technical geospatial support (FEMA, 2011a). This group utilises software such as HAZUS-MH (herein referred to as HAZUS) to better understand the repercussions of a disaster (software discussed in the next section). In turn, the RRCC receives national support from the National Response Coordination Center (NRCC).²¹ Considering the roles of all these actors, the EOC and potentially the JFO would take responsibility for designating shelters (FEMA, 2008a; Task Force on Riverside County Mass Care and Shelter, 2011).

The EOC would act in consultation with a jurisdiction's Mass Care Coordinator (National Mass Care Strategy, 2014).²² Within two hours of when a disaster occurs, the Mass Care Coordinator (who leads a mass care/emergency assistance task force) will inventory all existing available shelter space within a 250-mile radius of the incident (FEMA, 2005). Recommendations are then made to the EOC, and eventually the Mass Care Coordinator will either directly or through the Public Information Officer (PIO) disseminate shelter information to the public.

The requisite course material to qualify as a Mass Care Coordinator does not prescribe how to select emergency shelters and, generally speaking, advocates for a flexible decision process. Important considerations would include an assessment of the disaster and, more specifically, the ensuing infrastructural damage and debris that would preclude safe travel to and safety within habitable facilities. In this regard, a zone approach to categorise areas of damage would be useful, depicting not only who is displaced but also where safe shelters might be located (FEMA, 2012a). Another priority is designating shelters within the geographic area of where displaced people reside or, alternatively, near transportation hubs (National Mass Care Strategy, 2014). However, according to the *Shelter Field Guide* (ARC & FEMA, n.d.), if other nearby shelters are already operating, then "opening another shelter may actually be

²¹ As the ICS was designed to manage incidents, the RRCC and the NRCC operate above the incident level and follow another management protocol known as the Multi-Agency Coordination Systems (MACS; FEMA, 2011a).

²² To qualify for this position, one must have experience with emergency response planning, mass care shelter operations, procurement of feeding operations as well as operational experience in an Emergency Operation Center (EOC). Furthermore, this person must complete course work covering the Incident Command System (ICS), the National Incident Management Systems (NIMS), the National Response Framework (NRF) as well as other topics relevant to emergency shelters, including training with FEMA's National Shelter System (NSS; FEMA, 2012b).

counterproductive, as it may cause confusion, unduly strain scarce resources, or overburden logistical support.” Building off this last point, during large-scale evacuations, an adequate number of locally trained staff might not be available for immediate deployment. The ARC recommends a minimum of six trained staff per 100 displaced people (Task Force on Riverside County Mass Care and Shelter, 2011). Sheltering people in large-scale venues demands additional staff; indeed, these shelters require, according to FEMA,

significant resources to operate, manage, and support. This option [a large-scale venue] is not cost effective when sheltering a population above 5,000. Increased numbers of security guards and police officers as well as mental health professionals are needed to meet the needs of survivors in this type of operation/facility. (FEMA, 2012a)

Although the Red Cross can open shelters across the nation and deploy additional volunteers (as occurred during Hurricane Katrina), they prefer to shelter people locally and expect that the local chapters are self-sustainable for up to five days; however, as reported in a 2008 testimony before a subcommittee of the U.S. House of Representatives,

In New York City, Red Cross officials noted that it has identified enough shelters to optimally accommodate more than 300,000 people, but that it has only enough personnel locally to simultaneously operate 25 shelters, for a total sheltering capability of 12,500 people. (Fagnoni, 2008)

Among other factors, opening a shelter requires displaced people and trained emergency staff, where the ratio between these two populations has implications for the number, location, and type of operational facilities.

Preparation of Data. Allocating displaced people to shelters involves simultaneously allocating emergency personnel to shelters. In other words, greater control over displaced people’s shelter destinations is accompanied by greater precision in distributing emergency personnel. As is the current practice, unpredictable shelter occupancies are susceptible to either redundancy or deficiency of on-site emergency personnel, which in the immediate aftermath of large-scale, no-notice evacuations, where personnel are limited in number, would either shortchange needed assistance at certain shelters or require further afield shelter choices, both of which curtail the effectiveness of an emergency response. Alternatively, and irrespective of social network benefits, not having to predict which shelters displaced people will attend (for at least a subset of the population via shelter assignments) would result in better utilisation of resources. The benefits are two-fold: (1) without rerouting displaced people when shelters reach capacity, fewer shelters are required because emergency management can reduce the

disparity between under- and over-utilised shelters, and (2) without rerouting emergency personnel, more shelters can be immediately operational (or better operated) because emergency personnel can be preemptively stationed to meet the occupancy demand (or future occupancy demand) of displaced people. A novel consideration during evacuations is to think in terms of controlling shelter occupancies. This possibility has never existed before and thereby falls outside emergency management's lexicon of strategic preparedness and response. Peering into the literature and seeing a gap in potential benefits, where these benefits are aligned with the current mission of the Red Cross, lends credence to the idea that while new technology can advance the very mission of emergency response, so too does this technology require new ways of thinking. Conversely, with an eye to deliver even greater benefits to displaced people, what are the limitations of the current state of technology?

Without precedence for answering what shelter occupancies are best, one can appeal to a more immediate, technical question: What algorithms can allocate displaced people to shelters? In the first instance, one can demonstrate the effectiveness of allocation techniques irrespective of optimal input. This requires selecting reasonable shelter occupancies and evoking a research design sensitive to the constraints of various allocation techniques. Certain graph partitioners, like METIS (Karypis & Kumar, 1999) and SCOTCH (Pellegrini, 2010), would allow emergency management to select partitions/shelters of different sizes. Without further modification, the same cannot be said of known hypergraph partitioners or, for that matter, the greedy algorithms implemented within this research. To have access to the full range of allocation techniques, using k -way partitions, where all shelters are the same size, is a straightforward and justifiable approach. For illustrative purposes, this research will allocate 400 people per emergency shelter. Within the NSS, missing data aside, the median shelter capacity across Oregon and Washington is 225 displaced people, so this occupancy selection of 400 will preclude usage of the smallest shelters as well as prevent widespread disbandment of emergency personnel. Again, this occupancy is neither correct nor incorrect; it allows for this research to move forward and stands as a bookmark for future investigation.

As for missing data (namely missing shelter capacities), in accordance with how emergency management might conduct itself, allocating displaced people to emergency shelters where the capacities are unknown and might be exceeded would pose an unnecessary risk that could potentially break apart communities. For this reason, missing capacity data will not be tactically replaced with best estimates within this research. In practice, if the number of emergency shelters is limited, then perhaps looking within the lower quantile range of shelter

capacity distributions for each shelter building type would be a way to conservatively correct for missing data and ultimately introduce more shelters for use.

After applying the above constraints to the NSS data, one can then look at the remaining emergency shelters and use the facility names as an indicator of a shelter's normal function. Accordingly, most emergency shelters are schools (78%), predominately elementary, middle, and high schools (though some colleges are listed as well). Churches comprise the second largest category of shelters (12%). The remaining emergency sites (10%) include fairgrounds, community centres, civic centres, recreational centres, expo centres, exhibition halls, monasteries, club facilities, stadiums, sports camps, etc. A breakdown of the data by population instead of facility type would produce slightly different results; however, only facility type is presented here as this knowledge will play a role in further selecting shelters, i.e., allocating displaced people to facilities not destroyed by a simulated earthquake.

Earthquake Dataset

One way to introduce a credible map of displaced people is to simulate a disaster. While a disaster leaves a distinct spatiotemporal footprint, the emerging patterns of displacement are also tightly bound to household income levels, building types, and demographics. These patterns of displacement— as opposed to uniform landscapes of displacement²³—have implications for effectively allocating displaced people to emergency shelters; indeed, varying geographic clusters, gradients, and densities of impacted individuals challenge the underlying allocation procedures as well as directly affect possible social compositions at shelters.

Available Data. What type of disaster should be simulated in Portland, Oregon? Natural hazard mitigation plans for Portland, which include analysis of potential hazards, have been documented at the state, county, and city level (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2017; Oregon Department of Land Conservation and Development, 2015; Portland Bureau of Emergency Management, 2010). While limited in scope to natural hazards, these government documents feature in-depth contributions from subject matter experts,²⁴

²³ To have no pattern of displacement would entail utterly pervasive displacement (everyone is displaced) or randomly distributed displacement (disaster has no geographic or demographic impact, resulting in non-discriminate, widespread displacement of people). Except for small islands or contained populations, or if a hazard randomly occurs, one can expect that hard/soft boundaries and zones of displacement as well as other localised patterns are prevalent.

²⁴ For example, the “Portland Natural Hazard Mitigation Plan” draws expertise from the Department of Geology and Mineral Industries, Portland State University Geology Department, Oregon Climate Change Research Institute, and the National Weather Service (Portland Bureau of Emergency Management, 2010).

detailing the state of knowledge regarding the most severe threats to Portland. Further publications can expound upon these threats; however, such a compendium of site-specific, multi-disciplinary hazard analysis is unique within the literature, owing to the circumstance of a government exercising due diligence to protect its people. Within these documents, one can draw attention to the most pressing and credible natural threats to Portland.

Potential Disasters. Beginning with the geological challenges referenced in the “Portland Natural Hazard Mitigation Plan” (Portland Bureau of Emergency Management, 2010), the city of Portland, Oregon straddles three crustal fault lines, each capable of producing a magnitude (M) 6.8 earthquake (according to the moment magnitude scale). Additionally, most of the Pacific Northwest, which includes Portland, lies within the Cascadia Subduction Zone. This is where the Juan de Fuca plate plunges beneath the North American plate. The convergence of these tectonic plates can produce a M 9.0 or greater earthquake. Furthermore, as the Juan de Fuca plate sinks, it generates heat and begins to melt, creating magma chambers responsible for nearby active volcanoes, including Mt. Adams, Mt. Hood, Mt. St. Helens, and Mt. Jefferson. Since Mt. St. Helens’ catastrophic 1980 eruption, this volcano remains potentially the most volatile in the region. While the city of Portland is far enough away to avoid a direct threat (what the U.S. Geological Survey defines as lava flows, pyroclastic flows, or lahars), the city is prone to experience significant ashfall.

Historical records of Portland indicate that a massive flood or severe weather event has a greater than 33% chance of occurring each year. Other hazards include wild/urban interface fires (20-33% likelihood), erosion (10-20% likelihood), and landslides (100% likelihood; Portland Bureau of Emergency Management, 2010). These hazards have varying degrees of impact on the population. As for displaced people, floods have historically led to American Red Cross intervention (Horter, 2018). Of the 14 major floods recorded from 1847 to 2007 for both the Willamette and Columbia River basins (the Willamette River flows directly through downtown Portland), one flood of particular severity occurred on Memorial Day of 1943, which inundated the former city of Vanport, located outside the city limits of Portland, with 10 to 20 feet of water. This flood demolished the city, resulting in 18,500 displaced residents. More recently, in 1996 the Willamette River reached 100-year flood levels (Portland Bureau of Emergency Management, 2010), displacing more than 6,000 residents and requiring the American Red Cross to open more than 50 shelters (Horter, 2018). For any given year, there is a one in 25% chance of a similar event occurring (Portland Bureau of Emergency Management, 2010).

While floods have caused Portland significant damage in recent history, the city has not experienced any major earthquakes, leading to complacency in retrofitting older, unreinforced masonry buildings to make them seismically safe (Oregon Department of Land Conservation and Development, 2015). In Portland, 62.5% of buildings were constructed before 1970, when the building code did not provide for seismic events (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2017). Compounding the problem, few of the region's 1,382 bridges and overpasses have been retrofitted to withstand earthquakes (Oregon Department of Land Conservation and Development, 2015). Additionally, "Most of the state's major critical infrastructure such as energy sector lifelines, transportation hubs, and medical facilities is particularly vulnerable to damage from liquefaction and long periods of shaking" (Oregon Department of Land Conservation and Development, 2015).

A number of devastating earthquakes around the world, however, have awakened Portland to its own disaster preparedness; the "geologic settings for the [2004] Indonesia and [2012] Japan earthquakes are virtually identical to the Cascadia Subduction Zone" (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2012). Geological evidence suggests that 18 Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) megathrust earthquakes ranging from M 8.8 to M 9.1 have occurred in the last 10,000 years; a return period of roughly 530 years, which sets the probability of recurrence within the next 50 years at 7 to 12%. (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2017; Oregon Department of Land Conservation and Development, 2015). As the last CSZ earthquake was estimated at M 9.0 on January 26, 1700, the risk of another event is mounting (Oregon Department of Land Conservation and Development, 2015).

Comparing the destructive forces and aftermath of a Cascadia Subduction Zone earthquake with that of a local, crustal Portland earthquake, one must consider both the logarithmic increase in energy released from one magnitude to the next as well as the decrease in seismic intensity as waves travel through the ground. Indeed, the shaking felt from a M 9.0 earthquake 100 miles away would be similar to the shaking felt from a local M 6.0 earthquake 10 miles away (Oregon Department of Land Conservation and Development, 2015). Using economic loss as a measure of damage, the largest recorded earthquake near Portland occurred roughly 30 miles away in the town of Scott Mills in 1993, measuring a M 5.6 and causing \$30 million in damage (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2012). Despite the CSZ's location, 12 to 14 miles offshore of Oregon followed by another 60 to 80 miles to Portland, a M 9.0 CSZ earthquake would cause an estimated \$8.6 billion in damage (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2012). However, if the point of comparison is not local, historical earthquakes but rather local, potential earthquakes, then one must consider the three faults

directly beneath Portland: the Portland Hills fault, the East Bank fault, and the Oatfield fault. With respect to the Portland Hills fault, which extends through the downtown area, the estimated return period for a M 6.0 earthquake is 1,500 years and for a M 7.05 earthquake, 14,500 years. The estimated 50-year probability of occurrence is respectively 3.50% and 0.35% (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2012, 2017). While the chance of such an earthquake is low, if the Portland Hills fault were to rupture, the economic loss for a M 6.0 earthquake would be almost as devastating as the CSZ earthquake. A M 7.05 Portland Hills earthquake would be a worst-case scenario, with an estimated economic loss of approximately 51.5 billion dollars (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2012, 2017).

To make matters worse, all these estimates are likely significantly under-represented as the software used to generate them, HAZUS, does not account for unreinforced masonry structures (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2017), which are widespread in downtown Portland. In turn, the HAZUS output for injuries and casualties should be treated as a lower-bound estimate, particularly for a daytime earthquake scenario; the difference between a daytime (2 p.m.) and nighttime (2 a.m.) scenario is that people leave the downtown area in the evening to reside in their predominately wood-frame houses, which are much better at withstanding earthquakes and ultimately not collapsing. The city of Portland estimates that a daytime Portland Hills earthquake would result in 45,414 injuries and 3,417 deaths while, in contrast, a nighttime earthquake would result in only 12,074 injuries and 626 deaths (Multnomah County Emergency Management, 2012, 2017). The number of reported displaced people should be impacted by these casualty counts; however, as the number of casualties is small relative to the overall population, the fact that HAZUS does not incorporate casualties into its displaced persons calculation is not a major oversight and leads to simplified output (i.e., the number of displaced people does not reflect the time of day the earthquake occurred).

Modelling Earthquakes. Weighing all the possible threats facing Portland, as this research aims to utilise a realistic map of displaced people from a large-scale evacuation, a decision was made to recreate Portland's worst-case scenario, a maximum magnitude earthquake along the Portland Hills fault. While past studies report the economic loss and number of casualties from such an earthquake, this research seeks to generate probabilities of displacement as the primary output. Keeping with tools used in the literature, HAZUS has been selected to perform this analysis.

HAZUS is software developed and freely distributed by FEMA to estimate potential losses from earthquakes, hurricane winds, floods, and tsunamis (USEHAZUS, n.d.-b). With

over 60 user groups across the United States and abroad, HAZUS has a substantial user base (USEHAZUS, n.d.-a). As noted above, this software is used by emergency management within FEMA's Regional Response Coordination Centers (RRCC). Additionally, the U.S. military's Weapons of Mass Destruction Civil Support Teams (WMD-CST), which are a part of each state's National Guard unit, have expertise in modelling natural disasters (Emergency Management Institute, 2011). In 2007, the National Defense Authorization Act (NDAA) expanded the mission of WMD-CSTs to respond not only to chemical, biological, radiological, and nuclear (CBRN) incidents but also man-made and natural disasters that result or could result in catastrophic loss of life or property (National Guard Bureau, Department of Defense, 2011). WMD-CST certification is offered through the Defense Nuclear Weapons School (DBWS) run by the U.S. Defense Threat Reduction Agency (DTRA), where HAZUS is part of the curriculum (Defense Threat Reduction Agency, 2016). Furthermore, HAZUS has interoperability with other software used by WMD-CSTs, namely the Consequence Assessment Tool Set (CATS). This latter software has been designed by FEMA and DTRA to assess the consequences of both natural and human-induced hazards (Samuels et al., 2012).

While other software can model losses from earthquakes (see Erdik et al., 2011), HAZUS is very much integrated into the current knowledge base and protocols of those managing disasters, making this software a logical choice to simulate an earthquake followed by an evacuation within the city of Portland. The decision to use HAZUS is also grounded in understanding the capabilities of this software. As FEMA is concerned with housing people after an evacuation, HAZUS is not only equipped to estimate casualties (which is the extent of most other software's social assessment), but additionally, HAZUS can estimate the number of displaced people during a disaster. This type of output is of great importance for this research.

Content of Data. Before performing any risk assessment, HAZUS is foremost a database, where the quality of the inventories determines the reliability of the simulations. While the national embedded inventories within HAZUS can provide credible output, augmenting the database with local information, such as regional soil maps, would improve the model's accuracy. Other than basic demographic and boundary data, HAZUS contains information regarding hazards, general building stock, essential facilities, high potential loss facilities, transportation systems, lifeline utility systems, hazardous materials, agricultural products, and vehicle data. Additionally, HAZUS contains data relevant to economic and social loss (FEMA, 2022). Looking within the hazard data, the probabilistic ground motion data is

provided by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) in Golden, Colorado with refinements made by the state agencies of California and Nevada. As HAZUS supports modelling historical earthquakes, this type of data has been compiled from the ANSS Worldwide Earthquake Catalogue, the National Earthquake Information Center (NEIC), and the Earthquake Seismicity Catalogue Volume I.

With such detailed input, HAZUS can produce quite comprehensive output, covering multiple categories of loss or damage. Examples include contour maps of ground shaking intensities and ground displacements, along with liquefaction and landslide probability maps. Structural and nonstructural damage is predicted for the general building stock, essential facilities, and high potential loss facilities (the latter refers to structures such as dams and nuclear plants). In the wake of an earthquake, inundated areas and hazardous material sites are also output, and as for ensuing fires, the number of ignitions and percentage of burned areas by census tract are reported. HAZUS generates the amount of debris that could end up in the streets, including its weight and material. At a very detailed level, the estimated number of leaks and breaks in the pipeline system as well as the loss of beds in hospitals are also output. Economic loss associated with general building stock includes structural and nonstructural costs of repair or replacement, loss of contents, business inventory loss, relocation costs, business income loss, employee wage loss, and loss of rental income. As for social losses, casualties are reported at four levels of severity based on three different times of day, and what is most important for this research, the number of displaced households as well as the number of people requiring temporary shelter is output (Mitigation Division, 2013b).²⁵

To assist users in operating HAZUS and gaining familiarity with its underlying methodologies, FEMA has published an “Earthquake Model User Manual” and “Earthquake Model Technical Manual,” which are both extensive (over 800 and 700 pages respectively; see Mitigation Division, 2013a, 2013b) Focusing specifically on predicting who is displaced, HAZUS delineates between displaced households and people requiring short-term shelter. The former concerns the loss of habitable dwelling units; HAZUS calculates the probability of residents without power and/or water immediately after an earthquake as well as whether dwelling units are likely vacated from damage. The number of vacated dwelling units is more specifically a function of both structural damage and perceived damage (Mitigation Division, 2013b). Indeed, past research has shown that single-family homes are more likely to tolerate

²⁵ The methodology does not account for displaced people resulting from fires that occur after an earthquake or flooding due to dam failure. People seeking refuge because of hazardous materials being released are also not factored into the calculation.

damage (and not vacate) compared to multi-family homes. In this respect, while completely damaged dwellings will result in displaced households, HAZUS treats moderately and extensively damaged dwellings with more subtlety, assigning a weighting factor for displacement that corresponds with the type of home and severity of damage.

As for people requiring short-term shelter, HAZUS considers people's income levels, ethnicity, age, and household ownership (whether they own or rent their dwelling unit). The importance placed on each of these factors is represented by weights (sum is equal to 1.00), where the default income weight factor is highest (0.73), followed by the ethnicity weight factor (0.27). Both age and household ownership weight factors are preliminarily set to zero. Within each of these categories are default "relative modification factors," which can be interpreted as the percentage of households within each category that would require short-term shelters if their dwellings become uninhabitable. Income levels are subdivided into five brackets; for the lowest bracket, households earning less than \$10,000 would have a 0.62% probability of displacement, while at the other end of the spectrum, households earning greater than \$35,000 would have a 0.13% probability of displacement. For ethnicity, studies suggest that people who are Black or Hispanic (weight factors of 0.48 and 0.47) are more likely to be displaced than people who are White, Asian, or Native American (weight factors of 0.24, 0.26 and 0.26 respectively; Mitigation Division, 2013a).

Preparation of Data. Simulating a Portland Hills earthquake begins by installing HAZUS from FEMA's flood map services centre (FEMA, n.d.). At the time of conducting the earthquake simulations for this research, HAZUS-MH 3.0 was installed.²⁶ In order to run HAZUS, a compatible version of ArcGIS (which in this case is ArcGIS 2.2) must first be installed. Accompanying state maps can then be downloaded; these contain the inventory data. One should note that these maps can only be downloaded from within the United States (and the regional setting on one's computer must also be set accordingly). As the damage from a Portland Hills earthquake extends beyond the city, maps of Oregon and Washington were downloaded and placed into HAZUS' inventory folder.

For earthquakes, HAZUS can perform simulations with data down to the census tract level; while this level of aggregation lacks the resolution of census block data (which theoretically can be simulated), this level of aggregation is nevertheless quite detailed. The

²⁶ Updated versions are constantly being released. The newest version, HAZUS 4.0, now supports tsunami modelling.

region specified for a Portland Hills earthquake does not need to include every census tract within the states of Oregon and Washington; the impact of a Portland Hills earthquake would be somewhat localised, at least in terms of destructive force. All tracts within Multnomah County, which includes those that comprise Portland, as well as all tracts within an approximately 115-mile radius from the centroid of Portland, were selected. This distance encompasses other nearby large cities, like Eugene, Oregon, which might feel some minor shaking from this earthquake.

The desired earthquake scenario would be considered a “source event.” Other scenarios might include a “historic epicenter event” or a “probabilistic event.” As the Portland Hills fault is a reverse-slip fault with a dip angle of 60 degrees, the default attenuation function was thereby set to “West US, Extensional 2008 – Reverse.” The characteristic moment magnitude for this fault line is 6.8.²⁷ Regarding the rupture length, the subsurface length is approximately 27.2 miles (43.7 km) while the surface length is approximately 22 miles (35.5 km). As the rupture length is not particularly long and as the epicentre lies deep beneath the earth’s surface, the exact placement of the epicentre does not make a tremendous difference in terms of damaging Portland (several tests were conducted to confirm this assertion). Ultimately, the epicentre was placed south of the city (the coordinates were set to 45.5156, -122.677). After the earthquake was simulated, a “direct social losses” analysis was conducted. The results, i.e., the number of displaced households as well as people requiring short-term shelters per census tract, were then mapped. Due to the size of the simulation, the process was conducted for Oregon and Washington separately. The data for each state was then exported and merged together in ArcGIS.

Eventually, the output from this simulation will inform the selection of *individually* displaced households, the number and location of which are specified (along with the social connections between household members) within the infectious disease model data. One should note that HAZUS 3.0 uses 2010 census data, whereas the infectious disease model (EpiSimdemics) was designed earlier and uses 2000 census data. Over the course of a decade, between 2000 and 2010, Portland has grown in population (Census Bureau, 2011). Therefore, to make these two datasets compatible, the number of displaced people (as an absolute value) identified within HAZUS has been transformed into a percentage of displaced people. This way the proportion of displaced to non-displaced people is preserved across population counts.

²⁷ Instead of following the literature, where a Portland Hills earthquake was simulated as a M 7.05, this simulation used the M 6.8 default HAZUS setting.

In other words, the number of displaced people selected from within the infectious disease model data would not be artificially inflated by data generated from the newer HAZUS model.

Besides being used for generating a map of displaced people, the output from an earthquake simulation can also begin to shed light on which emergency shelters should be selected. While the Red Cross emergency shelters are not necessarily part of the HAZUS inventory, as noted earlier, 78% of the emergency shelters are schools, and every school in the greater Portland area is included as an essential facility within the HAZUS inventory. Furthermore, after simulating an earthquake, results can be obtained regarding both the functionality of schools as well as the amount of structural damage incurred. HAZUS classifies structural damage by severity: slight, moderate, extensive, and complete damage. The software can also output at least slight, at least moderate, and at least extensive damage. Buildings that exhibit “at least extensive damage,” which broadly implies their partial collapse or failure (Mitigation Division, 2013a),²⁸ would arguably be untenable as emergency shelters. Using the damage of schools as a proxy for the damage of Red Cross shelters, the average probability of schools exhibiting “at least extensive damage” was calculated for each census tract. Other factors, like damage to the road network or debris in the streets, might also weigh against the selection of certain emergency shelters; however, the output from HAZUS did not show any significant damage or hindrance in this respect, and therefore no data was stored regarding these two potential impediments.

Road Network Dataset

One reasonable scenario is that people select or are assigned to the nearest emergency shelter. Given that a set of displaced households and a set of emergency shelters are located somewhere in a geographic plane, one can theoretically use Euclidean distance to allocate displaced people to nearest shelters and thereby (re)create the *neighbourhood effect* that one would expect from nearest shelter selection or assignments. If the goal is to analyse social compositions at emergency shelters, why add complexity by introducing a road network? The reason is that if one superimposes a road network over this plane of points that represent displaced households and emergency shelters, whereby people are constrained to move along line segments, then suddenly the nearest shelters change as well as the social composition at shelters. The road network has the effect of increasing randomness in shelter populations.

²⁸ Each classification has a unique definition that corresponds with the type of building stock damaged. For more details, please refer to the “Earthquake Model Technical Manual.”

To this end, movement from an origin to a destination is not simply dictated by the road network layout; indeed, apart from traffic signals and one-way streets, road networks have hierarchical structures, ranging from private roads to multilane motorways. These hierarchies exacerbate the sparseness of roads used to travel from one destination to another. As people gravitate toward motorways to cover greater distances in less time, potentially very few pathways might practically be utilised, particularly when travelling long distances. With many emergency shelters accessed along a few pathways, the socio-spatially distance between people sharing (or competing for) the same shelter increases.

Road networks not only play a role in displaced people's access to emergency shelters, but in turn, knowing how displaced people navigate road networks, and more specifically, knowing which shelters are nearest to displaced people's households, should influence which emergency shelters are opened in the first place. The concept of "nearest" can be understood as a function of distance or time. Optimising for time is much more complex, requiring simulating the interactions between people as they move through the road network. Indeed, simply having a map of average vehicle travel speeds under normal traffic conditions at various times of the day would not likely represent what happens during a no-notice evacuation. An agent-based model (ABM) could potentially help determine which emergency shelters are nearest in terms of travel time. That said, optimising for travel time is an objective that is important but distinct from what is being researched here. While minimising travel time to shelters is not the focus of this research, the *difference* in travel time between nearest shelters (whichever ones are selected) and socially optimised shelters is relevant—as stated earlier, the difference in travel times could serve as a gauge to adopt or forgo socially oriented evacuations. With this in mind, the road network will serve two purposes for this research: first, the road network will be used to select emergency shelters based on nearest distance to households; second, an ABM will be introduced after emergency shelters have been selected as a way to understand the impact of travel time between various allocation scenarios. Both these steps require obtaining a virtual road network and preparing it to simulate the movement of people.

Available Data. The road network used in this research is from OpenStreetMap (OSM), which provides editable, crowd-sourced street data for most of the world. The motivation for OSM emerged in response to the restrictive use policies of companies offering

proprietary mapping and navigation services.²⁹ After major disasters, OSM has become a platform to rapidly map changing or uncharted landscapes to support humanitarian aid. This has resulted in freely available maps not only of well-trodden places but also of previously neglected or poorly mapped regions of the world (Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team, n.d.; Palen et al., 2015).

As for acquiring a map spanning northern Oregon to southern Washington, due to limitations in transferring large and complex data, one cannot export such a map directly from OSM. One approach is to freely download state-wide OSM data from the software consulting and development firm Geofabrik (<https://download.geofabrik.de>);³⁰ however, using state-wide data for both Oregon and Washington, which includes moderately large cities beyond the study area (such as Seattle), would result in unnecessarily long runtimes when conducting road network analysis. A more tactical approach, and the one adopted for this research, is to download a bounding box (from a mirror of the OSM database) of only the greater Portland, Oregon area through software called Overpass API (<http://overpass-api.de/>).

Content of Data. To simulate people's movement on this road network, the network must be completely traversable. OSM contains data that might prevent vehicles from reaching a destination or, otherwise, throw an error message or warning within certain software. Some examples include road closures or barriers that limit vehicle mobility; the latter includes swinging, lifting and chained gates as well as bollards and ground spikes. Temporary barriers, such as debris and logs, could also restrict vehicle movement. Other times, OSM users might input illogical street data, for example, when a one-way street also leads to a dead-end. Furthermore, the streets could be inadvertently disconnected from the larger road network, which would leave vehicles stranded on roadway "islands." Notwithstanding user input errors, these disjointed road segments are also artefacts found at map boundaries; this is where an otherwise connected road network dips inside a bounding box, where the only path to access other roads within the bounding box would require travelling outside the bounding box, i.e., along roads that are no longer part of the map.

Resolving the above problems by creating a single, "clean" road network that would be compatible with all subsequently used software is not necessarily advisable; this approach may

²⁹ Companies such as TomTom (<https://www.tomtom.com/>) and HERE (<https://www.here.com/>) offer detailed street data; however, purchasing this data, even with academic pricing, would likely deter replication of findings. Additionally, the data available from their premium services is not necessary for this research.

³⁰ Geofabrik produces these maps using a command-line Java application, Osmosis (Osmosis, 2023).

result in information loss by catering to the simplest input required for all software to operate. As various analytical tools used within this research can directly read OSM data, using network cleaning procedures inherent to these tools (or methods involving the least modifications respective to each software) ensures that all relevant OSM data is utilised to the fullest extent.

Preparation of Data. This research will take advantage of two pieces of software requiring “clean” road networks: (1) ArcGIS Network Analyst, which is a network-based spatial analysis tool for solving routing problems (used to determine which emergency shelters are nearest to displaced people’s households), and (2) MATSim, which is a framework for large-scale transportation simulations (used to compare travel times to emergency shelters). Beginning with the former, along with enabling ArcGIS Network Analyst, ArcGIS Editor for OSM toolbox was downloaded and installed; this latter software loads and converts OSM data into “Network Configuration Files,” the format used by Network Analyst.³¹ As there is no ruleset for this conversion, a built-in network configuration sample file, DriveGeneric.xml, was loaded as a template for vehicle routing. After the OSM data was imported into Network Analyst, a new “OD cost matrix” was set up, routing vehicles from every household and emergency shelter (points of origin) along least-cost paths to a single destination point that was positioned within the largest road network component. The OD cost matrix solver is one of the fastest and most scalable algorithms within Network Analyst, and while the numeric results are not of interest here, the warnings flagged by this algorithm, on the other hand, are useful in identifying non-traversable road network links.

Prior to running the OD cost matrix solver, some road network impediments can be easily disabled for all routing algorithms. This includes “point barriers,” which were not only disabled (within the “Analysis Settings” tab of “Layer Properties”) but, moreover, completely removed as a Network Analyst data source (within the “Sources” tab of “Network Dataset Properties”). Likewise, “access” and “closed roads” were also disabled. Now when running the solver, the most likely non-traversable road network warnings thrown are either (1) a one-way street leading to a dead-end or (2) road segments that are disconnected from the largest road network component.

Using this list of flagged errors/warnings, one can then zoom in on each road network impediment and correct it. One approach is to bypass the non-traversable roads by manually

³¹ A known problem with ArcGIS Editor for OSM is that “background processing” needs to be disabled. After loading and creating a network dataset, background processing can be enabled for better computational performance.

moving each stranded household or emergency shelter onto the nearest traversable roadway link. The other option is to delete the non-traversable roads, which would have the same effect; once again, the households or emergency shelters would connect to the nearest traversable roadway link. This research used the second approach. The road network is now prepared to run any of the more complex algorithms free of vehicles being stranded.

The other software that uses road networks within this research, MATSim, can also import OSM data. MATSim has a built-in network converter, `OsmNetworkReader`. This converter makes use of OSM's "highway tag," which categorises each road as either a motorway, trunk, primary, secondary, tertiary, minor, unclassified, residential, or living street. The program then assigns each road type a default legal speed limit (maximum speed). Differentiating between a legal speed limit and the actual speed vehicles travel (herein referred to as "free speed"), MATSim also includes a default weighting factor to correct for either decreases in free speed, for example, due to traffic signals (traffic signals are otherwise not corrected for in this research) or increases in free speed due to not honouring the legal speed limit. A default number of lanes as well as "flow capacity" are also attributed to each roadway type. The flow capacity simply denotes the maximum number of vehicles per time unit that can exit/pass a road link.³²

For any given road, if the OSM data contains the max speed or number of lanes, then `OsmNetworkReader` will overwrite the default values. The software also checks the OSM data for one-way streets and roundabouts (the latter is a type of junction, which is converted into a one-way street). In the case where trunks, primary, or secondary roads are marked as one-way streets, the default number of lanes is changed from one to two.³³

After the OSM data is read into MATSim, the road network geometry can then be simplified. To this end, roadways are often comprised of multiple adjoining roadway links, which allow roadways to curve or change directions. MATSim includes a function to replace all roadways that span from one intersection to another intersection with a single link (called using `reader.setKeepPath(False)`). This effectively reduces the number of roadway links for the greater Portland, Oregon area.

³² A simulation can run faster or use less computational resources by drawing from a sample of the population. If this is done, then the proper traffic congestion can be reintroduced via adjusting the flow capacity by a factor equivalent to the population sampling rate.

³³ One should note that unlike ArcGIS Editor for OSM, `OsmNetworkReader` does not import turn restrictions (e.g., no right turn, no left turn, no straight-on or no u-turn are considered), which might lead to slightly shorter and less accurate shortest-distance routing paths compared to ArcGIS Network Analyst.

The road network still needs to be cleaned, which is accomplished with MATSim's NetworkCleaner. This program removes all road links that cannot be accessed by all other road links. NetworkCleaner first removes road links that either have no other link feeding into or exiting from it (i.e., one-way streets that are also dead ends). The software then identifies the largest network component (commented within the code as the "largest cluster") and then rids the network of all smaller components. The road network is now ready for MATSim to run simulations without being flagged as non-traversable.

Who Needs Shelter?

Methodological Overview

Although this research focuses specifically on displaced people at emergency shelters, displaced people cannot be treated as the sole agents within simulations when the desired output is travel time to emergency shelters. On the road network, people seeking shelter will interact with those who are not displaced as well as those who have made alternative housing arrangements, and these interactions will increase traffic congestion to more realistic levels.

As an evacuation features different levels of traffic on the road network at different times, the people represented by the synthetic social network data are categorised into subgroups. Each subgroup has a generalised objective, which more importantly is associated with vehicles being placed on or off the road network over the course of the evacuation. One of these subgroups, those seeking refuge at emergency shelters, consists of households treated as variables, allocated in separate experiments to either (1) random, (2) nearest, or (3) social-nearest shelters. Each of these experiments is simulated against a much larger backdrop of people, which brings into play two other noteworthy subgroups. The first includes people who travel home and find that their residence is perfectly habitable; these people will not be displaced, and their journey will end at this point. The second subgroup includes people who travel home and then must travel again to reach habitable accommodations, such as visiting non-displaced friends or family. The travel plans for these last two subgroups are held constant across all experiments.³⁴ The remainder of this section is dedicated to showing and discussing how these subgroups, those acting as both the experimental variables and constants, are logically selected and routed by combining information from across all acquired datasets.

³⁴ However, their routes might slightly vary in reaction to different patterns of people seeking shelter.

Categorise People During an Evacuation

The earthquake data and the synthetic population data share overlapping spatial and demographic features, which allows one to create a household-level representation of who might require temporary shelter in Portland, Oregon during an evacuation. To this end, HAZUS makes a distinction between (1) displaced households and (2) people requiring temporary shelter. Taking some liberty, if one interprets the latter as a subgroup of the former, then households that fall outside of this subgroup would essentially form another distinct category of households. In other words, displaced households can be subdivided into two categories: (1A) those requiring temporary shelter and (1B) those who have found alternative housing. Furthermore, as HAZUS incorporates household demographics as weighted modification factors when generating probabilities of people requiring temporary shelter, this internal logic can be lifted and applied to the synthetic population. Thus, instead of randomly selecting people requiring temporary shelter among the displaced households, a more nuanced selection can occur at the household level by taking advantage of the demographics captured within the synthetic population data.

More precisely, the first step is to spatially overlay the earthquake and synthetic population data. Using software such as ArcGIS, households from the synthetic population data can be associated with census tracts from the earthquake data.³⁵ Given the total number of households and the total number of people within each census tract (derived from this spatial overlay) as well as the percentages of displaced households and the percentages of people requiring temporary shelter within each census tract (the two outputs described in the earthquake data section), one can determine how many displaced households and people requiring temporary shelter must be selected within each census tract from the synthetic population data. With this information, one can then generate a random sample of displaced households. As for people requiring temporary shelter, while a target number of people has now been calculated, selecting this subpopulation from displaced households based on demographic factors requires several additional steps.

Beginning with defining what demographic factors can be readily utilised within simulations, although HAZUS considers multiple demographics when determining the probability of people requiring temporary shelter, only “ethnicity” and “household income” are preloaded into the software with weighted default values. Of these two demographics, household income is also present in the synthetic population data. Moreover, while HAZUS

³⁵ This can be accomplished with ArcGIS’ “Select by Location” tool.

contains population data at the census block level (the smallest geographic unit used by the United States Census Bureau), the output resolution for its earthquake modelling is at the census tract level. Therefore, the household income levels have been averaged across all census blocks within census tracts. On the other hand, households within the synthetic population dataset have income levels directly associated with census block data. This means that a more refined selection of people requiring temporary shelter is possible by reapplying HAZUS' income weighting factor on a house-by-house basis within the synthetic population data.

Select Displaced People

How can one simultaneously randomly select displaced households, where households contain various numbers of people, while also satisfying the objective that the total number of people across all selected households equals a specified value? This begs a very simple solution: For each income bracket within each census tract, randomly select enough households such that the sum of all household members is equal to or just exceeds the specified number of displaced people. In cases where the specified number is exceeded, the last household (or one household randomly selected) must then be divided into household members requiring and not requiring shelter. This of course is a perfectly feasible scenario, which could affect up to 2,060 households in this given disaster scenario (i.e., 412 census tracts, each containing five household income brackets). On the other hand, splitting apart households, where some members seek shelter and others are perfectly fine is strange. At the expense of slightly sacrificing a pseudo-random selection process, one can methodologically preserve both the household as a unit of measure and cumulatively have members across households sum to specified totals. The most straightforward approach involves an iterative process of randomly selecting households that sum to specified totals, and if the households do not exactly sum to those specified numbers, then the process is repeated until they do. Conversely, if selecting displaced people randomly is deemed more important than selecting an exact number of displaced people, then what is above referred to as the "last household" should be randomly included or excluded. One can furthermore tighten the variance by subjecting the last household to either inclusion or exclusion based on which outcome (inclusion or exclusion) minimises the deviation from specified totals (with a coin toss to settle ties). This last approach was chosen for this research.

The appropriate method is context dependent. In the case of selecting who will be displaced for a simulation, this research chose to preserve the household as a unit of measure while emphasising a random selection process and slightly de-emphasising the specified

displaced totals projected by HAZUS. Strict adherence to HAZUS output might take priority if the output were a prediction of who is displaced; however, this research uses HAZUS simply as a guide for generating a realistic displaced population, and the selection process thereby reaffirms this perspective.

Displaced People Not Requiring Temporary Shelter. Several hierarchical subgroups have been created thus far. The first division is between displaced households and non-displaced households. Displaced households are then further subdivided into two groups: displaced households requiring temporary shelter and displaced households *not* requiring shelter, i.e., people who found alternative housing. Now one can take a closer look at those who found alternative housing, and given the data acquired for this research, create yet another subdivision: people visiting non-displaced friends or family *within* the greater Portland area and those finding accommodation *outside* the greater Portland area. The motivation for this last categorical division is to create a framework not simply for placing vehicles on the roadway (thus impeding those seeking emergency shelter) but, moreover, to create two distinct patterns of vehicle movement: the first being an interwoven pattern, characterised by people bi-directionally crossing each other's paths (this is typified by displaced people travelling to friend's houses, but as these friends are not displaced themselves, some directionality away from the disaster is still apparent); the second pattern is one of dispersion, characterised by displaced people moving uniformly away from the disaster's epicentre (this is typified by displaced people leaving Portland and travelling farther afield to safety). By controlling the ratio between displaced people travelling *within* and *outside* the greater Portland area, a method to interpolate between these two roadway patterns will be proposed.

The primary use of social networks within this research is to allocate displaced people to socially oriented emergency shelters; however, within the greater context of an evacuation, social networks would realistically serve a more preliminary function, that of friends and family providing displaced people with housing prior to any need for displaced people to seek temporary shelter. Unfortunately, no studies have been conducted regarding the extent to which certain social network structures make people more or less prone to needing emergency assistance. While intuitively, social networks (alongside household income and ethnicity) could become a weighted "modification factor" within HAZUS and help determine which census regions require temporary shelter, the fact of the matter is that social network data collection is in its infancy, and analysing such data regarding who requires temporary shelter is simply nonexistent. Absent knowing specifically what network structures would prevent

displaced people from requiring shelter—whether being the number of social connections or the geographic separation of egos from alters—this research is not positioned to recommend a new modification factor scheme without empirical evidence.

On the other hand, instead of using social networks to identify *who* requires shelter, given that other well-studied factors are employed in this determination (for example, household income levels), subsequently using social networks to identify *where* those not requiring shelter should go adds a layer of realism to simulations; indeed, using the social network in this way not only places a representative number of vehicles on the roadway, but it frames the entire evacuation in social terms. This perspective is sorely needed. While this research focuses on the social compositions of displaced people at emergency shelters, more holistically (and in practice), non-displaced people might very well identify themselves as willing to host a certain number of displaced people within their social networks, that is, at a given “social distance” away (say one or two friends-of-a-friend away) for a specified time period. Using social networks as a vetting process to host displaced people within non-displaced households before they require emergency shelters is beyond the scope of this research, but a more extensive model could look at this additional social dimension as well as the geographic relationships between displaced people staying at homes and displaced people staying at shelters,³⁶ and more broadly, the socio-spatial relationships between displaced people and the host community.

As for the realism of displaced households visiting friends and family during an evacuation, in terms of vehicle movement patterns, using social networks in this manner does not fully capture the complexity of where people would likely travel during an evacuation, and thereby the road network will be loaded but perhaps not in the most realistic way. Indeed, tourists and people passing through Portland should be present on the road network, but the acquired dataset does not account for them. Additionally, the synthetic social network is geographically bound and does not depict people travelling to friends and family in neighbouring towns or states. Due to such cases, one might expect heavier use of motorways as people try to evacuate the city than would be represented in simulations based purely on rewiring social network structures within the greater Portland area. Likewise, operable hotels within and near Portland might be destinations of choice for many (excluding those in the

³⁶ One approach is to send displaced people to their socially closest acquaintance. Alternatively, sending displaced people to the household of an acquaintance who also lives near an emergency shelter might prove advantageous. Certain services and information sharing might be available for displaced people at emergency shelters, which could be utilised during the day without displaced people having to spend the night at the shelter.

lowest household income brackets); however, hotel locations and capacities are not part of the acquired dataset. As hotels are often located off motorways, once again, visiting these unaccounted destinations would likely entail heavy motorway travel. Seemingly, a more realistic evacuation simulation must somehow create more traffic on motorways. As displaced people visiting friends and family within the greater Portland area will mostly be travelling short distances along local roads within the heart or fringe of the city (where most people live), some of these displaced people should be rerouted outside of the greater Portland area, where farther travel distances and an ever-decreasing road network density would place more displaced people on motorways.

Without knowing exactly how many displaced people to send outside the greater Portland area to replicate expected conditions on motorways during evacuations, this research first examines non-displaced people who *could* host others and then, by exclusion, allocates the remaining population to the boundary of the greater Portland area. To this end, one precondition for friendship would be some initial amount of time spent together. The synthetic population data not only contains social network connections but “contact” time between connections. Using this information, viable hosts were treated as those non-displaced people whose contact time with displaced people was greater than 10 minutes during a nominal day. This number can be adjusted up or down to establish a minimal hosting threshold. Those below the threshold (or those who have no non-displaced social acquaintances to begin with) will be rerouted outside the greater Portland area. Recognising that people who spend time together may not do so by choice and that time spent together may not be the best indicator of friendship or, more precisely, a willingness to host others, if more vehicles need to be placed on motorways to simulate a realistic evacuation, then randomly selecting additional households to evacuate outside the greater Portland area would be a non-presumptuous way to accomplish this.

Although a method has now been proposed to gain some control over simulating traffic patterns during an evacuation, what these traffic patterns are supposed to represent is still unknown and a challenge to predict. Going forward, studying past evacuations might lend insight into what percentage of people will leave a city during certain types of disasters.³⁷ This could be complemented with more in-depth studies on human behaviour to create a first

³⁷ Predicting who will evacuate is a very complex problem. For example, people’s experience with past disasters, particularly those that occurred in recent history, represent one of many factors contributing to how people perceive, interpret and act when confronted with a threat. Whether to evacuate or not is also not entirely an individual-based decision. A city’s mayor, for example, might place a recommended or mandatory evacuation order.

principles model of who might host displaced people and which displaced people are willing to be hosted. In the first instance, however, this research did not arbitrarily select an unknown number of people to evacuate the greater Portland area. On the other hand, through an intuitively-set contact time threshold, the number of possible hosts was slightly reduced, which thereby sent more people outside the city.

The specific logic used to determine who will seek refuge with a social acquaintance is as follows: for each displaced household not requiring temporary shelter, after looking at each household member's non-displaced social acquaintances, the non-displaced social acquaintance who shared the most cumulative contact seconds with one or more of the displaced household members was selected for hosting the entire displaced household. No minimum or maximum age restriction is applied regarding which households can or cannot host displaced people. Likewise, the maximum number of displaced households that a non-displaced household can host is also not restricted. The only restriction imposed is a minimum contact time of 10 minutes between people during a typical day, which is introduced to ensure that a meaningful social relationship can form between displaced people and potential hosts. The selected host's household location then became the travel destination for the displaced household.

The travel destination for those without meaningful social acquaintances is specified as the closest intersection point between the road network and a 75-mile radius placed around the geographic centroid of Portland, a distance that encompasses the entire synthetic population dataset. This 75-mile radius is also the minimum distance that would encircle all selected Red Cross emergency shelters (which will be discussed shortly). As vehicles within the simulation disappear off the roadway when they reach their destination, it is imperative that vehicles travelling to the perimeter do not disappear before people travelling to emergency shelters reach their destination—this could prematurely reduce traffic congestion and impact travel times to emergency shelters. The radius should also not be too large; the larger the roadway map, the longer the simulations will take to run.

For those people evacuating to the perimeter, after generating a list of coordinates where the 75-mile radius and roadway network intersect, the closest of these coordinates (destinations) to each displaced household (origin) was solved using ArcGIS Network Analysis' "OD cost matrix." This requires a cost function, input as either travel distance or travel time. As noted earlier (in the road network data section), during a no-notice evacuation, vehicle travel speeds may not coincide with given speed limits, which is what ArcGIS uses to calculate travel time in its OD cost matrix. Travel distance, by contrast, is a measure that does

not fluctuate with roadway conditions, which makes it easily quantifiable. In this particular instance, however, inputting travel time into the OD cost matrix would result in more closest destination points being selected on motorways, which ultimately would increase traffic on motorways during the simulation and better fulfil the purpose of why vehicles are being sent outside the greater Portland area in the first place. To complicate the matter, in order to make simple, declarative statements regarding which Red Cross shelters to select, this research will eventually describe using a distance cost metric—selecting some destinations (Red Cross shelters) using distance and other factors (nearest exit points leading outside of the greater Portland area) using time creates an inconsistency, which is not inherently problematic but perhaps over-complicates the simulation setup. Arguably sacrificing some realism for simplicity, this research used a distance cost metric to determine at which points a subset of displaced people will exit the greater Portland area.

If the goal were to place more vehicles on motorways during evacuation simulations, then why not select intersections where specifically motorways, as opposed to all roadways, overlap with the 75-mile radius? While the motorways are likely underutilised with the current simulation setup, having everyone exit the greater Portland area only using motorways is also not realistic; particularly with traffic congestion on motorways, local roads will provide alternative routes out of the city. Local roads would also be used by people who do not live near motorways—it would be counterintuitive to have vehicles traverse unnecessary long distances within the simulation to convene with a heavily-used motorway. To further qualify what has been proposed, the method of sending a subset of displaced people to the closest coordinates where the road network and a specified radius intersect would increase motorway traffic, not by the greatest number of vehicles but still substantially and, moreover, in a manner that makes sense. With enough information and foresight, the number of people exiting the city can be scaled up or down to more realistically capture the traffic patterns on the roadway during an evacuation. This method does not require data beyond what has already been proposed, and the method can readily be applied to any city-wide evacuation simulation.

Displaced People Requiring Temporary Shelter. A method for selecting a representative subset of people requiring emergency shelter based on demographic attributes can draw inspiration from several literary tracks, including stratified sampling (a method from survey design) and congressional apportionment (a method from political sciences). Stratified sampling is a process of collectively dividing a population into mutually exclusive subgroups before performing a probabilistic sampling procedure (often a simple random sample). In the

case of this research, the subgroups (also known as strata) can represent different household income brackets. As people from similar household income brackets might geographically cluster together, stratifying the population and randomly selecting displaced households from within each stratum would lend itself to a more nuanced displaced person map.

Congressional apportionment has a slightly different relationship with stratification. While stratified sampling is typically accompanied by justification as to why and how strata should be defined, apportionment begins with pre-defined strata (in the case of the United States, 50 strata representing each state), and the emphasis shifts to a very precise calculation of sampling sizes that proportionally represent each state's population (the United States Constitution, Article 1, Section 2, Clause 3, mandates apportionment and defines state populations according to the most recent decennial census). Each sample of the population has a delegated representative, i.e., an elected person who is sent to the House of Representatives, and the number of representatives is determined by congressional districts. A state with more congressional districts has more seats in the House of Representatives and thereby has greater influence over the national agenda.³⁸

While stratified sampling and congressional apportionment have distinct literary traditions, Wright (2012) demonstrates that fundamentally these are special cases of a more general problem:

In particular, we demonstrate the equivalence of two well-known problems—the optimal allocation of the fixed overall sample size N among L strata under stratified random sampling and the optimal allocation of the $H = 435$ seats among the 50 states for apportionment of the U.S. House of Representatives following each decennial census.

Wright concludes that recent apportionment methods, which by design minimise variance, would benefit random stratified sampling procedures; in the best of cases, random stratified sampling utilises controlled rounding that may generate variable results (Wright, 2012). The precision in congressional appointment is of paramount importance, with real legislative consequences for under or overrepresenting individual state interests. As a result, the non-integer, fractional portions that almost always accompany a fair distribution of voting power require unbiased discretisation (neither favouring large or small states) while simultaneously

³⁸ There are also non-voting members in the House of Representatives, which includes delegates or resident commissioners from the five inhabited U.S. territories as well as from the federal district of Washington D.C. These members are not part of the apportionment process.

preserving the overall expected number of representatives (currently set at 435 seats)—practically speaking, having fractions of representatives is an impossibility.

In Appendix B, the research details how different apportionment methods resolve the integerisation problem. These methods inform the development of a new apportionment method that is better suited for the context at hand, i.e., selecting displaced people requiring temporary shelter.

Three Evacuation Scenarios for Those Requiring Temporary Shelter

Nearest Optimised Shelter Allocation

Having already selected destinations for everyone not requiring temporary shelter, the research must now focus on those who do require temporary shelter, namely which shelters are available and which ones might be selected. Using only the Red Cross shelter data, the shelters that could host greater than 400 people were selected as initial candidate shelters. After overlapping the Red Cross data with the earthquake data, one can now determine whether any of those candidate shelters are severely damaged; for this research, if any shelter had a greater than 5% chance of receiving extensive damage from the earthquake, then those shelters were removed from the list of candidate shelters. As noted earlier, HAZUS determines the probability of building damage based on construction material. That said, not all candidate emergency shelters are included in the HAZUS database. Knowing that 78% of shelters are schools and that the remaining shelters are likely of a similar construction type and meet a similar building code standard, and given that all schools are part of the HAZUS database and are represented in almost every census tract, the average damage to schools for each census tract was used as a proxy for determining the average damage to emergency shelters.

Which Red Cross shelters should be made publicly available depends upon the evacuation objective. This research has not put forward a socially oriented method for selecting emergency shelters (the focus has been on socially allocating displaced people to emergency shelters regardless of which shelters are selected). On the other hand, the literature contains well-defined methods for selecting a subset of closest-distance emergency shelters from a given set of household locations; these methods solve what is more generally known as the capacitated p -median problem. Solving the capacitated p -median problem entails not only selecting shortest-distance emergency shelter locations, but simultaneously, it involves allocating displaced people to those shelters.

The capacitated p -median problem (CPMP) consists of allocating p facilities (medians) among m candidate facilities (potential facilities or medians) to serve n demand points while minimising the sum of the travel costs between medians and demand points, with the additional constraint that the capacity of each median is not exceeded by the demand points assigned to it. The CPMP is NP-hard (Garey & Johnson, 1979), and for this research, the method used should be compatible with GIS data as input. Fortunately, location-allocation models have been “loosely coupled” with GIS software, such as ArcGIS and TransCAD, since the late 1990s (Church, 2002; Lei et al., 2016). With the p -median problem’s theoretical and computational links with location set-covering and maximal covering location problems (Church & ReVelle, 1976)³⁹ as well as having a general formulation posed to support a diversity of special cases and multiple objectives (i.e., by varying how the objective coefficients are derived), Hillsman (1984) suggested that the p -median problem could act as the computational core for location-allocation and spatial analysis software. In this vein, the software used in this research, ArcGIS Network Analyst, generates an origin-destination matrix of shortest-path costs between medians and demand points, which is then reconstructed for a number of different problems through what ArcGIS refers to as “Hillsman editing” (ESRI, n.d.). The data is stored in a format specified by Densham and Rushton (1992b) and employs their Global Regional Interchange Algorithm (GRIA; 1992a), which is a computationally efficient modification of what Hillsman originally proposed to solve the p -median problem, the vertex substitution/interchange heuristic of Teitz and Bart (1968; Church, 2002). This leads to near-optimal CPMP results.

The justification for using the above-mentioned CPMP algorithm needs to be contextualised. Should one minimise the total (or average) travel costs to emergency shelters, or should one minimise the travel costs for those travelling the furthest (or longest)? Or from another perspective, should emergency shelters be filled as quickly as possible, or should they be filled to capacity as quickly as possible? These questions highlight two different approaches, respectively understood as the p -median problem (a minimsum problem) and the p -centre problem (a minimax problem). The latter p -centre problem consists of minimising the maximum travel cost to facilities, which could lead to a very different pattern of shelter selection. While this lesser-known p -centre was not used here, there are instances where this

³⁹ Set-covering problems attempt to identify the minimum number of facilities needed to serve all demand points within a specified distance or time. Maximal covering problems attempt to maximise the number of demand points served by a fixed number of facilities within a specified distance or time (Mohammadi et al., 2009). As all displaced people should have access to emergency shelters, a set-covering problem (as opposed to a maximal covering problem) could have been used in this research to identify nearest shelters; however, without having to specify a minimum travel cost, the capacitated p -median problem seemed more appropriate for this research.

would be the more reasonable protocol. For example, if people were evacuating by foot, minimising the maximum travel distance with the p -centre problem might be the difference between people (particularly the elderly and young) reaching and not reaching the shelters. If driving conditions become unsafe over the course of an evacuation (from water, ice, wind, debris, etc.), then an early spike in deteriorating conditions might warrant the p -median problem (get as many people out of harm's way as quickly as possible), whereas a later spike might warrant the p -centre problem (get everyone off the roads before conditions worsen). The decision to treat an evacuation as a p -median or p -centre problem is not straightforward, and with ethically-charged consequences, where sacrifices are unavoidable, this must be taken very seriously. The literature has completely neglected an ethical conversation revolving around the selection of nearest emergency shelters. Although this research is not focused on optimising nearest shelter selection, defining "nearest" is still necessary within this research and requires not only distinguishing between distance and time (as a travel cost) but also between who does and does not benefit from minimising this travel cost.

Unfortunately, minimax problems, such as the p -centre problem, cannot be expressed as a special instance of the p -median problem (Lei et al., 2016) and therefore are not featured within ArcGIS. This is a clear limitation of using the p -median problem as a general solver. On the other hand, this is not justification for simply bypassing the p -centre problem when circumstances call for it. One would need to solve the capacitated version of the p -centre problem, and as the p -centre problem is strongly influenced by outliers, i.e., those living far removed from the masses, one might consider removing l number of outliers and solving for a carefully established subset of the population (Charikar et al., 2001); this is also an ethical consideration.

Should this research be using a deterministic CPMP algorithm? Selecting emergency shelters requires predicting who is displaced, and thereby a practical approach must account for uncertainty. The two most common ways of addressing uncertainty for location-allocation problems are to either build stochasticity or robustness into the optimisation.⁴⁰ With a stochastic model, the uncertainty (in this case, those predicted to be displaced) would be governed by a probability distribution, where the objective is to minimise the expected cost. As for a robust model, the probability is unknown, and the uncertainty is specified by discrete or continuous range scenarios (such as multiple hurricane paths, each of which displaces

⁴⁰ For a recent survey on facility location optimisation in the context of humanitarian logistics, please see Boonmee et al. (2017).

different people), where the objective is to minimise either the worst-case cost (minimise the maximum expected cost across all scenarios) or minimise worst-case regret (minimise the maximum difference or ratio between the expected and optimal cost across all scenarios; Snyder & Daskin, 2006). While a stochastic model works well in the long run, it might perform poorly for any given scenario; emergency management might prefer to account for all possible scenarios with an overly conservative/pessimistic minimax regret approach. Addressing the distinction between stochastic and robust optimisation, Snyder and Daskin (2006) combine the advantages of both and then demonstrate that improvements in robustness are possible with only small increases in expected cost. Their research proposed a “stochastic p -robustness” heuristics for both the p -median problem as well as the uncapacitated fixed-charge location problem; the latter would be of interest when establishing (and resourcing) emergency shelters under economic constraints.⁴¹ One can furthermore utilise a capacitated version of the robust p -median problem (Rahmaniani et al., 2013).

Drawing a distinction between practice and research, a deterministic CPMP model would produce better (nearer) results than either a stochastic or robust model, so to establish an upper bound for displaced people visiting nearest shelters within a simulation it makes sense to deviate from practice and take advantage of a priori knowledge. In this vein, one can proceed in two directions: first, given probabilities of displacement by census tract, one can principally generate a sample population of displaced people and then run this population through a CPMP algorithm. This process is then repeated multiple times so that the generated sample population on average represents what occurs from random sampling. The second approach is to generate a single, one-off instance of a displaced population and then run this population once through a CPMP algorithm. This latter approach could produce an outlier sample; however, disasters are unpredictable, and the population selected should have no bearing on the success of the underlying algorithms. Additionally, the first approach places a great deal of emphasis on the predictive power of HAZUS, which is not the intention of this research. Using HAZUS to generate probabilities of displacement from which a sample displaced population is selected would fulfil the role of HAZUS as far as this research is concerned. Considering the computational effort of running a CPMP algorithm multiple times and the simplicity of presenting a single subset of emergency shelters, this research used a one-off probabilistic selection of displaced people and a deterministic CPMP algorithm to determine the locations of emergency shelters.

⁴¹ For another perspective on resourcing emergency shelter before a disaster see Sharawi (2007).

Within ArcGIS Network Analyst, running a CPMP algorithm is straightforward. First, a new location–allocation problem must be created. A list of the different location–allocation solvers can be then found in the “Problem type” drop-down menu, located within the “Advanced Settings” tab of “Layer Properties.” The solvers include the following: “Minimize Impedance,” “Maximize Coverage,” “Maximize Capacitated Coverage,” “Minimize Facilities,” “Maximize Attendance,” “Maximize Market Share” and “Target Market Share.” The CPMP is found under the name “Maximize Capacitated Coverage.” The default capacity should be set to 400 (this is the maximum occupancy allowed in each shelter).⁴² Within the “Analysis Settings” tab, the impedance should be set to “Length (Meters).” The travel direction should be set to “Demand to Facility.” As for travel restrictions, one should unselect “Access” and “Closed” (otherwise people living on private or closed roads will be unable to traverse the road network) while leaving selected “Oneway” and “TurnRestrictions.” U-turns at junctions should also be allowed. Within the “Network Locations” tab, the demand points should be set to snap to the middle of the closest road or junction. Within the “Accumulation” tab, “Length” and “DriveTime” should be selected as output. Lastly, after opening the “Network Analyst window,” the facility locations (shelters) need to be loaded as well as the demand points (households). The weight ascribed to each household should equal the number of people within that household. With these inputs, ArcGIS Network Analyst will select a subset of emergency shelters that will be used for the three allocation scenarios explored in this research. One of these scenarios, allocating displaced people to nearest shelters, has simultaneously been solved with this location-allocation algorithm. The remaining two scenarios, allocating displaced people to random and socially optimised shelters, are not geographically dependent—with the locations set, one can subsequently solve these remaining scenarios.

Random Optimised Shelter Allocation

Randomness should not be interpreted as the absence of intervention; self-chosen destinations likely have underlying patterns or regularities. That said, even as a theoretical concept, a random “composition” of displaced people has value as an experimental control. This prompts two related questions: (1) in terms of social consequences and travel costs, what happens when displaced people visit random shelters, and (2) using these same metrics, how do random shelter compositions compare with socially oriented and nearest distance shelter

⁴² For more accuracy, one should set the default capacity to 399. With 43,811 people visiting 110 shelters, the target number of people in each shelter is approximately 398.21.

compositions? These questions are slightly different and require a different random control setup. The first question entails no intervention on behalf of emergency management (nor any rational thinking on behalf of displaced people) when determining which shelters to select. This results in a random number of displaced people at shelters as well as a random population composition. On the other hand, the second question entails some degree of intervention; with shelters having different locations and potentially different capacities (or different target occupancies), a fair comparison between random and the other shelter compositions, most explicitly evident when computing total or average travel costs across all shelters, demands that the same number of displaced people visit each shelter. In other words, the number of displaced people should be constrained while the population composition remains random.

Ultimately, the above questions are both interesting, and while one may contend that one of the above questions/approaches holds greater merit than the other, this research puts forth a framework where a single random control suffices to answer both questions, namely, instead of using shelter capacities to specify desired occupancies at shelters, this research further specifies a k -way partition of displaced people into shelters. The impetus for this decision is not simply to resolve any dispute over what a random control means, but moreover, the k -way partition is introduced to expand methods in the next section (regarding social partitioning).

Indeed, research can make assertions based on multiple runs of an experiment. In the case of random assignments, by specifying a k -way partition of displaced people into shelters, one arguably does not need to enforce shelter occupancies. According to the law of large numbers (LLN) theorem, as the number of model runs increases, the arithmetic mean of displaced people within each shelter across all model runs will most certainly converge to the expected value calculated from a k -way partition. However, given a limited number of model runs (due to computational overhead), this research has chosen to guarantee an expected number of displaced people at each shelter; any variance thereby found in the results is solely attributable to another random variable, i.e., a random seed used in the agent-based model simulation.

More generally speaking, one should note that constraining the number of displaced people within each shelter is not simply a component of the underlying objectives, i.e., part of the method for generating nearest distance and socially oriented assignments. The constraint independently has strategic merit during evacuations; indeed, specifying and honouring shelter capacities, even with random assignments, would prevent emergency shelters from being

under- and over-utilised. In this research, random is an experimental control but also a baseline strategy, which all other strategies build upon and integrate into their solutions.

In light of constrained random assignments having strategic value, the exact method employed here should reflect what emergency management would ideally be trying to accomplish: random assignments that perfectly (not approximately) match the desired occupancies at shelters. Much like during the selection process, where a target number of displaced individuals needed to be converted into a target number of displaced households, the assignments process must allocate a target number of individuals to shelters while evacuating people not as individuals but as members of households/groups. As a point of contrast, the selection process was not an optimisation problem; selecting displaced people from the infectious disease model based on HAZUS output was required to generate a representative population for the simulations; however, the assignments process is fundamentally an optimisation problem. Indeed, socially oriented and nearest distance assignments have objective functions, and the proposed methods strive toward an optimal solution. The same can be said about random assignments.

An exact number of nearly random displaced people were assigned to each shelter by treating the assignment process as a multiple-knapsack problem (MKP). Household IDs were randomly shuffled and then passed into an MKP algorithm (the R package, *Adagio*, was used to solve the MKP), where knapsack sizes represent shelter sizes, and where object weights represent the number of people within each shelter. When using such an algorithm, for the most part the randomised household ID order is respected. For example, the first shelter contains the first N number of people in the shuffled list; however, sometimes the sum of those people does not exactly fulfil the target occupancy criteria. This leads to some swapping of households of different sizes beginning with those near the N th household in the random list. After the exact number of people in the first shelter is satisfied, then the second shelter is filled with people beginning where the list left off. This process is repeated until all the shelters contain an exact number of displaced people. As described above, the process does not quite respect random shuffling.

Social–Nearest Optimised Shelter Allocation

Against the backdrop of random and nearest shelter compositions, a method for generating socially oriented shelter compositions, as the primary variable within these experiments, will be explained. This research, however, will take a step beyond simply preserving displaced people's social networks; a method is put forth to simultaneously assign

displaced people to nearest shelters without sacrificing the social benefits. To this end, a unique feature of the experimental design, as concerns k -way partitioning, is that after having socially grouped equal numbers of people together, these groups can be assigned to random shelter locations or, more thoughtfully, to shelter locations that reduce displaced people's travel costs. For the more broadly applicable non- k -way scenario, where unique shelter capacities may be utilised, the hurdle associated with strategically assigning partitioned social groups to locations, which may or may not be interchangeably sized, can be overcome by embedding nearest shelter assignments into the same graph or hypergraph as displaced people's social connections, allowing the partitioner to solve multiple objectives simultaneously and potentially doing so with different target-sized partitions. This latter approach will be explored here.

Moreover, instead of solving the above problem using graphs, this research will showcase a methodology using more complex hypergraphs. One can easily deduce a method for graphs from this description. The starting point is taking the 20,910 households that require shelter and generating a new social network. As multiple individuals from a household might know one or more individuals from another household, the number of edges between households (or when aggregated, the edge weight between households) might be greater than one. Regarding the data used in this research, 99.6% of the households (20,839 households) share only one connection with another household.⁴³ However, the remaining, more connected households still need to be incorporated into a methodology, and in this case, appropriately represented within a hypergraph.

With a graph as a starting point (i.e., a social network derived from modifying an infectious disease contact network), one must first convert the graph into a hypergraph. In the most straightforward sense, converting from edges to hyperedges requires that two conditions are met: (1) all nodes that comprise a hyperedge are connected to one another, and (2) all edge weights between these nodes must share the same value. In other words, a hyperedge is a single edge connecting multiple nodes and has a single weight attributed to it. Thereby, given a community represented as a graph with the same edge weights, this research proposes passing such a graph through a maximal clique algorithm to effectively discover hyperedges (maximal cliques are the largest complete subgraphs, i.e., where all adjacent nodes in a graph are connected to one another; this creates what is known as a conformal hypergraph (Lauritzen,

⁴³ As for the remaining 0.4%, 311 pairs of households share 2 connections, 16 pairs of households share 3 connections, 2 pairs of households share 4 connections, 1 pair of households shares 5 connections, and 1 pair of households shares 6 connections.

Speed & Vijayan, 1984). How to reconstruct and prepare a graph with multiple connections between nodes/households for this maximal clique algorithm requires some interpretation. One method that remains faithful to the spirit of hypergraphs and preserving communities is proposed below.

Consider every pairwise connection between households as adding social value or social affinity between those households (the added value does not need to be linear). Regarding the synthetic network used in this research, while most households share only one connection, the number of household-to-household connections ranges from one to six. In this example, one strategy is to take the primary graph and use it to create six different subgraphs, where each subgraph can be thought of as a layer. The first subgraph contains all edges, i.e., all six edge values are represented in this subgraph. The second subgraph contains only edges from the top five greatest values. The third graph contains only edges from the top four greatest values. This logic is repeated for all six subgraphs, and the edge weights within each subgraph are set to one. These subgraphs are then merged and passed through a maximal clique algorithm. As a result, households that have greater social value/affinity for each other are now grouped together with greater redundancy by multiple layers of hyperedges.

Hypergraphs can be weighted in various ways. As already described, one can attribute greater value to grouped nodes by layering/overlapping hyperedges. This strategy is unique to hypergraphs and, more specifically, to hypergraph partitioning; the graph partitioner, METIS, for example, cannot accept overlapping edges, whereas its hypergraph counterpart, hMETIS (Karypis & Kumar, 1998), can do so, i.e., by accepting overlapping hyperedges. The only way for graphs to add value to grouped nodes is by adjusting edge weights, a feat readily accomplished by hypergraphs as well (via adjusting hyperedge weights). The different methods of weighting hypergraphs can be combined, which opens the possibility of creating new social structures. For example, one can group people together if and only if everyone knows each other and, additionally, values each other similarly (to illustrate this special case, see Figure 7). Revisiting the synthetic network used in this research, one can accomplish this by dividing the primary graph into six subgraphs, each of which represents a distinct edge value. Each of the subgraphs is then individually passed through the maximal clique algorithm. The formed hyperedges are then associated with a hyperedge weight (one of the six edge values). Taken together, these hyperedges form a hypergraph. Unlike the former approach, greater valued group connections are represented by hyperedge weights (as opposed to overlapping hyperedges). During this process, some community information might be lost; indeed, the

Figure 7

Note. Juxtaposing two ways of converting from graphs to hypergraphs. The latter is a special case, which emphasizes connections between people who not only know each other but also value their friendship similarly.

maximal cliques are being divided into smaller cliques (cliques with shared edge values), which creates a greater number of “fragmented” hyperedges.⁴⁴

Due to the sparseness of the given social network and the small percentage of households sharing more than one connection, the partitioned results for the above two methods should be similar. The presented methods thereby stand as gestures of what might be theoretically relevant given a denser and more intricately weighted social network. In future contexts, the nuances of converting edges to hyperedges might have social consequences and thereby benefit from more extensive research. Such an investigation would fall under a greater research umbrella, which includes how to appropriately weight edges and hyperedges (reflecting both the number of people belonging to a community as well as the ascribed value of one community in juxtaposition to other communities) as well as, even more broadly speaking, how to aggregate edges and hyperedges across multiplex or multi-view networks. This area of future research will be discussed in a subsequent chapter. For this experiment, the second proposed conversion between graphs and hypergraphs was implemented (a hypergraph with emphasis on shared connections of equal value, which is expressed via hyperedge weights).

When integrating nearest shelter assignments into a hypergraph, the correct setup has little room for interpretation. The basic concept begins with introducing virtual nodes (i.e., dummy nodes), which represent different shelters; as 110 shelters are available for displaced people in this experiment, 110 virtual nodes are created. Knowing the nearest shelter assignments from the p -median algorithm, new hyperedges can be drawn connecting each of the 20,910 displaced households to one of the virtual nodes. Taking advantage of the fixed vertices constraint within hypergraph partitioners, these virtual nodes are “fixed” into separate and distinct partitions, meaning that the hypergraph partitioner cannot partition these nodes together. This is accomplished by passing the hypergraph partitioner a fixed vertices file, where -1 is assigned to all node IDs in the social network (ID numbers 1 through 20,910), and sequential integers, beginning with 1 and ending with 110, are assigned to the virtual nodes (ID numbers 20,911 through 20,210). As for node weights, for nodes/households that comprise the social network, each is assigned a weight equal to the number of household members it represents, whereas for virtual nodes/emergency shelters, each is assigned a weight of 0.

⁴⁴ One should carefully note that one cannot convert from a graph to a hypergraph without knowing what a specific graph represents; while hyperedges might add layers of intended information (as the original graph structure might lack adequate expressiveness), hyperedges might also impose new ideas. Without being provided with a hypergraph from the start, some interpretation is necessary when converting from graphs to hypergraphs.

Regarding hyperedge weights, social network hyperedges are assigned weighted values ranging from 100 to 600, representing the number of pairwise household connections (1 through 6), that is, after being multiplied by 100. As for hyperedges connected to virtual nodes, their weights are all set to 1. With this setup, the hypergraph partitioner will never cut the social hyperedges at the expense of the nearest shelter hyperedges. In a sparse network, one would expect to see all hyperedges preserved, and the real function of the hypergraph partitioner is thereby to minimise the number of nearest shelter hyperedges cut in order to prioritise the preservation of social hyperedges.

The nature of the hyperedges connecting displaced households (nodes) to emergency shelters (virtual nodes) requires a point of clarity. Regarding the 20,910 displaced households, only 13,026 households (62.3%) have connections to other households. Looking only within this subset, in terms of maximal cliques (which inform the creation of hyperedges), an average of 2.36 households belong to any single maximal clique; in other words, the average number of pairwise household connections within a single maximal clique is 1.36. However, one should not overlook the fact that households can belong to multiple maximal cliques. In fact, the average household belongs to 2.21 maximal cliques (with several households belonging to up to 14 cliques). This raises the average number of pairwise household connections from 1.36 to 3.5, with one household boasting an astonishing 43 connections.

As many displaced households belong to more than one maximal clique, and as these different maximal cliques might be allocated (with a majority vote) to different nearest emergency shelters—which of course begs the possibility that households within maximal cliques are being allocated to different emergency shelters—then virtual nodes cannot be simply assigned to existing maximal cliques (or the hyperedges formed from these cliques). Since the virtual nodes have a fixed vertices constraint, any hyperedges containing two or more virtual nodes would be instantly cut. This holds true for all households that belong to different multiple cliques that, in turn, are assigned to different virtual nodes. In other words, attaching virtual nodes to the existing social hyperedges would break apart these structures. For this reason, new hyperedges connecting households to nearest shelters were created. As these hyperedges are pairwise connections, they are effectively the same as edges found in a graph. One might contend that this proposal to combine social and nearest shelter objectives thereby employs a hybrid graph-hypergraph methodology.

The hypergraph generated from the above procedures was passed into the hypergraph partitioner, PaToH (Çatalyürek & Aykanat, 2011), which was run 100 times using different random seeds. This hypergraph partitioner was selected as it consistently produces excellent

minimum cuts, or more specifically, PaToH consistently maximises its objective function, total communication volume (TCV).

Travel to a Safe Harbour

Routing People During an Evacuation

Without any disaster, what are the traffic conditions in the model? Out of the roughly 1.6 million people from the infectious disease model, 92.6% leave the house during a typical day. This does not mean that approx. 1.5 million people are driving at one time or another. On the contrary, not everyone has a vehicle, and not everyone is eligible to drive. Furthermore, multiple household members might share a vehicle, meaning that not all family members have access to a vehicle simultaneously. Some people with access to a vehicle might choose to carpool or use alternative means of transportation.

In the Portland dataset, most of the people who can drive, which is hereby defined as being 16 years of age or older and being a member of a household that owns a vehicle, have at some point left their home to visit their workplace or school. This accounts for 755,042 people. Regarding those who are not working and can drive, 320,886 people have left their homes during the day. Additionally, some people who can drive, either working at home (26,497 people) or not working at all (49,754 people; over half of whom are age 60 or older), have never left their household. This totals 1,152,179 people who can drive in the Portland dataset. One could refine this depiction by incorporating outside data from the U.S. Census Bureau.⁴⁵

When an earthquake strikes Portland at 2 p.m., what are the traffic conditions in the model? At this point in time, 367,653 people who can drive are at home. Roughly twice this number of people who can drive, specifically 784,526 people, are elsewhere. This might entail being at an activity location (724,119 people) or driving between activity locations (60,407 people). In other words, if everyone who can drive has access to their vehicle, then 62.85% of those vehicles would be parked somewhere away from home (i.e., at an activity location), 31.91% would be parked at home, and 5.24% would be driving on the road network.

Oftentimes households own fewer vehicles than the number of people who can drive. In such circumstances, which household members should be assigned a vehicle? The logic should be ideally formulated irrespective of whether or not a disaster occurs; however, certain

⁴⁵ For example, as the percentages of people commuting to work by automobile (either driving alone or carpooling) have been estimated for the Portland Metropolitan area, then one can appropriately scale the above figures. However, in light of having only data for households, other vehicle traffic (included deliveries, rental cars, emergency vehicles, taxis, school buses, through-traffic, etc.) has not been accounted for in this model, and accordingly, a decision was made to not further reduce the number of vehicles on the roadways.

liberties were taken in this research to better facilitate the disaster context. To this end, the simulated disaster response chosen for this research involves sending everyone home and, only after all household members have gathered, to then send these members together to a specified destination. This setup prompts yet another question: How can one determine when the last household member arrives at home, allowing the household to then evacuate as a unit? These questions were simultaneously answered by assigning the household members who are likely farthest away from their home at 2 p.m. a vehicle. The number of people assigned a vehicle was set proportional to each household's vehicle ownership count. Knowing when the last household member arrives home (because that person has a vehicle in this model) takes the guesswork out of determining when the subsequent action of evacuating should take place.

Another model convenience was to guarantee that each household has access to a vehicle. While not all displaced people own a vehicle (or even are able to drive), the only way to move people within the proposed simulation environment is by driving. Ultimately, placing more vehicles on the road and having a rough, lower-bound understanding regarding travel costs for all displaced people arguably outweighs alternative approaches, such as removing displaced people who cannot drive from both the traffic model and the final travel cost calculations while still maintaining space for them at shelters. One could also guarantee that not all households but, more narrowly, only displaced households would have access to a vehicle; the drawback here is that every time one selects a new subset of displaced people, then one must additionally select a new subset of vehicles, making the model setup more accurate but also less flexible (or otherwise more demanding), particularly when dealing with future cases involving multiple, stochastic model runs.

As for determining the farthest household members and assigning them vehicles, while the infectious disease model features time-stamped data where everyone is located in the greater Portland area, this pertains only to activity locations. As noted above, tens of thousands of people are driving between activities at 2 p.m., and their exact locations have yet to be specified. One inclination is to run a nominal day agent-based model (ABM) simulation and then grab all vehicle coordinates at 2 p.m. to determine which household members are truly farthest from their homes. However, running this simulation requires (as input) assigning people to vehicles (the desired output), which leads to circular reasoning. Alternatively, one could assign everyone within an ABM a vehicle, but this may not result in realistic traffic loads on the road network. Moreover, running a nominal day ABM simulation as a prerequisite to an evacuation ABM simulation seems computationally excessive for selecting a small subset of vehicle coordinates that can be otherwise approximated.

For vehicles travelling along the roadways at 2 p.m., their coordinates were calculated using the following logic: a line segment was drawn through Euclidean space between people's activity coordinates before and after 2 p.m. Knowing the end time for the activity immediately before 2 p.m. and the start time for the subsequent activity as well as where 2 p.m. linearly sits between these two specified times, points were then (re)interpolated onto the drawn line segments, reflecting where commuting vehicles might be located at 2 p.m.. With all vehicle coordinates taken into consideration, one can now discover those farthest away household members and assign them vehicles. Hypothetically, as a post-step procedure, one could now run a nominal day ABM simulation with the above-assigned vehicles, followed by identifying all vehicle coordinates at 2 p.m. This would more accurately place vehicles onto well-commuted road segments. Again, in keeping with a flexible model design and minimising computation time, the above-outlined interpolation technique seemed adequate.

Having assigned only certain people to vehicles in this model, the resulting number of drivers at activity locations at 2 p.m. has slightly dropped to 699,348 (representing 60.7% of the total population that can drive). Only 56,685 vehicles will be found on the road network (representing 4.92% of the total population that can drive). As for the latter, given a 2 p.m. evacuation (which is a time when many people are about to start or finish an activity), roughly 30% of vehicles on the road network are essentially located in their own driveway. This is determined by looking at distances between interpolated coordinates and household coordinates; the coordinate system used (WGS84) traditionally rounds to four decimal places, which renders very close coordinates indistinguishable (distances equal to zero). Excluding those who are essentially home, the total number of vehicles needing to return home is 739,081 vehicles.

In the aftermath of the simulated earthquake, two potential journeys are generated: (1) people travelling from a 2 p.m. activity outside of the home to their household, and (2) people travelling from their household to a safe destination. Some people will travel both legs of this journey while others will travel one or the other, or possibly neither leg. Additionally, some people will travel but not by using a vehicle on the roadway. Others will travel on the roadway but not add to traffic congestion; these people will be sharing a vehicle with other household members. To the latter point, during the first leg home, each vehicle was set to carry a single individual (this was done to increase roadway traffic); however, during the second leg, each vehicle was set to carry all household members. Of course, some household members were at work or another activity location together at 2 p.m., which may or may not entail that a vehicle was shared (potentially 1,783 vehicles could be removed from the first leg). In a similar vein,

as pertains to the second leg, many households could have evacuated with multiple vehicles. Indeed, while 3,671 households were provided with a vehicle not owned by them (simply to move people within the model), this number is more than offset by households that could have potentially evacuated using their multiple owned vehicles, i.e., an additional 15,329 vehicles could be added to the second leg. Another consideration is that some households are so large that two or more five-seat vehicles would be required for transport; technically this should result in 568 vehicles (whether owned or not) being added to the second leg. Without introducing outside data and notwithstanding some impracticalities, for simplicity the proposed model setup used one vehicle per person travelling home and one vehicle per household during the evacuation.

The general plan is for everyone to return home (first leg) and for the farthest away displaced household member to return home and then evacuate with his or her household members (first leg followed by second leg). Sometimes evacuating household members were all home at 2 p.m., which means these households could evacuate immediately. This accounts for 5,922 people. The total number of vehicles in the model is now 745,003, comprising 739,081 vehicles returning home, of which 19,673 will subsequently evacuate, alongside 5,922 vehicles that evacuated immediately. The total number of vehicles evacuating at some point in this model is 25,685.

One can now associate each of the 745,003 vehicles with three sets of coordinates: 2 p.m. coordinates (outlined in this section), household coordinates (provided directly from the infectious disease model data), and evacuation coordinates (the subject of previous sections). Some of these coordinates will be left blank. To summarise the evacuation locations, 20,910 households (43,811 people) will evacuate to one of 110 emergency shelters, 4,605 households (13,863 people) will evacuate to a friend's household, and 170 households (319 people) will evacuate outside a 75-mile radius placed around the centroid of Portland. In order to understand travel costs to emergency shelters, only the evacuation coordinates that concern the 20,910 vehicles evacuating to emergency shelters are subject to change, that is, depending on whether nearest shelter assignments, social assignments, or random assignments are being tested.

Apart from defining the above coordinates, one could hypothetically also equip an evacuation model with departure times. Depending on the nature of the disaster, people may not react to the disaster all at once. Maybe those on roadways would continue to their next destination before deciding what to do next, or maybe a delay would occur where information is exchanged or disseminated. In this disaster scenario, an earthquake should be fairly noticeable the moment the ground shakes, so arguably everyone would be aware of the disaster

at nearly the same time. As for when people decide to travel home (or evacuate from their home) post-earthquake, a Dirac delta distribution was used, i.e., people instantaneously were set to travel home, which might be a worst-case scenario (Lämmel & Klüpfel, 2012; for a summary of evacuation decision modelling literature see Yang, Morogul, Ozbay & Xie, 2016). The same logic was applied to the transition period from when vehicles return home to when they evacuate; in other words, these vehicles simply pick up household members without spending time at home. If people depart at different times, then the resulting travel costs would need to be adjusted accordingly.

Simulate Movement Along Routes

The coordinates and departure times (or lack thereof) can be used to create what in MATSim is known as a “population” file. Each “person” within this file (i.e., vehicle) has an ID, which for tracking purposes can be either set to a household ID (as all household members are sharing one vehicle) or set to a person ID. Each person has a “plan,” which at the most basic input level consists of “activities” interspersed with “legs.” Activities have a categorical “type,” allowing one to label these activities for future reference (for example, “2 p.m.,” “home,” and “shelter”) as well as associated x- and y-coordinates (a vehicle’s starting point will not be these coordinates but the nearest roadway “link”; MATSim’s ScenarioManager calls the `getNearestLink()` function). As this evacuation features only vehicle transportation (not pedestrian or multi-modal transportation), all legs are specified as “car.” A single population file was generated for nearest shelter assignments and social assignments; however, 40 different population files were generated for random assignments (no singular “optimal” random plan is proposed, so averaging results across multiple random runs is necessary). In addition to a population file, MATSim requires a “network” file and “configuration” file to run.⁴⁶ The network file is simply the road network (the creation of which has been described earlier).

A single MATSim configuration file was set up to run all experiments, where the only difference between configurations was the random seed parameter. Serving as a template, a configuration file was produced by a MATSim extension/contribution, one specifically designed by Dr. Gregor Lämmel for studying evacuations (Lämmel et al., 2016) and used to model evacuations scenarios of Hamburg, Germany (Hugenbusch, 2012) and Podang,

⁴⁶ One could also create a “facility” file for the shelters. Instead of creating population files for each experiment, one could create a single population file and have each experiment call a much smaller facility file. Saving space was not an issue, so this additional step was not taken in this research.

Indonesia (Taubenböck et al., 2013). With a simple graphical user interface (GUI), this evacuation contribution was run from within Eclipse IDE for Java developers and served as an entry point into MATSim, where one could simulate small-scale evacuations while becoming familiar with MATSim parameters and formatting. The only external input for this contribution is a road network, specifically an OSM file. After being prompted to load the road network, one can then visually draw circles or polygons over a map display to create exclusion zones as well as specify a population to evacuate from within these zones.⁴⁷ At this point, the software has generated a MATSim configuration file, an ESRI shape file (the drawn circles or polygons), a population file and a network file. The latter only contains roadway links within and overlapping the created shape files. Extra “virtual” roadway links were added, connecting all roadway links that intersect and terminate outside each shape file together. These virtual links connect to a final virtual link (all these new links are of equal length and ascribed an infinitely fast flow capacity). Instead of running shortest distance algorithms from every person’s origin to multiple exit destinations (all roads intersecting the shape file), one can now specify the final virtual link at the sole exit point, reducing the problem to a multi-source single-destination problem (see Han et al., 2006; Chen et al., 2011). Using these generated files, the contribution software will run the main MATSim modules and output a number of custom statistics and visualisations pertaining to the evacuation.

Without ever entering the command line, one could use the contribution software and, before running the final step, substitute the generated population file and network file with ones created for Portland. This approach avoids the need to design a configuration file from scratch as well as produce relevant output; however, the Portland road network is so massive that the contribution software’s visualisations will not function properly. Moreover, with access to a supercomputer, which can run multiple MATSim evacuations simultaneously, creating an executable program that runs from the command line is necessary. With this in mind, and building off this evacuation contribution, a new configuration file was designed that made as few changes as possible to the original contribution’s configuration file. This would operate alongside a command line executable MATSim snapshot (version 0.9.0).

In a more traditional commuter transportation context, MATSim would emulate real-world travel behaviour by simulating, scoring, and re-planning trips over multiple iterations until a Nash equilibrium is reached whereby travel plan scores cannot be further improved.

⁴⁷ The software also supports the ability to add road closures and has a built-in bus stop editor for evacuations simulations involving public transportation.

This would simulate rational thinking on behalf of commuters who would adjust their travel plans to reflect learned road network conditions. Evacuations, however, are one-time events that interrupt conditioned, daily movement patterns; people evacuating should arguably not have the foresight that accompanies MATSim's "re-planning" step. On the other hand, some everyday knowledge is still applicable when navigating during an unforeseen circumstance. In fact, without any iterative re-planning, well-known and easily avoidable roadway bottlenecks would create unreasonable traffic congestion within such a simulation. As Lämmel et al. (2016) remark, "[F]ar more research is needed to definitively answer how people choose evacuation routes, or how many learning iterations are required to realistically reflect assumed anticipation skills adequately." Keeping with Lämmel's configuration file, all events during the simulation are recorded in an "events" file, which is produced every 10 iterations. By iteration 11 (technically the 11th iteration since counting starts at zero), trip planning would reflect some semblance of disorder while, at the same time, foreseeable road congestion problems would be avoided. Without further modifying the configuration file, the model was set to start counting at zero iterations and finish counting at 10 iterations.

The only major change to the configuration file was the addition of three activity parameters, which represent every vehicle's 2 p.m. household and evacuation location. Given that MATSim's results are not deterministic, this configuration file was replicated 40 times, each with a different random seed. These configuration files will result in MATSim running 40 slightly different versions for each of the three experiment scenarios (nearest, social, and random assignments), resulting in 120 simulations in total. Each configuration file was set up to call the same MATSim executable and network file as well as a single population file representing either nearest or social assignments. As for the population files representing random assignments, even with 40 different population files (which would result in variability notwithstanding using a single random seed), the different configuration files (with different random seeds) were still implemented to ensure that other than the variables being tested, all aspects of the simulation, including random seeds, were consistent across the three experiment scenarios.

All these files were uploaded to the University of Cambridge's high-performance computer cluster, Darwin. This allows one to run the 120 simulations on independent nodes (each node has 16 cores and 63,900 MB of memory; the simulations are memory intensive, using most of the memory available). The Darwin cluster has its own configuration file; here instructions were provided on where to read and write files as well as the number of threads to use. These threads are distinct from the number of threads one can specify within MATSim's

configuration file. Performance issues will not be covered in this report, but it should suffice to say that output will be the same regardless of thread configuration.

After running the MATSim simulations, a program was created to take the “events” file and, where applicable, calculate each vehicle’s travel distance and travel time to household and/or evacuation destinations. These metrics are the main output for the simulations. Another program was built primarily for visual feedback. This program reports the network clearance time on each roadway link (the amount of time needed for all vehicles to leave a given link) as well as the total flow across each roadway link (the number of vehicles that traverse a given link). Together these metrics are useful for understanding which roadway links are heavily used and where bottlenecks are forming in the model. This is complemented by a program that extracts the coordinates of all vehicle locations at any specified time during the evacuation, allowing one to create a static image of the evacuation. To dynamically inspect the evacuation, videos were created using MATSim’s open-source visualiser, OTFVis (Strippgen, 2016), and later, a more powerful paid-for visualiser, Via (Rieser, 2016).⁴⁸

Results

The results showcase the importance of an evacuation ABM, where the explored measure of time demonstrably contributes to a more complete understanding of the evacuation (see Figure 8, Figure 9, Figure 10, Figure 11, and Figure 12). While measures of time certainly exaggerate measures of distance (e.g., a roughly 5% difference in distance between random and social–nearest shelter assignments becomes a roughly 15% difference in time between random and social–nearest shelter assignments), the exaggeration is not consistent, which provides insight into traffic conditions within the model. Taking the random scenario, for example, travelling 49.77 miles to shelters takes 160.59 minutes while travelling significantly farther, 81.73 miles, to exit Portland takes less time, 141.47 minutes (see Table 1). In this case, vehicles destined for emergency shelters are travelling at approximately 19 m.p.h., compared to vehicles destined to exit Portland travelling at approximately 35 m.p.h. While travel to emergency shelters is relatively slow, travel to friends’ houses (the shortest travel distance in the model) is even more arduous: the average speed plummets to less than 10 m.p.h. Vehicles travelling farther are also travelling faster, which might indicate that highways are faster arteries of travel and/or perhaps traffic congestion diminishes at Portland’s outskirts.

⁴⁸ Via was designed by Dr. Marcel Rieser while working at the company Senozon. After Dr. Reiser left Senozon, he started a company called Simunto, which took over the development and support of Via in January 2018 (Rieser, 2018). The version of Via used in this research was acquired from Senozon.

Figure 8

Location of People Seeking Emergency Shelter

← 2 p.m. 5 p.m. 8 p.m. 11 p.m. 2 a.m. →

Note. Distribution of people seeking a social-nearest shelter at 2 p.m., when the disaster strikes.

Figure 9

Location of People Seeking Emergency Shelter

← 2 p.m. 5 p.m. 8 p.m. 11 p.m. 2 a.m. →

Note. Distribution of people seeking a social-nearest shelter at 5 p.m., 3 hours after the disaster strikes.

Figure 10

Location of People Seeking Emergency Shelter

← 2 p.m. 5 p.m. 8 p.m. 11 p.m. 2 a.m. →

Note. Distribution of people seeking a social-nearest shelter at 8 p.m., 6 hours after the disaster strikes.

Figure 11

Location of People Seeking Emergency Shelter

← 2 p.m. 5 p.m. 8 p.m. 11 p.m. 2 a.m. →

Note. Distribution of people seeking a social-nearest shelter at 11 p.m., 9 hours after the disaster strikes.

Figure 12

Location of People Seeking Emergency Shelter

← 2 p.m. 5 p.m. 8 p.m. 11 p.m. 2 a.m. →

Note. Distribution of people seeking a social-nearest shelter at 2 a.m., 12 hours after the disaster strikes.

Table 1

	Shelter Miles	Shelter Minutes	Friends Miles	Friends Minutes	Exit Miles	Exit Minutes
Random	49.77	160.59	11.85	73.16	81.73	141.47
Social-Nearest	47.27	136.67	11.84	72.82	81.72	142.32
Nearest	45.33	120.93	11.84	71.57	81.80	142.54

Note. Average distance (miles) and average time (minutes) from displaced people's households to emergency shelters, friend's households, and exits along the perimeter of the greater Portland area.

While the ABM can advance one's understanding of traffic conditions within the model, more importantly, all else being equal, the resulting travel times to emergency shelters are significantly different across the three scenarios (see Figure 13). Indeed, travel times to both friends' houses and exit points are respectively consistent across all scenarios; however, average travel time to shelters ranges essentially from 161 minutes (2 hours, 41 minutes) for random shelter assignments to 121 minutes (2 hours, 1 minute) for nearest shelter assignments, a difference of 40 minutes. Social–nearest assignments were somewhere in between: 137 minutes (2 hours, 17 minutes). In other words, social–nearest assignments fall approximately 60.3 % of the way between a random and best-case (nearest shelter) scenario.

How do nearest shelter assignments compare to social–nearest shelter assignments when success is a function of minimising edges/hyperedges cut? Beginning with the social–nearest shelter assignments, one can quantify how much of the original social network is preserved or, alternatively, how much of the hypergraph structure is preserved. The hypergraph was constructed to emphasise households that share an equal social affinity for one another (see above), which results in partitioning that is slightly different from a more generic setup. In this case, 76.31% of hyperedges were completely preserved during hypergraph partitioning. As some of the hyperedges are weighted (i.e., some households have more than one connection with other households), the cost as opposed to the number of hyperedges preserved is slightly higher at 76.88%. This latter percentage is a better indicator of the hypergraph partitioning performance—the hypergraph partitioner tends to avoid cutting higher weight hyperedges, expressed here as a slightly better percentage.

Figure 13

Note. Upon overlapping kernel density estimation (KDE) plots of random, nearest, and social-nearest shelter assignments, the probability distributions appear quite distinct.

One can derive the number of social edges cut directly from the input file (the hypergraph) and the output file (the assignments list). The first step to analysing the social network—and this applies both to analysing edges and hyperedges—is to remove all the virtual nodes from the output (these virtual nodes represent nearest shelters, not households that can have a social connection). At this point, one can look at the household IDs within each hyperedge and replace those with shelter IDs from the assignments list. For the most part (76.31% of the time), all the shelter IDs within each hyperedge should be the same, meaning these hyperedges are completely kept intact. Calculating the number of edges from hyperedges involves connecting each pair of nodes within a hyperedge with a unique edge (i.e., forming a *complete graph* from nodes within each hyperedge). The number of edges that comprise each hyperedge would thereby equal $u \times (u - 1)$, where u is the number of nodes. However, hypergraphs typically contain overlapping hyperedges, so one must subsequently remove all duplicate edges before reporting the actual number of edges preserved during hypergraph partitioning. As a reality check, one can replace household IDs with shelter IDs, where the household IDs are not from the input hypergraph but from the graph that produced the input hypergraph. The number of preserved edges calculated from this original graph should be identical to those derived from the input hypergraph. Indeed, the hypergraph contains all the information of the original graph as well as has an additional layer of interpretation built on top of it.⁴⁹ Regardless of the method used, the number of edges preserved from the original social network is 71.28% (or by weighted edge cost, 71.72%).⁵⁰

Noting a roughly 5% difference between preserving the overall graph and the overall hypergraph and a less significant, roughly half-a-percent difference between the total number and the total cost of edges/hyperedges preserved, this research will maintain the distinction between graph and hypergraph results while forgoing the distinction between the nearly identical total number and total cost of edges/hyperedges preserved. While slightly understating the partitioning results, the research will proceed to report the simpler *total number* of edges/hyperedges preserved. This approach best represents the percentage of

⁴⁹ Graphs (which use edges) are not only more intuitive than hypergraphs (which use hyperedges), but within social network analysis (SNA), more tools have been specifically developed to analyse graph structures. As future datasets might feature hypergraphs only (having not been derived from graphs), despite potentially losing some information, converting to graphs does have benefits/conveniences, which is why a method for such a conversion is presented here.

⁵⁰ More specifically, 30,182 out of a possible 42,340 edges were preserved across 110 different shelters. Please note that as edges can be *directed*, the number of edges between any pair of nodes is traditionally counted as two, one edge in each direction. On the other hand, the graph here contains only *undirected* edges, so the number of shared edges is half that, i.e., 15,091 out of a possible 21,170 edges were preserved, which results in the same 71.28%.

preserved household-to-household connections instead of individual-to-individual connections.

Shifting to nearest shelter assignments, for the 13,026 displaced households travelling to shelters (all of which have at least one shared edge with another displaced household seeking shelter),⁵¹ out of a potential 21,170 available shared edges, only 781 shared edges or roughly 3.69% of edges were preserved. This is better than a random shelter assignment, where one would statistically expect slightly less than 1% of edges to be preserved (more specifically, approximately 0.91%). Although nearest shelter assignments would on average preserve over four times more social connections than assigning people to random shelters, this is still a proportionally small number. When looking more closely at the average number of connections within individual shelters, one of the shelters preserved 18.37% of displaced people's potential edges. Indeed, some shelters are geospatial hubs for keeping intact social networks while the majority of shelters are not.⁵²

In terms of hyperedges, 356 out of 12,189 hyperedges (3.01%) were preserved. Given that the average number of households comprising a hyperedge is 2.36, and given that the less numerous hyperedges that connect multiple vertices are more likely to be cut,⁵³ one would expect the percentage of hyperedges preserved to be slightly less than the number of edges preserved. These hyperedges are being split on average across 2.3 different shelters (at least one hyperedge was split across nine different shelters).⁵⁴ Of course, a household can have multiple hyperedges, and some of these hyperedges might end up in a single shelter or otherwise split across multiple shelters.

Bringing into focus the trade-off between social connections and travel times, while the nearest shelter assignment methodology preserves 3.69% of edges (or 3.01% of hyperedges) and ensures that 100% of households visit their nearest shelter, the social–nearest shelter

⁵¹ As a reminder, the 13,026 displaced households are a subset of the 20,910 displaced households seeking shelter who, more specifically, share at least one edge in common. In other words, 7,884 households have no social connections in common.

⁵² One can also quantify the preservation of social networks in absolute terms, whether households have none, some or all their connections kept intact. Out of 13,026 households, 1,283 households managed to preserve at least one edge (with one household preserving 6 edges). Given that most households share only one edge with another household, if at least one edge is broken, which is the case for 12,836 households, then the vast majority or 11,743 households will end up with zero social connections at shelters. That said, 1,093 households will have access to some of their social network, and 190 households will have access to their entire social network.

⁵³ In this model setup, the number of vertices contained in a hyperedge does not correspond to the weight of that hyperedge. The weight of any given hyperedge is determined by the number of social connections between members of different households. In other words, keeping together hyperedges with a larger number of vertices is not prioritised over keeping together hyperedges with a small number of vertices.

⁵⁴ Please note that the results presented here have been rounded to the nearest hundredth decimal place, which means that rounding errors would be exacerbated when making further calculation from these reported results.

assignment methodology preserves 71.28% of edges (or 76.31% of hyperedges) and ensures that 43.52% of households visited their nearest shelter.⁵⁵ The k -way partitioning was confirmed to be correct; with a target occupancy size of slightly less than 400 displaced people for each of the 110 shelters, the maximum shelter imbalance was ± 4 people within any given shelter (with an average shelter imbalance of ± 2 people). The total imbalance was 143 people, meaning that 143 out of 43,811 people, or less than 0.33% of the displaced population, would need to be relocated to have perfectly balanced partitions.

According to the outlined method, each household (node) has a single hyperedge connecting it to a single nearest emergency shelter (virtual node), which means that if this nearest shelter hyperedge is broken, then one might expect that household's shelter location to default to random; however, if a household is not part of the 43.52% of households visiting their nearest shelter, then this household still might share a social hyperedge with someone who is part of this 43.52%. With the law of transitivity in effect, if geo-proximity has anything to do with why people are socially connected, then to adopt a biological vernacular, one might expect to see some degree of commensalism, where the social network bolsters not nearest but nearer shelter locations. To illustrate this point, if 43.52% of people visit nearest shelters (taking on average 120.93 minutes to evacuate) and the remaining 56.38% of people visit random shelters (taking on average 160.59 minutes to evacuate), then the evacuation time (as a weighted average) should be approximately 143.33 minutes. Interestingly, although not unexpectedly, the simulated evacuation time as reported from the ABM is 136.67 minutes, which means that the presence of a social network in the absence of a "nearest shelter network" improves average evacuation time.

From another perspective, some of the 43.52% of households visiting their nearest shelter would end up at nearest shelters randomly, so on a spectrum between random shelter assignments (which preserve 0.91% of nearest shelters) and nearest shelter assignments (which preserve 100% of nearest shelters, as solved for using a capacitated p -median problem algorithm), then social–nearest shelter assignments fall approximately 43% of the way between random and optimised nearest. On the same spectrum, using random shelter assignments as the lower bound and nearest shelters assignments as the upper bound, but replacing average nearest shelters percentages (binary results) with average ABM travel times (continuous results), one would find that social–nearest shelter assignments fall 60.3% of the way between random and

⁵⁵ The hypergraph partitioner, PaToH, produces a very consistent output. Across 100 runs, the worst result was 42.7% of people visiting nearest shelters (less than a 1% difference from the best result).

optimised nearest. This roughly 40.23% increase in performance, from 43% to 60.3%, suggests that the underlying social network has geospatial attributes that augment the secondary objective of helping displaced people reach shelters faster.

To summarise and refine the results, considering the different outcomes of a Portland evacuation, sending people to nearest shelters would overwhelmingly destroy the social network—3.69% of the social network would be preserved. In marked contrast, a method has been proposed that preserves 71.28% of the social network while simultaneously routing people to nearby (and oftentimes nearest) shelters, which is demonstrated with at time cost roughly 60.3% of the way between random assignments and optimised nearest assignments.

Future Research

One possible trajectory is to devise a real-time, streaming method to simultaneously preserve displaced people's social networks while also assigning these people to nearest shelters. As the research will develop streaming methods for social assignments (see Chapters 4, 5, and 6), the remaining hurdle is doing the same for nearest assignments, followed by combining the two objectives together, preferably while allowing individuals themselves (or the average of individual preferences, for example) to define a trade-off between nearest and socially optimised shelter assignments.

Toward this end, solving nearest shelter assignments statically with the capacitated p -median problem (CPMP) has proven more computationally intensive than graph or hypergraph partitioning. A streaming version of the CPMP should be cognisant of run-time, perhaps employing a fast k -nearest neighbourhood (k NN) algorithm on the road network to avoid generating a full origin-destination cost matrix. A large body of literature has covered this topic; for a survey of notable algorithms, see Abeywickrama et al. (2016). To maintain balanced nearest shelter assignments, the k NN results (as distances to shelters or as shelters ranked by distances) could be integrated into the proposed streaming social assignment algorithm. Furthermore, without cementing the relative importance between objective functions—minimising travel cost, maximising social network structure, and balancing partition sizes—one might consider substituting the upcoming algorithm's weighted sum optimisation (which aggregates maximising social network structure and balancing partitions into a single, composite function) with a Pareto efficient, multi-objective optimiser. Pareto optimisation would allow one to explore the best compromises between two or three of the above criteria, i.e., those solutions where any single criterion can be improved only by

worsening one of the others. There is precedence for modelling graph partitioning as a multi-objective optimisation problem using a Pareto-based evolutionary algorithm (Farshbaf & Feizi-Derakhshi, 2009).

Lastly, although the results for social-nearest shelter are compelling, one could likely improve these results. The hypergraph partitioning method used here, PaToH, is not particularly “well-tuned” to fixed vertices (Aykanat et al., 2008; see also Alpert et al., 2000; Predari et al., 2017). For better performance, one should keep apprised not only of partitioners that generally outperform PaToH but also partitioners—such as multi-level k -way partitioners, including kPaToH (Aykanat et al., 2008) and others (Predari et al., 2017)—that specifically excel in a context where fixed vertices are present.

Chapter 3

A Family in Portland

While the pursuit of certain evacuation objectives might sound appealing in the abstract, how these objectives perform in practice and how this performance is interpreted requires context. Simulations provide a means to create context and rehearse evacuations prior to implementation. In Chapter 2, a model of Portland, Oregon becomes the backdrop for such rehearsals. With respect to the outcomes presented, while knowing the average percentage of social connections preserved at shelters is meaningful, the value one ascribes to this percentage might change upon knowing who is present and absent at shelters. Likewise, how one interprets average travel times may vary depending upon the circumstances of those travelling. Indeed, one should recognise that framing success in terms of averages, percentages, and distributions strips away the identities of people and places, the specificity of which could matter.

The simulations in Chapter 2 contain rich evacuation narratives. By immersing oneself within these narratives, one might find that certain details affect their plausibility. Moreover, every detail is a variable, and modifying these variables could reveal opportunities or oversights that factor into a successful evacuation. Engaging with and manipulating narratives aligns with *design thinking*, which is a human-centred approach to innovation that draws upon creativity, visualisation, experimentation, and abductive reasoning (see Micheli et al., 2019). While one can use simulations to evaluate intervention strategies (see Chapter 2), one can also use them to create new, immersive contexts from which to rethink and redesign these strategies. Indeed, research and design go hand in hand; this chapter focuses on the latter.

No scientific claims are made in this chapter. The true impetus is neither to make scientific inquiry more comprehensible or engaging via narrative/storytelling (*cf.*, Dahlstrom, 2014), nor to present an example of how intricate city-wide evacuation modelling can be at the micro level. Rather, the research seeks to draw attention to the value of rehearsing evacuation objectives from the perspective of those evacuating. As an example of this process, the next section will describe a family during an evacuation and what they would experience upon committing to different shelter options. The details behind this story owe to the simulation created in Chapter 2 and are presented *in situ*, without embellishment. That said, one can easily imagine how the outcomes of this story (or a similar story) would improve by attributing weight to social connections and/or by prioritising social connections belonging to certain family members.

Illustrating an Evacuation

A family of three, including a mother and her two daughters, wake up and are ready to leave their house by 8:30 a.m. They live in a single-story, wooden-framed house located on SW Thomas Street in Portland, Oregon. Their hilly neighbourhood is known as South Portland (formerly called Corbett–Terwilliger–Lair Hill) and comprises a narrow corridor of houses situated south of downtown Portland, flanked by the Willamette River and the West Hills.

The mother drives just over half a mile south to pick up a passenger and then drives 10 minutes north to where she works, the Women’s Health Center in the Kohler Pavilion, which is part of the Oregon Health & Science University. She arrives at 8:50 a.m. and works until 4:30 p.m. She then drives further north to drop off a friend at a small business. After 15 minutes of socialising followed by another 15 minutes of driving, the mother returns home to meet her children at 5:30 p.m.

The two daughters, ages six and seven, have nearly identical schedules. They both attend Winterhaven Elementary School until 2:30 p.m. The school is located across the Willamette River in the Brooklyn neighbourhood. At 2:45 p.m., they participate in recreational activities in downtown Portland, and then at 5 p.m., they depart for home, arriving at 5:30 p.m.

This would be a typical day for the family, but at 2 p.m., a severe earthquake occurred in the Portland area. This damaged many of the buildings and streets within the city and, more broadly, within the greater county of Multnomah. While Portland is located in Oregon, the city borders the state of Washington, which was also damaged by the earthquake (see Figure 14). As the school buses were already at the school, prepared to take children either to their homes or after-school activities, a decision was made based on the known roadway conditions to send everyone home.⁵⁶

Unfortunately, the family returned to find their house uninhabitable. This particular family did not want to burden others for accommodation. Additionally, being in a lower household income bracket effectively dissuaded this family from searching for a hotel. The family was not only displaced; they required shelter. This was true for roughly 7% of those living in the South Portland neighbourhood (see Figure 15).

⁵⁶ If the conditions were much worse, a reunification protocol would have gone into effect, whereby the mother (as the parent/guardian or, otherwise, any individual identified by the mother as an emergency contact) would have picked up the children from school.

Figure 14

Note. Portland is located in Multnomah County in northern Oregon and borders the State of Washington.

Figure 15

Note. The subject family resides in a census tract in Portland, Oregon, where 7.13% of the people have a probability of requiring temporary shelter.

Considering the structural damage to candidate evacuation sites, 110 shelters were quickly made available to the public, each expected to host approximately 400 people (see Figure 16). At this point the family, or more specifically the mother, must choose a shelter. She does not know how many other people are evacuating and whether the nearest shelters will reach capacity before she arrives, forcing her to travel farther afield in a worst-case scenario. In terms of distance, the nearest shelter, Rose City Park Presbyterian Church, is 5.6 miles to the northwest. She would be driving toward the heart of Portland and would need to cross the Willamette River. Directly west are two shelters, Elsie Stuhr Adult Center and New Vision Fellowship Church, which are 8.4 miles away, and just north of these shelters is another one, Cedar Hills Recreation Center, which is 7.9 miles away. To the southwest is St. Anthony Catholic Church school, located 8.2 miles away, while directly south is Lake Grove Christian Church, which is 8.9 miles away. Without knowledge of road conditions, selecting the nearest shelter in terms of travel time is not immediately obvious. Having to compete with other displaced people for shelter space also calls into question the decision to visit the absolute nearest shelter in the first place.

Facilitating the decision-making process, emergency management could assign displaced people to the nearest emergency shelters with the objective of reducing the average travel cost for all known evacuees. In such a case, from any one displaced person's perspective, he or she may not be assigned to the absolute nearest shelter—this would be impossible due to the demand for and capacity of given shelters. With regard to the family, the nearest shelter (the shelter assigned to the family that would benefit displaced people as a whole) would be 23.7 miles away at Christian Gospel Assemblies. This trip would typically take 35 minutes without traffic (according to the fastest route in Google Maps; Google, n.d.-a);⁵⁷ however, in the wake of the earthquake, the trip would take 102 minutes (according to an agent-based model). The incentive for the family to travel extra distance would be partially attributable to the peace of mind in knowing that a spot at this shelter has been reserved for them.

In contrast, emergency management could implement a different objective function: to simultaneously preserve displaced people's social network connections while also sending displaced people to nearest shelters. Complying with this optimisation, the family would travel even farther to the assigned shelter, travelling 44.6 miles to McKay High School. The trip takes between 45 and 50 minutes without traffic (according to the fastest route in Google Maps;

⁵⁷ Shelter locations are attributable to the National Shelter System (NSS) database. This research cannot guarantee the correctness of this database.

Figure 16

Note. Location of shelters in a 75-mile radius from the centroid of Portland.

Google, n.d.-b); however, it would take the family 113 minutes post-earthquake (according to an agent-based model). In other words, instead of the family taking 102 minutes to reach the nearest emergency shelter, the family could travel an extra 11 minutes to a different shelter where friends and other social acquaintances would be present. Compared to other evacuees, this family will reach their shelter rather quickly; the average travel time is roughly 137 minutes, and some people will spend more than 12 hours driving to shelters.

Upon reaching a shelter, the family will encounter other displaced people, some of whom will be neighbours. Within two streets of the family's SW Thomas Street household address are 37 other households seeking emergency shelter (see Figure 17). If the nearest shelter optimisation were implemented, eight of these neighbouring households would end up in the same shelter as the family. None of these neighbours happen to be acquaintances of the family. However, one might expect the shelter to be comprised of people with similar backgrounds and experiences.

One should not be so quick to assert that the family will encounter friends at the nearest emergency shelter. Assigning people to the geographically nearest shelters may inadvertently separate neighbours from each other. As a case in point, the family's friends predominately do not live in the same neighbourhood as the family. The children have a few friends nearby, but most of their friends are located across the river where their school is located. The mother has no friends living in the immediate vicinity (see Figure 18); her social network is dispersed throughout the city and suburbs. The mother's friends comprise mostly her work community, and indeed, her place of work (being specialised) draws in people from the greater Portland area. In contrast, the children know most of their friends through school, which unsurprisingly has local attendees (see Figure 19). When the earthquake strikes at 2 p.m., most of the family's friends are also either at work or at school, so the act of returning home creates greater physical distance in this family's ego social network.

In the wake of the earthquake, the family will know eight other families who also become displaced. Three of these families will be hosted by their friends while the remaining five will seek safe harbour at emergency shelters. As stated above, when visiting the nearest shelter, the family will not encounter any of their social acquaintances; however, under the social-nearest shelter scenario, when the family is assigned to McKay High School, they will know four families at the shelter (see Figure 20). The fifth family they know who is also seeking shelter will be assigned to a different shelter. This other family is acquainted with two people at this different shelter, each of whom knows four people (and through a chain of friends, this family will be connected to 91 other people at this different shelter). If this family were to visit

Figure 17

Note. Within two streets from the subject family’s location are 37 other households requiring shelter. None of the people within these households are friends with members of the subject family. Regardless, some of these neighbouring households end up in the same shelter as the subject family (numbers vary depending on the assignment scheme).

Figure 18

B Household Locations
Scale: 1" = 1 MI

Note. Location of the family's friends.

Figure 19

Friends' Relationship to Subject Family

Friends' Locations at 2pm

Note. The family predominately have friend connections via work (mom) and school (younger and older child). When the earthquake strikes at 2 p.m. most of these friends are also at work or school.

Figure 20

Shelters Housing Family and Friends

Note. Given either a nearest optimal shelter assignment (scheme 1, denoted by red circles) or socially optimal shelter assignment (scheme 2, denoted by blue circles), this figure shows the location, number, distance, and relationship of the family's friends vis-à-vis the family as determined under each of the allocation schemes.

McKay High School, they would only be directly acquainted with the subject family (via the older child) and experience a far smaller *social reach* through the older child's social network.

The social landscape could not be more different between nearest shelter and social–nearest shelter scenarios. In the nearest shelter case, 9 out of 182 families will have one or more friends at the shelter (see Figure 21). As for the social–nearest shelter, 127 out of 182 families will have one or more friends at the shelter (see Figure 22), a roughly 14-fold increase. Absent studies regarding social interactions within emergency shelters, one cannot easily ascertain what this means for the subject family. On the one hand, the social–nearest shelter scenario opens the possibility for the family to be introduced to other families via their friend network, or if not introduced, then to experience an unspoken comfort in observing longstanding friendships between nearby people and the accountability that underlies those friendships. On the other hand, if everyone is in cliques as opposed to being alone, then the family might have trouble initiating social interactions with members of these cliques. A greater number of pre-arranged social connections at emergency shelters may not necessarily increase sociability at shelters.

Looking closer at the social–nearest shelter case, the mother will have one work connection, the older child will have two recreational friends, and the younger child will have a school friend (see Figure 23). As for the latter, the younger child's school friend's parents have three work friends at the emergency shelter—these friends and their respective family members are unknown but possibly introducible to the subject family. In turn, one of these workplace friends-of-a-friend knows three additional families, and so a chain of possible introductions begins to present itself. Looking at this chain (or network component) of families, the subject family can trace a route to 11 other families. Simply communicating that the subject family directly knows four other families at the emergency shelter understates the broader positive and/or negative social implications captured within the social network structure. While difficult to interpret, indirect social interactions—individual-to-individual, group-to-group, and individual-to-group interactions—will be at play within the shelter.

The story highlights details that are both relevant and irrelevant during an evacuation. Of course, what is relevant for one family might be irrelevant for another, and vice versa. Relevancy might also become apparent by modifying the details within the story or by elaborating upon them. For example, more information on existing relationships between the subject family and who specifically is present and absent at different shelters might reveal that the number of social connections preserved is not as important as the quality of these social

Figure 21

Note. This image shows the social connections found at the subject family's emergency shelter when everyone is assigned to nearest optimal shelters. A small handful of households (roughly 2% of households in the shelter) have one or more connections. Not displayed are 173 households, including the subject family, without connections.

Figure 22

Note. This image displays the social connections found at the subject family's emergency shelter when everyone is assigned to socially optimal shelters. The subject family has four connections, and the vast majority of people (127 households or roughly 70% of households) have one or more connections. Not displayed are 55 households without connections.

Figure 23

(C) Household Relationships

Note. Relationships between households.

connections, or perhaps not as important as ensuring that certain family members have social connections.

One should not overlook (as is common when people are described by numbers) that each family has a unique story and that these stories are interconnected. Indeed, shelter assignments that benefit one family could simultaneously hurt another family. Should one treat all families equally, and how can one accomplish this when some families are more connected than others? Are certain families more in need of social connections? Just as rehearsing evacuations from multiple independent perspectives could reveal opportunities for future work, so too could one proceed by exploring the effects that different design strategies have on interconnected people.

Chapter 4

Relevant Partitioning Methods

Relevant Context

Every large-scale disaster is unique. Myriad challenges present themselves, including the imminent need to ensure people's safety and mitigate the physical impact of the disaster. An effective response requires establishing information channels, both to understand the "ground conditions" as well as to disseminate guidance. Critical to the success is identifying who requires shelter and then directing these people along safe and efficient routes to emergency shelters. As an evacuation might occur before, during, or after a disaster, and with different information about the disaster available at each of these stages, accompanied by a different urgency to evacuate people, this research contends that a defining characteristic of a shelter assignment algorithm is adaptability. To this end, this research will build an interpretation of adaptability over multiple chapters. As a starting point, this chapter will examine the partitioning features that contribute to a flexible shelter assignment algorithm. This algorithm will allow one to compare different ways of partitioning data and, considering what data is available, ultimately cater to different evacuation scenarios.

Drawing upon partitioning literature (see Appendix C), which partitioning attributes or "features" are relevant? One might think about each partitioning feature and what role it could play in a shelter assignment algorithm. This could involve reimagining what the data represents and, more broadly, what evacuation scenarios seem credible. Sometimes the utility of a partitioning feature only becomes recognisable in light of or in coordination with other partitioning features. Moreover, partitioning is only one component of a shelter assignment algorithm—for certain partitioning features to serve a purpose, one must be innovative with the non-partitioning components of the algorithm. Indeed, if one treats partitioning features as subroutines, then interspersed between them are other functions and subroutines (and potentially large modules), which are tasked with determining what (and when) data is collected, partitioned, and disseminated, alongside processing that data in various ways to facilitate meaningful shelter assignments. This creative exercise of recontextualising partitioning features goes hand in hand with evaluating outcomes. Indeed, the relevant partitioning features are those that contribute to an algorithm that outperforms other algorithms in some instances.

A shelter assignment algorithm could comprise every partitioning feature hypothesised as relevant—insofar as each inclusion is explainable vis-à-vis the larger algorithm—and one might additionally have theoretical grounds to justify when to parameterise for each feature.

However, prior to implementation, one should conduct experiments to validate these assumptions and provide guidance in cases where best practice is not obvious. Toward this goal, this research will explore and compare the utility of three partitioning strategies in upcoming experiments (see Chapter 5). As for the current chapter, although a number of partitioning features are hypothesised as relevant (i.e., presented as having potential strategic importance), this research also acknowledges that initially equipping the shelter assignment algorithm with partitioning features not used in the upcoming experiments is unnecessary. As another practical simplification, one can select a partitioner from the existing literature whose core partitioning features align with the research objective and, if necessary, allow one to readily expand the feature set.

While not extending a selected partitioner to handle every conceivable strategy is a decision that narrows the research scope, only selecting a *single* partitioner is a decision that introduces limitations within the study design. Addressing this latter case, if a shelter assignment algorithm accommodates multiple strategies, then any given strategy would likely employ a subset of the available partitioning features. For every subset of partitioning features, one could likely identify different existing partitioners that either have those features or can be readily modified to have them. In order to understand and leverage the full potential of any given strategy, one should attempt to pair the partitioning features with a partitioner that brings about the best shelter assignments. In fact, one reason to select a particular strategy is to improve outcomes via access to a preferred partitioner or, if no partitioner always dominates, access to more choices in partitioners. In terms of added complexity, at the very least this involves creating a portfolio of complimentary partitioners for each strategy and then selecting, potentially automatically using algorithm selection (see Kerschke et al., 2019),⁵⁸ the best partitioner.

On the other hand, the decision to not introduce added complexity and instead select a single partitioner that works with all presented strategies has allowed this research to pursue complexity in other ways. This research does not claim to advance the inner logic of partitioning or advance how complimentary partitioners are selected. The primary contribution is how to couch partitioning within a greater shelter assignment algorithm. Indeed, the research presents different ways to determine who requires shelter and then how to prepare this data for partitioning, along with making sense of the output. While one can improve performance by

⁵⁸ If selecting the best partitioner cannot be determined a priori, algorithm selection can happen in real time. As an example pertaining to the closely related problem of clustering, please see Carnein et al. (2020).

replacing or tuning a partitioner, so too can one improve performance by incorporating different partitioning features into a shelter assignment algorithm. The latter approach involves engaging with the evacuation context and, if prioritised, places considerable emphasis on what is unique to this research.

This chapter will proceed by categorising partitioning features as contextually relevant or irrelevant. With an eye to narrow the scope of the study, this research further considers whether the relevant partitioning features contribute distinctly or redundantly toward advancing context-driven strategies, to which the following logic is applied: if multiple partitioning features serve the same function but a subset of them have additional or more comprehensive functionality, then this research will prioritise and include within the proposed algorithm these latter partitioning features. Additionally, while the proposed algorithm is engineered to incorporate only those partitioning features required to conduct the upcoming experiments, so too is the algorithm extendible in the sense that partitioning features not used in the experiments, specifically those flagged as strategically relevant, can be seamlessly integrated into future studies. The research will then review existing partitioners that have these partitioning features. Lastly, a single partitioner is selected and extended for inclusion within a shelter assignment algorithm.

Excluded Partitioning Features

Imagine the vertex as a person. While the “think like a vertex” paradigm challenges one to adopt a local view of the graph—to make calculations pertaining to a vertex based on its neighbours—a vertex further requires physical representation within the context of this research. Indeed, if graph partitioning is to virtually simulate opportunities for real-world interactions, then one cannot treat a social network as a purely non-spatial entity, distinct and decoupled from the spatially-bound people that produce and experience it.

Certain partitioning features fail to meet the needs of this research because they cannot appropriately represent people being allocated to shelters. Specifically, the following partitioning features should be excluded:

- vertex cuts
- node replication
- edge partitioning
- edge-centric partitioning

Additionally, the following partitioning features (although perfectly viable) are not initially included within the proposed shelter assignment algorithm due to a narrow research scope:

- repartitioning nodes
- migrating nodes
- dynamically partitioning nodes (after an assignment is made)

As social networks exhibit a highly skewed power-law degree distribution, the literature on distributed graph processing would point to partitioning these graphs using vertex cuts (VC). However, real people are not divisible and cannot exist in multiple places at the same time. Partitioning methods involving vertex cuts and node replication are illogical when imagining the vertex as a person. Similarly, edge partitioning and edge-centric partitioning,⁵⁹ which refer to balancing the number of edges across partitions (Bourse et al., 2014; Filippidou & Kotidis, 2015a; Roy et al., 2013; Schlag et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018), imply the use of vertex cuts and replication, and are likewise contextually unsuitable.

Partitioning strategies that involve repartitioning nodes, migrating nodes, and dynamically partitioning nodes (Soudani et al., 2019) are justifiable in special/limited circumstances but are ill-suited as overarching, indiscriminate strategies. Indeed, one can make a strong argument for withdrawing and replacing shelter assignments, for example, provided that the locations of shelter reassignments are en route to where displaced people are already heading. Continuing with this example, when using GPS to navigate to an emergency shelter, if this application were to identify a closer shelter that has equal or greater social value, then rerouting would seem welcome.⁶⁰ If having to travel farther, or if having already settled into a shelter, then the response to (re)routing displaced people to a more socially oriented shelter becomes less obvious.⁶¹ With respect to implementation, recommending a shelter reassignment demands knowing the real-time location of displaced people and then using this information along with real-time traffic reports to identify alternative shelters that are more appealing in

⁵⁹ The term “edge centric” is not always contrasted with “vertex centric.” Some authors refer to vertex centric more loosely, namely, that each vertex has a local view of the graph structure and not whether a vertex or edge is being partitioned (e.g., Soudani et al., 2019).

⁶⁰ In fact, automatically identifying shorter routes and rerouting is a standard feature within many navigation applications.

⁶¹ If shelter assignments were to continuously reflect the increasing knowledge of who requires shelter, then people might be reassigned to multiple emergency shelters over the course of a single evacuation. Apart from the obvious migration cost, excessive updates could potentially undermine people’s confidence in a shelter recommendation. On the other hand, instances arise where people may want to relocate to a different shelter. For example, someone might visit the closest shelter out of convenience, and as the evacuation progresses, a different shelter fills with family and friends. There might be a social threshold at which point one decides to relocate to that shelter, i.e., the migration cost is justified.

terms of travel time and/or social composition and, if multiple shelters fall within this category, resolve which alternative shelter is the most suitable. How many displaced people would benefit from being reassigned would likely depend on multiple factors, including the spatial distribution of shelters. Given that not everyone would benefit, this research has initially pursued more fundamental strategies.

Thus, while any given partitioner might have a number of desirable characteristics, if it makes use of vertex cuts, node replication, edge partitioning, or edge-centric partitioning, then this partitioner becomes contextually unsuitable. On the other hand, if a partitioner operates by repartitioning nodes, migrating nodes, or dynamically partitioning nodes, then although such a partitioner is excluded from further study within this research, one might nevertheless find utility for this partitioner in future work. For example, S-PowerGraph (Xie et al., 2015) is a streaming graph partitioning algorithm that replicates vertices, a feature that defies representation within the evacuation context. In contrast, AKIN (Zhang et al., 2018) takes streaming edges as input, and while it does not replicate nodes, the partitioner migrates (or repartitions) nodes incident to incoming edges. With some adjustments, a partitioner such as AKIN could serve a role within a more elaborate evacuation plan.

Included Partitioning Features

One possible narrative begins with a family at their home. They are either preparing for an impending disaster or assessing damage that already occurred. At some point, the family deems their home uninhabitable and decides to visit an emergency shelter. They grab their essential belongings and evacuate. This general narrative is shared by multiple families, differing only in its starting time and duration.

How can a shelter assignment algorithm interface with this narrative? To begin, just as everyday people receive information about an impending disaster, so too can emergency management receive, if not provide, this information. While not knowing exactly how this information is perceived and would factor into someone's decision-making process, emergency management could nevertheless acquire a generalised understanding of how various demographics would respond to a disaster and attribute some weight to a formulated prediction of who requires shelter (USEHAZUS, n.d.-b). In this case, shelter assignments could be generated and disseminated prior to anyone making such a request.

Accurately predicting the location and severity of a disaster is not straightforward, and accurately predicting how those affected will respond is an additional challenge. Shifting intervention further down the timeline, another possibility is to wait for people to express a

need for shelter. One could potentially learn of correlations between these people—considering their shared spatial and/or social proximities alongside other shared demographic attributes—and then formulate a prediction of who within the remaining population requires shelter. Although shelter assignments would be generated for both people requesting shelter and the remaining population, one should only disseminate assignments to those requesting shelter. This incentivises people needing shelter to request needing shelter, and with each additional request, one continues to update and strengthen a model’s prediction accuracy, which should ultimately lead to better shelter assignments.

Knowing with absolute certainty who will request a shelter allows one to reserve space at emergency shelters for these people. With such knowledge, one should forgo assigning people to the best shelter in the moment and instead assign people to the best shelter that will eventually transpire. That said, what if the prediction is inaccurate? A probabilistic prediction becomes less useful if it cannot accurately reflect the true underlying probabilities. With a concern for prediction accuracy, one might turn to generating shelter assignments using only the most reliable or well-calibrated data.⁶² In this respect, one could argue that people who request a shelter assignment not only have a very high probability of visiting a shelter but this probability is also quite reliable.⁶³ Whether shelter requests form the basis for predicting who will require shelter (see above) or speak directly to who currently requires shelter, one can expect the ensuing shelter assignments to be generated within a certain timeframe, specifically after people decide to visit a shelter and, generally speaking, before they start travelling.

How people interact with an application can influence the underlying algorithm. For example, an application could learn that people require shelter either by asking for this information or by being offered this information. While the same information would be obtained, one can infer a difference in when the information is obtained. When people initiate the conversation of needing shelter (for example, by launching and running a mobile

⁶² For a discussion on how calibration is a critical facet of accuracy, please see Lindhiem et al. (2020). The classic example of calibration pertains to weather forecasting. If on 100 separate days a forecaster predicts a 20% chance of rain, then the prediction is well calibrated when it rains on 20 of those days. Likewise, while someone requiring a shelter is a binary event/classification, either a shelter is required or not (c.f., it either rains or not), deciding ahead of time how to group people together at shelters while also respecting shelter occupancies demands a well-calibrated, probabilistic prediction of who will become displaced and require shelter.

⁶³ Of course, some granularity exists. Someone requesting a shelter recommendation is probably slightly less likely to visit a shelter than someone navigating to a shelter. Likewise, all else being equal, the probability of someone already at a shelter, which is 100%, should be slightly higher than someone requesting or navigating to a shelter. If someone communicates that no shelter is required, then this information is probably also quite reliable. On the other hand, if someone communicates that a shelter *might be* required (or expresses an inclination toward needing or not needing a shelter), then although this is firsthand information, one can also argue that this information is less reliable. Indeed, one should question whether optimism or pessimism bias, alongside risk aversion, is distorting the estimate of this self-reported “diagnostic.”

application), this would occur sometime after people decide to visit a shelter and before they start travelling. In comparison, when an application initiates this conversation—for example, by texting the question, “Do you require shelter?”—one has multiple reasons to believe that shelter requests will occur earlier in this timeframe. First, the idea of resolving where to evacuate is imparted potentially before people would reflect upon this themselves. Second, contact initiated by an application is time saving. For example, people would not need to remember a certain website (with a login) or cellphone number, or whether they have previously downloaded an application to their mobile device. Third, asking a question invokes a response. In other words, the motivation to respond might not originate from an urgent need for a shelter assignment but from a prompt to answer a question.

The question, “Do you need shelter?” also does not presuppose that people are ready to evacuate. If people say they need shelter, this could imply they are either preparing to evacuate or are fully ready to evacuate pending a recommended shelter assignment. If they never express such a need, one could infer that no shelter is needed or that a shelter is not urgently needed. Therefore, upon receiving an affirmative response to needing shelter, a reasonable follow-up would be, “When ready to leave, please press ‘get directions.’”⁶⁴ Particularly, although not exclusively, relevant to forecastable disasters such as hurricanes, while someone might very well select “yes” and then immediately select “get directions,” the sequence of communication would suggest some time delay between user inputs.

Whenever shelter requests inform shelter assignments, the following principle is at play: maximise the separation in time between collecting data, i.e., collecting shelter requests, and generating output, i.e., generating emergency shelter assignments. Intuitively, this allows for more data to influence the output. In practice, for people ready to evacuate, their generated shelter assignments would be potentially influenced by social acquaintances who will evacuate after them, specifically those people who requested shelter but are still preparing to evacuate. In turn, for those preparing to evacuate, when they eventually do evacuate, their shelter assignments would not simply be a reaction to who is currently at shelters or heading to shelters; indeed, their shelter requests have already influenced where they and recently evacuating acquaintances should go. This foresight is achievable without interrupting or delaying (or delaying minimally) the flow of an evacuation by initiating a natural dialogue, one that separates through a series of questions and answers the time from when people would

⁶⁴ If directions are presumed unnecessary (which depends largely on recommended shelter locations relative to home locations), then one might alternatively prompt, “When ready, please press ‘get shelter location’ for the most updated recommendation.”

request a shelter assignment (the input) from the time when people would act upon knowing the location of a shelter assignment (the output).

With multiple ways for an application to interact with a generalised narrative of pre-evacuation behaviour, although each interaction is associated with different collected data or access to data, ultimately this data requires being partitioned to generate shelter assignments. In this respect, one can point to a combination of partitioning features that together would facilitate partitioning notwithstanding what form the data takes. Indeed, a partitioner could become exceptionally adaptable by incorporating the following partitioning features into its design:

- batching
- fixed vertices
- node weights
- edge weights
- restreaming

For displaced people without a shelter assignment, one can set the window or batch size to include one of these people (to generate near real-time assignments), a group of these people (to generate time-delayed assignments), or all these people at once (to generate predicted assignments). Departing from the literature, the window or batch (herein referred to as batch) is not exactly sliding or tumbling but, if anything, expanding. Specifically, the batch is comprised of two categories of displaced people: an “ever-expanding” group who have received shelter assignments and another group who have yet to receive shelter assignments, where the internal transfer of people from the latter group to the former group, which occurs when shelter assignments are disseminated, could be described as sliding or tumbling. Borrowing from the hypergraph partitioning literature, fixed vertices can represent displaced people already assigned to emergency shelters. This allows the partitioner to simultaneously consider the relationship between people with and without shelter assignments while only (re)positioning those without shelter assignments. Node weights and edge weights, among having other uses,⁶⁵ can reflect the predicted probabilities of people requiring shelter, which enables the partitioner to generate shelter assignments for people who may need shelter in the future.

⁶⁵ For example, if nodes represent individuals, then node weights could expand this notion to mean people travelling together, where the weight (as an integer) corresponds to the number of people (e.g., a family or household).

The above combination of partitioning features affords one tackling the shelter assignment problem a great deal of flexibility. Although these features are somewhat auxiliary to the core logic of partitioning, this research nevertheless considers these features fundamental or nonreplaceable as they allow the partitioner to interface with the evacuation context. As for determining the core logic of partitioning, one must predominately shift focus and analyse not the capabilities of partitioning but the performance of partitioning.

The flexibility gained by controlling the batch size seemingly cuts across broad partitioning categories in which different partitioners excel. For example, when a batch of unassigned people is large, generating shelter assignments using a static graph partitioner would seem appropriate. However, when a batch size comprises a single unassigned person (as when assigning people one at a time to shelters), although one could still use a static graph partitioner, namely, by representing all but one person as fixed vertices, this certainly would be a poor decision. Compared to using a greedy, streaming graph partitioner, output measures would not improve, and in fact, runtime could become prohibitively expensive. Approaching the problem differently, when a batch size of unassigned people is large, although one could generate shelter assignments using a streaming graph partitioner, this would undermine the purpose of creating a batch—one should be taking advantage of a more encompassing, if not global, viewing of the social network when partitioning.

One could integrate both a static and streaming graph partitioner into a shelter assignment algorithm. The challenge is determining a critical batch size that justifies the implementation of one approach over the other, which is partially dependent upon the computational demand associated with evacuation scale and urgency. Alternatively, instead of using multiple partitioners, this research finds that a single partitioner with a feature known as restreaming is well-suited for both small and large batch sizes. When the batch size contains a single unassigned person, one can set the number of restreams to one. As batch sizes increase, so too should the number of restreams increase. This allows more time for convergence to equilibrium, where no additional restreams would further improve shelter assignments. A backtracking algorithm could automate this parameterisation. As noted in the literature (see Appendix C), restreaming partitioners can outperform METIS, the standard static graph partitioner, for social networks up to hundreds of thousands of nodes. For massive-scale batches, one might have to further delineate between when to implement restreaming graph partitioning and static graph partitioning, but at least initially, restreaming graph partitioning stands as a sensibly adaptive approach that simplifies the research.

Beyond paving the way to conduct experiments with various batch sizes (see Chapter 6), restreaming has implications for future research. As restreaming is a greedy approach to partitioning, one could in theory customise the objective function for each displaced person. This opens new and interesting possibilities for research that cannot be explored via static graph partitioning.

The research will now more closely examine two partitioning methods, LDG and FENNEL, which have restreaming versions. While equipping either partitioner to handle edge weights and fixed vertices for batch processing is trivial, introducing node weights is nontrivial and requires additional explanation.

Selecting a Partitioning Method

Upon visiting each node once in a stream, LDG can guarantee perfectly balanced partitions while FENNEL cannot. In practice, strict adherence to desired shelter occupancies could be consequential. For example, shelters might have a limited number of sleeping cots or blankets. Alternatively, if emergency management is conservative with their resources, or if compromising safety, comfort, sanitation, etc., at emergency shelters seems trivial in the wake of a disaster, then approximately balanced shelter occupancy might be satisfactory.

Consider also that LDG only produces balanced partitions upon the completion of an evacuation; FENNEL, on the other hand, maintains relatively balanced partitions throughout the evacuation. In other words, the flow rate of displaced people into shelters using LDG might be inconsistent across shelters; certain shelters could experience a trickle of incoming people while others experience an inundation of people. While difficult to speculate its implications, this distinction might have some relevance, for example, concerning the speed of processing displaced people arriving at shelters and the initial quality of care at shelters. That said, consistency in flowrate (or lack thereof) becomes a moot point if one balances partitions using only the known number of displaced people—those previously assigned to shelters and those in a batch—instead of using a predicted number of displaced people formulated at the onset of an evacuation.

Specific to the restreaming variant of LDG and FENNEL, both methods can guarantee perfectly balanced partitions; however, the latter requires tempering the partitioning imbalance across restreams to achieve this. In other words, instead of establishing a principled trade-off between keeping people together and respecting shelter occupancies (which is required when generating shelter assignments during a single pass), the first pass focuses almost entirely on keeping people together, and with each additional pass, the emphasis shifts to ensuring that

shelter occupancies are respected. In this manner, the algorithm incrementally cherry-picks (for better or worse) the weakest-connected people and redistributes them across shelters.

In a scenario where all displaced people requiring shelter are known upfront, whether restreaming FENNEL is tempered or untempered should have little to no bearing on computational efficiency. However, what if additional people suddenly require shelter? With a dynamic change to the social network, if this change is accompanied by a pressing need to generate shelter assignments, then the evacuation would benefit from the untempered version of restreaming FENNEL. With the untempered version, for example, one could append people to a stream without having to generate all assignments anew. According to Nishimura and Ugander (2013),

When FENNEL is tempered across restreams, the resulting partitioning becomes increasingly rigid, unable to adjust to dynamic changes in a graph. In this way, FENNEL is only appropriate for dynamic graphs in its untempered form, precluding situations where exact balance is important.

Additionally, when FENNEL is tempered across restreams, due to an initial slackness in partitioning imbalance, one cannot stop halfway into running multiple restreams and report assignments without having to worry about the partitions being excessively imbalanced. This aspect of computational efficiency will be revisited in Chapter 6. Taking all this into account, depending on whether restreaming FENNEL is tempered or untempered, it can either guarantee exact partition balance (when tempered) or handle networks dynamically (when untempered). Unlike restreaming LDG, restreaming FENNEL cannot realise both of these conditions at the same time.

As another layer of consideration, one must weigh the significance of both guaranteeing exact partition balance and processing networks dynamically (achieved with restreaming LDG) against meeting only one of these conditions but also producing slightly higher quality partitions (achieved with restreaming FENNEL). Indeed, restreaming FENNEL outperforms restreaming LDG, as measured by the fraction of edges cut (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013).⁶⁶ The objective function of FENNEL and thereby restreaming FENNEL is also associated with maximal quasi-cliques (Tsourakakis et al., 2012; see also Abello et al., 2002), which is a generalisation of maximal cliques, where the largest size subgraphs are almost entirely connected or *complete* (Brunato et al., 2008). Maximal clique detection is how one constructs

⁶⁶ Experiments were conducted using the tempered version of restreaming FENNEL. In exchange for some partitioning imbalance, the untempered version should cut even fewer edges.

a conformal hypergraph (Lauritzen et al., 1984). If hyperedges are retained during partitioning, then one should expect restreaming FENNEL to be particularly adept at reducing communication volume. Moreover, restreaming FENNEL has an intimate relationship with modularity maximisation (Tsourakakis et al., 2012; Nishimura & Ugander, 2013), which is the most widely cited method of community detection (Newman & Girvan, 2004). Although modularity is not used to evaluate restreaming LDG or restreaming FENNEL, restreaming FENNEL’s objective function seems better suited to preserving community structure.

Alternative partitioning methods to restreaming LDG and restreaming FENNEL include EGYPT (Tsourakakis, 2015), a two-hop approach that would function as a natural extension to LDG or FENNEL, and CST (Filippidou & Kotidis, 2015b), a condensed spanning tree approach that shows promising results while embracing a fundamentally different design methodology. These methods are both introduced in Appendix C (see “Initialisation Before Partitioning” section), and their reported partitioning quality does not reflect how they would perform without initialisation. One might also look to the streaming hypergraph partitioning literature for plausible partitioning methods, beginning with Alistarh et al. (2015) and Epple (2017), as well as streaming graph partitioning algorithms that emphasise reducing communication cost (without replication) instead of the fraction of edges cut (Chen & Huan, 2016). Lastly, one could construct a multi-criteria objective function, such as presented by Mayer et al. (2017) and incorporate a specific community detection metric as part of the score.

Each of the above partitioners excels in a particular scenario. If not selecting a partitioner to meet specific demands, then what is of central importance, across all scenarios, is keeping together as many displaced people as possible at emergency shelters. Therefore, the primary motivation for selecting restreaming FENNEL, and more specifically the untempered version, is this method’s partitioning quality as concerns minimising the fraction of edges cut (as demonstrated in experiments) and its relationship with modularity maximisation (as discussed theoretically). Restreaming FENNEL is also well couched in the literature. Researchers have independently verified its partitioning quality (see Appendix C). Furthermore, the method has been integrated into the software PowerLyra (Chen, Shi, et al., 2015), which has undergone its own extensive evaluation. Other researchers have introduced a variety of techniques to reduce restreaming FENNEL’s computational overhead, and one can draw upon this knowledge if greater computational efficiency is necessary (see Appendix C).

Parameterising FENNEL

A traditional graph partitioning problem attempts to minimise the number of edges cut across all partitions subject to a hard cardinality constraint, whereby a minimum partition size is enforced (i.e., defined by the number of nodes divided by the number of partitions multiplied by an imbalance parameter). In contrast, FENNEL relaxes the hard cardinality constraint by formulating a global objective function consisting of two elements: the summation of minimising the number of edges cut (inter-partitioning cost) and minimising the imbalance of partition sizes (intra-partitioning cost; Tsourakakis et al., 2012).

Building toward a formal understanding of FENNEL, the following notation has been lifted from Nishimura and Ugander (2013):

Let $P^t = \{P_i^t, \dots, P_k^t\}$ denote a k -way partitioning of the node set at time t , where P_i^t is the set of nodes in partition i at time t and $P_i^t(u)$ denotes the partition that contains node u . A streaming algorithm is sequentially presented a node u and its neighbours $N(u)$, and it must assign u to a partition i utilising no more information than contained in the current partitioning P^t . Over the course of a stream, the time counter advances by one for each node it examines.

As Nishimura and Ugander succinctly re-formalise, FENNEL thus maximises the following objective function:

$$H = \sum_{u \in V} |P^t(u) \cap N(u)| - \frac{\alpha}{2} \left| \sum_{i=1}^k |P_i^t| \right|^\gamma.$$

When making streaming assignments, one must assign node u to a partition that maximises the change $\Delta H_i^t(u) = |P_i^t \cap N(u)| - \frac{\alpha}{2} [(|P_i^t| + 1)^\gamma - (|P_i^t|)^\gamma]$, which to first order approximation (being exact for $\gamma = 2$) corresponds to FENNEL's assignment rule (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013):

$$\operatorname{argmax}_{i \in \{1, \dots, k\}} |P_i^t \cap N(u)| - \alpha \frac{\gamma}{2} (|P_i^t|)^{\gamma-1}.$$

As the number of neighbours in a partition increases, represented by $|P_i^t \cap N(u)|$, the score of the partition increases. The partitioning imbalance is ensured with a penalty function based on the number of vertices in the partition, $|P_i^t|$. More specifically, as described by Battaglino et al. (2015),

we exponentially weight the edge counts [i.e., the number of neighbours in a partition] by the size of partitions $|P_i^t|$, relatively dampening the scores for partitions that are too large (but penalising only lightly for small differences in size). This gives us two

parameters: the linear importance of partition size to the score, α , and the exponential rate at which increasing partition size incurs a greater penalty, γ .

For parameterising the function, when $\gamma = 1$, the intra-partitioning cost is no longer a convex increasing function; in effect, the imbalance parameter is ignored, leaving $|P_i^t \cap N(u)|$ to minimise the number of edges cut (potentially resulting in all nodes assigned to a single partition). On the other hand, when γ increases, emphasis is placed on the imbalance partitioning cost. Tsourakakis et al. (2012) proceed to demonstrate that when balancing is enforced, $1 \leq \gamma \leq 2$ amounts to interpolating between assigning nodes to the “most number of neighbours” (Stanton & Kliot, 2012) and the “least number of non-neighbors” (Prabhakaran et al., 2012).

As for their experiments, Tsourakakis et al. (2012) find that when $\gamma < 1.5$, the imbalance becomes unacceptably large for real-world applications. When $\gamma = 1.5$, however, they report that FENNEL produces an imbalance essentially identical to METIS and delivers the best *pointwise* results given their testing domain (γ ranges from 1 to 4 with a step of 0.25). That said, the fraction of edges cut when $\gamma = 2$ is almost the same (see Tsourakakis et al., 2012), and moreover, $\gamma = 2$ carries an interesting combinatorial interpretation. Indeed, the above assignment rule becomes the streaming equivalent to modularity maximisation with an Erdos-Rényi random graph null model, where node pairs are connected with probability α (Tsourakakis et al., 2012; Nishimura & Ugander, 2013). Following in the footsteps of Nishimura and Ugander (2013), this research parameterised FENNEL with $\gamma = 2$, bringing about this special case instance of the objective function.

Tsourakakis et al. (2012) focus primarily on the γ parameter, which interpolates between two state-of-the-art heuristics (Prabhakaran, 2012; Stanton & Kliot, 2012); however, the published results suggest that while interpolation does marginally improve results, FENNEL moreover owes success to the principled selection of the α parameter. Recall that FENNEL can represent the “least number of neighbours” or “non-neighbours” (NN) heuristic when $\gamma = 2$. Given that FENNEL parameterised with $\gamma = 1.5$ and $\gamma = 2$ produces nearly the same fraction of edges cut (Tsouakakis et al., 2012), and considering that FENNEL parameterised with $\gamma = 1.5$ significantly outperforms the NN heuristic (Tsourakakis et al., 2012, Table 3), then a great deal of FENNEL’s success is attributable to the α value. As for setting α , this research begins with what Tsourakakis et al. (2012) recommend for a one-pass, streaming version of FENNEL, implementing a principled choice of α irrespective of whether such a choice is truly optimal:

$$\alpha = m \frac{k^{(\gamma-1)}}{n^\gamma},$$

where m is the number of edges, n is the number of nodes, and k is the number of partitions. Using Nishimura and Ugander’s (2013) presentation of FENNEL, which deviates slightly from the original (cf., Tsourakakis et al., 2012), the value of α should be multiplied by 2. This ensures proper scaling of α within the objective function (as specified above).

While calculating α requires knowing a priori the number of nodes and edges in a graph, the context at hand involves an unbounded stream; indeed, knowing exactly who requires shelter at the onset of an evacuation is improbable. As a resolution, this research continually recalculates α as nodes accumulate (i.e., as more shelter requests are known during an evacuation). One should expect these recalculations to stabilise and converge over the duration of an evacuation. Furthermore, potentially large fluctuations in α should be mitigated when node assignments are batch processed, particularly given a large first batch.

Parameterising Restreaming FENNEL

As conceived by Nishimura and Ugander (2013), the concepts of *restreaming* and *tempering* go hand in hand. In fact, the authors use interchangeable terminology to denote their modification of FENNEL, sometimes referring to their approach as “restreaming FENNEL” and other times as “tempered FENNEL.”

To parameterise restreaming FENNEL, Nishimura and Ugander (2013) would likely draw attention to tempering, i.e., exponentially increasing the α parameter with each restream. As Nishimura and Ugander (2013) explain,

tempering increasingly emphasizes balance, while granting time in the earlier streams to finding high-quality partitions. Alternatively, had FENNEL been run with too high an initial α , the algorithm would have resorted to placing nodes in partitions based solely on balance and without regard to the quality of the partitions.

On the other hand, the final partitioning quality is insensitive to the initial value of α (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013), that is, given α is substantially lower than n/k (partitions are equally balanced when $\alpha > \lceil n/k \rceil$).

Unfortunately, by entangling restreaming with tempering, Nishimura and Ugander (2013) have not conducted experiments that compare restreaming with and without tempering. A decision was therefore made to disassociate the concepts of restreaming and tempering by initially exploring the untempered version of restreaming FENNEL and adopting a principled choice of α , which is maintained across restreams.

As a note toward future research, tempering lends itself to a more expansive implementation than currently addressed by the literature; unique to the given context, one could temper the partitioning imbalance *within* batches (across restreams) as well as *across* batches. The latter involves relaxing the balancing constraint early in the evacuation and then tightening it as the evacuation progresses. This concept is not exclusive to restreaming FENNEL; indeed, when assigning partitions using METIS, for example, then with each new batch, one could reduce the imbalance parameter.⁶⁷ Future research could more thoroughly examine these methods.

Weighted Variant of FENNEL

While this research makes extensive use of restreaming FENNEL, several proposed strategies will additionally require that the assignment algorithm handle both node weights and edge weights. Faraj and Schulz (2021) recently proposed a weighted version of FENNEL. Their assignment rule merits an explanation, and one beyond that which the authors provide.⁶⁸

Regarding both FENNEL and its restreaming variant, this research found Nishimura and Ugander’s (2013) explanation succinct and thereby adopted their notation. As concerns detailing the weighted variant of FENNEL, this research must introduce additional definitions, and finds that borrowing some notational cues from Tsourakakis et al. (2012) contributes to a more clear and concise explanation. Furthermore, as Faraj and Schulz (2021) base their notation on Tsourakakis et al. (2012), this decision allows one to more easily cross-reference the results derived herein.

Given a graph with a set of edges E and a set of nodes U , where the number of each is represented by m and n respectively, one can consider partitions P of U into k subsets, $S_i \subseteq U$, for.⁶⁹ The set of edges cut by the i th subset S_i is denoted by

$$e(S_i, U \setminus S_i).$$

⁶⁷ A significant challenge is predicting the end state of the evacuation—the total number of nodes and edges—which is required to specify α and temper across batches. When social networks are being revealed in real time, although the literature addresses how to artificially scale them (e.g., Musaafer et al., 2020; Staudt et al., 2017), one must still specify to what extent. As a starting point, for different types of disasters, knowing historically the rate at which displaced people enter Red Cross shelters (which is not exactly the same as the rate at which people require shelter) could be useful information when predicting the total number of nodes. Albeit a blurry distinction, instead of tempering *across* batches, one could also apply shorter-range, time-series forecasting to tempering *within* batches by slightly adjusting α towards its final value.

⁶⁸ The research acknowledges the contribution of Alex S. Arvanitakis for formulating the upcoming equations. These equations speak to the intention of Faraj and Schulz’s (2021) assignment rule but do not defend the correctness of it.

⁶⁹ One can think of this as $S_i \subseteq P^t$ using Nishimura and Ugander’s (2013) notation.

The optimisation problem is to minimise simultaneously the “value” of edges cut by the partition while ensuring that all subsets S_i have roughly the same value. One might say “value” rather than “size” because the point is to generalise the original FENNEL algorithm to a situation where the edges and nodes carry weights. To ensure subset value parity, one needs an auxiliary real function $c(x)$. Following Tsourakakis et al. (2012), consider the class

$$c(x) = \alpha x^\gamma,$$

which depends on two parameters, $\alpha > 0$ and $\gamma \geq 1$.⁷⁰

This research also defines node weight w_u and edge weight w_e functions, $w_u: U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $w_e: E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which are normalised in the sense that

$$\sum_{v \in U} w_u(v) = n \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{e \in E} w_e(e) = m,$$

so that the original version of FENNEL, which is unweighted, is the special case where $w_u(u) = w_e(e) = 1$. The weights of subsets of nodes $S \subseteq U$ and subsets of edges $T \subseteq E$ are defined in the natural way,

$$w_u(S) = \sum_{u \in S} w_u(u) \quad \text{and} \quad w_e(T) = \sum_{e \in T} w_e(e),$$

so $w_u(U) = n$ and $w_e(E) = m$ in the unweighted case.

One can now define the objective function $g(\mathcal{P})$ to be *maximised*:

$$g(\mathcal{P}) = m - \underbrace{\left(w_e(\partial e(\mathcal{P})) + \sum_{i=1}^k c(w_u(S_i)) \right)}_{f(\mathcal{P})},$$

where $\partial e(\mathcal{P})$ is the set of all cut edges $\cup_{i=1}^k e(S_i, U \setminus S_i)$. Note that maximising the function $g(\mathcal{P})$ corresponds to minimising $f(\mathcal{P})$, which is the objective of the k -way partitioning problem.

Given a partition \mathcal{P} and a “new” node u , one can assign u to a subset S_i such that the difference $\delta g(u, S_i)$ in g between the resulting partition $\mathcal{P}'(i)$ —where $S_i \rightarrow S_i \cup \{u\}$ —and original partition is greatest. The two terms in the objective function $g(\mathcal{P})$ contribute as follows. From the difference of the terms $w_e(\partial e(\mathcal{P}))$ for \mathcal{P} and $\mathcal{P}'(i)$, one obtains

$$+w_e(e(\{u\}, N(u) \cap S_i)),$$

which represents the weight of all edges ending with one end on u and another in S_i . From the difference of $\sum_{i=1}^k c(w_u(S_i))$, one obtains

⁷⁰ This intra-partition cost function is chosen to be super-modular (Tsourakakis et al., 2012). Its properties allow one to adjust the extent to which an imbalance in subset size affects the value of the objective function.

$$\begin{aligned}
-c(w_u(S_i) + w_u(u)) + c(w_u(S_i)) &\approx -w_u(u) \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=w_u(S_i)} \\
&= -w_u(u) \alpha \gamma (w_u(S_i))^{\gamma-1},
\end{aligned}$$

the associated change in the cost function. Note that once again for $\gamma = 2$, this is exact and not an approximation.

Consideration of these terms motivated the use of the greedy assignment rule proposed by Faraj and Schulz (2021), which states that an additional node u should be added to whichever partition subset S_i maximises the quantity

$$w_e(e(\{u\}, N(u) \cap S_i)) - w_u(u) \alpha \gamma (w_u(S_i))^{\gamma-1}.$$

When using this greedy assignment rule, one should pay particular attention to the node and edge weight functions (as described above). When node and edge weights are not equal to one—e.g., when node weights represent probabilities of people requiring shelter, and/or when edge weights signify relationships between people that are valued differently—one can respect the ratio between these weights (in a simple manner) by multiplying the unnormalised probabilities, P_u and P_e , by the scaling factors,

$$\frac{n}{\sum_{u \in U} P_u(u)} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{m}{\sum_{e \in E} P_e(e)},$$

and in so doing, maintain the principled choice of α , as prescribed by Tsourakakis et al. (2012).

As a concluding remark, just as Nishimura and Ugander (2013) extended FENNEL to create restreaming FENNEL, so too can one extend this weighted variant to operate with multiple restreams. In the next chapter, restreaming FENNEL and, in some instances, a weighted version of restreaming FENNEL will serve as a foundation from which to introduce more advanced techniques.

Chapter 5

Three Partitioning Strategies

A reasonable expectation is that a successful emergency shelter assignment algorithm will make use of real-time data. One might in practice employ an *adaptive* strategy, where real-time data, taking the form of knowing who requires shelter, is used to generate on-the-fly shelter assignments. Alternatively, one might employ an *adaptable* strategy, where using real-time data is not a characteristic of the algorithm but a capability of it. In the latter case, one could generate shelter assignments pre-evacuation (i.e., not in real time) based on a prediction of who will require shelter. What makes this approach viable is the capability to pivot to real-time data, that is, to change the trajectory of outcome measures if warranted. More generally, one can endorse the integration of multiple strategies into an emergency shelter assignment algorithm, where different strategies excel at different points in time during an evacuation.

For any given scenario, one can imagine different algorithms running in parallel, each executing a unique shelter assignment strategy. Through a retrospective lens, one could easily identify which strategy performs best. One might further discover that switching between shelter assignment strategies mid-evacuation leads to even better outcomes. When evaluating strategies in real time, keep in mind that what might initially appear as poor assignments could set up and become very good assignments. One could also correctly identify a strategy better than the one being implemented; however, the benefits of switching to this strategy might be marred by a transition cost, where improvements never materialise. While a potential research direction is identifying when to “jump tracks” from one strategy to another, i.e., how to evaluate the trajectory of outcome measures, this begs the more preliminary question of whether switching between strategies mid-evacuation is warranted in the first place. This research thereby proposes to investigate the consequences of switching (or not switching) between shelter assignment strategies as well as the consequences of making a correct decision to switch that is either premature or delayed.

This research will present three shelter assignment strategies that extend restreaming FENNEL or its weighted variant (see Chapter 4). The first strategy uses probabilities of people requiring shelter to generate assignments pre-evacuation. This method is herein referred to as the static prediction strategy. In the event that probabilities of those requiring shelter are unattainable or unreliable, this research presents two additional strategies that incorporate near real-time data. Under the first alternative strategy, as people request shelter, the social relationships between these people and those already at shelters (or en route to them) are used to generate assignments. This method is herein referred to as the real-time batch strategy. Under

the second alternative, as people request shelter, one can learn where they are becoming displaced and use this geographic information to formulate probabilities of requiring shelter for the remaining population. Generating shelter assignments in this way is herein referred to as the dynamic prediction strategy.

Static Prediction Strategy

While one cannot truly know who requires shelter pre-disaster, one can formulate a reasonable prediction. In the United States, for example, those involved with emergency management—federal agencies, research institutions, and regional planning authorities—make use of the nationally standardised risk modelling methodology, HAZUS, for disaster preparedness and mitigation. Among the many outputs, HAZUS can quantify “social impacts,” which include estimates of displaced households and shelter requirements.

Given that one can predict who will require shelter, one can also incorporate this prediction into a graph or hypergraph partitioner to generate shelter assignments. Recall that k -way partitioning requires that the sum of node weights within each partition be approximately equal. If node weights represent the probability of individuals requiring shelter and these probabilities are accurate, then while the shelter assignments (which reserve space for people who may and may not require shelter) could be significantly imbalanced, one nevertheless should expect the number of actual people visiting each shelter to be approximately equal.

Turning to the other objective of k -way partitioning, namely, reducing the fraction of edges cut, one can further propose that partitioning should avoid, as a matter of priority, cutting edges between people whose joint probability of requiring shelter is high. From this perspective, edge weights should represent, at least in part, the *product* of adjacent node weights (assuming that node weights are greater than or equal to one). That said, as prediction accuracy diminishes, at a certain point weighting edges in this manner becomes counterproductive. If one were to bypass this proposed technique and set all edge weights to one, given an accurate prediction, the partitioner should not perform quite as well; however, given an inaccurate prediction, the partitioner should also not perform quite as poorly.

Upon implementing the static prediction strategy, one should be prepared to switch away from it, as foreseeable limitations are inherent to this approach. First, the evacuation must be large enough to justify using this strategy. As concerns the central limit theorem, the larger the target shelter occupancies, the narrower the margin of error when relying on probabilities

to reach these occupancies.⁷¹ Second, as a compounding problem, the probabilities require precision and accuracy. If the benefits of the static prediction strategy come from having a global view of who requires shelter (as opposed to a narrow, real-time view), then the question becomes how much imprecision and inaccuracy can this approach tolerate before a strategy using a streaming, real-time view produces better results?

Real-Time Batch Strategy

From the standpoint of extending the partitioning literature, the real-time batch strategy requires the least explanation. Unlike the static prediction strategy, where a novel use of node weights and edge weights is introduced (which could be applied to other partitioning contexts), the real-time batch strategy does not make use of these. The algorithm is essentially a composite of existing partitioning features—batching, fixed vertices, and restreaming—novelly applied to the evacuation context (see Chapter 4). When using the real-time batch strategy, the batch size of unassigned displaced people is a subset of the population. This aligns with a common notion of batching, and with respect to those already at shelters, combines with fixed vertices in an intuitive way.

This research has introduced multiple ways to batch process nodes (see Appendix C) and, in practice, advocates for batch processing in a window that is “expanding” while “sliding” (see Chapter 4). However, with over 500 scenarios to test (as to be discussed), experiments are conducted using an “expanding” while “tumbling” method, which is computationally more efficient.

Methodologically speaking, the real-time batch strategy is also a stepping stone to what is presented next, the dynamic prediction strategy, which makes use of every partitioning feature proposed thus far: node weights, edge weights, batching, fixed vertices, and restreaming. Drawing a distinction between collecting data and generating assignments is essential for both the real-time batch strategy and the dynamic prediction strategy. With the latter, one must further distinguish between generating assignments and disseminating assignments.

⁷¹ To compensate for a wide margin of error, one might tighten the imbalance constraint and/or accept less balanced partitions. One could also correct for partitioning imbalance by switching to real time data. In theory, this switch would occur earlier (or immediately) for small evacuations and later (or not at all) for massive evacuations.

Dynamic Prediction Strategy

If people become displaced, then their neighbours are more likely to become displaced. This basic assumption is cast against the notion that a physical disaster impacts a geographic area. With finer granularity, if people with similar resources and dispositions (financial, social, educational, cultural, etc.) are more likely to reside in close proximity, and assuming that a physical disaster impacts different demographics asymmetrically, then one might very well find spatial clusters of people who require shelter within a larger area of displacement.

Apart from the spatial relationship between those currently displaced and those not (yet) displaced, one can also point to a temporal relationship. If one can observe an evacuation unfolding, then by noting where displaced people requiring shelter reside and presuming that these locations are part of spatial clusters (beyond Poisson clumping) that will form or continue to form, that is, after controlling for population density, one can formulate in real time a prediction of who will require shelter in the future. By integrating this concept with partitioning, this research proposes the dynamic prediction strategy.

For people who register to receive a shelter assignment recommendation, one must acquire from them what the Red Cross already considers routine information, namely, their pre-disaster address (Disaster Cycle Services, 2016). In the event of a disaster, these people will be asked whether they require shelter. Taking their responses as “yes” or “no” labels (1s or 0s) and their pre-disaster addresses as x- and y-values, one can pass this information into a generalised additive model (GAM).⁷² Conceptually speaking, above a plane in Euclidean space containing points that describe relative distances between pre-disaster addresses, GAMs generate a visually smooth, three-dimensional surface (determined within this work as a penalised thin plate regression spline),⁷³ which is *higher* in locations where more people respond “yes” (a source area) and *lower* where more people respond “no” (a sink area). As the evacuation is underway and more labels are collected, this smooth surface becomes more contoured and more precisely indicates the addresses of people requiring shelter. For people

⁷² Compared to machine learning techniques that would serve a similar purpose (a topic covered in the discussion), both generalised linear models (GLMs) and generalised additive models (GAMs) are relatively “mature” statistics, supported by a plethora of studies guiding their general usage and interpretability (Phillips et al., 2006; see also Elith et al., 2005). This aligns with a recommendation by Merow et al. (2014), who “suggest that researchers develop a comprehensive understanding of regression models in general and GLMs in particular, as these represent the foundation of almost all of the more complex modelling frameworks.” Without straying too far from this recommendation, while GAMs methodologically admit more complexity than GLMs (Merow et al., 2014), GAMs operationally are simpler. More specifically, GAMs are a semi-parametric extension of GLMs that also have, according to Hastie & Tibshirani (1986), “the advantage of being completely automatic, i.e. no ‘detective work’ is needed on the part of statistician” (see also El-Bachir & Davison, 2019; Hastie & Tibshirani, 1990).

⁷³ This technique is primarily investigated by Wood (2003) and is part of the R language software package, mgcv (Wood, 2023), used in this research.

who have not responded to needing shelter (i.e., those without a “yes” or “no” label), one can identify the points representing their pre-evacuation addresses within the plane and then project upward to read where the z-axis intersects the smooth surface. The distance to the surface will fall in the interval (0,1), with 0 implying no need for shelter and 1 implying a definite need (see Figure 24).

In the case of the dynamic prediction strategy, batching allows one to collect more responses to needing shelter prior to making a prediction that affects shelter assignments. By collecting more responses, one is not only left making fewer predictions (which of course is beneficial), but the additional “yes” and “no” labels further refine the surface created by GAMs, which in turn improves prediction quality.

For people who respond “yes,” this research sets their probability of needing shelter to 99%. For those who respond “no,” this research sets their probability to 1%.⁷⁴ For everyone else, the GAM generates their probability of requiring shelter. Those who respond to needing a shelter (notwithstanding how they respond) are divided into two groups: those who have already received a shelter assignment, denoted as fixed vertices, and those (within a batch) who are waiting to receive a shelter assignment, denoted as unfixed vertices. Everyone else within the disaster zone (those who have not responded to needing shelter) also falls into the category and is represented by unfixed vertices.

Provided with a full view of the social network, the dynamic prediction strategy tracks similarly in logic to the static prediction strategy. The probabilities become node weights between 1 and 99 after multiplication by 100 and rounding to the nearest whole number. For nodes connected by an edge, their respective node weights are multiplied together to create an edge weight. A file containing node weights and edge weights, along with a file describing fixed vertices, are passed to a partitioner, which generates shelter assignments. As discussed elsewhere, unlike with the static prediction strategy, one should not disseminate these shelter assignments to those who have not requested them. If people can look up their shelter

⁷⁴ To acknowledge that a prediction is always associated with uncertainty, one should use 99% instead of 100% probability when someone responds “yes” to needing shelter. This difference should not affect the partitioning results. In practice, one might purposefully reduce this percentage. As one example for this reduction, while driving to a shelter, a family might contact a friend who offers to host them, and thereby, the family never visits the shelter. The decision to use 1% instead of 0% probability when someone responds “no” to needing shelter is more deliberate and could affect partitioning results. The virtual presence of acquaintances at shelters (who most certainly will not arrive) becomes a deciding factor for people who actually require shelter whenever two or more shelters are equally attractive according to the objective function. One consequence is that even if displaced people have no additional connections at shelters, the connections that do exist at shelters might be buttressed by virtual one-hop connections (via people who never arrive), which could indicate that people connected at shelters are part of the same community. Generally speaking, more research is necessary to unpack the consequences of using virtual acquaintances while partitioning.

Figure 24

Probability of Requiring Shelter

Note. A visual representation of how a GAM is created and used within an evacuation context. The height of the GAM surface corresponds to the probability of people requiring shelter beneath it.

assignments, they will no longer have a reason to make requests. The spatial data associated with shelter requests is what allows GAMs to update in real time, which leads to better predictions and, ultimately, better assignments.

Data and Parameters

As for data used in the experiments, this research has created socio-spatial networks, upon which different simulated physical disasters are overlaid (see Appendix D). The area of intersection is ascribed different probabilities of households requiring shelter. The static prediction strategy takes these probabilities, along with the associated social networks, and transforms this data into node weights and edge weights, which are then passed into a partitioner to generate shelter assignments pre-disaster. The real-time batch strategy and the dynamic prediction strategy do not use probabilistic data.

As a prediction can go awry in multiple ways, *relative to* the predicted evacuation zones, this research examines what happens when the actual/observed evacuation geographically either (1) shifts or (2) randomises to different extents. Simulations were run with prediction inaccuracy ranging from 0% to 100% in increments of 20%. For each percentage of inaccuracy, each household's probability of requiring shelter is replaced with a binary "yes" or "no" response to needing shelter, and after partitioning, the shelter assignments of people who responded "yes" are evaluated. The real-time batch strategy and the dynamic prediction strategy make use not of the predicted probabilities but these real-time binary responses.

For each way the prediction goes awry, this research generates shelter assignments using a combination of data from 50 social networks, 50 predicted evacuee lists, and six sets of 50 evacuee lists, where each of the six sets respectively represents one of the prediction-inaccuracy levels. The shelter assignment algorithm also internally keeps track of who is assigned to shelters (a generated "fixed vertices" file) and their shelter assignment.

Although prediction-based strategies are well addressed by static graph or hypergraph partitioning, since the real-time batch strategies benefit from a fast and flexible approach, this research uses restreaming FENNEL and its weighted variant (see Chapter 4). This decision places emphasis not on comparing different partitioners but on comparing different strategies or combinations of strategies.

The executable was written in the Python 3 programming language and interfaces with R programming language to access the statistics package `mgcv` (Wood, 2023) used to run the

GAMs.⁷⁵ As for parameterisation, restreaming FENNEL is set to run 10 restreams, and the number of partitions is set to four. The static prediction strategy was applied using just one batch (making fixed vertices unnecessary) while each batch for both the real-time batch strategy and the dynamic prediction strategy consisted of 50 people who responded “yes” to needing shelter.

Selecting Outcome Measures

Having incorporated streaming partitioning methods based on Tsourakakis (2012) and Nishimura and Ugander (2013), this research also appropriates their output measures, fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance. While other measures are also suitable (see Appendix E), they do not directly shape the objective function of the partitioner used.

Conceptually speaking, this research often emphasises the importance of preserving *each* social connection, a position that arguably communicates better when each social connection is represented as a whole number, i.e., as edges cut as opposed to the fraction of edges cut. On the other hand, the fraction of edges cut has some notable advantages. This measure allows one to easily compare thoughtfully partitioned assignments with those randomly partitioned (for k -way partitioning, the average fraction of edges cut for random hash assignments is $1 - 1/k$). Moreover, the fraction of edges cut measure allows one to compare partitioned results from social networks of different sizes.

As this research features two ways a prediction could go awry, so too does this research systematically portray both predictions erring in a manner where different people with different social connections require shelter. This research is therefore comparing social networks of different sizes. Furthermore, if a prediction goes awry in a way that appears geographically random, then well-formed spatial clusters of people requiring shelter are being scattered. As social connections are associated with geographic proximity (as per their construction in this research), this results in fewer connections between people who require shelter. Therefore, when analysing partitioned assignments, although the number of edges cut might seem relatively modest, one must consider that these social networks also have fewer edges.⁷⁶ In this particular scenario, one should report not the edges cut but the fraction of edges cut.

⁷⁵ Basic code for restreaming FENNEL was provided by Justin Vincent, who is also acknowledged in the original restreaming FENNEL article (see Nishimura & Ugander, 2013). The code is freely available at Vincent’s website (Vincent, 2013). To run GAM in the mgcv package, the basic code used is as follows:
`m <- gam(shelter~s(x,y,k=100),family="binomial",method="REML")`.

⁷⁶ For example, suppose a network of people requiring shelter is comprised of 100 nodes and 300 edges. In the case where the prediction is excellent, upon these people visiting the shelter assigned to them, 10% of edges are cut across all shelters (i.e., 30 edges cut). Now suppose that the people requiring shelter are geographically

Evaluating Outcome Measures After Combining Strategies

The experiments conducted in this research measure the fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance as an effect of switching between different partitioning strategies at different points in time as the prediction goes awry in different ways and to different extents. The relationships between these factors are presented in several tables. Within these tables, each column represents a different percentage of prediction accuracy, from completely inaccurate (0%) to completely accurate (100%). Each row represents a different percentage of the evacuation complete, from no one having evacuated (0%) to everyone having evacuated (100%). Corresponding with these conditions/headings, each cell contains the mean fraction of edges cut (and standard deviation) at the end of the evacuation upon switching either (1) from the static partitioning strategy to the real-time batch strategy or (2) from the static partitioning strategy to the dynamic partitioning strategy. These two ways of switching between partitioning strategies are evaluated in relation to two ways the prediction could go awry—hence, four tables are created. Four more tables are similarly created to evaluate strategy changes using partitioning imbalance.

Determining an acceptable trade-off between the fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance is an essential part of any partitioning problem. As partitioning algorithms minimise the fraction of edges cut *subject to* partitioning imbalance, one defines this trade-off via partitioning imbalance, which is typically a hard constraint set to 0%, 1%, 3%, or 5% imbalance (see Walshaw, 2023). In the context of an evacuation, one must further consider that partition sizes, i.e., shelter occupancies, are likewise subject to partitioning imbalance. For any given shelter, one should set the uppermost “target” shelter occupancy slightly below the shelter capacity determined by the Red Cross. The “extra space” should equal the percentage of the target occupancy specified as the partitioning imbalance.

Using this framework, one can maximise the number of people at shelters (or minimise the number of operable shelters) by reducing the partitioning imbalance. Alternatively, one might prioritise reducing the fraction of edges cut by relaxing the partitioning imbalance to some degree. In practice, one would not expect the total occupancy across all shelters to approximate the total number of people seeking shelter, and if this were to happen, emergency

somewhat less concentrated or more scattered than expected. As a result, these people are less acquainted, which results in a network comprised of 100 nodes and 100 edges. Keeping with the original assignments that resulted in 10% edges cut, a slight discrepancy in who actually requires shelter should increase the percentage of edges cut, which results in say 20% edges cut (i.e., 20 edges cut). If one were to report only the number of edges cut without considering the total number of edges in the social network prior to partitioning, then the poor prediction would seem better than the excellent prediction, with 20 edges cut as opposed to 30 edges cut. Of course, acknowledging that the social network of the poor prediction is one-third the size changes the interpretation.

management could always decide to open an additional emergency shelter and thereby redistribute people with a more generous partitioning imbalance.⁷⁷ Given this flexibility, the shelter assignment problem is less concerned with the tightness of partitioning imbalance (c.f., typical partitioning applications) and more concerned with enforcing a given partitioning imbalance.

When choosing a partitioning imbalance percentage to enforce, one should consider simulating the effect on the fraction of edges cut. For a typical partitioning simulation, one would simply adjust the partitioning imbalance parameter and report the fraction of edges cut; however, upon introducing the concept of switching between strategies, one would additionally have to create and adjust a “time to switch” parameter, as this would also impact the fraction of edges cut.

When implementing two (or more) strategies sequentially, each strategy unto itself does not need to pursue an acceptable trade-off between outcome measures; the strategies can compensate for one another. As for how this would occur, the justification for switching between strategies across time as opposed to interpolating between them is that on a relative basis one strategy excels early in the evacuation and the other strategy excels late in the evacuation. Furthermore, if one strategy excels at minimising fractions of edges cut and the other strategy excels at minimising partitioning imbalance (i.e., taking into account prediction accuracy), then as long as the second strategy can adapt to previously made assignments, one measure should improve and the other measure should worsen (relatively speaking) when switching between strategies over time.

This research employs a combination of strategies that could give rise to these conditions. As the static prediction strategy cannot adapt to previously made assignments, one should lead with this strategy. Both the real-time batch strategy and the dynamic prediction strategy are adaptive, meaning one can employ them at any time. Another reason to start with the static prediction strategy is that it utilises only data collected pre-disaster, whereas the other strategies utilise a real-time data feed, which at least initially, does not lend itself to productive shelter assignments.⁷⁸ Furthermore, even if the static prediction strategy is somewhat inaccurate, the fraction of edges cut is unlikely to worsen substantially over time. However,

⁷⁷ All else being equal, adding partitions will typically increase the fraction of edges cut. However, adding partitions while decreasing partitioning imbalance might have the opposite effect. Understanding this relationship in detail requires further research.

⁷⁸ With the real-time-batch strategy, shelter assignments will initially appear mostly random, influenced not by social connections but by partitioning imbalance. With the dynamic prediction strategy, while shelter assignments are initially made using a nearly complete social network, little data is available to prioritise social connections between people who actually require shelter.

the same cannot be said about partitioning imbalance, which requires one to accurately predict who requires shelter.⁷⁹ The dynamic prediction strategy is unique in that predictions are constantly updating and thereby become more accurate with time. As the real-time batch strategy generates shelter assignments only for those who request them (i.e., it does not rely on probabilities), this strategy is even more accurate, allowing one to finetune the partitioning imbalance to whatever is desirable.

In cases where the static prediction strategy is somewhat inaccurate, any postponement in switching strategies could increase partitioning imbalance, a cost that likely accrues with time. The longer one takes to switch, the less time remaining in the evacuation to correct or recover from any deficit in partitioning imbalance. On the other hand, postponement could also reduce the fraction of edges cut (i.e., switching immediately to using less data is not necessarily productive), and if this decrease over time is relatively steeper than the increase in partitioning imbalance, then one might strategically postpone switching strategies. A reason to switch mid-evacuation, for example, would be if the decrease in the fraction of edges cut is represented by an exponential decay function, where many social connections are initially preserved, but where the growing cost in partitioning imbalance eventually dominates the diminished return of preserving a few extra connections. Another reason to switch in mid-evacuation concerns how one might approach the cost-benefit analysis. In this context, while some leeway or tolerance in partitioning imbalance would likely improve the fraction of edges cut, if the number of displaced people at emergency shelters begins to exceed not only desirable shelter occupancies but shelter capacities, then one must account for a reduction in comfort, safety, and resources (food, bedding, medical personnel, etc.), which very quickly could become untenable.⁸⁰

Of central interest to this chapter is whether sequentially combining strategies has merit. A useful point of reference from which to evaluate outcomes is therefore the performance of

⁷⁹ By way of example, suppose an emergency shelter can hold 100 people. If everyone assigned to this shelter has a 10% probability of requiring shelter, then one would need to assign 1,000 people to this shelter to fill it. Although the vast majority of these people would never require shelter, as the shelter assignments are based on partitioning, most of these people would nevertheless be acquainted. Now suppose the prediction is wrong, and more people require shelter than expected. For every 1% increase in the probability of people requiring (beyond what was predicted), the partitioning imbalance would increase by 10%. Intuitively, as the unexpected people visiting the shelter are acquainted, the fraction of edges cut would not experience the same increase.

⁸⁰ Is there a need for the Red Cross to redefine shelter capacities based on whether shelters are comprised primarily of strangers or social acquaintances? Comfort, safety, and resources, alongside other factors that determine shelter capacities, are certainly linked to the physical number of people at shelters. However, one should note that comfort, safety, and resources also have a social component. If the reason shelter capacities are exceeded is due to partitioning imbalance, then this implies the presence of social acquaintances at shelters, which in turn might justify a slight increase in shelter capacities. Conceptually speaking, thinking of the fraction of edges cut as a social matter and partitioning imbalance as a physical matter is an overgeneralisation.

one strategy acting alone. As discussed, the only strategy that can reliably act alone is an adaptive one, e.g., the real-time batch strategy or the dynamic prediction strategy. As for another useful point of reference, given that some partitioning imbalance is acceptable (see discussion above), this research posits that relative to the partitioning imbalance achieved with an adaptive strategy, increasing this amount by 1% is either nominal or at least not egregiously untenable in some scenarios. Of course, what is of interest here is not whether a 1% increase in partitioning imbalance is acceptable but whether it is justifiable. To reach this determination, this research evaluates the resulting improvement in the fraction of edges cut. The research also determines how long one would postpone switching strategies (as a percentage of the evacuation completed). The results obtained from this postponement are then compared to the results obtained when never switching strategies. Repercussions for switching or not switching, and doing so too early or too late, are also presented in the output tables and analysed. In cases where the partitioning imbalance decreases with postponement, the research will also draw attention to this benefit.

Results

If people are evacuating from a slightly different location than predicted (see Appendix D), then when the prediction is 80% accurate (see Table 2), one should continue using the static prediction strategy until roughly 20% to 25% of the evacuation is complete before switching to the real-time batch strategy. Against the backdrop where an immediate switch to the real-time batch strategy produces an approximately 5% partitioning imbalance (the lowest value for this accuracy level; see Table 3), the above assessment is contingent upon a willingness to exchange an additional 1% partitioning imbalance for approximately an additional 3% improvement in the fraction of edges cut (specifically in the range, 2.80% to 3.27%). Instead of this additional 3% improvement, to achieve an additional 4% improvement, one would essentially never switch from using the static prediction strategy. This would result, however, in approximately an additional 33% increase in partitioning imbalance, bringing the total to over 38% partitioning imbalance.

In a scenario where the prediction is 100% accurate, one would likewise switch strategies when the evacuation is 20% to 25% complete, and the additional 1% partitioning imbalance would exchange for slightly more than an additional 3% improvement in the fraction of edges cut (specifically in the range, 3.26% to 3.48%). If one never switches from the static prediction strategy, then instead of this additional 3% improvement, one can additionally

Table 2

Mean and Standard Deviation of Fraction of Edges Cut
When Switching Mid-Evacuation from the *Static Prediction Strategy* to the *Real-Time Batch Strategy*
Given the Prediction Goes Awry from "Shifting"

Evacuation Complete	0%	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%
	17.00 (2.30) *	16.66 (2.10) *	17.02 (2.53) *	16.35 (2.46) *	16.72 (2.61) *	16.84 (2.68) *					
	17.50 (2.82) *	16.60 (2.85) *	16.97 (2.70) *	16.77 (2.68) *	16.35 (2.37) *	16.26 (2.69)					
	21.38 (3.24)	19.19 (3.11)	17.16 (2.81)	16.12 (2.50) *	15.53 (2.34) *	15.63 (2.38) *					
	25.41 (4.26)	21.79 (3.38)	18.16 (3.27)	15.72 (2.92)	14.55 (2.28)	14.60 (2.59)					
	30.01 (4.57)	25.32 (3.58)	20.59 (2.84)	16.26 (2.94)	13.92 (2.32) *	13.58 (2.46) *					
	34.37 (5.18)	28.19 (4.06)	22.05 (3.24)	17.27 (3.33)	13.45 (2.49)	13.36 (2.58)					
	39.13 (5.26)	31.35 (4.66)	23.96 (3.31)	17.67 (3.49)	13.30 (2.45)	12.70 (2.72)					
	42.66 (5.64)	34.34 (5.61)	25.55 (3.80)	18.16 (3.45)	13.12 (2.44)	12.33 (2.29)					
	45.35 (5.76)	36.70 (5.91)	27.29 (4.40)	19.08 (3.45)	13.26 (2.46)	12.10 (2.24)					
	47.28 (6.08)	38.67 (5.76)	28.71 (4.61)	19.53 (3.65)	13.35 (2.23)	11.83 (2.22)					
	49.29 (5.45)	39.77 (5.50)	29.21 (5.12)	19.61 (3.56)	13.25 (2.54)	11.69 (2.27)					
	49.31 (4.88)	39.86 (5.16)	29.60 (4.75)	19.86 (3.77)	13.33 (2.27)	11.55 (2.28)					
	48.99 (4.36)	40.12 (5.31)	30.32 (4.69)	20.25 (3.83)	13.50 (2.33)	11.43 (2.21)					
	47.11 (3.65)	39.11 (4.72)	30.11 (4.66)	20.68 (3.54)	13.48 (2.52)	11.44 (2.18)					
	45.29 (3.46)	37.76 (4.54)	29.77 (4.54)	20.61 (3.67)	13.60 (2.67)	11.40 (2.31)					
	42.57 (4.18)	35.58 (4.03)	28.56 (3.89)	20.20 (3.69)	13.62 (2.78)	11.38 (2.27)					
	38.84 (4.71)	32.51 (4.20)	26.84 (4.01)	19.74 (3.79)	13.62 (2.77)	11.31 (2.28)					
	34.61 (5.12)	28.82 (4.45)	24.34 (3.75)	18.87 (3.62)	13.51 (2.77)	11.32 (2.28)					
	29.59 (6.26)	24.63 (5.19)	21.53 (4.16)	17.61 (3.80)	13.38 (2.75)	11.36 (2.28)					
	23.63 (7.00)	19.89 (5.91)	18.13 (4.62)	15.70 (3.88)	13.08 (2.79)	11.40 (2.29)					
	16.51 (8.28)	13.77 (6.63)	13.70 (5.07)	13.23 (3.98)	12.67 (2.86)	11.41 (2.31)					

0% Partition Imbalance

> 50% Partition Imbalance

20% Partition Imbalance

50% - 30.01% Partition Imbalance

40% Partition Imbalance

30% - 10.01% Partition Imbalance

60% Partition Imbalance

10% Partition Imbalance

80% Partition Imbalance

Partition Imbalance within Additional 1% of Top Row

100% Partition Imbalance

Evacuation Prediction Accuracy

Note. The top row depicts the fraction of edges cut when using the real-time batch strategy alone, and the bottom row depicts the fraction of edges cut when using the static prediction strategy alone. The right-most column depicts the fraction of edges cut when the evacuation is predicted with 100% accuracy. The asterisks and greyscale overlay pertain to partitioning imbalance and are derived from values presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Mean and Standard Deviation of Partitioning Imbalance
When Switching Mid-Evacuation from the *Static Prediction Strategy* to the *Real-Time Batch Strategy*
Given the Prediction Goes Awry from "Shifting"

Evacuation Complete	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
0%	1.049 (3.53) *	1.044 (3.12) *	1.052 (3.50) *	1.059 (3.82) *	1.049 (3.56) *	1.045 (3.04) *
10%	1.049 (3.70) *	1.053 (3.63) *	1.050 (3.31) *	1.046 (2.79) *	1.056 (3.73) *	1.061 (3.93)
	1.082 (5.30)	1.077 (5.00)	1.070 (4.92)	1.062 (4.06) *	1.057 (4.40) *	1.052 (3.48) *
	1.076 (3.94)	1.086 (4.65)	1.088 (4.98)	1.075 (4.88)	1.061 (4.09)	1.059 (4.59)
20%	1.103 (4.83)	1.092 (5.11)	1.108 (4.89)	1.095 (5.52)	1.058 (4.12) *	1.052 (3.33) *
	1.145 (5.15)	1.145 (4.51)	1.124 (4.89)	1.119 (4.80)	1.070 (4.70)	1.059 (3.25)
30%	1.218 (6.62)	1.199 (6.13)	1.168 (6.21)	1.133 (4.69)	1.086 (5.93)	1.066 (4.38)
	1.322 (8.75)	1.270 (7.77)	1.221 (6.73)	1.172 (5.95)	1.109 (5.49)	1.056 (4.03)
40%	1.443 (13.08)	1.353 (9.44)	1.270 (7.20)	1.201 (7.07)	1.119 (5.21)	1.061 (4.13)
	1.585 (16.37)	1.457 (11.09)	1.339 (8.94)	1.246 (7.00)	1.127 (5.78)	1.062 (4.13)
50%	1.723 (21.31)	1.574 (14.78)	1.420 (8.79)	1.297 (8.24)	1.143 (6.53)	1.063 (4.25)
	1.585 (16.37)	1.691 (17.51)	1.497 (11.77)	1.346 (9.35)	1.159 (7.13)	1.062 (3.62)
60%	2.025 (30.03)	1.812 (20.04)	1.576 (14.38)	1.386 (10.21)	1.176 (7.95)	1.064 (3.61)
	2.189 (34.16)	1.942 (22.97)	1.665 (16.26)	1.432 (10.62)	1.194 (8.19)	1.065 (3.45)
70%	2.348 (38.17)	2.075 (26.82)	1.763 (18.18)	1.494 (12.63)	1.222 (8.11)	1.072 (3.39)
	2.511 (41.68)	2.214 (29.44)	1.864 (21.16)	1.552 (13.82)	1.245 (8.73)	1.070 (3.40)
80%	2.675 (45.40)	2.353 (32.12)	1.966 (23.32)	1.615 (15.34)	1.268 (9.75)	1.076 (3.42)
	2.838 (49.01)	2.493 (35.83)	2.076 (25.17)	1.677 (17.39)	1.296 (10.10)	1.078 (3.71)
90%	3.010 (52.41)	2.637 (38.98)	2.184 (28.34)	1.744 (19.61)	1.322 (11.04)	1.080 (3.65)
	3.185 (55.49)	2.776 (41.73)	2.296 (30.91)	1.821 (21.97)	1.351 (12.33)	1.080 (3.68)
100%	3.368 (57.53)	2.930 (43.84)	2.419 (33.22)	1.904 (23.99)	1.382 (13.55)	1.084 (3.71)

Evacuation Prediction Accuracy

> 50% Partition Imbalance

50% - 30.01% Partition Imbalance

30% - 10.01% Partition Imbalance

≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

* Partition Imbalance within Additional 1% of Top Row

Note. The top row depicts the partitioning imbalance when using the real-time batch strategy alone, and the bottom row depicts the partitioning imbalance when using the static prediction strategy alone. The right-most column depicts the partitioning imbalance when the evacuation is predicted with 100% accuracy. Partitions are balanced perfectly when their value equals 1.000.

Table 4

Mean and Standard Deviation of Fraction of Edges Cut
When Switching Mid-Evacuation from the Static Prediction Strategy to the Real-Time Batch Strategy
Given the Prediction Goes Awry from “Randomization”

Percentage of Evacuation Complete	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
0%	16.58 (1.73) *	16.50 (1.93) *	17.30 (1.77) *	18.13 (1.99) *	18.30 (2.18) *	18.31 (2.11) *
10%	16.25 (1.67) *	15.87 (1.99) *	16.59 (1.75) *	17.22 (2.02) *	17.29 (1.74) *	18.12 (2.01) *
20%	15.94 (1.73) *	15.67 (1.87) *	15.96 (1.60) *	16.16 (1.79) *	16.27 (1.87) *	17.16 (1.79)
30%	15.68 (1.90) *	15.08 (1.83) *	15.22 (1.62) *	15.09 (1.87) *	15.12 (1.78) *	15.25 (1.79) *
40%	14.86 (1.73)	14.38 (1.73) *	14.21 (1.84) *	14.25 (1.58) *	14.46 (1.90) *	14.50 (1.69) *
50%	15.27 (1.58)	14.22 (1.85)	13.83 (1.29) *	13.50 (1.59) *	13.38 (1.58) *	13.42 (1.71) *
60%	15.88 (1.82)	13.94 (1.66)	13.20 (1.39)	12.83 (1.39) *	12.62 (1.55) *	12.78 (1.66) *
70%	16.40 (1.69)	14.01 (1.57)	13.13 (1.73)	12.27 (1.41) *	12.26 (1.35) *	12.44 (1.48) *
80%	16.83 (1.82)	14.41 (1.27)	13.02 (1.54)	11.95 (1.45)	11.82 (1.48) *	11.91 (1.58) *
90%	17.40 (2.02)	14.70 (1.42)	13.14 (1.59)	11.69 (1.46)	11.59 (1.37) *	11.68 (1.40) *
100%	17.70 (2.01)	15.06 (1.41)	13.35 (1.43)	11.70 (1.35)	11.36 (1.27) *	11.41 (1.36) *
	18.21 (2.19)	15.45 (1.62)	13.69 (1.54)	11.54 (1.39)	11.17 (1.27) *	11.33 (1.30) *
	18.47 (2.00)	15.6 (1.730)	14.00 (1.48)	11.60 (1.33)	11.08 (1.26) *	11.19 (1.27) *
	18.89 (1.88)	15.77 (1.59)	14.08 (1.48)	11.71 (1.30)	11.05 (1.29) *	11.11 (1.29) *
	18.96 (1.96)	15.88 (1.46)	14.04 (1.67)	11.78 (1.39)	10.98 (1.32)	11.06 (1.31)
	18.83 (2.15)	16.13 (1.48)	14.03 (1.64)	11.90 (1.46)	10.95 (1.31)	11.00 (1.33)
	18.63 (2.38)	16.13 (1.48)	14.06 (1.74)	11.98 (1.42)	10.96 (1.32)	10.98 (1.33)
	18.27 (2.29)	15.83 (1.48)	13.98 (1.66)	11.92 (1.48)	10.96 (1.37)	10.96 (1.37)
	17.74 (2.51)	15.41 (1.80)	13.78 (1.72)	11.84 (1.50)	11.00 (1.35)	10.96 (1.39)
	16.82 (2.78)	14.96 (2.03)	13.51 (1.81)	11.78 (1.46)	11.05 (1.34)	10.97 (1.40)
	15.60 (3.36)	14.26 (2.34)	13.09 (1.89)	11.70 (1.44)	11.10 (1.36)	11.01 (1.39)

> 50% Partition Imbalance

50% - 30.01% Partition Imbalance

30% - 10.01% Partition Imbalance

≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

Evacuation Prediction Accuracy

* Partition Imbalance within
Additional 1% of Top Row

100%

Note. The top row depicts the fraction of edges cut when using the real-time batch strategy alone, and the bottom row depicts the fraction of edges cut when using the static prediction strategy alone. The right-most column depicts the fraction of edges cut when the evacuation is predicted with 100% accuracy. The asterisks and greyscale overlay pertain to partitioning imbalance and are derived from values presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Mean and Standard Deviation of Partitioning Imbalance
When Switching Mid-Evacuation from the *Static Prediction Strategy* to the *Real-Time Batch Strategy*
Given the Prediction Goes Awry from “Randomization”

Percentage of Evacuation Complete	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
0%	1.021 (1.73) *	1.020 (1.68) *	1.018 (1.52) *	1.020 (1.72) *	1.023 (1.96) *	1.027 (2.13) *
10%	1.018 (1.17) *	1.018 (1.42) *	1.022 (1.63) *	1.019 (1.53) *	1.027 (2.04) *	1.032 (2.46) *
20%	1.018 (1.48) *	1.016 (1.14) *	1.018 (1.49) *	1.021 (1.48) *	1.027 (2.00) *	1.038 (2.53)
30%	1.018 (1.67) *	1.017 (1.4) *	1.022 (1.85) *	1.028 (2.03) *	1.029 (2.21) *	1.035 (2.93) *
40%	1.055 (6.41)	1.025 (2.31) *	1.022 (1.58) *	1.024 (1.85) *	1.026 (2.06) *	1.030 (2.32) *
50%	1.109 (7.96)	1.055 (6.26)	1.025 (3.13) *	1.023 (1.96) *	1.026 (1.76) *	1.036 (2.08) *
60%	1.141 (7.95)	1.104 (8.31)	1.061 (5.84)	1.026 (1.97) *	1.031 (2.01) *	1.035 (2.22) *
70%	1.156 (7.82)	1.129 (8.04)	1.080 (6.50)	1.027 (2.8) *	1.025 (1.51) *	1.035 (2.27) *
80%	1.173 (7.19)	1.141 (7.67)	1.099 (6.77)	1.031 (2.64)	1.026 (1.87) *	1.033 (2.58) *
90%	1.207 (6.92)	1.168 (7.03)	1.128 (6.66)	1.037 (3.08)	1.028 (1.58) *	1.034 (2.25) *
100%	1.245 (8.65)	1.184 (6.94)	1.151 (6.36)	1.061 (4.27)	1.027 (1.70) *	1.035 (2.39) *
	1.284 (9.55)	1.211 (7.18)	1.165 (5.90)	1.086 (4.63)	1.029 (2.19) *	1.035 (2.02) *
	1.326 (11.0)	1.253 (8.62)	1.182 (5.83)	1.107 (4.92)	1.028 (2.16) *	1.036 (2.41) *
	1.368 (11.35)	1.297 (9.43)	1.216 (7.22)	1.129 (5.6)	1.032 (2.35) *	1.037 (2.03) *
	1.414 (12.56)	1.335 (10.65)	1.251 (8.68)	1.141 (5.44)	1.038 (2.86)	1.038 (2.09)
	1.465 (14.27)	1.370 (11.25)	1.286 (9.60)	1.160 (5.03)	1.048 (3.03)	1.038 (2.15)
	1.515 (15.38)	1.411 (11.47)	1.319 (9.90)	1.177 (4.95)	1.058 (3.33)	1.040 (2.19)
	1.565 (16.19)	1.454 (12.76)	1.352 (10.11)	1.200 (5.76)	1.074 (3.68)	1.042 (2.17)
	1.620 (17.16)	1.503 (13.9)	1.390 (10.79)	1.228 (6.45)	1.084 (3.76)	1.044 (2.19)
	1.680 (18.22)	1.550 (14.73)	1.430 (11.90)	1.255 (7.37)	1.095 (3.75)	1.046 (2.20)
	1.743 (19.56)	1.603 (15.97)	1.475 (12.82)	1.285 (8.11)	1.106 (4.30)	1.048 (2.24)

Evacuation Prediction Accuracy

> 50% Partition Imbalance
 50% - 30.01% Partition Imbalance
 30% - 10.01% Partition Imbalance
 ≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

* Partition Imbalance within Additional 1% of Top Row
 ≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

Note. The top row depicts the partitioning imbalance when using the real-time batch strategy alone, and the bottom row depicts the partitioning imbalance when using the static prediction strategy alone. The right-most column depicts the partitioning imbalance when the evacuation is predicted with 100% accuracy. Partitions are balanced perfectly when their value equals 1.000.

Table 6

Mean and Standard Deviation of Fraction of Edges Cut
When Switching Mid-Evacuation from the *Static Prediction Strategy* to the *Dynamic Prediction Strategy*
Given the Prediction Goes Awry from “Shifting”

Percentage of Evacuation Complete	11.33 (1.94) *	10.96 (2.07) *	11.28 (2.16) *	10.85 (2.05) *	10.90 (2.02) *	11.40 (1.92) *
0%	13.15 (2.39) *	12.42 (2.63) *	11.98 (2.34) *	11.21 (2.08) *	11.26 (2.02) *	11.32 (2.02) *
10%	17.12 (3.00) *	15.66 (2.62) *	13.49 (2.82) *	11.66 (2.16) *	10.95 (2.02) *	11.37 (1.88) *
20%	22.02 (3.80) *	19.03 (3.28) *	15.74 (2.55) *	12.44 (2.32) *	11.07 (1.92) *	11.33 (1.97) *
30%	27.07 (3.82)	22.44 (3.44)	18.42 (2.70) *	14.20 (2.55) *	11.33 (2.12) *	11.03 (2.23) *
40%	32.85 (4.78)	26.40 (3.82)	20.81 (3.17)	15.34 (2.95)	11.32 (2.12) *	11.30 (2.24) *
50%	37.65 (5.58)	30.37 (4.96)	22.90 (3.48)	16.56 (3.12)	11.91 (2.52)	11.14 (2.53) *
60%	42.88 (5.98)	34.99 (6.00)	25.75 (4.15)	18.15 (3.31)	12.41 (2.19)	11.08 (2.05) *
70%	46.27 (5.43)	38.73 (6.04)	28.66 (4.51)	19.68 (3.70)	12.82 (2.34)	11.04 (2.15) *
80%	48.33 (5.35)	41.33 (5.42)	31.45 (5.22)	20.82 (4.24)	13.16 (2.15)	11.11 (2.10) *
90%	49.70 (4.74)	42.67 (4.90)	33.43 (5.51)	22.54 (4.40)	13.53 (2.44)	11.16 (2.27) *
100%	50.11 (3.77)	42.98 (4.51)	35.00 (5.25)	23.49 (4.75)	14.03 (2.37)	11.23 (2.22) *
	49.90 (3.20)	42.74 (4.21)	35.53 (4.62)	24.46 (4.64)	14.42 (2.66)	11.27 (2.18) *
	48.19 (3.13)	41.32 (3.89)	34.89 (4.36)	25.26 (4.68)	14.67 (2.70)	11.32 (2.21) *
	46.19 (3.76)	39.75 (4.34)	33.77 (3.96)	26.01 (4.46)	15.08 (2.79)	11.42 (2.23) *
	43.50 (4.43)	37.36 (4.51)	31.88 (3.70)	25.51 (3.92)	15.27 (2.91)	11.40 (2.22)
	39.66 (5.00)	34.18 (4.76)	29.60 (4.06)	24.39 (3.77)	15.55 (2.91)	11.42 (2.26)
	35.18 (5.67)	29.98 (5.28)	26.64 (4.27)	22.41 (3.70)	15.45 (2.78)	11.43 (2.27)
	30.04 (6.67)	25.60 (5.81)	23.06 (4.48)	20.16 (3.84)	15.21 (2.86)	11.43 (2.27)
	23.83 (7.24)	20.37 (6.27)	18.94 (4.81)	17.26 (3.95)	14.31 (2.79)	11.44 (2.29)
	16.51 (8.28)	13.77 (6.63)	13.70 (5.07)	13.23 (3.98)	12.67 (2.86)	11.41 (2.31)

0%

20%

40%

60%

80%

100%

> 50% Partition Imbalance

50% - 30.01% Partition Imbalance

30% - 10.01% Partition Imbalance

≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

Evacuation Prediction Accuracy

* Partition Imbalance within
Additional 1% of Top Row

Note. The top row depicts the fraction of edges cut when using the *dynamic prediction strategy* alone, and the bottom row depicts the fraction of edges cut when using the *static prediction strategy* alone. The right-most column depicts the fraction of edges cut when the evacuation is predicted with 100% accuracy. The asterisks and greyscale overlay pertain to partitioning imbalance and are derived from values presented in Table 7.

Table 7

Mean and Standard Deviation of Partitioning Imbalance
When Switching Mid-Evacuation from the Static Prediction Strategy to the Dynamic Prediction Strategy
Given the Prediction Goes Awry from “Shifting”

Percentage of Evacuation Complete	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
0%	1.053 (2.26) *	1.051 (3.00) *	1.052 (2.52) *	1.053 (2.57) *	1.047 (2.55) *	1.054 (2.58) *
10%	1.040 (1.69) *	1.045 (2.12) *	1.046 (2.07) *	1.057 (2.92) *	1.047 (2.34) *	1.054 (2.88) *
	1.045 (2.02) *	1.049 (2.03) *	1.051 (2.59) *	1.051 (2.42) *	1.048 (2.04) *	1.055 (2.60) *
20%	1.061 (2.61) *	1.049 (2.39) *	1.050 (2.51) *	1.053 (2.24) *	1.053 (2.13) *	1.056 (3.09) *
	1.078 (3.02)	1.075 (2.83)	1.059 (2.96) *	1.055 (2.48) *	1.051 (2.50) *	1.056 (2.93) *
30%	1.113 (3.55)	1.096 (3.07)	1.075 (2.89)	1.069 (2.48)	1.056 (2.09) *	1.052 (2.89) *
	1.173 (5.24)	1.134 (4.04)	1.107 (3.31)	1.076 (3.03)	1.059 (3.07)	1.054 (2.52) *
40%	1.254 (7.77)	1.187 (5.49)	1.140 (4.14)	1.095 (3.19)	1.062 (3.10)	1.051 (2.59) *
	1.382 (13.70)	1.259 (7.56)	1.177 (4.91)	1.117 (3.53)	1.074 (3.35)	1.057 (2.63) *
50%	1.533 (18.54)	1.365 (11.74)	1.224 (6.11)	1.152 (4.09)	1.085 (3.57)	1.051 (2.25) *
	1.692 (23.83)	1.497 (16.07)	1.296 (8.26)	1.179 (4.59)	1.091 (3.82)	1.056 (2.55) *
60%	1.848 (28.74)	1.626 (19.32)	1.370 (11.50)	1.216 (5.85)	1.099 (4.14)	1.056 (2.49) *
	2.003 (32.85)	1.763 (23.13)	1.470 (14.69)	1.256 (7.94)	1.117 (4.12)	1.059 (2.54) *
70%	2.172 (36.65)	1.907 (25.81)	1.577 (18.10)	1.311 (9.71)	1.133 (4.71)	1.061 (2.43) *
	2.335 (40.38)	2.049 (29.29)	1.697 (20.41)	1.377 (11.76)	1.158 (5.28)	1.063 (2.52) *
80%	2.501 (43.44)	2.194 (31.64)	1.816 (22.73)	1.449 (14.32)	1.182 (6.58)	1.065 (2.71)
	2.667 (46.73)	2.337 (34.49)	1.936 (24.86)	1.535 (16.30)	1.207 (7.34)	1.067 (2.90)
90%	2.835 (49.86)	2.484 (37.24)	2.053 (26.88)	1.623 (18.32)	1.241 (8.58)	1.072 (3.10)
	3.007 (53.00)	2.630 (40.05)	2.171 (29.32)	1.711 (20.55)	1.276 (9.73)	1.075 (3.25)
100%	3.185 (55.63)	2.773 (42.27)	2.291 (31.41)	1.804 (22.25)	1.326 (11.74)	1.077 (3.49)
	3.368 (57.53)	2.930 (43.84)	2.419 (33.22)	1.904 (23.99)	1.382 (13.55)	1.084 (3.71)

Evacuation Prediction Accuracy

> 50% Partition Imbalance
 50% - 30.01% Partition Imbalance
 30% - 10.01% Partition Imbalance
 ≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

* Partition Imbalance within Additional 1% of Top Row
 ≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

Note. The top row depicts the partitioning imbalance when using the dynamic prediction strategy alone, and the bottom row depicts the partitioning imbalance when using the static prediction strategy alone. The right-most column depicts the partitioning imbalance when the evacuation is predicted with 100% accuracy. Partitions are balanced perfectly when their value equals 1.000.

Table 8

Mean and Standard Deviation of Fraction of Edges Cut
When Switching Mid-Evacuation from the Static Prediction Strategy to the Dynamic Prediction Strategy
Given the Prediction Goes Awry from “Randomization”

Percentage of Evacuation Complete	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
0%	11.14 (1.52) *	11.10 (1.39) *	11.66 (1.74) *	11.73 (1.40) *	11.63 (1.85) *	11.10 (1.75) *
10%	11.09 (1.50) *	11.17 (1.39) *	11.72 (1.69) *	11.64 (1.51) *	12.10 (1.79) *	11.39 (1.64) *
20%	11.12 (1.47) *	10.96 (1.74)	11.28 (1.95) *	11.41 (1.90) *	11.26 (1.46) *	11.23 (1.54) *
30%	11.59 (1.20) *	10.99 (1.40) *	11.23 (1.34) *	10.96 (1.61) *	10.95 (1.30) *	11.11 (1.49) *
40%	11.90 (1.27)	11.14 (1.24)	11.25 (1.45) *	11.04 (1.42) *	11.00 (1.55) *	10.92 (1.50) *
50%	12.47 (1.37)	11.31 (1.30)	11.14 (1.43) *	10.88 (1.24) *	10.66 (1.18) *	10.78 (1.42) *
60%	13.81 (1.50)	11.83 (1.36)	11.27 (1.46)	10.57 (1.25) *	10.53 (1.19) *	10.79 (1.40) *
70%	14.37 (1.60)	12.20 (1.38)	11.56 (1.49)	10.62 (1.30) *	10.40(1.22) *	10.72 (1.32) *
80%	14.99 (1.66)	12.93 (1.33)	11.81 (1.51)	10.64 (1.32) *	10.44 (1.21) *	10.73 (1.34) *
90%	15.80 (1.69)	13.50 (1.24)	12.21 (1.48)	10.76 (1.35)	10.48 (1.21) *	10.69 (1.32) *
100%	16.49 (1.70)	14.06 (1.35)	12.60 (1.55)	10.95 (1.33)	10.57 (1.20) *	10.75 (1.31) *
	17.02 (1.88)	14.51 (1.47)	12.97 (1.46)	11.06 (1.32)	10.64 (1.20) *	10.80 (1.32) *
	17.68 (1.93)	15.11 (1.59)	13.34 (1.52)	11.31 (1.35)	10.69 (1.28) *	10.82 (1.35) *
	18.08 (1.91)	15.35 (1.47)	13.64 (1.50)	11.53 (1.31)	10.74 (1.28) *	10.85 (1.35) *
	18.46 (1.92)	15.61 (1.36)	13.79 (1.60)	11.68 (1.38)	10.80 (1.29) *	10.88 (1.36) *
	18.55 (2.09)	15.79 (1.51)	14.00 (1.68)	11.87 (1.45)	10.86 (1.29) *	10.88 (1.36) *
	18.51 (2.23)	15.89 (1.35)	14.07 (1.65)	11.98 (1.47)	10.93 (1.33)	10.92 (1.36) *
	18.07 (2.37)	15.79 (1.50)	14.03 (1.66)	11.95 (1.50)	10.98 (1.37)	10.94 (1.38) *
	17.61 (2.61)	15.45 (1.83)	13.86 (1.72)	11.91 (1.51)	11.04 (1.36)	10.95 (1.39) *
	16.79 (2.78)	14.90 (2.08)	13.53 (1.81)	11.85 (1.44)	11.08 (1.36)	10.97 (1.40) *
	15.60 (3.36)	14.26 (2.34)	13.09 (1.89)	11.70 (1.44)	11.10 (1.36)	11.01 (1.39)

Evacuation Prediction Accuracy

> 50% Partition Imbalance
 50% - 30.01% Partition Imbalance
 30% - 10.01% Partition Imbalance
 ≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

* Partition Imbalance within Additional 1% of Top Row
 ≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

Note. The top row depicts the fraction of edges cut when using the dynamic prediction strategy alone, and the bottom row depicts the fraction of edges cut when using the static prediction strategy alone. The right-most column depicts the fraction of edges cut when the evacuation is predicted with 100% accuracy. The asterisks and greyscale overlay pertain to partitioning imbalance and are derived from values presented in Table 9.

Table 9

Mean and Standard Deviation of Partitioning Imbalance
When Switching Mid-Evacuation from the Static Prediction Strategy to the Dynamic Prediction Strategy
Given the Prediction Goes Awry from “Randomization”

Percentage of Evacuation Complete	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	100%
0%	1.030 (2.65) *	1.023 (1.78) *	1.026 (2.33) *	1.027 (2.08) *	1.037 (2.39) *	1.036 (1.91) *
10%	1.023 (1.64) *	1.021 (1.69) *	1.027 (2.32) *	1.029 (2.51) *	1.030 (2.25) *	1.034 (2.21) *
	1.027 (1.97) *	1.034 (2.85)	1.023 (1.79) *	1.024 (1.92) *	1.030 (2.25) *	1.035 (2.17) *
20%	1.032 (3.11) *	1.027 (2.27) *	1.027 (2.31) *	1.028 (2.22) *	1.036 (2.60) *	1.037 (2.12) *
	1.068 (6.17)	1.037 (3.67)	1.025 (1.81) *	1.025 (1.69) *	1.028 (1.67) *	1.034 (1.81) *
30%	1.119 (7.83)	1.065 (6.01)	1.033 (3.30) *	1.027 (1.86) *	1.033 (2.11) *	1.035 (2.07) *
	1.134 (7.25)	1.100 (7.12)	1.059 (5.11)	1.028 (2.54) *	1.031 (2.03) *	1.034 (2.02) *
40%	1.157 (7.51)	1.124 (7.43)	1.075 (5.41)	1.028 (2.51) *	1.028 (1.99) *	1.030 (1.97) *
	1.184 (7.33)	1.138 (7.44)	1.096 (5.46)	1.031 (2.77) *	1.026 (1.71) *	1.033 (2.15) *
50%	1.218 (7.79)	1.168 (7.18)	1.121 (5.63)	1.040 (2.73)	1.026 (1.80) *	1.033 (2.18) *
	1.254 (9.21)	1.190 (7.42)	1.141 (5.39)	1.058 (3.64)	1.027 (1.93) *	1.033 (2.22) *
60%	1.294 (10.03)	1.221 (7.52)	1.162 (5.99)	1.077 (3.92)	1.027 (1.79) *	1.036 (2.15) *
	1.336 (11.10)	1.255 (8.78)	1.186 (6.08)	1.098 (4.26)	1.024 (1.67) *	1.035 (2.27) *
70%	1.380 (11.78)	1.298 (9.33)	1.217 (7.40)	1.116 (4.53)	1.029 (2.17) *	1.035 (2.09) *
	1.422 (12.89)	1.337 (10.19)	1.250 (8.35)	1.132 (4.62)	1.037 (2.48) *	1.037 (2.15) *
80%	1.470 (14.29)	1.376 (11.53)	1.281 (9.25)	1.152 (4.70)	1.046 (2.77) *	1.039 (2.21) *
	1.516 (15.27)	1.415 (11.82)	1.315 (9.68)	1.171 (4.85)	1.056 (2.93)	1.040 (2.24) *
90%	1.569 (16.38)	1.454 (12.89)	1.350 (9.98)	1.197 (5.74)	1.071 (3.18)	1.041 (2.19) *
	1.623 (17.31)	1.502 (13.93)	1.387 (10.82)	1.223 (6.62)	1.080 (3.26)	1.044 (2.19) *
100%	1.681 (18.23)	1.551 (14.89)	1.429 (11.86)	1.252 (7.35)	1.091 (3.45)	1.045 (2.16) *
	1.743 (19.56)	1.603 (15.97)	1.475 (12.82)	1.285 (8.11)	1.106 (4.30)	1.048 (2.24)

Evacuation Prediction Accuracy

█ > 50% Partition Imbalance █ 50% - 30.01% Partition Imbalance █ 30% - 10.01% Partition Imbalance █ ≤ 10% Partition Imbalance

Partitioning Imbalance

█ * Partition Imbalance within Additional 1% of Top Row

Note. The top row depicts the partitioning imbalance when using the dynamic prediction strategy alone, and the bottom row depicts the partitioning imbalance when using the static prediction strategy alone. The right-most column depicts the partitioning imbalance when the evacuation is predicted with 100% accuracy. Partitions are balanced perfectly when their value equals 1.000.

achieve over 5% improvement in the fraction of edges cut. This would cost approximately an additional 4% partitioning imbalance, bringing the total to over 8% partitioning imbalance.

In a scenario where the prediction is less than 80% accurate, one conservatively should switch strategies upon completing the first 5% of the evacuation. Even when a prediction is 100% accurate, unless one can accept an 8% to 9% partitioning imbalance, one should switch to the real-time batch strategy in order to reign in the imbalance.

If the reason for prediction inaccuracy is due to randomness (see Appendix D), then the static prediction strategy becomes more effective (see Table 4; cf., Table 2). In cases where the prediction accuracy is 80% or better, one can postpone switching to the real-time batch strategy until the evacuation is roughly 65% to 70% complete. Against the backdrop where an immediate switch to the real-time batch strategy produces an approximately 3% partitioning imbalance (see Table 5), in exchange for an additional 1% increase, the fraction of edges cut would improve by over an additional 7%. Compared to the above scenario, based on the relatively more gradual increase in partitioning imbalance, if one were to switch to the real-time batch strategy, then one would continue with the static prediction strategy for a longer duration as well as begin with this strategy even when prediction accuracy is low.

When switching from the static prediction strategy to the dynamic prediction strategy, in the scenario where people are evacuating from a slightly different location than predicted (see Table 6), one can minimise the fraction of edges cut by always switching immediately to the dynamic prediction strategy. The one exception is the case where the prediction is 100% accurate. In this case, one could improve the fraction of edges to the greatest extent by switching strategies when the evacuation is 20% complete. This would happen at the expense of some partitioning imbalance (see Table 7). Alternatively, one could improve the fraction of edges cut, albeit to a lesser extent, by switching strategies when the evacuation is 35% complete. This would not harm partitioning imbalance, and in fact, improve it slightly. If one chooses to switch strategies when the prediction is 100% accurate, the amount the outcome measures would change (improve or worsen) is no more than an additional 0.5%.

In the scenario where prediction inaccuracy is attributed to randomness (see Table 8 and Table 9), one could argue that some postponement is warranted. This scenario is somewhat unique in that upon switching to the dynamic prediction strategy, both the fraction of edges cut and the partitioning imbalance generally first decrease and then increase as the evacuation is underway. However, the two outcome measures are not perfectly synced. Taking the lowest value of each outcome measure, one can identify the corresponding percentages of the evacuation complete and set these percentages as the endpoints of a closed interval depicting

loosely, due to variability in the results, the timeframes where there exists a trade-off between the two outcome measures. Stepping through each level of prediction accuracy in turn, one would switch to the dynamic prediction strategy when the evacuation is approximately 5% complete (for the 0% accurate case), 5% to 10% complete (20% accurate), 10% to 25% complete (40% accurate), 10% to 30% complete (60% accurate), 35% to 60% complete (80% accurate), and 35% to 45% complete (100% accurate).⁸¹ Compared to switching immediately to the dynamic prediction strategy, apart from a single exception (when the prediction is 20% accurate), one can always identify at least one point in time (within each of the described intervals) when switching strategies later in the evacuation improves *both* the fraction of edges cut and the partitioning imbalance. That said, compared to switching strategies immediately, the amount each outcome measure could improve is very slight, i.e., not greater than approximately an additional 1.23% improvement in the fraction of edges cut and 1.3% improvement in partitioning imbalance.

Turning to a comparison between the dynamic prediction strategy and the real-time batch strategy, when the prediction goes awry from “shifting” (see the first row of Table 6 and Table 7; cf., the first row of Table 2 and Table 3), one would on average observe an additional 5.65% improvement in the fraction of edges cut at the expense of an additional 0.20% partitioning imbalance using the dynamic prediction strategy. When the prediction goes awry from “randomisation” (see the first row of Table 8 and Table 9; cf., the first row of Table 4 and Table 5), one would on average observe an additional 6.13% improvement in the fraction of edges cut at the expense of an additional 0.83% partitioning imbalance. If allowing the partitioning imbalance for the real-time batch strategy to relax up to an additional 1%, then the dynamic prediction strategy would nearly always improve the fraction of edges cut within this constraint.

When comparing the use of the dynamic prediction strategy alone to switching between the static prediction strategy and the real-time batch strategy, in the specific scenario where the prediction goes awry from randomisation at 80% accuracy (see Table 4 and Table 5; cf., the first row of Table 8 and Table 9), switching between strategies performs better for both the

⁸¹ For any given range, the first (lower) percentage of the evacuation complete represents the best partitioning imbalance while the second (higher) percentage of the evacuation complete represents the best fraction of edges cut. The one exception is the case where the prediction is 80% accurate; the trade-off is reversed— partitioning imbalance improves while fraction of edges cut worsens with time. While one would generally find the best combination of outcome measures within these described ranges, the results are close in value (particularly early in the evacuation) and have some variability, so one might also find an acceptable combination of outcome measures on either side of these ranges. For example, at 20% accuracy, postponing until 15% of the evacuation is complete, which is just outside the described range, has both a fairly low fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance (c.f., 5% and 10% of the evacuation complete).

fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance when the switch occurs between 40% and 70% into the evacuation. Likewise, both outcome measures also improve at 100% accuracy when the switch occurs between 65% and 70% into the evacuation. For all other tested scenarios, including the other reason for the prediction going awry—across the columns and rows collinear with each cell—the dynamic prediction strategy used alone is always preferable, at least in terms of the fraction of edges cut (see the first row of Table 6 and Table 8; cf., Table 2 and Table 4). As for partitioning imbalance, while the dynamic prediction strategy is typically more imbalanced than the real-time batch strategy (see last paragraph), if one combines the real-time batch strategy with the static prediction strategy to improve the fraction of edges cut at the expense of up to a 1% increase in partitioning imbalance, then the difference in partitioning imbalance between the combined strategies and the dynamic prediction strategy becomes almost imperceptible (see Table 3 and Table 5, and see the first row of Table 7 and Table 9).

Considering two ways of switching between strategies, (1) from the static prediction strategy to the real-time batch strategy, and (2) from the static prediction strategy to the dynamic prediction strategy, and excluding cases where partitioning is extremely imbalanced, the latter/second combination always results in less fraction of edges cut (Table 6 and Table 9; cf., Table 2 and Table 4). Additionally, upon comparing every scenario pertaining to both combinations (i.e., comparing every cell to every cell), the partitioning imbalance for the second combination (the static prediction strategy and dynamic prediction strategy) is less than or equal to the partitioning imbalance for first combination (the static prediction strategy and real-time batch strategy) approximately 50% of the time when the prediction goes awry from randomisation (see Table 5 and Table 9) and approximately 95% of the time when the prediction goes awry from shifting locations (see Table 3 and Table 7).

Looking across all results, the specific instance when one should switch strategies depends on the reason for the prediction going awry, the level of prediction accuracy and, as a discretionary matter, how one chooses to manage the trade-off between the fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance. One should also note the potentially significant repercussions for partitioning imbalance if one misidentifies the reason for the prediction going awry, the level of accuracy and/or the state of the evacuation complete. In practice, one would have to identify these factors in real time and should be keenly aware of the desired window for switching to an adaptive strategy.

Discussion

Each of the methods presented has strengths and drawbacks. The real-time batch strategy is the most dependable strategy presented because no predictions are required; it focuses on people who actually require shelter. Implementing this strategy will always produce fairly balanced partitions while also reducing the fraction of edges cut. One can also switch to using the real-time batch strategy from a different strategy, potentially mitigating further loss in social connections if enacted quickly, and/or further imbalance across partitions. Additionally, one can tighten the partitioning imbalance parameter beyond what is ultimately desirable to compensate for severely imbalanced partitions.

The static prediction strategy is advantageous in that it allows one to preemptively formulate shelter assignments. This strategy, however, is highly sensitive to prediction inaccuracy, which can rapidly deteriorate partitioning imbalance. Tables 2, 4, 6, and 8 capture this with a gradient overlay that represents partitioning imbalance percentages 10 times higher than what is typically acceptable (cf., Walshaw, 2023). As a corrective procedure, whatever strategy follows the static prediction strategy will initially place greater emphasis on reducing partitioning imbalance than the fraction of edges cut. Although continuing with the static prediction strategy late into an evacuation could avoid a substantial increase in the fraction of edges cut, the partitioning imbalance would almost certainly become unacceptable.

In order to implement the static prediction strategy effectively in practice, one must overcome several challenges not yet addressed. First, how to identify ahead of time whether a particular disaster scenario is a good candidate for generating an accurate prediction is beyond the scope of this research. Second, how one knows the state of an evacuation well enough (in real time) to inform when to switch away from this strategy would require additional research. In response to these challenges, one might look to the dynamic prediction strategy, which offers an explanation of how to generate a prediction in real time, and given its effectiveness, one could use this strategy alone, that is, if real evacuation scenarios resemble those tested here.

Upon closer examination, one must conclude that results generated from the static prediction strategy, specifically those generated with 100% accuracy, are by no means the *beau ideal* of what is achievable in practice. Indeed, the dynamic prediction strategy is better at improving both outcome measures. This is somewhat surprising as the dynamic prediction strategy relies on using a real-time data feed to reverse engineer the location of homes impacted by a disaster, and from these learned locations, which are constantly being revised, assigns people probabilities of requiring shelter. These probabilities are not known upfront and are initially somewhat inaccurate, and yet, when making use of these probabilities, the shelter

assignments are better in the end. Another somewhat unexpected finding is that after switching away from the static prediction strategy, the dynamic prediction strategy is not only better than the real-time batch strategy at improving the fraction of edges cut, but in some circumstances (e.g., when the prediction goes awry from shifting), the dynamic prediction strategy is also far better at improving partitioning imbalance.

The dynamic prediction strategy is not without drawbacks. Although uninhabitable or perceived uninhabitable homes would likely exhibit spatial clustering, which is a precondition for this strategy, other non-spatial factors might be stronger indicators for why people require shelter (e.g., age, income, building construction method, number of friends, etc.). As people begin requiring shelter, one can likely identify these underlying factors and adjust predictions accordingly.⁸² Of course, even if somewhat indistinct, physical disasters always have a spatial boundary, and so one can always attribute some probability of requiring shelter to people's spatial proximity to a disaster. In this vein, an unexplored facet regarding the dynamic prediction strategy is analysing the repercussions to outcome measures when the spatial boundary is either too small or too large. While the boundary is predetermined in this research, one could have it grow or shrink in response to real-time information.

With respect to designing a shelter assignment strategy that accounts for spatial and non-spatial factors, this research would be remiss not to highlight the fact that many of these factors are embedded within social networks, and thereby, one might be inclined to draw not a spatial but *social* boundary around people likely impacted by a disaster. As for how one might achieve this, if people with certain community affiliations (explicitly and/or implicitly formed) are more likely to become displaced together and individually seek out shelter, then as individuals start requesting shelter assignments, one might consider propagating or transmitting their "label" of displacement across their pre-disaster social network in order to expand the real-time subnetwork being partitioned to account for (to some extent) those who might request shelter assignments in the near future.⁸³ The extent of propagation, whether into

⁸² One could, for example, add random effects to GAMs.

⁸³ The propagation or transmission of displacement across a social network is a peculiar concept. Displacement is not "contractable" or, from an analytical perspective, "traceable." It cannot diffuse across a network as if it were information (e.g., a message or rumour). On the other hand, displacement likely correlates with certain demographic attributes, and through the principle of homophily, people close or proximal to one another in a social network are more likely to share demographic attributes (Khanam et al., 2022; McPherson et al., 2001). Therefore, research could exploit a social network not as a channel for information but, alternatively, as a means of identifying people with shared experiences, where displacement might become a perpetuation of these experiences. One could leverage a social network in this manner even if the demographic attributes contributing to displacement are unknown; indeed, one could treat these attributes as hidden or latent variables within the network.

communities of those displaced (via community detection conducted on the pre-disaster social network) or, more simply, within k -hops of those displaced, and how these additional labels could influence shelter assignments for those requesting them is a provocative area of future research.

Introducing another layer of analysis, one might choose a shelter assignment strategy based on how it can facilitate data protection. To implement either the static prediction strategy or the dynamic prediction strategy, one would have to ask people for permission to access their social network data ahead of an evacuation. Implementing the dynamic prediction strategy would further require that people provide their pre-disaster address. In contrast, the real-time batch strategy does not need to access people's social network data until the moment they request a shelter assignment.⁸⁴ Indeed, while one can take certain measures to protect data, not having access to data in the first place offers the most protection and communicating this might broaden the appeal of the proposed application.

One could furthermore present people with the option to release their social network data. With some people granting and others withholding permission to access their data, one cannot realise the full potential of the static prediction strategy or the dynamic prediction strategy. In turn, this could motivate the future design of an algorithm that uses real-time information, enhanced with a scaled-back gesture of predictive foresight. Likewise, withholding social network data complicates how one would establish a "social boundary" and employ a prediction within it. To carve an exception, one can assign displaced people to shelters in real time based not only on their friends/acquaintances at shelters but, to extend the social boundary slightly, their "friends-of-friends" (FOF) at shelters. This is possible because the people being assigned to shelters and the people already at shelters (or assigned to them) have released their social network data, and thereby one can attempt to match the IDs of people who have not (yet) released their social network data in order to link displaced people to emergency shelters that are now hedged to become more socially connected.⁸⁵ That said,

⁸⁴ With the real-time batch strategy, while knowing people's social network prior to an evacuation may not be necessary, it could still be advantageous. For example, as part of the registration process, one could guide people through their own social network to identify useful connections. On the other hand, people may prioritise data protection over specifying which social connections to preserve and, thereby, opt to register some information beforehand and request that the application prompt them for additional information, such as access to social network data, only if an evacuation is underway and the release of their information would benefit themselves and/or those in their social network.

⁸⁵ For the mutual social acquaintances who have not explicitly consented to have their data used, Borgatti and Molina (2003) contend, "We do not believe this should be an [ethical] issue because people's perceptions of their fellows and their relationships with them are their own and they can choose to give those data to researchers." For a more in-depth analysis on "guidelines designed to safeguard participants in social network studies," please see the above cited article.

without direct access to the ego networks of the intermediary friends, one is not privy to connections between them and, therefore, is operating with a limited vision within this FOF social boundary. This research further explores the construction of a FOF shelter assignment strategy and how one might conduct experiments with it in Appendix F.

Apart from examining the extent of data, one can also take a closer look at the nature of data. Indeed, another challenge to implementing the dynamic prediction strategy is non-response bias. When people are prompted to respond “yes” or “no” to needing shelter, one might surmise that people who do not require shelter are *less likely* to respond. In other words, the number of “no” labels might be disproportionately underestimated. If one were to correct this bias by accurately estimating the true number of “no” labels, then not only would the prediction quality improve, but the overall number of labels collected and passed to a GAM would increase (i.e., over the same period of time), which should allow one to make reasonable predictions earlier in the evacuation.⁸⁶

As for another potential source of bias, people might respond quicker with either a “yes” or “no” to needing shelter, and although this type of bias will correct itself by the end of the evacuation, this would nevertheless lead to inaccurate predictions early in the evacuation. Ultimately, the size of biases and how they affect the shelter assignment algorithm, along with how to counter their negative effects, require further research.

Ultimately, the dynamic prediction strategy, much like the static prediction strategy, faces a challenge with partitioning data that does not accurately represent the conditions unfolding in real time. To address this deficiency, the real-time batch strategy presents a solution. However, upon evaluating strategies in terms of their performance, the real-time batch strategy, alongside the static prediction strategy, is generally inferior to the dynamic prediction strategy. This research, of course, is not only concerned with the performance of individual strategies (relative to each other) but how they perform when combined sequentially. The static prediction strategy, which under the best of conditions is unsuitable on its own (due to partitioning imbalance), could enhance both the real-time batch strategy and the dynamic prediction strategy, i.e., beyond how either of these adaptive strategies performs alone. On the other hand, to build on a previously mentioned concern, if the state of an evacuation is not known with some degree of accuracy, then one cannot realise the full potential for improvement, and to the contrary, the outcome could be substantially worse than using either

⁸⁶ One way to think about correcting for this type of bias is to convert a lack of responses to “no” labels as a function of elapsed time. That said, as this correction does not take effect immediately, it will not contribute to making predictions early in the evacuation.

the real-time batch strategy or the dynamic prediction strategy alone. While future research could focus on knowing the state of an evacuation well enough to leverage the benefits of switching between strategies, retrospective analysis allows one to better understand the risks associated with *not knowing* the state of the evacuation in real time.

With the dynamic prediction strategy performing well in these experiments, this research is motivated to address concerns inherent to the algorithm performing well in practice. As for improving the algorithm, one can replace the GAM with other spatial modelling techniques that are not susceptible to the above-mentioned biases.

Beyond GAMs

Although GAMs have robust performance when supplied with both “yes” and “no” labels (Zaniewski et al., 2002), and although GAMs are modifiable to perform exceptionally well when “no” labels are the norm (Virgili et al., 2018), one should not expect GAMs to maintain their performance when faced with bias, especially non-response bias, which affects “no” labels and does not correct over time (see Lobo, 2008). As a potential recourse, one might borrow techniques from species distribution models (SDMs; Elith et al., 2005; Elith & Leathwick, 2009; Guisan & Thuiller, 2005; Guisan et al., 2017; Peterson et al., 2012),⁸⁷ which correlate observed locations of species with environmental factors to predict their geographic distributions. One can find SDMs applied to other contexts (see Guillera-Arroita, 2015; Guisan & Zimmermann, 2000; Martínez-Minaya et al., 2018), including contexts with a sociological (e.g., Wieling, Montemagni, et al., 2014; Wieling, Nerbonne & Baayen, 2011) or anthropological bent (e.g., Yaworsky et al., 2020). What is of interest here is that survey efforts are oftentimes opportunistic, which results in the presence of species being recorded but not typically their absence. This is better known as *presence-only* data, which is akin to using “yes-only” labels.

Generally speaking, one should use *presence-absence* data when available (Elith et al., 2010; Guillera-Arroita et al., 2014; Zaniewski et al., 2002) and select an algorithm, such as a GAM, that is well-suited for this type of data (Norberg et al., 2019). On the other hand, if non-response bias is extensive, then from among the large number of algorithms used in species distributing modelling (Hijmans & Elith, 2021; Merow et al., 2014; Norberg et al., 2019), one might select an algorithm designed for presence-only data (Hastie & Fithian, 2013; Konowalik

⁸⁷ Species distribution models (SDMs) are sometimes referred to as habitat models or ecological niche models. One should note that these latter terms are inconsistently used within the literature (Kearney, 2006).

& Nosol, 2021), the most popular being a machine-learning algorithm called MaxEnt (Elith et al., 2010; Joppa et al., 2013).

Algorithms perform differently when supplied with different types of data. In cases where presence–absence data is available, when MaxEnt is run with presence-only data—which is the intended input for this algorithm (Guillera-Arroita et al., 2014)—one should note that it does not perform as well as GAMs (Fiedler et al., 2018; see also Becker et al., 2020; de Rivera & López-Quílez, 2017).⁸⁸ Conversely, although one can design GAMs to handle presence-only data (Zaniewski et al., 2002), MaxEnt and other algorithms are superior in this circumstance (Konowalik & Nosol, 2021; c.f., Becker et al., 2020).⁸⁹

Presence-only data is associated with its own set of challenges; however, these challenges—which specifically concern sampling bias and estimation of prevalence (Guillera-Arroita et al., 2015)⁹⁰—are not particularly consequential when generating shelter assignments. Beginning with sampling bias (Elith et al., 2010; Guillera-Arroita, 2016; Kramer-Schadt et al., 2013; Martínez-Minaya et al., 2018; Phillips et al., 2009; Rocchini et al., 2011; Tessarolo et al., 2014; Williams et al., 2002; Yackulic et al., 2012), what should occur when collecting presence-only data (as is matter of course when collecting presence–absence data) is that samples are drawn with equal probability from all points on a landscape. Unfortunately, oftentimes the expense, or more generally, the *effort* associated with conducting proper surveys is less than ideal. The literature emphasises bias pertaining to accessibility, also called “roadside” bias (Kadmon et al., 2004), where the landscape adjacent to roadways has a greater chance of being surveyed. Other sources of bias include surveys limited to marine or terrestrial protected areas and, of particular concern, surveys that neglect to venture far beyond urban centres (Tessarolo et al., 2014). In the context of this research, however, the location of people requiring shelter is not observed but self-reported. As this happens virtually (insofar that cellphone service is available), no location is unreachable or un-surveyable. That said, although everyone with a cellphone has the same opportunity to request a shelter assignment, if certain demographics associated with certain locations are unaware of this application/service, then presence-only data will remain susceptible to sampling bias.

⁸⁸ In fact, many comparative studies that feature presence–absence data do not include MaxEnt as a viable algorithm (e.g., Ahmed et al., 2021; Kargar et al., 2018; Norberg et al., 2019).

⁸⁹ Just as one can debate whether GAM is best suited for presence–absence data (e.g., Becker et al., 2020; de Rivera & López-Quílez, 2017; Kargar et al., 2018; c.f., Konowalik & Nosol, 2021), so too can one point to studies that take different positions on whether MaxEnt is best suited for presence-only data (e.g., Kaky et al., 2020; c.f., Konowalik & Nosol, 2021).

⁹⁰ According to Guillera-Arroita et al. (2015), a third fundamental challenge is imperfect detection. They note that this amounts to sampling bias for presence-only data.

The other perceived drawback of using presence-only data is that one cannot estimate the true probability of species occurring at different locations. Instead, one is left with a proportional or relative understanding of their distribution (Hastie & Fithian, 2013; Phillips & Elith, 2013; see also Guillera-Arroita et al., 2014; Guillera-Arroita et al., 2015; Martínez-Minaya et al., 2018). According to Phillips and Elith (2013), “[T]here is no panacea for lack of data, and if one really wants absolute (rather than relative) probabilities, there is generally no alternative to collecting some data.” As for the evacuation context, one must understand what purpose generating a prediction serves. While estimating the *absolute* number of people requiring shelter is necessary to determine how many emergency shelters to operate (a task already undertaken by the Red Cross), estimating the *relative* number of people at different locations is enough information to partition a social network effectively. In other words, the presented drawbacks are either reduced in severity or rendered nonexistent, suggesting that presence-only data is incredibly well suited to the evacuation context.

Returning to the crux of the problem, non-response bias, which specifically affects the number of “no” labels, is not a factor when using “yes-only” labels. One of the prevailing challenges with “yes-only” labels (or presence-only data) is sampling bias pertaining to accessibility, which is likewise generally not a factor within the evacuation context. What unifies these forms of bias is somewhat obfuscated by different contexts and terminology. To this end, data collected for SDMs is observed or detected; indeed, “species” cannot self-report their presence and location, and the associated bias, namely the freedom to not report or respond, does not exist. Nevertheless, the problem with certain people not responding to a survey (e.g., non-response bias) is remarkably similar to the problem with not surveying certain locations (e.g., sampling bias).⁹¹ Likewise, the reason why one can overcome these problems (or forms of bias) during an evacuation using “yes-only” labels is fundamentally the same: at any given moment, “yes” labels represent everyone who currently needs shelter, or in other words, “yes” responses are being surveyed or reported fairly.

⁹¹ One can raise this equivalence through a question: even if a landscape is thoroughly surveyable, if some people not requiring shelter (who presumably live in the same area) are non-responsive, then is the landscape essentially not thoroughly surveyed, leaving the collected responses prone to sampling bias? Recall what this research means by non-response bias, that while people will likely respond “yes” to needing shelter, people who do not need shelter might respond “no” or simply not answer. As the collected responses are associated with geographic locations, one can formulate a spatial analogy, where non-response bias affecting “no” labels is equivalent to *directing survey efforts to locations where people respond “yes” to needing shelter*. Taking pause to unpack the preceding italicised text, while prioritising any location over another is a clear example of sampling bias, the only way to realise this particular version of sampling bias is to know beforehand where to direct survey efforts, which entails having initially conducted a fair survey of “yes” response locations. Therefore, a prediction generated using “yes-only” responses (i.e., presence-only data) should circumvent this form of sampling bias and, by analogy, reaffirm a suitable approach to bypass non-response bias affecting “no” labels.

The literature on SDMs portrays sampling bias as a problem and not estimating prevalence as a limitation. Revisiting the latter, how this research uses a prediction does not end with a single partitioning (see above), but instead, the entire process is repeated, over and over again, as additional people request shelter. Against this backdrop, the concept of relative probability reemerges, not as a limitation (as SDM literature would frame it) but as a fundamental component within the greater methodology.

To this end, SDMs are not designed to predict the future; they are designed to predict what is not sampled, the “range” or occupied distribution of species (Anderson, 2012). To predict across time (and/or space), one would have to extrapolate from these models (Elith & Leathwick, 2009). This requires that SDMs capture existing and fundamental aspects of species’ niche, which are then *transferred* to a simulated future landscape, one identified as suitable for these species, notwithstanding whether species will truly occupy this landscape (Anderson, 2013; Charney et al., 2021; see also; Elith, Kearney & Phillips, 2010; Elith et al., 2010; McClanahan & Azali, 202; Wisz et al., 2008a; Yudaputra et a., 2020).⁹² Underlying the notion of transferability is the assumption of stationarity: “that the species’ response to predictor variables does not vary across space or time” (Anderson, 2013).

To straightforwardly apply SDM techniques to an evacuation, one can select predictor variables for people requiring shelter and then evaluate which of these variables are most important to the SDM, for example, by comparing plots from a jackknife (leave-one-out) cross-validation test (Guisan, et al., 2017; see also Phillips, 2017), calculated using the continuous Boyce index (Hirzel et al., 2006), a performance measure appropriate for presence-only data.⁹³ One can also evaluate how each predictor variable affects the SDM prediction by plotting their (marginal) response curve (Merow et al., 2013; Phillips, 2017; see also Elith et al., 2005; Guisan et al., 2017; Hannemann et al., 2015). Moreover, if one can simulate future states of a disaster (such as by forecasting a hurricane’s track and intensity), then given a model fitted or trained to predict suitable conditions for people currently requiring shelter, as long as the

⁹² Pertaining to both existing and future landscapes, species may not fully occupy (or disperse into) areas suitable to them. In such cases, their occupied distributions are said to lack equilibrium. As a matter of transferability, “any model trained with current data risks underestimating the potential suitable environmental and geographical range for species in a new area or time period” (Varela et al., 2009). Please also note that transferability into non-analogue environmental conditions (i.e., conditions outside model calibration) requires further consideration (see Anderson, 2013; Guevara et al., 2017; Hannemann et al., 2015).

⁹³ More common SDM performance measures, such as the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) and the true skill statistic (TSS), have been criticised for their dependence on sample prevalence (see Leroy et al., 2018). In the evacuation context, estimating sample prevalence from presence-absence data is subject to error due to response bias, so this dependency is a potential issue.

predictor variables persist, one can transfer the model to simulated future states of a disaster, which allows one to investigate the geographic distribution of people who will require shelter.

Apart from typical challenges associated with transferring SDMs,⁹⁴ this methodology is only applicable to certain types of evacuations. Indeed, not all disasters are both forecastable and prone to evolve over an extended duration.⁹⁵ Oftentimes disasters, or more accurately, their actual or perceived physical impacts, do not evolve from the time people start requesting shelter (e.g., people start evacuating after a disaster has occurred), in which case transferring SDMs into a simulated forecast is unnecessary.

Whether to specify a method in which SDMs (generated in real time) are applicable for non-evolving disasters or, leading with methodological factors, to have SDMs take advantage of real-time data instead of forecasted data (as a matter of simplicity and/or reliability), one could generate multiple, sequential predictions to keep pace with up-to-date information that reveals (with greater and greater accuracy) where people need shelter. What requires “transfer” is no longer the model but the modelling results, beginning with those results generated at the initial state, which should continue to hold relevance as the disaster progresses.

Without introducing external data from a simulated forecast, if the early states of an evacuation are predictive of the end state, then one is making the following assumption: given a sample of people who require shelter, as the sample size increases with time, the relative mean density of people who require shelter will either remain constant (first-order stationarity) or will follow a determinable trajectory.⁹⁶ One should also note that estimating the absolute, as opposed to relative, number of people who require shelter at different time intervals does not provide (without ancillary assumptions) additional information this research would consider

⁹⁴ Extrapolating into a forecasted geography is particularly risky when environmental conditions/variables are more extreme than those used to fit or train the model. The challenge becomes, at least in part, how to interpret suitable conditions that lie beyond the now truncated response curves (Anderson, 2013; Guevara et al., 2017; Hannemann et al., 2015; see also Austin & Nicholls, 2009). If a physical disaster is forecasted to move or expand with similar or weakening intensity (and given that environmental conditions are not drastically different across the forecasted area of impact), then truncated response curves are a non-issue. On the other hand, if a disaster is forecasted to become more severe, then one has no way of knowing, for example, whether this severity is associated with a tipping point, where many people would suddenly require shelter.

⁹⁵ The latter condition affords people the opportunity to request shelter in reaction to different states of a disaster.

⁹⁶ One could potentially forecast a future state that is first-order stationary. This could involve taking advantage of time-series forecasting using space-state models (Durbin & Koopman, 2012; Douc et al., 2014) or time-varying vector autoregressive models (Haslbeck et al., 2021), the latter being a special case of the former. Generating a short-term forecast might prove useful, for example, if the location of people requiring shelter evolves over time. More precisely, however, one would have to generate this forecast quite early in the evacuation, preferably before the first batch of assignments is disseminated. If this is not possible and the forecast is itself evolving, then until the forecast stops evolving, shelter assignments could be negatively influenced. More research is needed into how the magnitude, timing, and reason associated with an evolving landscape affects predictions and, moreover, partitioning quality.

useful, i.e., an estimate of the absolute number of people who *will* require shelter. How this research approaches making predictions about the future, including the applicability of these predictions, is rooted in these concepts. A relative understanding of the distribution is precisely what the dynamic prediction strategy, for example, requires not only for partitioning (as a method) but for the partitioning results to hold value and contribute positively to what ultimately becomes the social composition at shelters.

Setting aside challenges associated with presence-only data or “yes-only” labels, namely, sampling bias and estimation of prevalence, and why one might perceive these challenges differently within the evacuation context, the SDM literature brings to the forefront additional issues that one cannot overlook. In a very specific instance of species distribution modelling, and one that closely parallels the context at hand, Tessorolo et al. (2014) found that sampling bias pertaining to accessibility, although statistically significant, was far less important than one might expect; the authors determined that the greatest factors affecting SDM performance were the type of species, followed by the sample size. Beginning with the sample size, despite the potential, for example, of MaxEnt to perform quite well with small samples (Baldwin, 2009; Hernandez et al., 2006; Pearson et al., 2006; Soutan & Safi, 2017; Virgili et al., 2018; Wisz, 2008b), the challenge with making a real-time prediction early in the evacuation, i.e., when the sample size is particularly small, will nevertheless persist. As for the type of species, the findings of Tessorolo et al. (2014) coincide with Segurado & Araújo (2004), who conclude that “Generally, species with large areas of occupancy and great extents of occurrence (i.e., truly widespread) had greater overall errors (i.e., Kappa statistic).” Contextually, the quality of a prediction would seemingly depend on the type of disaster and the vulnerability of specific people, both of which may contribute to either widespread or concentrated areas of displacement. This research has only explored two ways an evacuation could go awry; determining when (and when not) to rely on a prediction when generating shelter assignments would require a more comprehensive investigation into different evacuation scenarios.

Drawing upon an earlier part of the discussion, perhaps the most interesting unexplored evacuation scenario would feature a disaster that impacts different locations over time, resulting in a growing number of people seeking shelter. If the disaster were to stop evolving prior to the end of an evacuation, then one might initially generate shelter assignments using the proposed real-time batch strategy and only switch to using a prediction-based strategy after a good prediction can be established. In other words, new scenarios not only allow one to more

thoroughly test existing shelter assignment strategies, they also challenge one to explore new combinations of strategies in order to deliver the best results.

Conclusion

In summary, this research presents three shelter assignment strategies, the static prediction strategy, the real-time batch strategy and the dynamic prediction strategy, each of which has a different relationship with when data is collected and when shelter assignments are generated and then disseminated. The chapter examines whether using a combination of these strategies, implemented sequentially, performs better than any strategy alone. While starting with a static prediction strategy and then switching to a real-time batch strategy (at a very specific point in the evacuation timeline) produces better results than either strategy alone, the dynamic prediction strategy generally outperforms this combination approach. When the static prediction strategy is combined with the dynamic prediction strategy, this produces even better shelter assignments; however, as is true whenever switching between strategies, one runs a substantial risk of overshooting the timeframe where benefits are observed.

Upon closer inspection, whether the dynamic prediction strategy is used alone or in conjunction with static predictions strategy, it is susceptible to non-response bias. Although the data used in this research does not contain this bias, one should account for it in a real-world setting. One could address this issue by replacing the strategy's spatial prediction model (i.e., GAM), which uses presence-absence data (to borrow a term from SDMs), with a spatial prediction model that uses presence-only data. As for another issue, and one not so easily resolved, this research speculates that while a dynamic prediction strategy might perform well for disasters that have already occurred, this strategy is likely a poor choice (as currently presented) for ongoing disasters that continue to evolve. The findings support the notion that the best strategy or combination of strategies depends on the evacuation scenario.

Continuing with how shelter assignment methods can take advantage of the temporal nature of evacuations, the next chapter examines how to use social network analysis (SNA) to maximise results when software runtime is an issue.

Chapter 6

Limited Time Partitioning Strategy

Node Ordering

This research advocates that a shelter assignment algorithm takes advantage of batch processing within a sliding window. One can introduce this quite naturally. For example, a mobile phone application could ask whether someone is interested in staying at an emergency shelter. If the person answers “yes,” after confirming their mode of transportation and who will be accompanying them, the application can then prompt, “When ready to leave, please press ‘get directions.’” Depending on whether the initial emergency message is posted as a watch, warning, advisory, or forecast, the buffer time from when people request a shelter to when a shelter is assigned could be hours or, if a threat is imminent, minutes or seconds. Moreover, a constant trickle of people requesting shelter assignments, particularly over a short timeframe, where each new request might very well alter the optimal partitioning within a sliding window, requires that a shelter assignment algorithm update exceptionally quickly. Alternatively, one can either introduce a time delay or generate assignments without considering the most recent shelter requests.

When implementing FENNEL in Java on a single machine with Intel Xeon CPU at 3.6GHz, the wall-clock time for partitioning a roughly 41.6 million node Twitter social network (with over 1.4 billion edges), excluding the time required to load the graph into memory, takes about 40 minutes (Tsourakakis et al., 2012). In comparison, METIS takes 8.5 hours to partition the same network (Tsourakakis et al., 2012). In this case, although FENNEL is partitioning over one million nodes per minute, one should take note that multiple iterations take longer. For example, Nishimura and Ugander (2013) use 10 iterations when conducting experiments with restreaming FENNEL. If restreaming FENNEL converges to a final partitioning before 10 iterations, then when no further improvements are observed, one can backtrack to the last iteration or halt iterating to save time. As described in Appendix C, other techniques are also useful in this regard. That said, even with a fast implementation of restreaming FENNEL, the rate at which people request shelters could exceed the time required to converge on a best result. Alongside investigating how to improve runtime as well as how to (if warranted) implement a delayed response, another consideration is how to improve output metrics using restreaming FENNEL when convergence is not feasible.

Practically speaking, each displaced person requesting an emergency shelter assignment cannot trigger restreaming FENNEL to start anew—this would interrupt and postpone the algorithm from generating assignments. Additionally, adding new people into the

sliding window would have no benefit until everyone already within the sliding window is assigned to an emergency shelter. In other words, after restreaming FENNEL activates and before the first stream is complete, any person requesting an emergency shelter is in the interim effectively placed in a holding pattern. Taking advantage of this brief pause, one simple operation is to prioritise displaced people who first requested a shelter. As restreaming FENNEL more effectively partitions nodes later in the stream,⁹⁷ one can adopt a “first come, last serve” node-ordering strategy. This logic also paves the way to prioritise any individual, such as someone requiring greater social support, by simply placing their representative node near the end of the stream. On the other hand, one should not blindly adopt this strategy; individuals with certain network attributes may in fact benefit very little or not at all when placed later in the stream, and/or their placement could adversely affect global output measures (e.g., increase the average fraction of edges cut). As for a different albeit potentially not incompatible strategy, instead of developing a node order based on specifying which individuals benefit, one could theoretically develop a node order that benefits global output measures. Keeping in mind that nodes early in the stream are a potential source of attachment for nodes later in the stream, the goal is to identify a node order that optimises this relationship, where each node “seeds” the partitions, directing subsequent nodes via the objective function toward a more desirable outcome.⁹⁸

As for setting expectations for node ordering within a sliding window, one should acknowledge that node orderings can be either beneficial or adversarial for streaming graph partitioning. If ideal node orderings exist, one might reason that these ideal node orderings are not a substitute for a global view of the network (which can be obtained retrospectively, post-evacuation). Likewise, the concept of restreaming—where nodes are revisited multiple times to improve their assignments relative to a given partitioned state—should be less affected by node orderings. That said, even if partitioning does not improve after restreaming FENNEL

⁹⁷ A quick experiment can demonstrate this concept. Using 100 social networks generated in Appendix D, pass each social network through restreaming FENNEL, and run the algorithm until converging on a best solution. For analysis, based on the streaming order, sequentially place each node into one of 10 bins and calculate the average fraction of edges within each bin. One should find that the last bin (containing the last nodes in the stream) has roughly 3% less fraction of edges cut than those in the first bin (containing the first nodes in the stream). In other words, nodes at the end of a stream have a slight advantage.

⁹⁸ Introducing this last concept by way of example, part of a node-ordering strategy could involve placing people with no connections last in the stream. If the only governing principle is that individuals placed later in the stream benefit, then placing those with no connections (i.e., those with nothing to gain) last is a poor decision. However, the principles at play here are slightly more complex; indeed, when applied to a single stream, this node-ordering strategy should improve global output measures.

completes all of its restreams, any improvement to early streams, particularly the first stream, could still play a role in a time-sensitive evacuation scenario.

For a single stream, the central literature on FENNEL focuses on two graph traversal node orderings—breadth-first search (BFS) and depth-first search (DFS)—and finds that FENNEL does not benefit from these ordering schemes. In fact, with certain parameters (specifically, when $\gamma = 1.25$), random node ordering outperforms BFS and DFS, at least in terms of partitioning imbalance (Tsourakakis et al., 2014). What is not considered, however, is that social network analysis (SNA) has a long history of characterising the most important nodes in a network according to different centrality indices.⁹⁹ With output from multiple centrality indices reinterpreted as ranked node orderings, one can investigate whether hierarchical relationships between nodes (as captured by these orderings) affect global outcome measures for FENNEL.

If centrality-based node orderings can not only affect but improve FENNEL (and potentially restreaming FENNEL), either significantly or marginally, this does not mean that one can easily identify the logic necessary to create these node orderings. To be forthright, this research does not pretend to have such insight. Instead of designing a new centrality-based node ordering to improve FENNEL, this research proposes to investigate centralities that already exist in the literature as the basis for developing a readily available node ordering strategy. This proposal is submitted against the backdrop that over 200 centralities have been developed for various applications (Jalili et al., 2015), each of which could be a candidate solution. By running Monte Carlo simulations to obtain outcome measure distributions under multiple experimental conditions (i.e., under multiple node orderings), one can then conduct statistical hypothesis testing to determine if there is any significant difference between the experimental conditions.

Hypothesis Testing

Social Network Analysis (SNA) has yet to inform a node ordering procedure for FENNEL. One can begin this examination by specifying the independent variable as centrality-based node orderings. Where the literature does feature a node ordering procedure (albeit not from the SNA literature), two dependent variables are specified: fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance. With respect to nodes *passed to* FENNEL, the research thereby formulates two non-directional, null hypotheses:

⁹⁹ For an introduction to centrality, please see de Nooy et al. (2018).

H_{01} : Centrality-based node orderings do not affect fraction of edges cut and

H_{02} : Centrality-based node orderings do not affect partitioning imbalance,

as well as non-directional, alternative hypotheses:

H_{a1} : Certain centrality-based node orderings affect fraction of edges cut and

H_{a2} : Certain centrality-based node orderings affect partitioning imbalance.

If either null hypothesis (H_{01} or H_{02}) is rejected, then one might subsequently ask, which specific centrality-based node orderings are effective? To answer this question, this research will consider random node orderings as the control group in a post-hoc, pairwise multiple comparison test. Please note that while this control serves as a useful benchmark for experiments, it is not intended to realistically depict the status quo. More likely than not, some features about people and/or their environment could result in emergency shelter requests being serially correlated.

As node orderings may affect FENNEL and restreaming FENNEL differently, this research thereby posits two additional null hypotheses, H_{03} and H_{04} , and their alternatives, H_{a3} and H_{a4} . These new hypotheses are identical to those described above (H_{01} , H_{02} , H_{a1} , and H_{a2}); however, they are formulated with respect to nodes passed into restreaming FENNEL. In this case, although the research expectations may not lean as strongly toward rejecting the null hypotheses and subsequently identifying (if warranted) at least one significant departure from the control, if this were to happen, one might pursue a different implementation of node orderings in practice.

Centrality Measures

This research analysed 54 centrality measures, which were selected from the CentiServer website (Jalili et al., 2015). The website features a technical definition for each centrality measure alongside network requirements, software links, and referenced literature.¹⁰⁰ Jalili et al. (2015) also maintain a web-based application, where users can upload network files

¹⁰⁰ This resource is constantly updated with new centrality measures. The original article specifies 110 unique centrality measures (Jalili et al., 2015). At the time of writing, 231 centrality measures are defined. Please note that recently added centrality measures might be pending definitions and other useful information. Also note, aligned with how CentiServer reports centrality measures, if centrality measures originate from distinct authors, this research treats them as distinct. One should keep this in mind when analysing output scores that are identical. A good example is Markov centrality (White & Smyth, 2003) and random walk closeness (Noh & Rieger, 2004). While these centrality measures share the same equation, the authors draw upon different literature to independently support their claims. Another example is degree centrality (Proctor & Loomis, 1951; see also Freeman, 2002) and strength (Barrat et al., 2004), which despite being uniquely formulated, behave the same when supplied with an unweighted network.

Table 10

Centrality	Source	Centrality	Source
Local assortativity	Brain Connectivity Toolbox	K-core decomposition	CentiServer
Alpha	CentiServer	Kleinberg's centrality (HITS)	CentiServer
Average distance	CentiServer	Laplacian centrality	CentiServer
Barycenter centrality	CentiServer	Leverage centrality	CentiServer
Betweenness	CentiServer	Lin centrality	CentiServer
BottleNeck centrality	CentiServer	Load centrality	CentiServer
Bridging centrality	CentiServer	Lobby Index	CentiServer
Centroid centrality	CentiServer	Local clustering coefficients	CentiServer
Closeness (Freeman)	CentiServer	Markov centrality	CentiServer
Closeness (Variant/Latora)	CentiServer	MNC centrality	CentiServer
ClusterRank	CentiServer	Radiality centrality	CentiServer
Communicability betweenness centrality	CentiServer	SALSA	CentiServer
Community centrality	CentiServer	Semi local centrality	CentiServer
Cross clique centrality	CentiServer	Strength (weighted vertex degree)	CentiServer
Current flow closeness centrality	CentiServer	Stress centrality	CentiServer
Dangalchev closeness centrality	CentiServer	Subgraph	CentiServer
Decay centrality	CentiServer	Topological coefficient	CentiServer
Degree centrality	CentiServer	MCC centrality	Cytoscape: CytoHubba
Diffusion degree	CentiServer	LAC	Cytoscape: CytoNCA
DMNC centrality	CentiServer	Network centrality	Cytoscape: NetworkAnalyzer
Eccentricity	CentiServer	Neighborhood connectivity	Cytoscape: RINalyzer
Eigenvector	CentiServer	Random walk betweenness	FastCentiScape
Entropy centrality	CentiServer	Effectiveness centrality	UCINET
EPC	CentiServer	Network fragmentation	UCINET
Flow betweenness centrality	CentiServer	Network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted)	
Geodesic K-path centrality	CentiServer	Political independence index	UCINET
Information centrality	CentiServer		

to their server and, upon specifying centrality measures from a drop-down menu, a new job is created and scores are calculated. Along with this web-based application, this research also used algorithms readily available from other sources, including Cytoscape (Shannon et al., 2003) and its plug-ins, cytoNCA (Tang et al., 2015), cytoHubba (Chin et al., 2014), and RINalyzer (Doncheva et al., 2011), as well as UCINET (Borgatti et al., 2002), Brain Connectivity Toolbox (Rubinov & Sporns, 2010), and FastCentiScaPe (Scardoni et al., 2015; see Table 10).

Social Networks

As the selected centrality measures are not necessarily designed to handle disjointed networks and/or networks containing nodes without connections,¹⁰¹ and as the selected centrality measures can operate without geographic information, this research proposes to set aside the networks generated in Appendix D and conduct experiments using a relatively simpler network type.

Sala et al. (2010) demonstrate that synthetic networks generated using a modified nearest-neighbour (NN) algorithm provide a relatively accurate representation of real-world social networks. Using their NN algorithm, 40 networks were generated, consisting of 100 nodes each. The power-law exponent parameter was set to 1.5, matching the average degree distribution and clustering coefficient of several online social networks (Sala et al., 2010). The code was provided by Sala et al. (2010) as a Python module for NetworkX (Hagberg et al., 2008).

Experimental Design

If runtime is the critical factor motivating a single pass of restreaming FENNEL and, in turn, the exploration of node orderings to improve outcome measures, then pre-calculating node orderings on the whole social network prior to a disaster and storing these calculations (and potentially prefetching them) would seem a fitting methodology, one that replaces “expensive” input/output runtime computation with a simple array indexing operation. Without such a procedure, one would have to pay considerably more attention to computational resources when selecting centrality measures. For example, calculating centroid centrality (Scardoni et al., 2009) would likely not be feasible in real time; however, one could employ a lookup table to retrieve the output almost instantaneously. Of course, some people might

¹⁰¹ Two conditions that would merit attention prior to implementation.

register their social information during the evacuation, so one can never truly bypass runtime considerations.

Another appealing method is to restrict centrality measure calculations to the subset of people requiring shelter. The advantage of this approach is that centrality scores derived from this subset may rank differently (relatively speaking) compared to scores derived from the overall population. The disadvantage to this approach pertains to implementation—as the social network of people requesting shelters will emerge in real time, one would have insufficient data, at least initially, to determine centrality.

Separating research from practice, this research will test centrality-based node orderings under the best of conditions, knowing a priori who requires shelter. This sets an upper bound for what is achievable in practice (at least with the given network type), which seems appropriate because as of writing, node orderings are not assumed to be effective under any circumstance.¹⁰²

To this end, this research has generated 40 social networks. Each of these social networks is evaluated according to 54 centrality measures. Upon evaluation, each centrality measure outputs a centrality score, one for each node. According to these centrality scores, nodes are then ranked/ordered both from high to low (HL) and low to high (LH). Serving as the control, 40 random node orderings are also generated. In cases where centrality scores are tied, the associated nodes are ranked sequentially, the order of which is randomised. If centrality scores return a null value, as nodes cannot be omitted or treated as missing data,¹⁰³ after all nodes with a centrality score are ranked/ordered, those with a null value are appended to the end, the order of which is randomised. These node orderings are then passed through restreaming FENNEL. The outcome measures, fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance, are produced after a single stream as well as after 10 restreams.

Method of Analysis

A preliminary examination of fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance reveals the presence of outliers across roughly one-third of the collective node ordering distributions. With an interest in hypothesis testing rather than estimation, and provided that such testing

¹⁰² As the null hypotheses were conceived in response to the literature, the question of how to best implement node orderings—which is a context-specific question—would logically follow if the null hypotheses were rejected.

¹⁰³ In this research context, all nodes (i.e., people) must be assigned to a partition (i.e., a shelter).

should be robust to outliers, this research employs non-parametric analysis. The following procedures are relatively straightforward.

To test the null hypotheses, H_{01} , H_{02} , H_{03} , and H_{04} , this research uses the Kruskal-Wallis test (Kruskal & Wallis, 1952) to determine whether the outcome measures from different node orderings originate from a common distribution. If $p \leq .05$, then the null hypotheses are rejected, which means that at least one node ordering stochastically dominates another node ordering. If the outcome measures are continuously and identically distributed, then one can further interpret the Kruskal-Wallis test as an omnibus test for median difference (and if distributions are symmetrical, then as an omnibus test for mean difference; see Brightwell & Dransfield, 2013; Dinno, 2015). For this research, with no distributional assumptions, the inference is cast in terms of stochastic dominance.

By way of background, the Kruskal-Wallis test extends the Mann-Whitney U test (Kruskal & Wallis, 1952), which is used to compare two groups, and is often defined in relation to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), where the Kruskal-Wallis test is the non-parametric equivalent that does not rely on assumptions of approximate normality. ANOVA also assumes homogeneity of variance, and if this latter assumption is not met (i.e., node ordering scores are heteroscedastic), then one might otherwise employ an alternative parametric test or extension of ANOVA, such as Welch's ANOVA (Welch, 1951) or a special instance of Hotelling's T^2 . (Moder, 2007; Moder, 2010; see also Liu, 2015).¹⁰⁴ As a measure of stochastic dominance, the Kruskal-Wallis test can also confront heteroscedasticity (Vargha & Delaney, 1998).

If any presented null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis, H_{a1} , H_{a2} , H_{a3} , or H_{a4} , this research will conduct (specific to the hypotheses rejected) a post-hoc, pairwise test for multiple comparisons on mean rank sums with one control, specifically Dunn's test (Dunn, 1961; Siegel & Castellan, 1988) adjusted with a Benjamini-Hochberg procedure to reduce family-wise Type I error inflation (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995).¹⁰⁵ With the control set to "random ordering," one can determine which node ordering schemes are performing the same as random (i.e., reject if $p \leq .05$). One can further report which node orderings are significantly better and worse than random.¹⁰⁶

¹⁰⁴ Please note that these parametric tests are traditionally followed by a multiple comparison test, such as Games-Howell, Tamhane's T_2 , Dunnett's T_3 , or Dunnett's C test (Lee & Lee, 2018; Shingala & Rajyaguru, 2015). As to be discussed, non-parametric tests (such as Kruskal-Wallis) would be followed by a different multiple comparison test.

¹⁰⁵ Type I error is the rejection of the null hypothesis when it is true (Schaffer, 1995).

¹⁰⁶ Although the direction of the hypothesis is not assumed with two-tailed tests, one often finds the direction of the alternative hypothesis reported, along with other results, as the difference in central tendency. For independent

Dunn's test performs exceptionally well when the number of groups is large (Dolgun & Demirhan, 2017). Under this condition, Dunn's test is recommended over other multiple comparison tests (Dolgun & Demirhan, 2017), such as Nemenyi's procedure (Nemenyi, 1963), Conover's procedure (Conover, 1999), and Steel-Dwass-Critchlow-Fligner's procedure (Spurrier, 2006). Furthermore, when pursuing multiple inferences simultaneously, researchers traditionally emphasise significant ones by controlling the family-wise error rate (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995). As an alternative control procedure, Benjamini and Hochberg (1995) consider not only whether any error was made (i.e., the probability of at least one Type I error) but moreover the proportion of erroneous rejections, what they term false discovery rate (FDR). Their procedure is one of the more powerful methods to control family-wise Type I errors (Félix & Menezes, 2018) and is used in this research to adjust p -values.

All calculations for the Kruskal-Wallis test and Dunn's test are conducted in R using the PMCMR package, now called PMCMRplus (Pohlert, 2022). Following convention, tied rankings are averaged (Conover & Iman, 1981).¹⁰⁷

Results

When passing nodes into FENNEL, the Kruskal-Wallis test shows that certain node orderings significantly affect both fraction of edges cut ($X^2 = 2654.1$, $df = 108$, $p < .001$) and partitioning imbalance ($X^2 = 1024.5$, $df = 108$, $p < .001$). When passing nodes into restreaming FENNEL, once again the Kruskal-Wallis test shows that certain node orderings have a significant effect ($X^2 = 202.11$, $df = 108$, $p < .001$; $X^2 = 317.41$, $df = 108$, $p < .001$).

Upon rejecting the null hypotheses, H_{01} , H_{02} , H_{03} , and H_{04} , the research conducted *post-hoc* tests to determine which (if any) specific node orderings significantly differ from a random node ordering. To present the findings, beginning with FENNEL, node orderings are sorted from best to worst (low to high) according to the mean rank value of their fraction of edges cut. Along with reporting the p -values from Dunn's test (interpreted for significance) and the mean rank difference from the control, this research also reports the median fraction of edges cut (see Table 11).¹⁰⁸ These output measures are also reported for partitioning imbalance,

sample tests, the direction is typically expressed as the *mean difference*; however, given the non-parametric setting, this research opted to report the *mean rank difference* from the control.

¹⁰⁷ Please note that not all research follows this convention; sometimes tied rankings are handled with a random method (e.g., Elamir, 2015).

¹⁰⁸ As median values are easier to interpret than mean rank values, and as they generally pair well with non-parametric analysis (Jurečková et al., 2012), this research presents in Appendix G the median values (see Figure G) and their rankings (see Table G1 and Table G2).

Table 11**Single Stream - Best to Worst Node Orderings**

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Fraction of Edges Cut				Significant
			Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value		
A	Leverage centrality HL	0.442	536.525	-470.262	0.146		
B	Flow betweenness centrality HL	0.448	673.675	-333.112	0.336		
C	Betweenness HL	0.448	684.65	-322.138	0.337		
D	Topological coefficient LH	0.454	733.525	-273.262	0.432		
E	Load centrality HL	0.451	761.075	-245.712	0.458		
F	Effectiveness centrality HL	0.457	762.912	-243.875	0.458		
G	Stress centrality HL	0.456	772.812	-233.975	0.476		
H	BottleNeck centrality HL	0.461	879.625	-127.162	0.69		
I	Network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) HL	0.456	893.175	-113.612	0.72		
J	Random	0.462	1006.788	0.0	N/A	N/A	
K	EPC HL	0.46	1034.688	27.9	0.921		
L	Centroid centrality HL	0.464	1040.912	34.125	0.912		
M1	Degree centrality HL	0.471	1061.75	54.962	0.861		
M2	Strength (weighted vertex degree) HL	0.471	1061.75	54.962	0.861		
N	Random walk betweenness HL	0.467	1086.538	79.75	0.807		
O	Lobby index HL	0.466	1134.9	128.113	0.69		
P	Community centrality HL	0.469	1152.538	145.75	0.653		
Q	Network centrality HL	0.469	1157.975	151.188	0.645		
R	Political independence index HL	0.466	1159.588	152.8	0.645		
S	Closeness (Variant/Latora) HL	0.47	1184.4	177.612	0.588		
T1	Dangalchev closeness centrality HL	0.47	1190.088	183.3	0.579		
T2	Decay centrality HL	0.47	1190.088	183.3	0.579		
U1	Current flow closeness centrality HL	0.473	1232.062	225.275	0.487		
U2	Information centrality HL	0.473	1232.062	225.275	0.487		
V	K-core decomposition HL	0.473	1256.9	250.112	0.454		
W	Average distance LH	0.47	1262.112	255.325	0.447		
X1	Markov centrality HL	0.473	1269.562	262.775	0.435		
X2	Random walk closeness HL	0.473	1269.562	262.775	0.435		
Y	Communicability betweenness centrality HL	0.472	1275.0	268.212	0.433		
Z	MCC centrality HL	0.471	1276.862	270.075	0.433		
AA	MNC centrality HL	0.472	1289.5	282.712	0.415		

Single Stream - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Fraction of Edges Cut				
		Median	Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value	Significant
AB1	Barycenter centrality HL	0.474	1330.788	324.0	0.337	
AB2	Closeness (Freeman) HL	0.474	1330.788	324.0	0.337	
AB3	Lin centrality HL	0.474	1330.788	324.0	0.337	
AB4	Radiality centrality HL	0.474	1330.788	324.0	0.337	
AC	Cross clique connectivity HL	0.472	1354.762	347.975	0.312	
AD	Laplacian centrality HL	0.477	1365.25	358.462	0.296	
AE	Geodesic k-path centrality HL	0.472	1420.188	413.4	0.21	
AF	Network fragmentation HL	0.476	1454.338	447.55	0.168	
AG	Eccentricity LH	0.478	1458.962	452.175	0.165	
AH	Local assortativity HL	0.48	1512.575	505.788	0.113	
AI	Diffusion degree HL	0.478	1512.975	506.188	0.113	
AJ	Entropy centrality LH	0.479	1570.738	563.95	0.073	
AK	LAC HL	0.479	1592.688	585.9	0.061	
AL	Semi local centrality HL	0.481	1611.912	605.125	0.052	
AM	ClusterRank HL	0.479	1616.6	609.812	0.051	
AN1	Eigenvector HL	0.48	1631.125	624.338	0.046	*
AN2	Kleinbergs centrality (HTS) HL	0.48	1631.125	624.338	0.046	*
AO	Alpha LH	0.484	1654.575	647.788	0.038	*
AP	Bridging centrality LH	0.481	1655.888	649.1	0.038	*
AQ	Subgraph HL	0.486	1669.95	663.162	0.034	*
AR	Local clustering coefficients HL	0.489	1745.538	738.75	0.016	*
AS	Local clustering coefficients LH	0.484	1751.95	745.162	0.015	*
AT	DMNC centrality HL	0.491	1858.775	851.988	0.005	**
AU	Local assortativity LH	0.491	1938.675	931.888	0.002	**
AV	Political independence index LH	0.494	2041.9	1035.112	<.001	***
AW	Neighborhood connectivity LH	0.494	2106.612	1099.825	<.001	***
AX	Bridging centrality HL	0.499	2182.75	1175.962	<.001	***
AY	Neighborhood connectivity HL	0.497	2259.662	1252.875	<.001	***
AZ	ClusterRank LH	0.498	2338.312	1331.525	<.001	***
BA	Alpha HL	0.501	2357.462	1350.675	<.001	***
BB	Entropy centrality HL	0.505	2599.05	1592.262	<.001	***

Single Stream - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Fraction of Edges Cut				
		Median	Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value	Significant
BC	SALSA HL	0.506	2749.112	1742.325	<.001	***
BD	Eccentricity HL	0.515	2822.588	1815.8	<.001	***
BE	DMNC centrality LH	0.521	2968.862	1962.075	<.001	***
BF	Network centrality LH	0.524	2996.95	1990.162	<.001	***
BG1	Current flow closeness centrality LH	0.517	2997.375	1990.588	<.001	***
BG2	Information centrality LH	0.517	2997.375	1990.588	<.001	***
BH	Closeness (Variant/Latora) LH	0.523	3021.4	2014.612	<.001	***
BI	Network fragmentation LH	0.519	3027.838	2021.05	<.001	***
BJ	Average distance HL	0.52	3044.075	2037.288	<.001	***
BK	Geodesic K-path centrality LH	0.524	3069.738	2062.95	<.001	***
BL	LAC LH	0.521	3074.05	2067.262	<.001	***
BM1	Dangalchev closeness centrality LH	0.523	3120.712	2113.925	<.001	***
BM2	Decay centrality LH	0.523	3120.712	2113.925	<.001	***
BN	Subgraph LH	0.524	3153.575	2146.788	<.001	***
BO	Community centrality LH	0.524	3173.462	2166.675	<.001	***
BP	Semi local centrality LH	0.528	3187.975	2181.188	<.001	***
BQ1	Markov centrality LH	0.523	3208.1	2201.312	<.001	***
BQ2	Random walk closeness LH	0.523	3208.1	2201.312	<.001	***
BR1	Barycenter centrality LH	0.524	3209.675	2202.888	<.001	***
BR2	Closeness (Freeman) LH	0.524	3209.675	2202.888	<.001	***
BR3	Lin centrality LH	0.524	3209.675	2202.888	<.001	***
BR4	Radiality centrality LH	0.524	3209.675	2202.888	<.001	***
BS	Stress centrality LH	0.529	3217.85	2211.062	<.001	***
BT	Centroid centrality LH	0.526	3227.7	2220.912	<.001	***
BU	MINC centrality LH	0.527	3230.475	2223.688	<.001	***
BV	Laplacian centrality LH	0.527	3230.55	2223.762	<.001	***
BW	Flow betweenness centrality LH	0.525	3236.925	2230.138	<.001	***
BX	EPC LH	0.526	3242.3	2235.512	<.001	***
BY	Leverage centrality LH	0.534	3255.512	2248.725	<.001	***
BZ1	Eigenvector LH	0.529	3269.725	2262.938	<.001	***
BZ2	Kleinbergs centrality (HITS) LH	0.529	3269.725	2262.938	<.001	***

Single Stream - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Fraction of Edges Cut				
		Median	Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value	Significant
CA	K-core decomposition LH	0.527	3289.112	2282.325	<.001	***
CB	Betweenness LH	0.528	3290.712	2283.925	<.001	***
CC	BottleNeck centrality LH	0.527	3292.675	2285.888	<.001	***
CD	Topological coefficient HL	0.525	3323.05	2316.262	<.001	***
CE	Network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) LH	0.53	3379.325	2372.538	<.001	***
CF	Load centrality LH	0.528	3384.625	2377.838	<.001	***
CG	Gross clique centrality LH	0.53	3446.55	2439.762	<.001	***
CH	Random walk betweenness LH	0.533	3450.988	2444.2	<.001	***
CI	MCC centrality LH	0.533	3471.05	2464.262	<.001	***
CJ	Communicability betweenness centrality LH	0.54	3484.238	2477.45	<.001	***
CK	Effectiveness centrality LH	0.534	3487.075	2480.288	<.001	***
CL	Diffusion degree LH	0.531	3510.012	2503.225	<.001	***
CM	Lobby index LH	0.535	3533.438	2526.65	<.001	***
CN1	Degree centrality LH	0.532	3536.062	2529.275	<.001	***
CN2	Strength (weighted vertex degree) LH	0.532	3536.062	2529.275	<.001	***
CO	SALSA LH	0.539	3556.975	2550.188	<.001	***

Table 12**Single Stream - Best to Worst Node Orderings**

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Partitioning Imbalance			
			Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value	Significant
A	Leverage centrality HL	1.04	2155.238	-119.575	0.619	
B	Flow betweenness centrality HL	1.04	2015.475	-259.337	0.321	
C	Betweenness HL	1.04	1689.362	-585.45	0.042	*
D	Topological coefficient LH	1.04	1689.362	-585.45	0.042	*
E	Load centrality HL	1.04	1825.088	-449.725	0.087	
F	Effectiveness centrality HL	1.04	2062.062	-212.75	0.406	
G	Stress centrality HL	1.04	1731.912	-542.9	0.048	*
H	BottleNeck centrality HL	1.04	1918.262	-356.55	0.172	
I	Network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) HL	1.04	1503.012	-771.8	0.019	*
J	Random	1.04	2274.812	0.0	N/A	N/A
K	EPC HL	1.04	1735.95	-538.862	0.048	*
L	Centroid centrality HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*
M1	Degree centrality HL	1	1316.662	-958.15	0.003	**
M2	Strength (weighted vertex degree) HL	1	1316.662	-958.15	0.003	**
N	Random walk betweenness HL	1.04	1922.3	-352.512	0.173	
O	Lobby index HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*
P	Community centrality HL	1.04	1825.088	-449.725	0.087	
Q	Network centrality HL	1.04	1825.088	-449.725	0.087	
R	Political independence index HL	1.04	1964.85	-309.962	0.229	
S	Closeness (Variant/Latora) HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*
T1	Dangalchev closeness centrality HL	1.04	1782.538	-492.275	0.067	
T2	Decay centrality HL	1.04	1782.538	-492.275	0.067	
U1	Current flow closeness centrality HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*
U2	Information centrality HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*
V	K-core decomposition HL	1.04	1875.712	-399.1	0.127	
W	Average distance LH	1.04	1875.712	-399.1	0.127	
X1	Markov centrality HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*
X2	Random walk closeness HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*
Y	Communicability betweenness centrality HL	1.02	1363.25	-911.562	0.004	**
Z	MCC centrality HL	1.04	1549.6	-725.212	0.019	*
AA	MNC centrality HL	1.04	1778.5	-496.312	0.067	

Single Stream - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Mean Rank	Partitioning Imbalance		Adjusted P-Value	Significant
				Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value		
AB1	Barycenter centrality HL	1.04	1735.95	-538.862	0.048	*	
AB2	Closeness (Freeman) HL	1.04	1735.95	-538.862	0.048	*	
AB3	Lin centrality HL	1.04	1735.95	-538.862	0.048	*	
AB4	Radiality centrality HL	1.04	1735.95	-538.862	0.048	*	
AC	Cross clique connectivity HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*	
AD	Laplacian centrality HL	1.04	1642.775	-632.038	0.03	*	
AE	Geodesic K-path centrality HL	1.04	1642.775	-632.038	0.03	*	
AF	Network fragmentation HL	1.04	2135.05	-139.762	0.582		
AG	Eccentricity LH	1.04	1735.95	-538.862	0.048	*	
AH	Local assortativity HL	1.04	1817.012	-457.8	0.087		
AI	Diffusion degree HL	1.04	1829.125	-445.688	0.087		
AJ	Entropy centrality LH	1.04	2189.45	-85.362	0.718		
AK	LAC HL	1.04	1778.5	-496.312	0.067		
AL	Semi local centrality HL	1.04	1968.888	-305.925	0.233		
AM	ClusterRank HL	1.04	1829.125	-445.688	0.087		
AN1	Eigenvector HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*	
AN2	Kleinbergs centrality (HTS) HL	1.04	1596.188	-678.625	0.019	*	
AO	Alpha LH	1.04	2410.538	135.725	0.588		
AP	Bridging centrality LH	1.04	1829.125	-445.688	0.087		
AQ	Subgraph HL	1.04	1549.6	-725.212	0.019	*	
AR	Local clustering coefficients HL	1.04	1689.362	-585.45	0.042	*	
AS	Local clustering coefficients LH	1.04	1689.362	-585.45	0.042	*	
AT	DMNC centrality HL	1.04	1829.125	-445.688	0.087		
AU	Local assortativity LH	1.04	1689.362	-585.45	0.042	*	
AV	Political independence index LH	1.04	2499.675	224.862	0.381		
AW	Neighborhood connectivity LH	1.04	2049.95	-224.862	0.381		
AX	Bridging centrality HL	1.04	1735.95	-538.862	0.048	*	
AY	Neighborhood connectivity HL	1.04	1918.262	-356.55	0.172		
AZ	ClusterRank LH	1.04	1782.538	-492.275	0.067		
BA	Alpha HL	1.04	2972.312	697.5	0.019	*	
BB	Entropy centrality HL	1.04	2503.45	228.638	0.38		

Single Stream - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Partitioning Imbalance			Adjusted P-Value	Significant
			Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Mean Rank		
BC	SALSA HL	1.04	1735.95	-538.862	0.048	*	
BD	Eccentricity HL	1.04	2466.112	191.3	0.457		
BE	DMNC centrality LH	1.04	1638.738	-636.075	0.03	*	
BF	Network centrality LH	1.04	2851.4	576.588	0.046	*	
BG1	Current flow closeness centrality LH	1.04	2839.812	565.0	0.048	*	
BG2	Information centrality LH	1.04	2839.812	565.0	0.048	*	
BH	Closeness (Variant/Latora) LH	1.04	2431.375	156.562	0.543		
BI	Network fragmentation LH	1.04	2135.05	-139.762	0.582		
BJ	Average distance HL	1.04	2890.7	615.888	0.036	*	
BK	Geodesic K-path centrality LH	1.04	2627.325	352.512	0.173		
BL	LAC LH	1.04	2503.45	228.638	0.38		
BM1	Dangalchev closeness centrality LH	1.04	2596.1	321.288	0.217		
BM2	Decay centrality LH	1.04	2596.1	321.288	0.217		
BN	Subgraph LH	1.04	2460.638	185.825	0.467		
BO	Community centrality LH	1.04	2759.012	484.2	0.071		
BP	Semi local centrality LH	1.04	2871.588	596.775	0.042	*	
BQ1	Markov centrality LH	1.04	2639.175	364.362	0.165		
BQ2	Random walk closeness LH	1.04	2639.175	364.362	0.165		
BR1	Barycenter centrality LH	1.04	2820.962	546.15	0.048	*	
BR2	Closeness (Freeman) LH	1.04	2820.962	546.15	0.048	*	
BR3	Lin centrality LH	1.04	2820.962	546.15	0.048	*	
BR4	Radiality centrality LH	1.04	2820.962	546.15	0.048	*	
BS	Stress centrality LH	1.04	3050.512	775.7	0.019	*	
BT	Centroid centrality LH	1.04	2973.225	698.412	0.019	*	
BU	MINC centrality LH	1.04	2797.525	522.712	0.055		
BV	Laplacian centrality LH	1.04	3010.825	736.012	0.019	*	
BW	Flow betweenness centrality LH	1.04	2584.512	309.7	0.229		
BX	EPC LH	1.04	2507.225	232.412	0.379		
BY	Leverage centrality LH	1.04	2979.862	705.05	0.019	*	
BZ1	Eigenvector LH	1.04	2394.388	119.575	0.619		
BZ2	Kleinbergs centrality (HITS) LH	1.04	2394.388	119.575	0.619		

Single Stream - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Partitioning Imbalance				Significant
			Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value		
CA	K-core decomposition LH	1.04	2720.238	445.425	0.087		
CB	Betweenness LH	1.04	2909.838	635.025	0.03	*	
CC	BottleNeck centrality LH	1.04	2810.55	535.738	0.049	*	
CD	Topological coefficient HL	1.04	2766.825	492.012	0.066		
CE	Network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) LH	1.04	2728.05	453.238	0.087		
CF	Load centrality LH	1.04	2767.738	492.925	0.066		
CG	Gross clique centrality LH	1.04	2716.462	441.65	0.089		
CH	Random walk betweenness LH	1.04	2708.388	433.575	0.095		
CI	MCC centrality LH	1.04	2987.125	712.312	0.019	*	
CJ	Communicability betweenness centrality LH	1.04	2820.962	546.15	0.048	*	
CK	Effectiveness centrality LH	1.04	2995.2	720.388	0.019	*	
CL	Diffusion degree LH	1.04	2665.838	391.025	0.135		
CM	Lobby index LH	1.04	2766.825	492.012	0.066		
CN1	Degree centrality LH	1.04	2724.925	450.112	0.087		
CN2	Strength (weighted vertex degree) LH	1.04	2724.925	450.112	0.087		
CO	SALSA LH	1.04	1960.812	-314.0	0.226		

Table 13

Restreaming - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Fraction of Edges Cut				Significant
			Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value		
BW	Flow betweenness centrality LH	0.368	1608.85	-46.125	0.886		
R	Political independence index HL	0.366	1617.038	-37.938	0.901		
CE	Network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) LH	0.365	1648.062	-6.912	0.98		
J	Random	0.367	1654.975	0.0	N/A	N/A	
AV	Political independence index LH	0.374	1732.638	77.662	0.805		
C	Betweenness HL	0.371	1734.25	79.275	0.805		
AU	Local assortativity LH	0.368	1744.7	89.725	0.786		
AJ	Entropy centrality LH	0.368	1759.512	104.538	0.752		
CF	Load centrality LH	0.372	1777.025	122.05	0.711		
AX	Bridging centrality HL	0.367	1782.138	127.162	0.704		
F	Effectiveness centrality HL	0.368	1797.55	142.575	0.668		
Y	Communicability betweenness centrality HL	0.366	1808.675	153.7	0.645		
AG	Eccentricity LH	0.369	1812.188	157.212	0.642		
P	Community centrality HL	0.373	1836.425	181.45	0.584		
G	Stress centrality HL	0.371	1848.45	193.475	0.559		
N	Random walk betweenness HL	0.371	1869.562	214.588	0.512		
AH	Local assortativity HL	0.37	1920.775	265.8	0.401		
AP	Bridging centrality LH	0.375	1935.45	280.475	0.375		
CD	Topological coefficient HL	0.372	1946.912	291.938	0.356		
I	Network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) HL	0.371	1957.612	302.638	0.339		
BR1	Barycenter centrality LH	0.374	1973.875	318.9	0.312		
BR2	Closeness (Freeman) LH	0.374	1973.875	318.9	0.312		
BR3	Lin centrality LH	0.374	1973.875	318.9	0.312		
BR4	Radiality centrality LH	0.374	1973.875	318.9	0.312		
CH	Random walk betweenness LH	0.375	1984.312	329.338	0.307		
AF	Network fragmentation HL	0.375	1996.65	341.675	0.289		
BQ1	Markov centrality LH	0.37	1997.8	342.825	0.289		
BQ2	Random walk closeness LH	0.37	1997.8	342.825	0.289		
E	Load centrality HL	0.375	1999.95	344.975	0.289		
H	BottleNeck centrality HL	0.378	2001.712	346.738	0.289		
Z	MCC centrality HL	0.372	2026.35	371.375	0.256		

Restreaming - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Fraction of Edges Cut				
		Median	Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value	Significant
BA	Alpha HL	0.375	1330.788	2028.95	0.255	
BS	Stress centrality LH	0.376	1330.788	2038.675	0.242	
BJ	Average distance HL	0.37	1330.788	2039.088	0.242	
M1	Degree centrality HL	0.373	1330.788	2042.175	0.242	
M2	Strength (weighted vertex degree) HL	0.373	1354.762	2042.175	0.242	
A	Leverage centrality HL	0.373	1365.25	2046.475	0.242	
AO	Alpha LH	0.373	1420.188	2054.113	0.234	
BE	DMNC centrality LH	0.37	1454.338	2054.238	0.234	
AB1	Barycenter centrality HL	0.378	1458.962	2054.387	0.234	
AB2	Closeness (Freeman) HL	0.378	1512.575	2054.387	0.234	
AB3	Lin centrality HL	0.378	1512.975	2054.387	0.234	
AB4	Radiality centrality HL	0.378	1570.738	2054.387	0.234	
BH	Closeness (Variant/Latora) LH	0.375	1592.688	2057.6	0.234	
BI	Network fragmentation LH	0.376	1611.912	2066.65	0.234	
BY	Leverage centrality LH	0.378	1616.6	2073.725	0.231	
BT	Centroid centrality LH	0.376	1631.125	2076.912	0.229	
CB	Betweenness LH	0.375	1631.125	2078.275	0.229	
BD	Eccentricity HL	0.375	1654.575	2108.25	0.19	
U1	Current flow closeness centrality HL	0.377	1655.888	2109.85	0.19	
U2	Information centrality HL	0.377	1669.95	2109.85	0.19	
AC	Cross clique connectivity HL	0.376	1745.538	2149.25	0.147	
BV	Laplacian centrality LH	0.378	1751.95	2157.488	0.141	
BB	Entropy centrality HL	0.381	1858.775	2159.962	0.14	
D	Topological coefficient LH	0.38	1938.675	2164.0	0.139	
AD	Laplacian centrality HL	0.381	2041.9	2187.575	0.117	
L	Centroid centrality HL	0.375	2106.612	2191.525	0.115	
AR	Local clustering coefficients HL	0.382	2182.75	2198.638	0.111	
O	Lobby index HL	0.376	2259.662	2199.038	0.111	
S	Closeness (Variant/Latora) HL	0.375	2338.312	2213.575	0.102	
CN1	Degree centrality LH	0.38	2357.462	2234.025	0.087	
CN2	Strength (weighted vertex degree) LH	0.38	2599.05	2234.025	0.087	

Restreaming - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Fraction of Edges Cut				
		Median	Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value	Significant
CC	BottleNeck centrality LH	0.382	2235.525	580.55	0.087	
B	Flow betweenness centrality HL	0.38	2237.725	582.75	0.087	
CI	MCC centrality LH	0.381	2251.412	596.438	0.082	
BP	Semi local centrality LH	0.377	2256.55	601.575	0.08	
BF	Network centrality LH	0.379	2264.125	609.15	0.076	
BK	Geodesic K-path centrality LH	0.379	2268.838	613.862	0.075	
AI	Diffusion degree HL	0.378	2271.838	616.862	0.075	
BO	Community centrality LH	0.382	2280.712	625.738	0.071	
AQ	Subgraph HL	0.383	2283.788	628.812	0.071	
BU	MNC centrality LH	0.381	2318.025	663.05	0.053	
CJ	Communicability betweenness centrality LH	0.38	2326.65	671.675	0.05	
T1	Dangalchev closeness centrality HL	0.382	2351.662	696.688	0.04	*
T2	Decay centrality HL	0.382	2351.662	696.688	0.04	*
X1	Markov centrality HL	0.384	2352.112	697.138	0.04	*
X2	Random walk closeness HL	0.384	2352.112	697.138	0.04	*
Q	Network centrality HL	0.384	2360	705.025	0.04	*
BX	EPC LH	0.381	2373.288	718.312	0.037	*
BM1	Dangalchev closeness centrality LH	0.384	2389.288	734.312	0.033	*
BM2	Decay centrality LH	0.384	2389.288	734.312	0.033	*
AW	Neighborhood connectivity LH	0.384	2391.562	736.588	0.033	*
CK	Effectiveness centrality LH	0.388	2393.688	738.712	0.033	*
AL	Semi local centrality HL	0.383	2398.475	743.5	0.033	*
CA	K-core decomposition LH	0.383	2404.875	749.9	0.033	*
A5	Local clustering coefficients LH	0.381	2410.75	755.775	0.033	*
V	K-core decomposition HL	0.386	2412.662	757.688	0.033	*
BG1	Current flow closeness centrality LH	0.389	2431.888	776.912	0.028	*
BG2	Information centrality LH	0.389	2431.888	776.912	0.028	*
W	Average distance LH	0.383	2433.0	778.025	0.028	*
CO	SALSA LH	0.386	2450.538	795.562	0.027	*
AM	ClusterRank HL	0.385	2480.688	825.712	0.02	*
AZ	ClusterRank LH	0.388	2522.612	867.638	0.013	*

Restreaming - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Fraction of Edges Cut					Significant
		Median	Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value		
BZ1	Eigenvector LH	0.388	2525.825	870.85	0.013	*	
BZ2	Kleinbergs centrality (HITS) LH	0.388	2525.825	870.85	0.013	*	
K	EPC HL	0.384	2527.238	872.262	0.013	*	
BN	Subgraph LH	0.389	2541.562	886.588	0.013	*	
AT	DMNC centrality HL	0.39	2550.812	895.838	0.013	*	
BL	LAC LH	0.385	2550.838	895.862	0.013	*	
AN1	Eigenvector HL	0.385	2560.538	905.562	0.013	*	
AN2	Kleinbergs centrality (HITS) HL	0.385	2563.488	908.512	0.013	*	
CM	Lobby index LH	0.386	2577.325	922.35	0.013	*	
CL	Diffusion degree LH	0.39	2578.362	923.388	0.013	*	
CG	Gross clique centrality LH	0.388	2582.012	927.038	0.013	*	
AE	Geodesic K-path centrality HL	0.391	2603.175	948.2	0.013	*	
AA	MNC centrality HL	0.392	2645.938	990.962	0.012	*	
AK	LAC HL	0.393	2669.488	1014.512	0.011	*	
BC	SALSA HL	0.395	2751.362	1096.388	0.005	**	
AY	Neighborhood connectivity HL	0.392	2816.975	1162.0	0.004	**	

Table 14

Restreaming - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Partitioning Imbalance			
			Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value	Significant
BW	Flow betweenness centrality LH	1.04	2239.388	190.538	0.659	
R	Political independence index HL	1.04	2013.388	-35.462	0.925	
CE	Network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) LH	1.04	2520.65	471.8	0.29	
J	Random	1.04	2048.85	0.0	N/A	N/A
AV	Political independence index LH	1.04	2278.138	229.288	0.59	
C	Betweenness HL	1.04	2458.775	409.925	0.358	
AU	Local assortativity LH	1.04	2597.338	548.488	0.29	
AJ	Entropy centrality LH	1.04	2458.775	409.925	0.358	
CF	Load centrality LH	1.04	2160.225	111.375	0.816	
AX	Bridging centrality HL	1.04	2240.575	191.725	0.659	
F	Effectiveness centrality HL	1.04	2090.962	42.112	0.911	
Y	Communicability betweenness centrality HL	1.04	2730.95	682.1	0.29	
AG	Eccentricity LH	1.04	2227.825	178.975	0.665	
P	Community centrality HL	1.04	1786.575	-262.275	0.539	
G	Stress centrality HL	1.04	2275.662	226.812	0.59	
N	Random walk betweenness HL	1.04	1574.612	-474.238	0.29	
AH	Local assortativity HL	1.04	2370.525	321.675	0.444	
AP	Bridging centrality LH	1.04	2585.775	536.925	0.29	
CD	Topological coefficient HL	1.04	2513.225	464.375	0.29	
I	Network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) HL	1.04	2509.088	460.238	0.29	
BR1	Barycenter centrality LH	1.04	2265.762	216.912	0.59	
BR2	Closeness (Freeman) LH	1.04	2265.762	216.912	0.59	
BR3	Lin centrality LH	1.04	2265.762	216.912	0.59	
BR4	Radiality centrality LH	1.04	2265.762	216.912	0.59	
CH	Random walk betweenness LH	1.04	2284.75	235.9	0.586	
AF	Network fragmentation HL	1.04	2053.8	4.95	0.992	
BQ1	Markov centrality LH	1.04	2418.362	369.512	0.389	
BQ2	Random walk closeness LH	1.04	2418.362	369.512	0.389	
E	Load centrality HL	1.04	2101.638	52.788	0.911	
H	BottleNeck centrality HL	1.04	2110.725	61.875	0.911	
Z	MCC centrality HL	1.04	1624.112	-424.738	0.345	

Restreaming - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Partitioning Imbalance			Adjusted P-Value	Significant
			Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Mean Rank		
BA	Alpha HL	1.04	2370.525	321.675	0.444		
BS	Stress centrality LH	1.04	2270.712	221.862	0.59		
BJ	Average distance HL	1.04	2558.588	509.738	0.29		
M1	Degree centrality HL	1.04	1803.088	-245.762	0.559		
M2	Strength (weighted vertex degree) HL	1.04	1803.088	-245.762	0.559		
A	Leverage centrality HL	1.04	2230.3	181.45	0.665		
AO	Alpha LH	1.04	2208.062	159.212	0.711		
BE	DMNC centrality LH	1.04	2402.738	353.888	0.412		
AB1	Barycenter centrality HL	1.04	2099.162	50.312	0.911		
AB2	Closeness (Freeman) HL	1.04	2099.162	50.312	0.911		
AB3	Lin centrality HL	1.04	2099.162	50.312	0.911		
AB4	Radiality centrality HL	1.04	2099.162	50.312	0.911		
BH	Closeness (Variant/Latora) LH	1.04	2134.625	85.775	0.884		
BI	Network fragmentation LH	1.04	2336.725	287.875	0.497		
BY	Leverage centrality LH	1.04	2046.375	-2.475	0.992		
BT	Centroid centrality LH	1.04	2254.612	205.762	0.621		
CB	Betweenness LH	1.04	2117.338	68.488	0.911		
BD	Eccentricity HL	1.04	2456.3	407.45	0.358		
U1	Current flow closeness centrality HL	1.04	2091.738	42.888	0.911		
U2	Information centrality HL	1.04	2091.738	42.888	0.911		
AC	Cross clique connectivity HL	1.04	1577.088	-471.762	0.29		
BV	Laplacian centrality LH	1.04	2387.038	338.188	0.439		
BB	Entropy centrality HL	1.04	2143.712	94.862	0.86		
D	Topological coefficient LH	1.04	2058.75	9.9	0.992		
AD	Laplacian centrality HL	1.04	1968.025	-80.825	0.893		
L	Centroid centrality HL	1.04	1655.438	-393.412	0.364		
AR	Local clustering coefficients HL	1.04	2110.725	61.875	0.911		
O	Lobby index HL	1.04	1786.575	-262.275	0.539		
S	Closeness (Variant/Latora) HL	1.04	2184.938	136.088	0.764		
CN1	Degree centrality LH	1.04	2422.5	373.65	0.389		
CN2	Strength (weighted vertex degree) LH	1.04	2422.5	373.65	0.389		

Restreaming - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Partitioning Imbalance			Adjusted P-Value	Significant
			Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Mean Rank		
CC	BottleNeck centrality LH	1.04	2358.962	310.112	0.451		
B	Flow betweenness centrality HL	1.04	2363.912	315.062	0.444		
CI	MCC centrality LH	1.04	2157.75	108.9	0.816		
BP	Semi local centrality LH	1.04	2566.012	517.162	0.29		
BF	Network centrality LH	1.04	2295.025	246.175	0.559		
BK	Geodesic K-path centrality LH	1.04	2368.05	319.2	0.444		
AI	Diffusion degree HL	1.04	1746.162	-302.688	0.466		
BO	Community centrality LH	1.04	2161.412	112.562	0.816		
AQ	Subgraph HL	1.04	2124.762	75.912	0.902		
BU	MNC centrality LH	1.04	2538.825	489.975	0.29		
CJ	Communicability betweenness centrality LH	1.04	2415.888	367.038	0.389		
T1	Dangalchev closeness centrality HL	1.04	2179.212	130.363	0.764		
T2	Decay centrality HL	1.04	2179.212	130.363	0.764		
X1	Markov centrality HL	1.04	2055.462	6.612	0.992		
X2	Random walk closeness HL	1.04	2055.462	6.612	0.992		
Q	Network centrality HL	1.04	1912.762	-136.088	0.764		
BX	EPC LH	1.04	2296.312	247.462	0.559		
BM1	Dangalchev closeness centrality LH	1.04	2365.575	316.725	0.444		
BM2	Decay centrality LH	1.04	2365.575	316.725	0.444		
AW	Neighborhood connectivity LH	1.04	2672.438	623.588	0.29		
CK	Effectiveness centrality LH	1.04	2313.6	264.75	0.539		
AL	Semi local centrality HL	1.04	2005.962	-42.888	0.911		
CA	K-core decomposition LH	1.04	2577.575	528.725	0.29		
A5	Local clustering coefficients LH	1.04	2509.088	460.238	0.29		
V	K-core decomposition HL	1.04	1648.012	-400.838	0.364		
BG1	Current flow closeness centrality LH	1.04	2227.825	178.975	0.665		
BG2	Information centrality LH	1.04	2227.825	178.975	0.665		
W	Average distance LH	1.04	2316.075	267.225	0.539		
CO	SALSA LH	1.04	2594.862	546.012	0.29		
AM	ClusterRank HL	1.04	1605.125	-443.725	0.316		
AZ	ClusterRank LH	1.04	2222.875	174.025	0.665		

Restreaming - Best to Worst Node Orderings

Based on Fraction of Edges Cut (Mean Rank)

continued

ID	Node Orderings	Median	Partitioning Imbalance			Significant
			Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference From Control	Adjusted P-Value	
BZ1	Eigenvector LH	1.04	2637.75	588.9	0.29	
BZ2	Kleinbergs centrality (HITS) LH	1.04	2637.75	588.9	0.29	
K	EPC HL	1.04	1583.7	-465.15	0.29	
BN	Subgraph LH	1.04	2373.0	324.15	0.444	
AT	DMNC centrality HL	1.04	1709.888	-338.962	0.439	
BL	LAC LH	1.04	2327.638	278.788	0.519	
AN1	Eigenvector HL	1.04	1529.25	-519.6	0.29	
AN2	Kleinbergs centrality (HITS) HL	1.04	1572.138	-476.712	0.29	
CM	Lobby index LH	1.04	2194.025	145.175	0.755	
CL	Diffusion degree LH	1.04	2506.612	457.762	0.29	
CG	Gross clique centrality LH	1.04	2222.875	174.025	0.665	
AE	Geodesic K-path centrality HL	1.04	1652.962	-395.888	0.364	
AA	MNC centrality HL	1.04	1752.775	-296.075	0.479	
AK	LAC HL	1.04	1621.638	-427.212	0.345	
BC	SALSA HL	1.04	2182.462	133.612	0.764	
AY	Neighborhood connectivity HL	1.04	1695.85	-353.0	0.412	

which for cross-referencing purposes, are appended to the sorted node orderings (see Table 12). Following the above logic, the research creates separate figures for findings related to restreaming FENNEL (see Table 13 and Table 14).

When passing nodes into FENNEL, compared to the random control, most of the tested node orderings negatively affect the fraction of edges cut. Out of the 108 node orderings tested, 63 are significantly adversarial. As a general trend, centralities ordered from high to low (HL) tend to outperform their low to high (LH) counterparts. That said, both directions generally perform worse than random. Regarding a few notable exceptions, although the node ordering based on “leverage centrality HL,” followed by eight other node orderings, have a better (i.e., lower) mean rank score than random, these better rankings are not significant.

Partitioning imbalance tells a different story. While 19 node orderings perform significantly worse than random, 33 node orderings also perform significantly better. According to their mean rank, “degree centrality HL” and its weighted variant, “strength centrality HL” ($p = .003$), closely followed by “communicability betweenness centrality HL” ($p = .004$), produce significantly more balanced partitions than random.

Taking a conservative, “do no harm” approach to node ordering selection, one might confine the analysis to cases where the difference in mean rank from the control shows improvement with respect to both fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance. One can further consider pareto-optimal solutions in combination with significant results (see Figure 25). With an emphasis on minimising fraction of edges cut, one might utilise “betweenness centrality HL,” which unlike “leverage centrality HL,” produces significantly more balanced partitions than random ($p = .042$). To further improve partitioning imbalance, one might traverse the Pareto front to “network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) HL,” which is less likely to harm fraction of edges cut than “degree centrality HL” or “communicability betweenness centrality HL” while producing significantly more balanced partitions than random.

Turning to restreaming FENNEL, the only significant results are 37 node orderings that adversely affect fraction of edges cut. While three node orderings have a better mean rank score than random, two of them, “flow betweenness centrality LH” and “network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) LH,” score worse in terms of partitioning imbalance—the other node ordering, “political independence index HL,” is the more well-rounded option.¹⁰⁹ When

¹⁰⁹ Please note that the “political independence index” was run without negative edges, making it essentially the same as the “graph-theoretic power index” (Markovsky et al., 1988, 1993; see also Smith et al., 2014).

Figure 25

**Relationship Between Single Stream
Fraction of Edges Cut and Partitioning Imbalance**

Figure 26
 Relationship Between Restreaming
 Fraction of Edges Cut and Partitioning Imbalance

Max
 Fraction of Edges Cut

Max
 Partitioning Imbalance

Statistically Equivalent to Random

Legend
 ● Centralities
 ● Highlighted Centralities
 † Significant fraction of edges cut
 * Significant partitioning imbalance

restreaming is involved, one should not overlook the impressive performance of the experimental control, random node ordering, which nearly touches the Pareto front (see Figure 26).

Depending on the implementation, one might further report node ordering performance when subject to both FENNEL and restreaming FENNEL. If the batch size within a sliding window becomes too small, then restreaming FENNEL will behave similarly to FENNEL, and therefore one should attribute some weight to single stream outcomes. Accordingly, “flow betweenness centrality LH” and “network fragmentation (geodesic distance weighted) LH” (see above) are further problematic because they produce significantly worse partitions than the random control with respect to fraction of edges cut during a single stream ($p < .001$; $p < .001$). Examples of node orderings that perform well during restreaming with some carry-over performance to the single stream scenario include “community centrality HL,” “effectiveness centrality HL,” and “political independence index HL,” and with more emphasis on partitioning imbalance, “cross clique connectivity HL,” “MCC centrality HL,” and “random walk betweenness HL.”

When looking across all node orderings, given that the median range for fraction of edges cut when restreaming (0.365–0.395) is vastly superior to that found when using a single stream (0.442–0.540)—in fact, the ranges do not overlap—one should attempt to restream whenever time permits. The median range when restreaming is also narrower, which combined with knowing how exceptionally well random performs, speaks to placing more emphasis on the single stream context when looking to make performance gains. That said, as a single stream is presumably (and hopefully) the first of multiple restreams, one should attribute some weight, this time to restreaming outcomes. Examples of carry-over performance when restreaming include “effectiveness centrality HL,” “load centrality HL,” and “stress centrality HL,” the latter of which produces significantly more balanced partition than random ($p = .048$). To focus even more on balance, one might consider “centroid centrality HL,” “degree centrality HL,” and “MCC centrality HL.”

Discussion

In designing a shelter assignment algorithm, runtime is a critical factor. While improving computational efficiency is an obvious research direction, another and perhaps overlooked area of study is how to make better use of the time available. This research thereby proposes the use of centrality-based node orderings to improve outcome measures when

restreaming FENNEL does not have time to converge on its best solution. The principal finding is that node order makes a difference. With time for only a single stream, one can select a node ordering that significantly improves the outcome measures, fraction of edges cut, and partitioning imbalance. With ample time for restreaming, one can select a node ordering that is at the very least not significantly adversarial.

For both a single stream and multiple restreams, one can point to node orderings whose central tendencies are better than that of random but not significantly better in all respects. In such cases, one should reflect upon the risks and repercussions associated with implementation. On the surface, the expense passed to displaced people is not monetary, nor is it effort, time, or inconvenience. If certain node orderings are strictly of added value, but that added value is simply improbable, one could make an argument for implementation (or during analysis, less stringent p -values).

On the other hand, each node ordering tested has circumstantial benefits, which means a poorly selected node ordering is not without “side effects.” One possibility is selecting the wrong node ordering for a given evacuation scenario—for example, selecting a node order designed for a single stream when multiple restreams are the norm (or vice versa)—where such a selection becomes a significant impairment or missed opportunity for improvement. Another example is selecting node orderings that prioritise global outcome measures at the expense of individual outcome measures, where the latter is deemed important. Without an obvious all-encompassing solution, this research contends that instead of selecting a node ordering that works decently across multiple evacuation scenarios or one that attempts to satisfy every conceivable objective, one could obtain better results (i.e., with fewer compromises) by tailoring node orderings to meet time demands and objectives unique to each evacuation.¹¹⁰

As another point of critique, this research has not defined a node ordering that represents the status quo. If such a node ordering is guided by implicit factors, then it might perform better than random or (as with most tested node orderings) worse than random. As an alternative post hoc test, one might prefer not to ascribe undue meaning to randomness by embracing a slightly different methodology. Closely related to the problem of comparing k populations with a control is the problem of selecting the best among k populations (Gupta & Panchapakesan, 2002; Horn & Vollandt, 1996; see also Hsu, 1996). This would mark a

¹¹⁰ Acknowledging some uncertainty in forecasting who is displaced, one might still favour a robust node ordering, as achieved with consensus clustering (see Ghosh & Acharya, 2015), or a node ordering that improves worst-case evacuation scenarios. Either way, reducing the solution space to include only plausible network configurations, for example, should focus and improve results.

departure from asking whether node orderings are useful to asking, more directly, which node orderings should be used.

This research tested only a handful of node orderings based on centrality measures. These were selected from several libraries containing pre-written code. Many other published centrality measures were not included in this study (cf., Jalili et al., 2015). While none of the tested centrality-based node orderings is specifically oriented at improving streaming graph partitioning, Awadelkarim and Ugander (2020) recently developed a node ordering well-suited for this context, where the authors were able to improve the fraction of edges cut metric for the (re)streaming graph partitioner, Restreamed Linear Deterministic Greedy (reLDG). Their node ordering, called “ambivalence,” outperformed other node orderings for most tested networks. Keep in mind that real-world social networks at emergency shelters may not resemble any network tested by Awadelkarim and Ugander (2020) or, for that matter, any network tested by this research. Furthermore, node ordering performance often varies from network to network.

As for future work, beyond testing additional node orderings across multiple networks (e.g., Oldham et al., 2019), one could explore switching between different node orderings during an evacuation. The research has also not explored how the probability of displacement might influence node orderings. Another related area of research is whether certain node orderings can foster the reconstruction of social networks pre-partitioned according to probabilities of displacement. Lastly, one could further investigate the relationship between fraction of edges cut and partitioning imbalance. For example, as a potential method to improve fraction of edges cut without sacrificing partitioning imbalance, one might relax FENNEL’s balance constraint, which should translate into preserving additional edges, while simultaneously using a node ordering that improves partitioning imbalance, such as degree centrality, to zero-out the impact of this initial relaxation.

In conclusion, when using a streaming graph partitioning algorithm to generate emergency shelter assignments, one should not overlook the utility of centrality-based node orderings, which in certain circumstances could significantly improve outcome measures. After designing the larger gears of a streaming assignment algorithm, one might look to node orderings to bolster desired outcomes.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

This research has identified mobility as a catalyst for reuniting social acquaintances at shelters. At the urban scale, as people leave their homes and become mobile, an opportunity arises to (re)route people to recommended emergency shelters. Upon arriving at these shelters, people may further self-organise, not once but multiple times throughout their stay. Drawing upon shared experiences that span to the present moment, the communication/support that ensues can take on different forms, e.g., verbal or non-verbal, individual or collective, problem-focused or emotional-focused, etc. This support is not necessarily better or worse than (nor mutually exclusive from) other support available at shelters—the claim is only that having access to one’s social networks is beneficial, and reunification brings this about in a unique manner.

As mobility is a catalyst for reunification, so too does mobility add complexity to the reunification problem, challenging the adoption of graph or hypergraph partitioning in its most basic form. Supplied with contextually relevant data, the most well cited partitioner, the static graph partitioner METIS, can preserve network structure within shelters by minimising the number of social connections split across shelters (edges cut) while simultaneously distributing people roughly evenly (k -way partitioning) or unevenly (via “target partition weights”) in accordance with shelter occupancies. That said, reunification is not a static problem nor is preserving social connections always of central importance; methods for reunification must account for an unfolding series of experiences that together comprise displacement. Drawing from the greater narrative, the research focuses on how travel to shelters impacts what is socially achievable at shelters. This positions the research to refine the partitioning problem—its objectives and methods—while also orienting the study toward exploring what is both elemental and foundational, how to increase the presence (and decrease the absence) of social connections at emergency shelters.

Turning to a summary of Part 1, a social objective may become more appealing when integrated with other objectives. Indeed, the research acknowledges value in minimising travel time to shelters. Without knowing whether this “nearest” objective is preferable to a “social” objective, and to not exclude the possibility that both are important to some degree, the research examines *sensible* best- and worst-case scenarios for each objective, functioning individually and in combination. The results frame what would happen (i.e., the status quo) as well as what could happen (i.e., what to strive for with real-time interventions). As for combining the

objectives, while one could approach this in various ways,¹¹¹ the decision to initially make “social” a primary and “nearest” a secondary objective not only reduced the number of simulations (examining a singular social objective becomes redundant) but made for an intuitive experimental design with respect to examining and ultimately demonstrating synergies between the combined objectives. That said, what remains difficult to evaluate is how displaced people would perceive the trade-off between the individual and combined objectives. Context is important here.

The research conducted large-scale evacuation simulations specific to the greater Portland, Oregon area. These simulations combined time-stamped data of where each person is located every second of the day (data originally designed for infectious disease modelling at VBI) with each person’s probability of requiring shelter from a magnitude 6.8 earthquake along the Portland Hills reverse-slip fault (simulated by this research using HAZUS-MH). This information was integrated with Red Cross shelter data (from the American Red Cross), roadway data (from Open Street Maps), and census data (from the United States Census Bureau) to model random shelter assignments (formulated as a multiple-knapsack problem), nearest shelter assignments (formulated as a capacitated p -median problem), and social–nearest shelter assignments (formulated as a combined hypergraph partitioning problem and capacitated p -median problem). Travel times were calculated using ABMs (simulated by this research using MATSim). Against this backdrop, the average travel time to shelters would fall somewhere between 2 hours and 2 hours and 40 minutes, and without any social consideration, the average percentage of social connections preserved would fall between 1% and 4%. Framing what is possible, the use of social–nearest shelter assignments (where again, “social” is the primary objective) results in an average travel time of roughly 2 hours and 16 minutes with approximately 72% of social connections preserved.

Shifting from a macro- to micro-level presentation of the results, the research steps into the simulation and follows a single family throughout a typical day. With the introduction of the earthquake, the trajectory of this day abruptly changes. The family is presented with a choice, specifically to visit either a social–nearest or nearest shelter. By reflecting on this family’s story—their circumstance and how it influenced their evacuation decisions—the research exemplifies an ongoing “design process,” where a method designed and operating at a “high level” of abstraction is held accountable to the interests of real people in concrete

¹¹¹ For example, one could develop a multi-objective “weight function” (see Armenatzoglou et al., 2015).

instances (or more accurately, held accountable to a “lower level” of abstraction).¹¹² To borrow the constructivist view of Schön (1992; see also Dorst & Dijkhuis, 1999; Ralph, 2010), the research engages in a “reflective conversation with the situation.” Upon bringing into play the identities of displaced people and who is connected with whom, and reflecting upon their journey before and during an evacuation, the research asks the question (as a self-critique), to what extent does this level of situational descriptiveness/awareness change the current interpretation of a successful intervention? Such inquiry has informed the latest iteration of the “Portland Study” (Chapter 2), expanding its scope to include the non-social objective of minimising travel time. The decision to present this design process as an afterword (Chapter 3) speaks to its ongoing role: to expand and/or refine the proposed objectives in future work.

What should become clear is that one can always integrate travel time into the objective function; however, its importance will change with every situation, i.e., on a family-by-family, disaster-by-disaster basis. Although the research is not well-advised to comment on how families make decisions in extraordinary circumstances—whether rationally or emotionally, individually or collectively, maximising utility or minimising regret, etc.—the research can nevertheless sketch and rehearse different circumstances upon which decisions are made. These circumstances include how shelter recommendations are presented to the public. While in Chapter 3 this research presented a family with choices of simulated outcomes (social-nearest and nearest shelter assignments), one might in practice want to present choices upfront, as customisable inputs. A registration process that identifies what people value across a range of evacuation scenarios has the potential (depending on how these scenarios map onto reality) to unburden people of choices during an evacuation and, moreover, improve solution quality. A registration process also holds a mirror to the problem and proposed solutions, which is a non-neutral act (see Glückler & Panitz, 2021). This might be the first time a family has reflected upon what could happen to them and who is important to them. In turn, this may prompt people to set aside money for a hotel or devise a plan to stay with friends or family—this too is a form of customisation that recontextualises the proposed objectives.

Working against the contours of what is socially achievable are not only counter objectives but methodological hurdles. With respect to the latter, solving a partitioning problem is not only difficult (being NP-complete), but one must solve this problem with a limited, albeit growing view of who requires shelter. If one were to immediately and directly pass shelter

¹¹² Keep in mind that all models, to use the words of Hedström and Swedberg (1996), “by their very nature distort the reality they are intended to describe.”

requests to a partitioner, this would amount to solving a streaming graph or hypergraph partitioning problem. However, to not oversimplify the sequence of events, instead of immediately generating shelter assignments, one might exploit a time delay between when people request shelter and when they depart for shelter. In a similar vein, as not to conflate data collected with data partitioned (i.e., data associated with people versus data representing people), one might find other uses for shelter requests, such as verifying and/or informing predictions of who eventually requires shelter. When a prediction becomes the subject of partitioning, one benefits from a global view of the data—those who already requested, are requesting, and might request shelter. In turn, if one disseminates predicted shelter assignments in a streaming manner, i.e., only to those who are ready to depart, then people will continue to make shelter requests, and this source of data will continue to verify and/or inform predictions.

To interface with this context on all counts, Part 2 of this research generalises the problem: assigning people to socially oriented shelters is a graph or hypergraph partitioning problem operating specifically within a batch/window, where the batch/window size with respect to people who have yet to receive a shelter assignment could include one person or a group of people (potentially an entire population) who need and/or might need shelter. Batch processing is one of several partitioning “features” (i.e., parameters or constraints) categorised within Chapter 4 as relevant to the context at hand. This chapter moreover identifies several other partitioning features which if brought together would contribute to a single, adaptable partitioning algorithm. Stemming from this analysis, and considering the performance of candidate partitioners, the research selects the partitioner, restreaming FENNEL, and reviews how to extend it in preparation for the strategies and experiments that follow.

Different shelter assignment strategies could have different strengths or weaknesses depending on the underlying evacuation context. Even within a single evacuation, what is known about the evacuating population changes over time. This gives rise to a simple idea: perhaps certain strategies excel early and others late during an evacuation. In Chapter 5, synergies between sequentially deployed strategies are explored. The research presents three unique strategies—the static prediction strategy, the real-time batch strategy, and the dynamic prediction strategy—and then evaluates the performance of a shelter assignment algorithm that switches from the static prediction strategy to (1) the real-time batch strategy and (2) the dynamic prediction strategy at different percentages of the evacuation being complete subject to the static prediction strategy being inaccurate in different ways and to different extents. The results suggest that sequentially deploying these strategies can improve outcome measures above and beyond any one strategy acting alone, particularly when switching from the static

prediction strategy to the real-time batch strategy. The results also show that the dynamic prediction strategy nearly always outperforms all other strategies. Nevertheless, without conducting experiments across a wide range of scenarios, the inherent robustness of the real-time batch strategy (as a standalone or “switched to” strategy) speaks to a more readily implementable approach. The dynamic prediction strategy, particularly after extending it to handle response bias, has the potential to greatly improve outcomes and is most deserving of future work.

As people request shelter assignments and depart for them in a sequential manner, the social composition at shelters begins to reveal itself, and so too can one use this information to carefully time when strategies are deployed. In Chapter 6, the research steps within the presented strategies and questions whether the order/sequence of nodes (representing people) affects outcome measures when the partitioner, restreaming FENNEL, does not have time to converge on a best solution. Keeping in mind that one can rearrange nodes within a batch, the research introduces and tests 115 centrality-based node ordering schemes and finds instances where outcome measures are significantly affected, both adversely and favourably. Of notable interest, the greatest benefit lies not with preserving more social connections but with improving partitioning imbalance. In other words, while partitioning is typically understood as minimising the fraction of edges cut subject to not exceeding a specified partitioning imbalance (see Walshaw, 2023), this research also finds value in reversing the objective and constraint, i.e., minimising partitioning imbalance subject to not exceeding a specified fraction of edges cut.

Beyond methodological opportunities gleaned via examining the requisite background material, this research also introduces a new procedural perspective: shelter assignments should never be random. When a partitioner must break social connections, other social connections should take their place, and if not social connections, then some other criteria guiding people to more suitable emergency shelters. In Part 1, social connections are partitioned alongside “nearest” shelter connections. If a person were not acquainted with anyone seeking shelter, then this person would *almost* always be assigned to their nearest shelter. Even here, had that research enriched the network with connections representing second nearest and third nearest shelters, back-ups of back-ups, fewer people would have received a random shelter assignment. Part 2 approaches randomness differently. If one notices more random shelter assignments early in the evacuation than late in the evacuation, this is a telltale sign that one is generating assignments with a limited view of who requires shelter. The research responds with probability-based strategies (see Chapter 5): if one can predict with some degree of accuracy

who requires shelter, then the partitioner would have access to more connections at once and, with more degrees of freedom, cut fewer of these connections. That said, even if one has access to all connections at once, a restreaming partitioner may not have time to restream, i.e., to iteratively adjust assignments. The research responds with centrality-based node ordering schemes (see Chapter 6). These ordering schemes do not lessen the number of random assignments, nor do they function predictively. In theory, they operate by examining the network structure and selecting nodes/people, which if assigned to shelters early in the stream result in better assignments late in the stream.

In conclusion, having demonstrated several ways to preserve social connections at emergency shelters, a logical next step is to prioritise which social connections are most important. One can also extend this research to other contexts, e.g., the refugee crisis. In a space, such as an emergency shelter or refugee camp, where one cannot altogether “disconnect” from others, shelter assignments would permit some control or choice over the human landscape.

Future Work

Fostering a positive social experience at emergency shelters involves not only designing an algorithm that partitions social networks but also—as if one were optimising a “guestlist” for each partition/shelter—an algorithm that considers social interactions between acquaintances and non-acquaintances alike. Indeed, while this research has focused on preserving connections between people with long-standing histories, one might question what role new relationships play within shelters—are they a source of comfort or discomfort? For the non-acquainted, voluntary individual-to-individual, individual-to-group, and group-to-group interactions could manifest differently. Certain groups/communities might be more accepting of strangers, or perhaps strangers are more accepting of each other.

One has some control over non-acquainted interactions. By making shelters partially reservable, for example, one could adjust the ratio between evacuees who are more socially connected (those who reserved space at a shelter) and evacuees who are less socially connected (those who did not reserve space). Contributing to the effectiveness of this concept, and as a consideration in its own right, one should recognise that different partitioning methods could produce the same overall, inter-partitioning results while also producing very different compositions of people within each shelter (intra-partitioning results). For example, “spectral partitioning tends to produce bisections with very different degree distributions, usually with one densely connected partition containing nodes of high degree and the other with low degree

nodes that were successively ‘trimmed’ away from the first partition” (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013). Other partitioning methods tend to create partitions that are structurally more similar, e.g., FENNEL. One could alternatively modify a partitioner’s objective function to gain control over non-acquainted interactions.¹¹³ All these techniques of course beg a sociological investigation into what shelter interactions are desirable.

With finer granularity, people are not simply acquainted or not acquainted; relationships between acquaintances are often hierarchical. Before even asking people which social connections they prioritise, the network structure may provide clues. For example, when a person’s social network is split across two or more emergency shelters, one could argue that the best shelter assignment, particularly early in the evacuation, is the shelter containing the most “central” members of this person’s social network (i.e., according to one or more centrality indices). From a slightly different perspective, perhaps the best shelter assignment considers acquaintances who have the strongest propensity to form a community. Having edge weights reflect such a propensity is a common pre-processing step to enhance community detection (see Berry et al., 2011; Cao et al., 2016; Kakisim & Sogukpinar, 2017; Khadivi et al., 2011; Lai et al., 2010; Li et al., 2018; Long, 2019; Lu et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2015; Xiang et al., 2016; Zhang, 2015). This step might work equally well to enhance community formation during partitioning.

Apart from encouraging the formation of communities, one could have people “tag” communities and rate them—e.g., according to a Likert scale or visual analogue scale—so that communities represented within shelters are meaningful ones. A tag-aware recommendation system could assist in this respect. Furthermore, when certain tags are overly general, such as when they represent a religion as opposed to a religious denomination or a specific place of worship, one could employ a query-dependent variant of the community-detection problem known as *community search*, for example, to identify tagged communities bound by a distance constraint (Fang et al., 2020; Sozio & Gionis, 2010).

Another interesting direction for future work is to treat tagged communities as distinct layers in a *multiplex network*, i.e., “where the same set of nodes is represented in every layer, although the interaction between nodes might be different in each one” (Aleta & Moreno, 2019).¹¹⁴ The problem with layers being aggregated into a single, monoplex network is that

¹¹³ For example, if one knows the size of emergency shelters (i.e., their target occupancies) and can determine the size of communities requiring shelter, then one could in theory organise communities across shelters such that specified unoccupied space would remain within shelters for people who lack group affiliations.

¹¹⁴ To review the distinction between multiplex, multi-layer, and multi-view networks, please see Cruickshank (2020; see also Teng et al., 2021).

“this merging creates a new network with its own topology, and loses the topological features of the individual layers. This new topology is logically biased toward the initial topology of the denser layers (Pio-Lopez et al., 2021). On the contrary, when layers are kept distinct, one could perform community detection with greater discernment (Huang et al., 2021; Magnani et al., 2021). One could moreover identify layers that are redundant (in terms of people or their associated resources) and/or otherwise adversarial in bringing about desirable partitions. With respect to the latter, to guide how much weight/value one should ascribe to each layer, one might ask people during the registration process how they personally would resolve scenarios where several of their communities are vying for inclusion within a shelter. Would they prefer access to a certain community at the expense of several other communities? Complicating this matter, one might find that the combined value of multiple communities is greater than or less than the sum of their parts.

Alongside measuring community representation within shelters (which should not be confused with community detection within shelters), the research proposes several other novel measures of success in Appendix E, including the “aloneness” metric, the “rather be somewhere else” metric, and the “predicted together metric.” These measures further prompt a discussion not only into additional network factors that may contribute to success, e.g., measures of trust, cooperation, negative relationships, anti-communities, bonding social capital, bridging social capital, strong ties, weak ties, etc., but additional ethical considerations as well, e.g., concerns over self-segregation and deductive disclosure.

While future research could always prioritise social connections with greater and greater nuance, one could also take the research in a different direction. In fact, does one even need social network data to achieve desirable social outcomes? Perhaps a partitioning method based solely on minimising spatial proximities between people’s homes, for example, would result in an acceptable level of social network preservation. Not to be confused with nearest shelter assignments (see Part 1), this research has not examined shelter assignments based on people who live near each other.¹¹⁵

Turning the socio-spatial relationship upside down, what if one could recreate the existing “urban layout” of social networks within emergency shelters? While this is certainly an abstract concept, one should consider the challenge of finding members of one’s social

¹¹⁵ For literature about physical distances between social acquaintances, please see Appendix D. Additionally, instead of using a continuous distance function, one could use publicly available information to define nested contiguous regions (i.e., spatially constrained clusters) where shared experiences likely arise. One would then ascribe a weight to each region.

network among thousands of people within a stadium-sized emergency shelter. A potential solution is to spatially subdivide people within shelters by neighbourhood affiliation or into social clusters. With greater precision, as sleeping cots are often arranged into regular grids, one could map social networks onto these grids, where the goal is to minimise the physical distance between connected individuals or communities. This is closely related to the facility layout problem (Carrizosa et al., 2017, 2018; Jankovits et al., 2011) as well as certain graph visualisation/drawing techniques (see Appendix H).

To shift the context slightly, this socio-spatial mapping might also facilitate greater access to social connections within internally displaced people (IDP) camps. By way of example, in Haiti after the 2010 earthquake, makeshift tent cities emerged throughout the capital of Port-au-Prince. In an effort to relocate people from overcrowded camps (Senat & Belvert, 2017) and to reclaim both private and public land, the Haitian government (at the request of the United States) constructed “formal” or “regulated” camps on the outskirts of the city (Corbet, 2016). Despite the physical infrastructure and services provided, these formal camps lacked social infrastructure. One such camp, Corail Cesselesse, epitomised the problem:

The case of Corail is an example of a camp whose planning forgot social dynamics. It shows how a humanitarian perspective, that ignores displaced people as social and political subjects, is at odds with their aspirations. Humanitarian principles are applied at the expense of the social context: as if displaced people, just like the camp itself, are a-historic. This approach has deprived Corail’s IDPs of their life histories, their networks, and their ability to participate or to resist. (Corbet, 2016)

Insofar as large-scale IDP camps are planned, mapping social networks onto their spatial layouts may contribute beneficially to the initial state of social interactions, i.e., irrespective of the many possible futures intended (or not intended) for these camps.

Another contextual extension for this work is the refugee crisis. According to the Global Compact on Refugees (High Commissioner for Refugees, 2018), “There is an urgent need for more equitable sharing of the burden and responsibility for hosting and supporting the world’s refugees, while taking account of existing contributions and the differing capacities and resources among States.” To couch future research within this vision, reuniting not only families (Office of the High Commissioner on Human Rights, 2018) but people with long-standing histories outside their state of origin would present itself—again, with emphasis on shared responsibility, even if allocated disproportionately—as a streaming graph or hypergraph partitioning problem. The reason why more familiar clustering algorithms are contextually unsuitable is that the states hosting the greatest number of refugees, who are already making

“an immense contribution from their own limited resources to the collective good, and indeed to the cause of humanity” (High Commissioner for Refugees, 2018) would receive an inordinate number of refugees, exacerbating real and perceived burdens, which could for example “[affect] their own social and economic cohesion and development” (United Nations General Assembly, 2016) and result, politically speaking, in a reversal of sustained goodwill.¹¹⁶ To the contrary, the “key objective of the global compact is to ease pressures, particularly for low- and middle-income countries” (High Commissioner for Refugees, 2018). That said, clustering could still play a role *within* partitions (where partitions now represent states, not emergency shelters). Indeed, one might find greater trust and cooperation between refugees when they are grouped within many small socio-spatial clusters/neighbourhoods (see Macy & Skvoretz, 1998), a tactic that may also prevent (or not aggravate) resource scarcity and may reduce cultural friction between refugees and their host states as well as between refugees themselves.

One should also not trivialise the challenges of addressing many different actors who have unique and perhaps conflicting interests. For example, the criteria used to determine how many refugees each state should host, i.e., defining “target partition weights,” would undoubtedly become a contentious matter. In this vein, monetary distributions might become a necessary instrument to increase a state’s hosting capacity as well as incentivise (without mandating) refugee compliance. Another way to potentially improve compliance is to present refugees with multiple recommendations as to who will host them. This would add complexity to the partitioning problem and may require a fluid, “streaming” adaptation of incentives. Conflicting interests may also give rise to darker narratives. For example, while data protection is always a very serious matter, one can too easily imagine how refugees, and potentially those who assist them, could have their human rights limited or infringed upon if location-based information on refugees (e.g., their routes or assigned destinations) were improperly stored or shared, or not permanently and irreversibly anonymised (see OHCHR, 2018).

With refugees travelling hundreds if not thousands of miles, future research might also explore how to improve social dynamics en route to destinations. This would complement the future work already presented—if people are travelling from a similar origin to the same destination (due to a socially oriented recommendation), then they may also travel along similar paths. However, one could fortify this idea and take it much further. Applying Least Cost Path

¹¹⁶ Please also note that refugees can contribute economic and social wealth to those hosting them. “They can help to respond to demographic trends, labour shortages and other challenges in host societies, and add fresh skills and dynamism to the latter’s economies” (United Nations General Assembly, 2016).

(LCP) analysis (Herzog, 2016, 2020; Verhagen et al., 2019) to the refugee context, one could identify routes that not only minimise travel time (see Herzog, 2020) but routes where one's first or second language is spoken, where the distances between towns is minimised (i.e., where food and medicine are available), where cellphone service is dependable (to stay connected with loved ones), and/or where more strenuous and treacherous terrain is avoided (see Herzog, 2020), perhaps during certain times of the year. Refugees might also prefer to bypass areas with high crime rates and/or areas with steep gradients, where the risk of injury from falling is greater (see Sheehan & Gottschall, 2012). With respect to gradients, routes that best minimise pedestrian metabolic energy expenditure (Minetti et al., 2002) may differ from routes that best accommodate pushing a stroller or wheelchair, or more generally routes travelled with a cart (Herzog, 2010; Verhagen et al., 2019; see also Llobera & Sluckin, 2007).

To conduct LCP analysis on a street network, one could multiply the distance (i.e., base cost) associated with each street/edge by a "friction cost" (see Pingel, 2010), where the latter represents a combination of factors, including dynamic and anisotropic factors, that affect refugee mobility at a general, cultural, and personal level.¹¹⁷ One then runs Dijkstra's algorithm (Dijkstra, 1959) or the A* search algorithm (Hart et al., 1968) over this constructed network to find a least-cost path. The problem becomes more difficult when introducing multimodal route planning and schedule-based transport (see Bast et al., 2016), particularly if the goal is for refugees to make the greatest headway possible, either in terms of distance or obstacles overcome (e.g., crossing political or natural borders) given monetary constraints.

The refugee crisis deserves a coherent and comprehensive response. Tightly interwoven paths that span countries of origin, transit, and destination, where shared histories between people are perpetuated across time and place, could have a positive and profound impact on refugees. In coordination with the international community, one could responsibly facilitate this experience with technology that is itself borderless.

¹¹⁷ Following Verhagen et al. (2019), one could combine factors using multi-criteria analysis (MCA). As for a less obvious example of an anisotropic factor (c.f., Minetti et al., 2002), one might define the travel cost toward a town to be less than the travel cost away from a town. The assumption here is that after acquiring resources within a town, one's initial attraction to it may no longer apply.

Appendix A

Emergency Shelter Reunification Visualiser

Software is developed that visualises displaced people being assigned to emergency shelters in a streaming manner. One can load shelter assignments generated from any graph or hypergraph partitioner. Alternatively, the software can generate assignments using the graph partitioner METIS. One can additionally load a file specifying the order in which people are assigned to shelters (or have the software generate a random order). The primary output is a video file.

Videos created using this software display a partitioned screen, where each partition corresponds to a different emergency shelter. Displaced people are depicted as nodes, and if they know someone within their partition/shelter, then an edge is drawn connecting them. As nodes enter the screen, they initially appear large in size and then, over several frames, they shrink to a uniform dimension. These larger nodes draw attention to where changes are occurring to the network layout. Indeed, the network is not only growing, but the layout is constantly adapting in response. Real-time network “readability” is maintained, for example, by minimising the number of crossed edges and by keeping connected nodes close together. The research also improves readability by utilising the full space allotted to each partition; over the duration of the video, the camera within each partition “zooms out” to always keep the growing network tightly framed.

The contribution of this software extends to visualising edge cuts (EC) in a novel way. After a node enters the screen and edges are drawn, the visualiser begins drawing these cut or disconnected edges. They are depicted as “whiskers” emanating from the node that just entered the screen. While all nodes within a partition share the same colour, located at the end of these whiskers are very small nodes with different colours. These colours correspond to nodes in other partitions, i.e., acquaintances in other shelters.

The software is also equipped with another visualisation scheme/mode, namely, to colour nodes according to community affiliation. The software searches for communities using Infomap (Edler et al., 2023) and/or OSLOM2 (Lancichinetti et al., 2011). Nodes belonging to more than one community are drawn as circles, but instead of assuming a solid fill, their appearance resembles that of a pie chart with coloured sectors (see Gabardo, 2018; see also Sheikholeslami & Giannakis, 2018). Given a finite palette of distinct colours, the software

furthermore maximises the colour difference between spatially adjacent communities (see Gansner et al., 2010).¹¹⁸

As the presented software serves as introductory material—helping to communicate from the outset what the research intends to explore in subsequent chapters—a graphical user interface (GUI) is developed. The GUI makes liberal use of tooltips, which if hovered over, explain what different parameters mean for the evacuation context (see Figure A1, Figure A2, Figure A3, Figure A4, Figure A5, Figure A6, Figure A7, Figure A8, Figure A9, Figure A10, and Figure A11).

¹¹⁸ The software offers a choice between two simple, pre-defined colour palettes. One could alternatively create colour palates, where the number of colours corresponds to the number of detected communities and where the colours are themselves maximally distinct (e.g., Larsson, 2018).

Figure A1

Figure A2

Figure A3

Emergency Shelter Reunification Visualizer: /home/esrv/example/output

Emergency Shelter Reunification Visualizer

Open Project Wizard

Input Data
Identify a social network. A social network is comprised of nodes, which represent people, and edges, which represent a connection between people. Another name for "network" is "graph". After identifying a social network, please proceed to the sidebar, where one can adjust properties and/or run the simulation.

Input Graph
Graph File Path
Graph Format

Advanced Options

Input Node Order
Node Order File Path
Node Order Random Seed

Input Nodes to Ignore
Nodes to Ignore File Path

Input Node Labels
Node Labels File Path

If "new project" was selected, please identify a social network. The social network may contain weighted edges. This means that one can ascribe a relative social affinity to each social connection. *Format: Please use either METIS, edge list or GML and specify this format in the drop-down box below. Weights must be positive integers.*

Figure A4

The screenshot shows the 'Emergency Shelter Reunification Visualizer' interface. The main window title is 'Emergency Shelter Reunification Visualizer: /home/esrv/example/output'. The interface is divided into several sections:

- Partitioning:** Includes a description: 'Specify how people are assigned to emergency shelters. In this visualizer, emergency shelters are represented as partitions. Assigning people to shelters while minimizing the number of connections lost (as one objective) can be thought of as a graph partitioning problem.' It features a 'Partitioning Method' dropdown set to 'METIS assignments', an 'Assignments File Path' field with a 'Browse...' button, and a 'Number of Partitions' slider set to 4.
- Advanced Options:** Contains a 'Partitioning Properties' section with a 'Partitioning Imbalance' dropdown set to '1%' and a 'Minimize' dropdown set to 'edges cut'. Below this is a 'Partition Weights' field containing '0.25,0.25,0.25,0.25' and a 'Visible Partitions' field containing '0,1,2,3'. A 'Partitioning Random Seed' field contains '627957' and a 'Generates Seed' checkbox.

Five callout boxes provide detailed explanations for specific options:

- Callout 1:** Explains the 'METIS assignments' option, stating it visualizes preserving displaced people's social networks at emergency shelters. It also mentions the 'random assignments' and 'Hamilton apportionment' methods for determining the number of people assigned to shelters.
- Callout 2:** States 'Specify the number of emergency shelters.' pointing to the 'Number of Partitions' slider.
- Callout 3:** Explains that allowing some leeway with partition sizes (shelter occupancies) might allow for better partitioning performance.
- Callout 4:** Explains that the 'edges cut' option attempts to minimize the number of separated people (connections lost) to minimize the number of shelters people would need to contact.
- Callout 5:** States 'Shelters might have different recommended occupancies. Set the relative occupancies here.' pointing to the 'Partition Weights' field.

Figure A5

Figure A6

Figure A7

The screenshot shows the 'Emergency Shelter Reunification Visualizer' application window. The title bar reads 'Emergency Shelter Reunification Visualizer' and the address bar shows 'Open Project Wizard'. The interface is divided into several sections:

- Layout & Color:** Contains sliders for 'Force (LinLog only)' (set to 3), 'Attraction Factor' (0.012), 'Repulsion Factor' (0.048), and 'Number of Iterations' (20). It also has a 'Layout Random Seed' field with the value '161336' and a 'Generate Seed' button.
- Color Properties:** Includes a 'Color Scheme' dropdown set to 'pastel colors', a 'Color Random Seed' field with '448526', and a 'Generate Seed' button. Below are 'Single Node Color' (hex #777777), 'Border Color' (hex #d4d4d4), and 'Background Color' (hex #ffffff), each with a 'Pick Color' button.
- Node & Edge Properties:** Features a 'Node Size Mode' dropdown set to 'highlight new', a 'Fixed Edge Size' dropdown set to '1 pixel', and 'Minimum Edge Size' and 'Maximum Edge Size' fields both set to '1 pixel'. It also includes 'Node Size Mode' (set to 'highlight new'), 'Fixed Node Size' (10 pixels), 'Minimum Node Size' (20 pixels), and 'Maximum Node Size' (60 pixels). There are 'Label Node Type' and 'Label Size' (10 pixels) dropdowns, and a 'Cut Edge Node Size' field (10 pixels) with a note 'Only available with visualize cut edges mode'. A 'Cut Edge Percentage of Length' slider is set to 50%, and there is a 'Show Cut Edge Labels' checkbox.
- Border Properties:** Includes 'Border Size' (1 pixel) and 'Padding' (60 pixels) fields.

Four callout boxes provide detailed explanations for specific layout options:

- SpringBox:** 'SpringBox creates a visually appealing layout. One can also experiment with LinLog, which is an energy-based model that subsumes Newman and Girvan's popular clustering measure, modularity.'
- Iterative Adaptation:** 'As each node enters the screen, the layout must adapt. This is accomplished by iteratively applying repulsion and attraction forces between nodes. A greater number of iterations allows node positions to settle into a state of equilibrium.'
- Iterative Adaptation (repeated):** 'As each node enters the screen, the layout must adapt. This is accomplished by iteratively applying repulsion and attraction forces between nodes. A greater number of iterations allows node positions to settle into a state of equilibrium.'
- Highlight New:** 'The "highlight new" option directs the eye to the last node entering the screen. This node becomes smaller over time, eventually adopting a specified node size. The "degree centrality" option creates a gradient of node sizes that correspond to the number of edges incident upon a node.'

Figure A8

Figure A9

Figure A11

Appendix B

Context-Specific Apportionment Method

Historically, apportionment is solved by first determining how many people each person elected to Congress represents. This is achieved by dividing the aggregated U.S. population by the total number of seats to be apportioned, resulting in what is called the standard divisor. One then divides each state's population by the standard divisor to determine the required number of representatives. The resulting nonnegative numbers are known as the *standard quota*, which is oftentimes comprised of fractional parts. Rounding a quota down (i.e., applying a floor function) results in what is called the *lower quota* whereas rounding a quota up (i.e., applying a ceiling function) results in the *upper quota*. At this point, numerous apportionment methods have been proposed to fairly resolve these fractional parts. The first method adopted by the House is known as the Hamilton method, which keeps each quotient's whole number and drops the fraction. This typically produces a surplus of congressional seats, which are then allocated one at a time to states with the largest fractions. Other methods, for example, might also drop the fraction (Jefferson method, also known as d'Hondt method), round to the nearest whole number (Webster method), or round at the geometric mean (Huntington–Hill method), followed by iteratively modifying the standard divisor up or down until the quotas add to the correct total number of apportioned seats. A rich history of the political and mathematical conversations that accompany congressional apportionment methods, both those adopted by Congress and those that remain purely speculative, is presented by Belinski and Young (2001; first published in 1982). These mathematicians have furthermore injected their own analysis into this history, including a proof of impossibility, whereby if a quota rule is enforced (this is where the standard quota can neither deviate above the upper quota or below the lower quota), then commonsense paradoxes arise, including what has been termed the Alabama paradox, the population paradox and the new state paradox (Belinski & Young, 2001). Conversely, if these paradoxes do not exist, then an apportionment method must violate the quota rule.

With the quota rule in place, congressional apportionment is cast, methodologically speaking, as a more precise rounding problem than stratified sampling. These two implementations that involve rounding are further supported by the more general literature on controlled rounding (Cox, 1987; Goodman & Kish, 1950). Indeed, generating tables that contain only multiples of a given rounding base that perturb, aggregate, and simplify data while simultaneously ensuring tabular additivity has a range of applications; this generalised rounding problem is most heavily cited in the context of protecting data confidentiality

(Salazar-González et al., 2004). Closer to the task at hand, the creation of artificial populations, as used for microsimulations, also struggles with integration. The infectious disease model acquired for this research utilises an iterative proportional fitting (IPF) technique to generate artificial sets of individuals and households by first estimating a joint distribution based on disaggregated (relatively small but very representative) PUMS microdata samples along with aggregated summary tables from the U.S. Census Bureau. As one cannot run an agent-based model with fractions of agents, one must then integerise the fitted data before selecting a representative population, which is not a straightforward process (Choupani & Mamdoohi, 2016; Lovelace & Ballas, 2013). The acquired infectious disease model (generated by TRANSIMS) overcomes the integerisation problem in a nondeterministic manner, by selecting N agents using Monte Carlo draws (Pritchard & Miller, 2011). Other methods to generate synthetic microdata include combinatorial optimisation (Williamson et al., 1998) and Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulations (Farooq et al., 2013; for a recent overview see Ye et al., 2016); these methods are probabilistic and thereby avoid the problem of integerisation. One should also note that certain large-scale simulations, such as the SimBritian model, handle population synthesis and integerisation deterministically (Ballas et al., 2005). Deviating from the presented literature, the problem this research faces is not fitting microdata to aggregated data but, very much the opposite, associating aggregated data (probabilities of displacement by census tract) with acquired microdata (individual households).

With the above literature pointing to unavoidable subjectivity pertaining to nuances in allocating a sample population, this research capitalised on this fact and used integerisation as a means to slightly bias the selection process toward increasing or exaggerating displacement within household income brackets that already contribute to the largest numbers of displaced people. In the case where the vast majority of people within census tracts fall within one or two household income brackets (leaving small or nonexistent populations within the remaining brackets), a simple rounding procedure applied indiscriminately would intuitively over-select “rarely” displaced people. In turn, if people from similar household income brackets live in close proximity to one another, then this simple rounding would lead to more geographically scattered or, more precise, less densely displaced populations; indeed, such a rounding method seems counterintuitive, as one might expect dense clusters of displacement, i.e., from shared residencies collapsing or certain city blocks receiving extensive damage. Thereby, the approach taken by this research is to conform with existing methodologies insofar that a consensus has emerged regarding best practice; deterministically, this is exemplified by finding the standard quota. However, where there is room for interpretation, as with integerisation (found in the

later steps of apportionment as well as in stratified sampling and iterative proportional fitting), an opportunity exists to subtly alter the selection process to better conform, albeit subjectively, with the given context and expectations of where displaced people might emerge.

The above literature can inform a method for selecting people requiring emergency shelters. Unlike with an apportionment method, the total number of people requiring shelter within each census tract (equivalent to the total number of congressional representatives) must not simply represent the number of people within each household income bracket (equivalent to each state) but must also represent the probability of those people requiring shelter. To accomplish this feat, the “standard quota” is slightly altered to identify a representative number of people within each household income bracket according to each individual’s probability of requiring temporary shelter *with replacement*. The second step is to honour the actual number of displaced people within each household income bracket by correcting for any over-selection; an iterative process for “re-apportioning” over-selected people is proposed.

As the method for selecting a synthetic population borrows from multiple literary tracks, the language used here will be generalised. Instead of finding the standard quota by dividing the aggregated population by the standard divisor, the equation can be simplified by taking the reciprocal (multiplicative inverse) of the standard divisor and then multiplying by the aggregated population. The reciprocal of the standard divisor can be thought of as a “scaling factor,” which sets the stage for a language and logic more common to transportation modelling. For each census tract, given the five household income brackets, A , B , C , D , and E , the scaling factor S can be calculated as follows:

$$S = \frac{T}{(x_A \times y_A) + (x_B \times y_B) + (x_C \times y_C) + (x_D \times y_D) + (x_E \times y_E)}$$

where T is the total number of people requiring shelter, x_i is the number of people within income bracket i , and y_i is the probability of someone in income bracket i requiring temporary shelter. Note that the probability of someone within each of the respective income brackets requiring temporary shelter is represented by a modification factor as described within the HAZUS literature. Using the scaling factor S , one can calculate the number of people requiring temporary shelter within household income bracket i via the expression $S \times x_i \times y_i$.

If a population calculation does not yield an integer, then one might proceed by truncating the result, i.e., by taking the lower quota. The sum of all the fractional parts should total to a whole number, and the task then becomes to assign the individual units that comprise that whole number to one or more of the household income brackets. One approach can be easily understood by analogy. One can imagine a racetrack where five people (each

representing a household income bracket) are about to race one another. However, the people racing will not have a common starting point; the racers will be staggered along the track (each person will begin the race at a certain percentage of a full lap, one that corresponds with the fractional part of the above results). Each person will also travel at a different constant speed (i.e., set proportional to the above ratio). Under these conditions, whoever completes a lap first will receive an award (one of the discrete units). One should note that a possibility arises that someone travelling slowly might complete a lap before someone travelling fast, that is, if the starting point is biased in favour of the slow racer.

Considering the remaining lap distance and the rate of travel for each person, one can calculate who will complete a lap first. One can also calculate the position of each racer along the track at the time this occurs. These new positions are used to bias the next race. Now the person who just completed a lap has the largest disadvantage possible; however, if this person's rate of travel vastly exceeds the others, then this person might once again complete the next lap first. This process is continued until all the discrete units are awarded. A tie results in multiple discrete units being awarded or, if not enough discrete units remain, a random process resolves who won.

Taking probability into account, the above apportionment method, which essentially finds the standard quota and then uses a novel integerisation strategy, provides a relatively correct solution irrespective of potentially exceeding the actual number of displaced people within any given household income bracket. In this regard, the above formulation must be corrected. Revisiting what has been presented above with a slightly different emphasis, for each household income bracket, after multiplying the number of displaced people by their probability of requiring temporary shelter, the resulting numbers are locked into a ratio, where the sum of people across this ratio is then scaled up or down (using a scaling factor) until a target number of people requiring temporary shelter is reached. When scaling the ratio upward, the relatively correct number of people selected from each household income bracket might exceed the actual number of people available. Of course, one can only select either a subset of the displaced population or the entire displaced population as requiring temporary shelter. What this means is that after employing the above version of apportionment, if the actual number of people within any household income bracket *is exceeded*, then the excess people from all exceeded household income brackets must be "re-apportioned" using only household income brackets that still have people from which to select. With H household income brackets, this re-apportioning could occur $H - 1$ times.

For the given Portland model, roughly 75% of displaced people require temporary shelter. At such a high percentage, re-apportioning within the 412 census tracts is quite common. One should also note that even before re-apportioning, due to liberties taken with the data (where people requiring temporary shelter are interpreted as a subset of displaced people), instances arise where the number of people requiring temporary shelter must be reduced to equal the number of displaced people within a given census tract.¹¹⁹ Overall, this results in a slight drop in the total number of people requiring temporary shelter within the model, from 48,754 to 43,789 people. In other words, the target number of people requiring temporary shelter within each census tract has been reduced (in certain cases) and then refined to furthermore represent the target number of people requiring temporary shelter at the household income bracket level. With target numbers of people in mind, selecting households that contain individuals can now be described.

When generating a sample of people requiring temporary shelter, one assumption this research makes is that people within the same household will evacuate together. Thus, for each census tract, given the total number of displaced households that fall within each household income bracket, one needs to randomly select a subset of these displaced households, such that the sum of the individuals that comprise varying household sizes (as closely as possible) equals the target number of people requiring temporary shelter within each household income bracket. This can be accomplished for each census tract by taking all the households within each income bracket and then randomly placing them within a list. Each of these households is then assigned a value determined by its position within the list, where this value equals the sum of every individual in the list prior to and including the household being assigned a value. For example, if the first household in the list contains A individuals, then this household receives a value of A . If the second household contains B individuals, then this household receives a value of $A + B$. If the third household contains C individuals, then this household receives a value of $A + B + C$. This process is repeated until each household in the list is assigned a consecutive sum-total value. The next step involves finding the consecutive sum-total value in the list that most closely matches the total number of people requiring temporary shelter within each household income bracket. If the closest match lies between two values, then a coin is flipped to select one of these values. The household associated with this selected value and every household with a lower value (those earlier in the list) is categorised as requiring temporary shelter,

¹¹⁹ In such instances, there is no need to apply apportionment or re-apportionment; everyone who is displaced also requires shelter.

whereas every household with a higher value (those later in the list) is categorised as not requiring temporary shelter. This outlined approach is one of many that could be used.

Appendix C

Survey of Partitioning Methods

Relevant Work

For a graph or hypergraph partitioner to operate, one must provide a social network and specify the number of partitions. The objective is to minimise the fraction of edges cut (for graph partitioning) or the total communication volume (for hypergraph partitioning) while keeping the partitions nearly equal in size (k -way partitioning is assumed). The output includes assignments and summary statistics. When applying partitioning to the evacuation context, one must necessarily deviate from this general portrayal.

In order to avoid significantly disrupting the flow of an evacuation, one must disseminate shelter assignments, at the very latest, immediately before each person starts evacuating. Confronted with this time constraint, the social network used for partitioning is invariably incomplete: the network is either fully viewable but potentially unreliable (as when predicting who requires shelter) or reliable but not fully viewable (as when learning who requires shelter in real time). In either case, one cannot simply employ partitioning as described above. Moreover, even with an additional constraint, such as time, imposed on the partitioning problem, one can nevertheless imagine multiple ways of integrating partitioning into a shelter assignment algorithm.

A profound understanding of what happens during an evacuation, combined with a superficial understanding of partitioning (and algorithms in general), will not fully prepare one to reimagine what could transpire during an evacuation. Without specifically knowing the effectiveness of various partitioning methods, one would unlikely engineer an approach involving certain performance trade-offs, such as briefly delaying an evacuation (which unto itself is perceived as undesirable) in order to improve shelter assignments. A strong grasp of the partitioning literature could help guide how one approaches partitioning within the evacuation context. For a recent survey on advances in graph and hypergraph partitioning, please see Çatalyürek et al. (2022). What follows is a brief review of some of the more pertinent literature.

Partitioning for Distributed Graph Processing

In order to speed up calculations performed over graphs—e.g., ranking web pages, detecting communities and identifying protein associations—as well as to overcome limitations in memory capacity when dealing with massive-scale graphs, one standard practice is to distribute graph data across a cluster of commodity computers as a pre-processing step to

running parallel computations. Many distributed graph processing platforms have recently emerged: Google’s Pregel (Malewicz et al., 2010) and its open-source version, Apache Giraph (Apache Giraph, n.d.), for iterative computations on input graphs as well as GraphLab (Low et al., 2012) for machine learning applications and Microsoft’s Trinity (Shao et al., 2013) for general graph management and big-data queries, etc. All of these platforms default to using a hash function to partition graphs (Echbarth & Kheddouci, 2014), leading to balanced partitions that exhibit high communication overhead due to an essentially random vertex distribution. Fortunately, these platforms also accept custom partitioning methods that better minimise inter-machine communication cost (Echbarth & Kheddouci, 2014). For example, the second version of GraphLab (version 2.1) incorporates PowerGraph (Gonzalez et al., 2012) to better partition graphs whose edges resemble a power-law degree distribution (Gonzalez, n.d.; Low, 2013).

The trajectory and evolution of distributed graph processing platforms away from hash-based partitioning is captured in a recent survey (Soudani et al., 2019), which catalogues and expounds upon experimental comparisons between state-of-the-art approaches (Abbas et al., 2018; Guo et al., 2017; see also Batarfi et al., 2015). As another point of academic congruence, the vertex-centric programming model has become the established paradigm for distributed graph processing platforms (McCune et al., 2015; Soudani et al., 2019). This model challenges one to “think like a vertex” (TLAV; McCune et al., 2015), i.e., to assume a local view of graph structure by evaluating each vertex based on its neighbours. While Pregel was the first to implement the TLAV approach in 2010,¹²⁰ several popular frameworks have followed; apart from the platforms cited above, more recent examples include GraphX (Gonzalez et al., 2014), PowerLyra (Chen, Shi, et al., 2015), and DRONE (Wen et al., 2019).

Partitioning With Vertex Cuts and Edge Cuts

Determining what vertices represent is an important factor when choosing the most suitable distributed graph processing platform. In particular, social networks exhibit a highly skewed power-law degree distribution (Barabási & Albert, 1999; Sala et al., 2010; Wilson et al., 2009), an attribute that is conducive to vertex cuts (VC) instead of edge cuts (EC; Bourse et al., 2014; Gonzalez et al., 2012; Low, 2013). To this point, the VC model copies or replicates vertices across multiple partitions, where the goal is to minimise the number of replications. When this model is applied to graphs with power-law connectivity (e.g., social networks), the

¹²⁰ As Junghanns et al. (2017) point out, the TLAV model resembles the much older *actor-based programming model*, as introduced in Agha (1985).

intuition is that cutting a small fraction of high-degree vertices shatters these graphs (Callaway et al., 2000; Kang & Faloutsos, 2011) and thereby minimises the overall number of replications (Low, 2013; see also Lim et al., 2017). In practice, this translates into reduced communication volume (Bourse et al., 2014).

Taking hypergraph partitioning as the *beau ideal* method to reduce communication volume (Çatalyürek & Aykanat, 1999; see also Li et al., 2017; Schlag et al., 2018),¹²¹ and given that graphs cannot be modelled with the same cut properties as hypergraphs (Ihler et al., 1993),¹²² the graph-based VC model closely resembles hypergraph partitioning while being less computationally intensive (Gonzalez et al., 2012; Low, 2013). One should note that hypergraph partitioners do not traditionally cut and replicate vertices; however, the literature presents exceptions, as cutting hypergraphs and cutting vertices are not mutually exclusive partitioning strategies (Selvitopi et al., 2012).

While most distributed graph processing platforms have a distinct EC or VC orientation (such as Pregel and PowerGraph respectively), hybrid models also exist. One example is PowerLyra (Chen, Shi, et al., 2015), which tackles skewed power-law degree distributed graphs by differentiating between high- and low-degree vertices. Accordingly, high-degree vertices are partitioned with vertex cuts, leveraging PowerGraph's three-phase GAS (Gather, Apply, Scatter) model (Gonzalez et al., 2012). Low-degree vertices are partitioned using edge cuts, implementing a custom heuristic called Ginger, which is inspired by the streaming graph partitioner, FENNEL (Tsourakakis et al., 2014). Other partitioners also differentiate between high- and low-degree vertices, where the former is prioritised for replication (Mayer et al., 2018; Petroni et al., 2015; Rad & Azmi, 2017; Salihoglu & Widom, 2013; Xie et al., 2014).

Beyond edge- and vertex-centric distributed graph processing frameworks, a larger taxonomy would include component-centric, path-centric, data-centric and block-centric (Heidari et al., 2018) as well as neighbourhood-centric and graph/subgraph-centric frameworks (Kalavri et al., 2018; Rao et al., 2018).

¹²¹ Li et al. (2017) demonstrate how standard graph partitioners can partition graphs using vertex cuts instead of edge cuts by performing a graph transformation, what they call split-and-connect (SPAC), prior to partitioning. Schlag et al. (2018) follow with an evaluation of this technique in a distributed memory parallel environment. Both Li et al. (2017) and Schlag et al. (2018) found that SPAC outperformed traditional VC partitioners, such as PowerGraph, but performed worse than hypergraph partitioners. They cite hypergraph partitioners as producing the highest quality partitions, but impractically slow runtimes mar their performance.

¹²² More accurately, transforming hypergraphs into graphs with the same cut properties is not possible without using negative weighted edges (Ihler et al., 1993). When vertex cuts are not involved, Ihler et al. (1993) recommend an approximation min-cut model: one can identify cliques and assign edges within each clique a weight of $1/|u| - 1$, where $|u|$ equals the number of vertices in each clique. For an illustrative example, please see Kucar et al. (2004). Other graph-to-hypergraph approximation models exist (Agarwal et al., 2014; Alpert & Kahng, 1995; Huang et al., 2017).

Streaming Partitioning

Within the distributed graph processing literature, reducing processing latency for near real-time graph analysis is well supported by streaming graph partitioning (Abbas et al., 2018). Instead of loading a graph before partitioning, efficiency is obtained by loading and partitioning graphs in a single step. In other words, streaming graph partitioners are graph loaders (McCune, et al., 2015; Patwary et al., 2019; Stanton & Kliot, 2012); they serially read graph data from a disk onto a cluster and make permanent partition assignments upon the first examination of each vertex or edge. The motivation to implement streaming graph partitioning is best captured by Stanton and Kliot (2012):

This is a simple and effective preprocessing step for large graph computation systems, as the data must be loaded onto the cluster any way. One might need to perform full graph partitioning once the graph has been fully loaded, however, as it will be re-partitioning an already partitioned graph, there will be less communication cost and it potentially may need to move fewer vertices, and will be faster.

Keeping in mind this utility, Stanton and Kliot (2012) compared 10 different streaming graph partitioning strategies and found that a simple greedy heuristic, Linear Determinist Greedy (LDG), obtained the lowest fraction of edges cut across all tested graph datasets. Their experiments focused on balancing the number of nodes in each partition; however, the authors additionally proposed an edge-balancing cost function (i.e., placing the same number of edges in each partition) for power-law degree-distributed graphs.

Another heuristic, FENNEL (Tsourakakis et al., 2014), builds on LDG's objective function by interpolating between assigning nodes to partitions with the greatest number of their neighbours (Stanton & Kliot, 2012) and the least number of their non-neighbours (Prabhakaran et al., 2012). Tsourakakis et al. (2014) found that FENNEL outperforms LDG, and this performance gap is echoed in Filippidou and Kotidis (2015a), where both heuristics were extended to partition multi-labelled graphs. Other subsequent experiments demonstrate that FENNEL performs slightly better than LDG (Filippidou & Kotidis, 2015b), particularly for highly-skewed graphs (Abbas et al., 2018), or competitively with LDG (Echbarthi & Kheddouci, 2014).¹²³

¹²³ To ensure their experiments with FENNEL produced balanced partitions, Echbarthi and Kheddouci (2014) set the γ parameter to 5, which is significantly higher than the value recommended by the original authors, where $\gamma = 1.5$ (Tsourakakis et al., 2014). This decision alters the behaviour of FENNEL and should reduce the fraction of edges cut by FENNEL.

Since LDG was first introduced, several authors have modified LDG's penalty function responsible for balancing the number of nodes across partitions; the result is a lower fraction of edges cut when partitioning a single stream (Echbarthi & Kheddouci, 2014; Li et al., 2019).¹²⁴ In another version of FENNEL, the balancing part of the objective function was modified to place the same number of edges (as opposed to nodes) in each partition, which as noted above, reduces communication volume (Bourse et al., 2014). Furthermore, Nishimura and Ugander (2013) explore multi-constraint partitioning by simultaneously balancing the number of nodes and edges across partitions. As both LDG and FENNEL are state-of-the-art streaming graph partitioners, distributed graph processing platforms have readily incorporated either node and/or edge streaming versions of these heuristics (Stanton, 2014; Tsourakakis, 2015).

Alternative methods to LDG and FENNEL are presented by Chen and Huan (2016), who develop two streaming graph partitioning heuristics, Combining Deterministic Greedy (CDG) and Affine Combining Deterministic Greedy (ADG). Following Bourse et al. (2014), these heuristics focus on reducing communication cost. More precisely, they attempt not only to allocate nodes to partitions with their greatest number of neighbours, but they also aggregate/combine edges between partitions whenever possible (Chen & Huan, 2016). The combined edges incur only the cost of a single edge (or an edge weight significantly lower than the sum of the combined edges). Taking a closer look at Chen and Huan's (2016) experiments featuring a social network, Slashdot0811 (77,360 nodes and 905,468 edges), the authors demonstrate that CDG and ADG generate partitions with lower communication costs than LDG. They also report that CDG outperforms LDG in terms of the fraction of edges cut when the number of partitions exceeds 16.

Restreaming Partitioning

When streaming a graph into partitions, each node is assigned to a partition based on the knowledge of where *previously* streamed nodes are assigned. By making a second pass over the stream, one can "repartition" each node with knowledge of where *all* nodes are assigned. Continuing with this logic, after each node is reevaluated and potentially reassigned, if other

¹²⁴ While these modified versions of LDG perform better than the original version of LDG, neither Echbarthi and Kheddouci (2014) nor Li et al. (2019) have thoroughly demonstrated an improvement over FENNEL. This would involve comparing LDG against versions of FENNEL with different γ parameter settings, including the γ values recommended by Tsourakakis et al. (2015). One should also note that LDG's node balancing penalty function is originally *multiplied* by the number of neighbours within a given partition (Tsourakakis et al., 2015). In contrast, Echbarthi and Kheddouci (2014) *subtract* while Li et al. (2019) *add* this penalty function. As the latter authors use the same datasets, one can determine that Echbarthi and Kheddouci's (2014) version of LDG performs best.

nodes are subsequently reassigned, then it makes sense to once again reevaluate the former nodes to see if better partitions are available. Advancing this concept, Nishimura and Ugander (2013) transform LDG and FENNEL into iterative processes, “restreaming LDG” and “restreaming FENNEL.” While LDG does not guarantee convergence over multiple restreams, FENNEL displays an exponential convergence rate toward one of many local optima (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013). The authors found restreaming FENNEL outperforms restreaming LDG.

Restreaming LDG and restreaming FENNEL are not straightforward extensions of their one-pass counterparts. For example, improvements resulting from modifying LDG’s node balancing penalty function (Echbarthi & Kheddouci, 2014) do not necessarily carry over into the restreaming context.¹²⁵ Additionally, unlike the one-pass version of FENNEL, restreaming FENNEL guarantees balanced partitions, that is, by tempering the node balance penalty function across multiple restreams (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013).

While maintaining good-quality partitions, one can achieve even lower runtime and memory costs by partially restreaming graphs. As an example, Echbarthi and Kheddouci (2014) partition the first loaded portion of a graph using restreaming LDG, followed by partitioning the remaining nodes as a single stream. In another instance, with FENNEL as the partitioning heuristic, Huang and Abadi (2016) reevaluate only the portion of a graph most likely to benefit from reassignment, i.e., nodes near where edges are being added or subtracted, and in particular, those nodes with few assigned neighbours.¹²⁶ Huang and Abadi (2016) also improve runtime and memory costs by employing a sliding window as well as improve the fraction of edges cut by incorporating vertex replication.

Without incurring additional cut edges from partially restreaming graphs, Battaglino et al. (2015) demonstrate the efficiency of restreaming over the entire graph with a distributed, parallel version of restreaming FENNEL while Li et al. (2019) propose a new cache structure for greater efficiency on a single commodity computer, as demonstrated using a modified version of restreaming LDG.

¹²⁵ Echbarthi and Kheddouci (2014) refer to their single stream modification of LDG as Fractional Greedy (FG). Their restreaming version is abbreviated as ReFG, and their partial restreaming version is abbreviated as PartFG. By juxtaposing Echbarthi and Kheddouci’s (2014) results found in Table II (specifically the FG and LDG column) with those in Table III (specifically the ReFG and ReLDG column), one can see that FG typically outperforms LDG while ReFG does not typically improve upon ReLDG.

¹²⁶ By way of example, in one of Huang and Abadi’s (2016) experiments, “a vertex with 10 neighbours is reassigned to a new partition upon receiving an 11th neighbour 13% of the time, while a vertex with 40 neighbours is reassigned to a new partition upon receiving a 41st neighbour only 2.5% of the time. Therefore, it is less cost-efficient to pay the reassignment examination cost for a vertex with a large number of existing neighbours, since it is likely that this examination work will be wasted, and the vertex will remain in its current partition.”

The limitation of one-pass partitioning with LDG or FENNEL is not the local view of the algorithms but the narrow view of an incomplete loaded graph (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013). Restreaming grants access to the entire graph; however, unlike offline partitioning, restreaming does not capitalise on a global view. That said, experiments conducted by Nishimura and Ugander (2013) show that restreaming FENNEL outperforms METIS (a standard offline graph partitioner) when partitioning small social networks (tens of thousands of nodes as opposed to millions).¹²⁷ As for partitioning web graphs, METIS consistently outperforms FENNEL (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013), which suggests that graph structure plays a role when determining best graph partitioning practices.

Window-Based Partitioning

Another extension to one-pass, streaming graph partitioning is window-based (or batch-based) graph partitioning. Conceptually, this approach involves *expanding* access to graph data prior to generating partition assignments. Methodologically, one accomplishes this by *constraining* offline (global) or restreaming (local) partitioning algorithms, confining their view of the entire graph to unassigned nodes within a window as well as previously assigned nodes within partitions.

Types of windows incorporated into streaming graph partitioning include tumbling windows (Echbarthi & Kheddouci, 2016; Jafari et al., 2021; Sajjad et al., 2016), where a data stream is processed in repeated, non-overlapping segments, and sliding windows (Firth & Missier, 2016; Huang & Abadi, 2016; Mayer et al., 2018; Patwary et al., 2019), where an overlapping intersection of data is maintained while advancing through a data stream.¹²⁸ Conducting experiments with sliding windows, Mayer et al. (2018) control window size as a trade-off between partitioning latency (i.e., speed) and quality (i.e., fraction of edges cut). Furthermore, when partitioning is underway, they recompute only high-scoring edges within the sliding window (a technique designed to reduce computational complexity) and sequentially assign only the best-scoring edge to a partition (where scores consider the partition capacity, node degree and clustering formations calculated after an edge is added to each partition).¹²⁹ Patwary et al. (2019) highlight what is fundamental to any window-base

¹²⁷ A study with more social networks would help establish this trend. Analysing six social networks, Nishimura and Ugander (2013) more generally contend that restreaming FENNEL is competitive with METIS when partitioning social networks.

¹²⁸ For an overview and comparison of windowing mechanisms, please see Lal and Suman (2020).

¹²⁹ Although not exclusive to window-based partitioning, Mayer et al. (2018) also employ an adaptive balancing parameter, which initially relaxes the balancing constraint and then tightens it over the course of partitioning.

technique: for each node being assigned to a partition, they search within the window for that node's neighbours and generate a partitioning assignment that considers these connections.

Demonstrating that window-base partitioning can accommodate offline partitioning, Echbarthi and Kheddouci (2016) modify the offline graph partitioner, METIS, to operate within a tumbling window. One should expect this window-based version of METIS to perform worse than its offline counterpart and—given that restreaming LDG and restreaming FENNEL are competitive with METIS (Nishimura & Ugander, 2013)—perform worse than restreaming heuristics. Echbarthi and Kheddouci (2016) confirm this assertion. The overlooked and relevant experiment would be comparing Echbarthi and Kheddouci's (2016) window-based version of METIS with a window-based version of restreaming LDG and/or restreaming FENNEL.

Initialisation Before Partitioning

Recall that nodes with few assigned neighbours are most likely to benefit from restreaming (Huang & Abadi, 2016). As the first nodes to enter a stream have few assigned neighbours, one can deduce that restreaming (or offline partitioning) these nodes, and thereby restreaming within an early operating tumbling window, would be particularly effective. More specifically, to counter what is known as a “cold start,” the first batch of nodes within a window should be large enough to seed the partitions, meaning that each partition would be ideally assigned some nodes (preferably high-degree, non-peripheral nodes from different communities), such that subsequently streamed nodes have a likely point of contact during partitioning.

Drawing on this concept, Filippidou and Kotidis (2015b) conduct experiments where they reserve 30% of graph edges for initialisation, followed by partitioning the remaining edges either in a single stream or window. Their partitioner stores a graph in a novel, condensed spanning tree (CST) structure, which enables the computation of several high-quality graph partitioning schemes. Their method outperforms both LDG and FENNEL when partitioning a single stream (Filippidou & Kotidis, 2015b). Specific to the planted partition model (also known as the stochastic block model), which is a classical random graph model that exhibits clustering (Mossel et al., 2015), Tsourakakis (2014) determines through a series of proofs what sampling size is necessary for the highly probable existence of at least one representative node within each partition. These proofs are used to initialise a streaming, two-hop greedy partitioning algorithm that outperforms LDG (Tsourakakis, 2014).

Node Order Before Partitioning

Stanton and Kliot (2012) demonstrate that streaming graph partitioners are susceptible to adversarial node ordering. This evaluation, combined with runtime and simplicity in mind, has prompted certain researchers to advocate for random node ordering (Guo et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2015). While random node ordering avoids theoretically worst-case partitioning performance, one also might take interest in generating the highest quality partitions possible. To this end, Stanton and Kliot (2012) explore two node orderings based on traditional methods of traversing and linearising graphs: breadth-first search (BFS) and depth-first search (DFS).¹³⁰ The basic concept is to provide streaming partitioners with connected nodes immediately because adjusting for retrospective connections is not possible under the streaming framework. For social networks, LDG performs best with BFS ordering, followed closely by DFS ordering (Stanton & Kliot, 2012). Random ordering performs the worst (Stanton & Kliot, 2012). The results are echoed by Abbas et al. (2018), where the authors confirm that DFS ordering outperforms random ordering when partitioning with LDG.

Citing the findings of Stanton and Kliot (2012), the authors of FENNEL also investigate BFS and DFS node orderings. They report that FENNEL is generally unaffected by node order (Tsourakakis et al., 2014), a conclusion reinforced by Abbas et al. (2018). That said, as concerns FENNEL's gamma parameter,¹³¹ when $\gamma = 1.25$, Tsourakakis et al. (2014) observe that BFS and DFS node ordering results in significantly worse partition balance. The generalisation that FENNEL is unaffected by node ordering is further contested by Echbarthi and Kheddouci (2016), who present results (see Table III and Table VI) suggesting that FENNEL performs better with a DFS order.¹³²

Depending on the partitioner and graph structure, node ordering could have either a considerable or minor impact on partitioning quality and balance, or no effect at all. One should further consider that significant improvement from node ordering might be inconsequential in light of other factors. For example, upon partitioning a co-purchasing network (featuring

¹³⁰ Beginning with an arbitrary node (the root node), BFS searches all neighbouring nodes at the present depth before progressing to greater depths while DFS searches the branch of a single neighbour to the greatest possible depth before backtracking and progressing with its search. BFS and DFS have a long history of improving the design of distributed graph algorithms. For an example, see Cheung (1983).

¹³¹ Please recall that the gamma value is responsible for interpolating between LDG assignments ($\gamma = 1$) and nearest neighbour assignments ($\gamma = 2$).

¹³² The methods responsible for producing Table III are specified in an earlier article (Echbarthi & Kheddouci, 2014), where FENNEL's γ value is set to 5. This γ value is not tested by Tsourakakis et al. (2014). Additionally, Echbarthi, and Kheddouci (2016) conduct experiments with different social networks than Tsourakakis et al. (2014). These differences might help account for the disparity between the results of Echbarthi and Kheddouci's (2016) and those of Tsourakakis et al. (2014).

Amazon data), LDG outfitted with BFS node ordering performs definitively worse than FENNEL. Specifically, this version of LDG cut 34% of the network edges (an improvement over LDG with random ordering, cutting 40%) while FENNEL cut 14% (Tsourakakis et al., 2014).

Apart from LDG and (circumstantially) FENNEL, other partitioners stand either to benefit or be disadvantaged by BFS and DFS node orderings. For example, Streaming METIS Partitioning (SMP) performs significantly better with DFS ordering, while BFS ordering offers no benefits and random ordering is “adversarial” (Echbarthi & Kheddouci, 2016). Another partitioning method, HDRF, has a lower replication factor (i.e., performs better) using random ordering than either BFS or DFS ordering (Petroni et al., 2015; see also Abbas et al., 2018).

Besides BFS and DFS, other node ordering schemes appear in the literature. For hypergraph partitioning, Alistarh et al. (2015) found that a greedy approach performs best when nodes are ordered by decreasing degree. Likewise, SHEEP (Margo & Seltzer, 2015) orders nodes by decreasing degree as part of constructing a small elimination tree, which becomes the structure that this algorithm partitions. GRACE is another partitioner that attributes much of its success to node ordering. In this case, “vertices and edges are ordered according to their graph-specific locality” (Prabhakaran et al., 2012).

One can also search outside the distributed graph processing literature for useful node order schemes. For example, Margo and Seltzer (2015) direct attention to literature on how to disassemble a network via minimising the number of nodes removed (a body of literature more generally referred to as “attack robustness” or “attack tolerance,” i.e., the robustness of a system based on the failure of its individual parts), where the “ensuing attack” order is essentially the opposite of their elimination tree order. Another body of literature related to attack tolerance is graph compression (Kang & Falouts, 2011). In this realm, SLASHBURN ordering outperforms degree ordering and several other centrality-based ordering schemes when used to compress a graph (Kang & Falouts, 2011).

More generally, other than degree centrality, very few if any other centrality scores are used to order nodes and then evaluate streaming graph partitioning performance. CentiServer is a comprehensive, web-based resource that has catalogued over 230 centrality scores that service a wide range of applications (Jalili et al., 2015). One can further combine these scores (Fei et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2019) or switch between them midstream. Regarding the latter option, Lyer et al. (2013) found that in the context of attack robustness, betweenness centrality is initially more effective at degrading social networks than other centrality scores tested;

however, after roughly 25% of the nodes are removed with betweenness centrality, then degree centrality becomes more effective.

While the very first comparative streaming graph partitioning study (Stanton & Kliot, 2012) emphasises the importance of node ordering (including an entire section, “Stream Orders,” dedicated to its exploration), the subject area has received little subsequent attention.

Repartitioning

Buluç et al. (2016) nicely present the dual objectives of repartitioning (not to be confused with “restreaming”) as a trade-off between partitioning quality and migration volume:

[W]hen the application graph changes over time, *repartitioning* becomes necessary. Due to changes in the underlying application, a graph partition may become gradually imbalanced due to the introduction of new nodes (and edges) and the deletion of others. Once the imbalance exceeds a certain threshold, the application should call the repartitioning routine. This routine is to compute a new partition II' from the old one, II . In many applications it is favorable to keep the changes between II and II' small. Minimizing these changes simultaneously to optimizing II' with respect to the cut (or a similar objective) leads to multiobjective optimization.

The authors further describe a linear approach to repartitioning, as put forth by Schloegel et al. (1997), where good repartitions are achieved (through a process termed diffusion), and the trade-off between edge cuts and migration cost is adjusted with parameterised heuristics; the parameters reduce vertex movement while marginally sacrificing edge cuts. This strategy is used by the parallel graph partitioner ParMETIS (Schloegel et al., 2002). Many other partitioners are also capable of repartitioning.¹³³

Streaming Hyperedge Partitioning

Many partitioning techniques designed for graphs extend to hypergraphs. Indeed, the TLAV paradigm resurfaces within the hypergraph partitioning literature (Heintz et al., 2019).¹³⁴ Following the framework of Stanton (2014), wherein LDG’s performance is theoretically explained, Alistarh et al. (2015) develop and justify a streaming computation

¹³³ For example, Buluç et al. (2016) mention the parallel version of JOSTLE (Walshaw & Cross, 2007) and PDibaP (Meyerhenke, 2013). As a matter of performance, PDibaP can repartition with a migration volume comparable to both ParMETIS and JOSTLE; however, with respect to maximum communication volume (MCV), PDibaP outperforms ParMETIS by 34–53% and JOSTLE by 12–19% (Meyerhenke, 2013).

¹³⁴ TLAV is referenced several times in Heintz et al. (2019). The article features MESH, which is a “a flexible distributed framework for scalable hypergraph processing” built on top of the GraphX framework.

model for the min-max hypergraph partitioning problem. This model is extended by Epple (2018), who incorporates a more flexible balance parameter and changes the objective function from edge to node balance partitioning. The resulting algorithm performs better than the original (Epple, 2018). The model is also extended by Taşyaran et al. (2021), who significantly reduced the algorithm's runtime. Restreaming hypergraph techniques are also part of the literature (Geppert, 2016; Jiang, 2018; Xu et al., 2014) as well as windows-based hypergraph partitioning techniques (Jiang, 2018). Drawing on the above streaming graph partitioning literature, Xu et al. (2014) transform LDG into a restreaming hypergraph partitioner as part of their larger, dynamic partitioning framework. Lastly, Tan et al. (2017) combine graphs and hypergraphs into a “hyperstructure” for partitioning, a strategy that overcomes the drawbacks associated with implementing one structure over the other.

Conclusion

The primary catalyst for this growing body of literature is a reaction to big data, where new methods are presented as computationally efficient. Albeit to a lesser extent, the literature also presents new methods to improve partitioning quality. The goal is nearly always the same: the partitioner should perform competitively with and, in some respect, surpass the standard graph partitioner, METIS. The literature additionally and more broadly speaks to the conditionality of performance gains. Sometimes improvements are associated with certain network types or premised on the existence of certain network structures. Even the number of partitions can influence whether a new partitioning method is deemed advantageous.

In terms of effectiveness, the conditions that set one partitioning method apart from another may lack clear delineation within the evacuation context. Conversely, partitioning methods designed to fulfil the same purpose might in fact require different treatment. For these reasons, Chapter 4 examines which aspects of partitioning are specifically relevant to evacuations.

As a closing remark, while the partitioning literature is rich with novel methods, what is often neglected is extending these methods to handle edge weights, node weights, and target partition weights. These features of partitioning do not belong to any one method, but they are just as relevant to the context at hand.

Appendix D

Constructing Socio-Spatial Networks

Within the Portland study, this research constructed a social network between displaced people, which became input data for partitioning experiments. The model used to construct this data was designed to be realistic, i.e., contain relatively few idealisations. However, how this data was then accessed and input into a partitioner—all at once and with perfect accuracy—was not realistic. Of course, the intention behind the Portland study did not demand realism in this respect; the intention was to bound a spectrum of possible shelter compositions using idealised random and idealised partitioned shelter assignments. In contrast, Chapter 5 acknowledges that real-world data used for partitioning is not ideally accessible. The data could be streaming and accurate or predicted and, most likely, inaccurate to some degree. This appendix describes how to construct a model to generate streaming data as well as predicted data that is quantifiably inaccurate for partitioning. In order to best isolate different reasons why a prediction could go awry while simultaneously altering the extent to which outcomes deviate from the prediction, alongside confronting the sheer number of possible scenarios (upon which multiple strategies are tested), this research proposes constructing a “toy model” that is simple and idealised for partitioning experiments in Chapter 5.

To create even this simplest representation of a social network between displaced people, one needs to model a social network and a physical disaster, alongside a way for these two phenomena to interact. This research finds common ground in 2-dimensional Euclidean space. Thereby, this appendix begins by examining real-world socio-spatial networks. The research then examines different ways a model can accurately portray reality, which includes techniques such as fitting a model to empirical observations and describing the verisimilitude of the generative process. After bringing into consideration the virtue of simplicity, a socio-spatial network model is then selected from among candidate models and thoroughly described. The research proceeds to superimpose disasters over the constructed socio-spatial networks to create data for Chapter 5.

Physical Dimensions of Social Networks

“Everything is related to everything else, but near things are more related than distant things” (Tobler, 1970). This holds true for social networks. In the words of Barthélemy (2011), “Space intervenes in the fact that the connection probability between two individuals usually decreases with the distance between them.” This idea is supported by a wealth of large-scale, empirical studies. For example, considering the social contact frequencies of people in Toronto

(Canada), Zurich (Switzerland), Eindhoven (Netherlands), Concepción (Chile), and Tokyo (Japan), Parady et al. (2020) found that the proportion of local contacts (<2 km) range between 17.9% and 30.1% and that face-to-face communication decreases as geographic distance increases. This decay function finds resonance throughout the literature; for example, the volume of electronic communications is also inversely proportional to geographic distance (Goldberg & Levy, 2009; Scellato et al., 2010) as are noteworthy and memorable social interactions (Latané et al., 1995). Research is ongoing to understand these interwoven contexts and to more concisely determine the nature of the decay (Barthélemy, 2011), which often follows an inverse power law or an exponential decay law (Daraganova et al., 2012).¹³⁵ As for the tail of the distribution, against a background probability of social connections (which are independent of geographic distance), certain synthetic network models maintain some degree of long-distance edge connectivity (Illenberger et al., 2013; Lambiotte et al., 2008; Liben-Nowell et al., 2005; Wickramasinghe et al., 2018; Wong et al., 2008). This points to the fact that geographic proximity alone cannot explain the emergence of all network structures, particularly triangles (Lambiotte et al., 2008), clusters (Daraganova et al., 2012) and transitivity (Illenberger et al., 2013) at long distances. Although proximity appears to predominately determine network structure (Butts, 2003; Liben-Nowell et al., 2005), Daraganova et al. (2012) more specifically conclude that “proximity may be more likely to give rise to initial tie formation than to more complex characteristics of network structure.” Speaking to this idea, Lambiotte et al. (2008) demonstrate that complex characteristics—namely the formation of triangles that extend over long distances—emerge when introducing mobility and migration into the construction of synthetic social networks.

Apart from the distance between members of a social network, one must also consider the population distribution (Backstrom et al., 2010; Butts et al., 2012; Illenberger et al., 2013; Liben-Nowell et al., 2005).¹³⁶ Indeed, inhomogeneous city sizes are captured by a Pareto distribution (Rafael, 2018) or, when separating the sizes into a simple ranking, by Zipf’s

¹³⁵ In the words of Daraganova et al. (2012), “the main distinction of the exponential decay law from the power law is in tie probabilities at large distances, i.e. the form of the tail. That is, for exponential decay functions the tie probability tends to 0 when distance increases more quickly than for the inverse power law functions. Hence, a tie probability at large distances equals virtually zero beyond some given point in an exponential decay function, while in power law functions a tie probability at large distances is non-negligible.” For this reason, Daraganova et al. (2012) find that a power law better fits the distribution of real-world data.

¹³⁶ This research uses the phrase “population distribution” interchangeably with “varying population density” and “inhomogeneous population distribution.” The latter word choices are used to emphasise the concept of variability.

Law.¹³⁷ Since the population distribution is the same at any scale (e.g., whether examining a continent, country or province), this implies that the distribution is fractal (Batty, 2006), a phenomenon more broadly reflecting the structure of many urban systems (Batty & Longley, 1994; Chen & Zhou, 2008).¹³⁸ Against this backdrop, Illenberger et al. (2013) found that the distance distribution of social contacts (proportional to $\sim d^{-1}$) is the same whether examining urban or rural areas. They explain that “individuals living in rural areas appear to compensate for the lower accessibility with a higher background probability to accept other persons as social contacts.” To account for inhomogeneous population densities, the authors incorporate into their model “a person specific constant c_i that varies with accessibility.” One should note that despite their efforts, Illenberger et al. (2013) were unable to generate a synthetic social network with the same degree of complexity as their empirical data. More specifically, their model could not reproduce transitivity unless they decreased their network size from 40,000 individuals to 500 individuals (which would thereby increase the probability of having a common neighbour) or unless they increased the negative exponent value of their empirically calibrated distance distribution.¹³⁹

One can also generate networks with realistic social attributes, where 2-dimensional Euclidean space facilitates network construction without the need to depict realistic spatial proximities between people. For example, both the distance distribution and the population distribution affect a social phenomenon known as *navigability*, i.e., how easily one can send a message across a social network to a random target recipient. Empirical studies, the most famous being Milgram (1967), reveal that real-world social networks exhibit a “small-world effect,” which makes them easy to navigate. Whereas Watts and Strogatz (1998) created a model to explain the presence of shortest paths in networks, Kleinberg (2000) created a model where one could *find* these shortest paths and thereby, without global knowledge of social networks, effectively send a message across them. According to Kleinberg, the probability distribution of long-range, geographic friendships that facilitate navigable social networks is proportional to $\sim d^{-2}$ (see also Comte & Mathieu, 2018; Fraigniaud & Giakkoupis, 2014).

¹³⁷ With many studies examining only the upper tail of the population distribution, one should be wary of “power law mimicry” (Perline, 2005). To avoid this mistake, Rafael (2018) used untruncated data to demonstrate that city sizes follow a Pareto distribution. Of course, one can view the population distribution through an even more nuanced lens—for example, Le Néchet (2015) identifies eight spatial indicators to classify population distributions within a metropolis.

¹³⁸ Please note, networks that are purely spatial, such as roadways and other urban infrastructure, have different attributes than social networks (see Barthélemy, 2014, 2018; Boccaletti et al., 2006).

¹³⁹ Acknowledging the lack of transitivity in this model, Arentze et al. (2012) incorporate transitivity into their large-scale, synthetic social network model to better simulate activity-based travel.

However, using friendship connections and geographic locations of over 1.3 million bloggers from the LiveJournal community, Liben-Nowell et al. (2005) found that this real-world social network is navigable despite having a distance distribution proportional to $\sim d^{-1}$. As Liben-Nowell et al. (2005) point out, the incongruity owes to the fact that Kleinberg constructed graphs with nodes positioned on a uniform p -dimensional lattice, whereas large-scale, real-world social networks exhibit spatial layouts with varying densities of people that are nonuniformly distributed. In other words, Kleinberg’s model is not sufficiently generalisable to explain how other spatial layouts—those without scaling properties analogous to a p -dimensional lattice—are navigable.¹⁴⁰ In response, Liben-Nowell et al. (2005) model the probability that people are friends by combining distance and density into a rank-based notion of geography. As Kleinberg later reflects, “[T]he grid-based model with the inverse-square distribution *corresponds* [emphasis added] to rank-based friendship in which there is one person resident at each grid node” (Kleinberg, 2006; see also Liben-Nowell et al., 2005). This rank-based approach was validated against a LiveJournal dataset (Liben-Nowell et al., 2005) as well as against a 2.9-million-user Facebook dataset (Backstrom et al., 2010).

While social networks generated by Kleinberg (2000) can accurately represent navigation across real-world landscapes, i.e., to the point of replicating Milgram’s experiment (Comte & Mathieu, 2018), if these networks are viewed as an “architectural site plan,” then one must acknowledge that they distort spatial realism. In terms of model construction, one could further argue that spatial realism is not a prerequisite for social realism. In fact, one can generate quite realistic social networks using non-Euclidian geometry, where nodes are embedded in a hidden metric structure of constant negative curvature (Boguñá et al., 2020; Friedrich, 2019; Kleinberg, 2007; Krioukov et al., 2010).¹⁴¹

When restricting model construction to 2-dimensional Euclidean space, one might contend that modelling the most realistic spatial conditions, i.e., the varying household densities, is necessary to generate social networks with the most realistic social network attributes. The literature supports this notion to some degree. Alizadeh et al. (2016) found that

¹⁴⁰ On this matter, a p -dimensional lattice generalises to any “less structured graphs with analogous scaling properties” (Kleinberg, 2000). For example, if one adopts a two-dimensional, fractal layout to represent the urban environment, such as a Sierpinski carpet (Mandelbrot, 1977), then the most efficient *navigation* across this fractal layout requires that one draw random, long-range connections between nodes according to the probability distribution identified by Kleinberg (see Roberson & ben-Avraham, 2006). Of course, when graphs have different scaling properties, the question is not whether these graphs achieve a $\theta(\log^2 n)$ delivery or navigation time, i.e., the same as in the Kleinberg model (cf., Carmi et al., 2009), but whether they achieve a realistic delivery time.

¹⁴¹ Literature on the relationship between social networks and hyperbolic geometry is extensive. Only a few relevant citations are included here.

taking social networks that omit from their construction an explicit representation of the physical space in which real-world social networks form (e.g., networks constructed on a regular ring lattice or networks constructed non-spatially) and then incorporating into their construction a uniform distribution of nodes embedded within 2-dimensional Euclidean space, followed by a nonuniform distribution of nodes (to represent varying household densities), is a progression toward higher network clustering, assortativity, and transitivity, i.e., toward more realistic social network structures. Beyond the three classical social network models tested by Alizadeh et al. (2016; namely, the Erdős-Rényi, Watts-Strogatz, and Barabási-Albert models), one might question whether other social network models can be constructed and potentially improved within nonuniform, 2-dimensional Euclidean space or whether their logic is irrevocably tuned to different spatial representations (e.g., hyperbolic geometry) or is simply non-translatable.

Keep in mind that if one restricts model selection to only those models with the most realistic spatial dimensions (or for that matter, to models based on any singular social network attribute, such as navigability), then not only would this severely reduce the number of candidate models, leaving few to consider (e.g., Alizadeh et al., 2016; Wickramasinghe et al., 2018), but moreover, it would undermine the significance of other, potentially more influential factors contributing to network realism. Indeed, fundamental methodological differences between the Erdős-Rényi, Watts-Strogatz, and Barabási-Albert models, for example, could have a greater bearing on the realism of social network attributes than different spatial layouts added to their construction (see Alizadeh et al., 2016).¹⁴²

¹⁴² Taking a closer look at Alizadeh et al. (2016), this conclusion is most obvious when comparing the Watts-Strogatz model and the Barabási-Albert model, alongside their uniformly distributed spatial implementations (see Table 3 and Tables 5 presented by the authors), namely because parameter settings are consistent between the original, non-spatial and new, spatial implementation of each model (cf., the Erdős-Rényi model; Table 1). Please note that this research adopts the terms/reference, “non-spatial” and “spatial,” even if they are somewhat descriptively inaccurate. With respect to clustering coefficient, density, average path length, assortativity, transitivity, mean degree, min. degree, max. degree, and std. degree, one can calculate the difference between the average non-spatial output values and the average spatial output values across the three parameters tested. One can also calculate the difference in average output values, both non-spatial and spatial, between the Watts-Strogatz model and Barabási-Albert model. Notwithstanding which network attributes are examined, the difference in output values between the two models is always greater than the output values associated with the presence/absence of space within a given model. Two exceptions emerge: the greater difference between the non-spatial and spatial implementation of (1) the Watts-Strogatz model with respect to average path length (specifically where $p = .001$, which is an outlier) and (2) the Barabási-Albert model with respect to max. degree. The conclusion that methodological differences between the Watts-Strogatz model and Barabási-Albert model are potentially the greater determinant of network realism hinges on the argument that the greater difference in network attribute values between the models is also a greater step towards (or away from) network realism. That said, this argument could prove incorrect if the most realistic network attribute values are nearly equally split between those produced by the two models. In such cases, one could argue, for example, using root mean squared error (RMSE), that certain network attributes owe greater realism to the presence/absence of space within a given model. Please also note that the above conclusion generally holds true when further evaluating nonuniformly

Networks Fitted to Socio-Spatial Attributes

A socio-spatial network must exhibit not only realistic social network attributes—high clustering coefficient, right-skewed degree distribution, hierarchical structures, positive degree assortativity, small-world phenomena, strong community structures, etc. (Clauset et al., 2008; Newman, 2003)—but also realistic spatial attributes. While the distance distribution between social network members is often parameterised (Barthélemy, 2011; Hayashi, 2006) and, albeit to a lesser extent, so is the population distribution (Alizadeh et al., 2016; Batty, 2006; Raimbault, 2018; see also Medina et al., 2000; Yook et al., 2002), these spatial attributes are rarely evaluated as outcome measures in synthetically constructed networks. One might consider evaluating the exponent value of the distance distribution (Liben-Nowell, 2005) or characterising its tail (Voitalov et al., 2019). Alternatively, one can measure the similarity between two distance distributions (i.e., the ground truth and the simulation) using the Jensen-Shannon divergence metric (Lin, 1991) or the Wasserstein distance metric (Kantorovich & Rubenstein, 1958; Kline, 2019; Villani, 2009). Measuring the population distribution is a more complicated problem (Duncan, 1957), one that touts a respectable list of measures. Even if one were to measure the distribution of density-based cluster sizes or modal-based cluster sizes (Menardi, 2016), further inquiry is required to explain the spatial organisation of clusters¹⁴³—this is a non-trivial matter.

The concept of *ideal* social or spatial network attribute values is generally absent in the literature. Instead, specifying whether such values fall within an *acceptable* range, one that conforms loosely with empirical studies, is more commonplace (e.g., Pfeffer & Carley, 2011). As a cautionary note, just because network attribute values fall within an acceptable range, unless these attributes are independent of one another, then the generated social network is not necessarily realistic. Needless to say, dependencies most certainly exist; hierarchical structures, for example, “can simultaneously explain and quantitatively reproduce many commonly observed topological properties of networks, such as right-skewed degree distributions, high clustering coefficients, and short path lengths” (Clauset et al., 2004).

One can alternatively and more fundamentally compare synthetically generated social networks with real-world social networks based on the *similarity* of their network attribute values (e.g., Sala et al., 2010; Topirceanu et al., 2013).¹⁴⁴ That said, even if certain models can

distributed spatial implementations of each model (see Table 9 and Table 11 by authors). In these cases, another exception might emerge in the Barabási-Albert model with respect to assortativity (see Table 11; cf., Table 5).

¹⁴³ Please see citations within Brown et al. (2005).

¹⁴⁴ Prior to identifying the most realistic social networks, one can also use similarity measures to finetune a set of model parameters (see Sala et al., 2010).

(re)produce realistic synthetic networks, Sala et al. (2010) highlight the fact that “current graph metrics remain incomplete, and some applications expose graph properties that do not map to existing metrics.” If network properties lack well-defined metrics and, therefore, are not considered when evaluating network realism, one can still account for these network properties when constructing networks.

A Generative Process to Construct Socio-Spatial Networks

Constructing social networks in space is a different project than constructing socio-spatial networks. While this research is concerned with generating socio-spatial networks, the nature of the methods—the role of “space” in network construction—dictates the relevance of the output measures and ultimately how one defines success. Expanding this concept, if a model is fitted to bring about certain socio-spatial network attributes, then one must ascribe a great deal of significance to those attributes and the relationships between them. On the other hand, if a model intimately captures the emergence and evolution of socio-spatial network formation, and the output is a mature state or snapshot of this process, then one might evaluate the generative verisimilitude of a model as opposed to what it produces.

How do social networks form in the first place? Analytical sociology places stock in explaining the *mechanisms* through which macro-level phenomena emerge (Hedström & Bearman, 2009; see also Manzo, 2014). One might question what linked chain of events (Conte, 2006; Ylikoski, 2019) or causal narratives (Crasnow, 2017), or perhaps “productive continuities” (Machamer et al., 1999), lead to a particular outcome.¹⁴⁵ As multiple linked chain of events can bring about the same outcome, i.e., equifinality (Richardson, 2003) or multiple realizability (Sawyer, 2004), mechanism-based theorising cannot lay claim to causality, but more modestly, it can demonstrate that a possible explanation exists (Hedström & Ylikoski, 2010; Schlüter et al., 2019; Ylikoski, 2019; see also Epstein, 1999). This explanation might be correct or incorrect; what is important here is that “descriptions of mechanisms render the end stage intelligible” (Machamer et al., 1999). With a concern for realism, regarding the transition from a possible explanation to a plausible one, “[t]he explanatory power of an explanation thus

¹⁴⁵ A Mechanism-based approach to scientific explanation is akin to Merton’s sociological concept of middle-range theory (Merton, 1968), which can be defined as “contextual generalizations that describe chains of causal mechanisms explaining a well-bounded range of phenomena, as well as the conditions that trigger, enable, or prevent these causal chains” (Meyfroidt et al., 2018). This approach also finds contemporary appeal in agent-based modelling (Elsenbroich, 2002; Hedström & Bearman, 2009; Hedström & Ylikoski, 2010), resonating strongly with Epstein’s (1999) motto for *generative social science*: “If you didn’t grow it, you didn’t explain its emergence.” This motto, however, requires some revision if one is to make *what-if* inferences beyond a particular set of simulation parameters (Marchionni & Ylikoski, 2013). Accordingly, Macy, and Flanche (2009) offer a befitting postscript: “If you don’t know *how* you grew it, you didn’t explain it.”

needs to be validated with empirical knowledge and data” (Schlüter et al., 2019; see also Boero & Squazzoni, 2005). An abductive argument (Lorenz, 2006; Squazzoni, 2010) drawing inference from contrastive counterfactuals (Ylikoski, 2011) transpires:

By presenting evidence in support of the assumptions of one mechanism and showing the absence of evidence for the assumptions of competing mechanisms, we increase the plausibility of the explanatory hypothesis. What separates proper mechanism-based explanations from mere mechanism-based storytelling is this kind of rigorous checking of the assumptions upon which the mechanism schemes rest. (Hedström & Ylikoski, 2010)

Absent concepts such as self-organisation and emergence, stochasticity and non-linearity, a “rigorous checking of the assumptions” might support a plausible explanation; however, for complex, adaptive systems (CAS), while the assumptions might be perfectly transparent, the generative process (i.e., the causal chain of events) they trigger is not necessarily opaque (Manzo, 2014). In other words, “if we rely on the cogs-and-wheels definition of mechanisms, we may wrongly assume we are offering a black box-free explanation simply because the mechanism is present in the initial configuration of the simulation” (León-Medina, 2017).

Having reviewed several important aspects about mechanism-based explanation, one can now apply this approach more narrowly to social network analysis. An explanation of social network attributes, i.e., stylised facts, as developed through generative network models, results in mechanism schemes (see Hedström & Ylikoski, 2010). These mechanism schemes describe how network attributes could in principle be produced. When dealing with CAS, however, an explanation would be incomplete without a narrative of how network attributes emerge. If the explanation is not only plausible but convincing, then as a litmus test, the explanation should be “hard to vary” (Deutch, 2011). For example, upon reexamining small-world effect and network navigability, which are network attributes explained by the Kleinberg model (Kleinberg, 2000), Dodds, Muhamad, and Watts (2003) find that “much about this ‘small world’ hypothesis is poorly understood and empirically unsubstantiated” while other researchers, such as Yang and Chen (2015) and Malkov and Ponomarenko (2016), defend their own underlying mechanism and point to multiple others that can explain navigability in real-world networks.¹⁴⁶ This is not to say that the Kleinberg model produces unrealistic networks;

¹⁴⁶ For a list of possible mechanisms that explain navigable small worlds, please see citations within Yang and Chen (2015) and Malkov and Ponomarenko (2016).

however, at a more granular level (see Gilbert, 2006), where researchers hold disparate views on what incentivises or motivates small world navigability, and the generative process would certainly fail to offer a “hard to vary” explanation.

This begs an important question: how can one generate social networks where the process justifies the outcome? According to many scholars, the most suitable tool to model the generative process is agent-based modelling (ABM; León-Medina, 2017). Accordingly, “agent-based simulation methods provide a technical infrastructure tightly coupled to the theoretical agenda of analytical sociology” (Hedström & Ylikoski, 2010). This research will now expound upon what is meant by complex systems and what makes ABM particularly adept at modelling them—no description of ABM would be complete without doing so. However, the value of ABM to this research is not simply its ability to model complex social phenomena but its ability to model spatial phenomena, a feature shared by the simplest of agent-based models and one necessary for generating socio-spatial networks.

A Tool to Construct Socio-Spatial Networks

Beginning with the issue of complexity, to borrow the words of Banos (2013), “[The whole is not only greater than the sum of the parts, but it is also completely different in nature, the emergence often involving a qualitative leap].”¹⁴⁷ This ideology is deeply rooted in complex, adaptive system (CAS) thinking, where its proponents aim to understand complex phenomena not by deconstructing but by reconstructing them (Banos, 2013). It also finds voice in “complexity economics”:

Complexity in other words asks how individual behaviours might react to the pattern they together create, and how that pattern would alter itself as a result. This is often a difficult question; we are asking how a process is created from the purposed actions of multiple agents. And so economics early in its history took a simpler approach, one more amenable to mathematical analysis. It asked not how agents’ behaviours would *react to* the aggregate patterns these created, but what behaviours (actions, strategies, expectations) would be upheld by—would be *consistent with*—the aggregate patterns these caused. (Arthur, 2015; see also Arthur, 2006)

¹⁴⁷ The original text is in French: “[T]out est non seulement plus que la somme des parties, mais il est également de nature complètement différente, l’émergence impliquant souvent un saut qualitative.” In part, Banos attributes this concept to the physicist and Nobel laureate, Philip Anderson, who wrote “More is Different.” For a more in-depth discussion on this facet of emergence, please see Corning (2002).

Agent-based computational economics (ACE) offers methods to represent an economy that, according to Arthur (2015), is perpetually “computing” itself. ACE modelling and its interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary counterpart, ABM, are particularly useful when equilibrium modelling (or more generally, equation-based modelling) is computationally or analytically intractable (Axtel, 2000; Edmonds, 2005; Epstein, 1999; Parker et al., 2003; Tesfatsion, 2006).¹⁴⁸ When an expression is not closed-form and requires an approximate solution, “the lack of analytical tractability must be compensated by an extensive knowledge of model behavior in the parameter space” (Raimbault, 2018). As pertains to ABM, a great deal of emphasis is placed on stability analysis (Lee et al., 2015; Perc, 2017; Schank, 2010), sensitivity analysis (García & Rodríguez-Patón, 2016; Lee et al., 2015; ten Broeke et al., 2016; Thiele et al., 2014) calibration, i.e., parameter fitting (Thiele et al., 2014) and, when making direct statements about reality (cf., Ylikoski & Aydinonat, 2014), validation (David, 2013; Graebner, 2017; Parker et al., 2003).

Agent-based modelling becomes more complex when heterogeneous agents are endowed with cognitive and decision-making abilities. The integration of Belief-Desires-Intention (BDI) and normative architectures into ABM, for example, bring this complexity to fruition (Adam & Gaudou, 2016; Balke & Gilbert, 2014; Ye et al., 2018). As models become more complex, tailoring parameter values to reflect real-world systems becomes increasingly ambitious (Conte & Paolucci, 2014), as does understanding and communicating the generative process (León-Medina, 2017). Researchers must account not only for simple interactions (at the micro-level) generating complex social phenomena (at the macro-level), but when agents *reflexively* monitor the “flow of social life” (Giddens, 1989; see also Goldspink & Kay, 2007), they must additionally account for downward causation, where complex, macro-level phenomena, such as social norms (Andrighetto et al., 2007; Hollander & Wu, 2011), constrain and incentivise micro-level beliefs, desires, intentions, etc. This leads to second-order emergence (Gilbert, 1995, 2002; Liveta et al., 2010; Squazzoni, 2008), also known as immergence (Castelfranchi, 1998; Conte et al., 2007; Squazzoni, 2007) or, in reference to Coleman’s (1990) famous “boat” diagram, macro-micro-macro phenomena (Squazzoni, 2007). More precisely, one should think of cognitively enriched agents as engaged in a constant feedback cycle (Castelfranchi, 1998). As Coleman (1993) explicates:

¹⁴⁸ Mathematical models are not always easily constructed or solved. Several circumstances are explored by Axtell (2000). This article offers an excellent treatment of the subject.

Thus structure at one time (macro-level) generates the conditions which together with existing interests shape the actions of actors (micro-level) that jointly [produce] outcomes which modify the structure of a later time (macro-level) which generates conditions that again (through constraints and incentives) shape actions (micro-level) that jointly produce outcomes (macro-level) and so on.

As pointed out by Gilbert (2006), however, this feedback cycle is unnecessary if micro-level behaviour is constant (an assumption held by economists when referencing market equilibrium). When distinguishing between biological, cognitive and social levels of abstraction (Gilbert, 2006), a more deleterious problem regarding complexity occurs when models operating at a lower level give rise to equifinality, such that insights gleaned from a causal pathway obfuscate a more generalised but significant, higher-level understanding of phenomena (Gilbert, 2006; Squazzoni, 2007). As for deciding whether research spans multiple levels of abstraction or peers within a single one, the decision to keep a model simple (even when empirical data is readily available for greater complexity) could align with the modelling objective; if a model serves an illustrative or analogical purpose, for example, then according to Edmonds et al. (2019), a relevant modelling strategy might benefit from the acronym, KISS (“Keep It Simple Stupid”), as opposed to KIDS (“Keep It Descriptive Stupid”).

What draws this research to ABM, however, is not the method’s distinct output—an appeal to the true data-generating process (DGP) being amply complex, which provides a backdrop uniquely suited for ABM—but rather this research is drawn to ABM’s distinct generative process, where in contrast to equation-based modelling, agent interactions are *explicitly* represented (Galán et al., 2009; Parunak et al., 2000). Part of what is explicitly represented—and unavoidably so—is an environment that mediates agent interactions (Ausloos et al., 2014; Davidsson & Verhagen, 2013; Gilbert, 2008), which in its simplest form is unobstructed, 2-dimensional Euclidean space.¹⁴⁹ Having to spatially model and explain agent interactions based on “construct-valid mechanisms and processes” (Alam et al., 2012) makes ABM an attractive method to generate socio-spatial networks. As social and spatial landscapes are often decoupled, agents become the “cognitive glue” (Edmonds, 2006).¹⁵⁰

¹⁴⁹ For a more in-depth review of spatial agent-based modelling (SABM), please see Manson et al. (2019). An important subcategory of SABM is agent-based modelling within geographical systems. To review the latter, please see Heppenstall et al. (2012).

¹⁵⁰ As a point of clarity, one should distinguish between agents interacting (spatially) to generate a social network and agents interacting within a pre-defined social network (i.e., interacting non-spatially). To distinguish between these objectives, please compare Alam et al. (2012) and Will et al. (2020) respectively. Regarding the latter, just as different spatial topologies (such as Moore or von Neumann neighbourhoods) or spatial topologies enacted through spatially constrained agent interactions (such as restricted agent vision or perception) are known to alter the diffusion or propagation of ideas and thereby potentially change the nature of collective action or social norms

Keeping the Model Simple

This research seeks to avoid making site-specific claims and would rather elicit a conceptual understanding of the impact disasters have on social networks, which are generalisable to many spatial contexts. The ramifications of such an approach are deliberated by Edmonds (2005). Strikingly reminiscent of Thorngate's "postulate of commensurate complexity" (Weick, 1979) and Levins' *desiderata* of model building (Levins, 1966), albeit more loosely prescriptive, Edmonds contends that given the pursuit of virtues associated with modelling—such as simplicity, accuracy, generality and specificity—not only does perfecting one or two of these virtues tend to degrade the others, but the most useful models are nearly always a constructive compromise. Reflecting upon this idea, this research positions itself to create a generalisable and simple model, an alignment that is unavoidably accompanied by some reduction in model accuracy.

The research has thus far introduced how one might approach generating socio-spatial networks. Simulating a disaster on these networks would seemingly follow as an *independent* modelling procedure—indeed, in the real world, an immediate disaster should have no bearing on how social networks are formed. That said, as a socio-spatial network model steps away from realism (as all models do), one must consider whether the manner of abstraction—the virtues pursued—befits the subsequent and overarching purpose.

Pulling into consideration the evacuation context, if social networks are spatial and physical disasters are spatial, then provided that these spaces intersect, one can specify and evaluate induced subgraphs of people requiring shelter in a narrow but principled way.¹⁵¹ The induced subgraphs can further represent either a prediction or observation of who requires shelter, and of central interest to this research, one can examine which shelter assignment strategies (or combinations thereof) perform best when these representations diverge. Of course, an important variable is the amount of divergence, i.e., prediction accuracy. When simulating a disaster that impacts a different region than predicted (where disaster size and magnitude are held constant), in order to simulate different percentages of prediction accuracy (e.g., 100%, 80%, 60%, 20%, and 0% accurate), the distance the observed/actual disaster would "shift" from its predicted region is contingent upon the underlying density of people within

(e.g., Flache & Hegelsmann, 2001), the same logic applies when simulating interactions on different network topologies (see Axtell, 2000; Banos, 2012; Rolf, 2014).

¹⁵¹ An induced subgraph is a subset of nodes, which includes all of the edges connecting these nodes (from the original graph). In contrast, a subgraph (not induced) is a subset of nodes and edges, which means that nodes within the subset may no longer share an edge (from the original graph). Although the terms "network" and "graph" are both quite common, and this research uses them interchangeably, the term "induced subnetwork" is not commonly found in the literature and is not used here.

households, which this research represents as nodes. To simulate prediction accuracy decreasing incrementally, if nodes are non-uniformly distributed in space, then depending on whether a disaster is superimposed over a spatial cluster or between clusters (over a city or between cities), the distance shifted would be respectively small or large. However, if nodes are uniformly distributed, then the distance shifted would be approximately equal between increments. From a slightly different perspective, if nodes are uniformly distributed, one can control prediction accuracy using the predicted and observed regions directly/exclusively (without needing to reference the nodes contained within them): treating regions as polygons, the percentage of prediction accuracy *approximately* equals the area of overlap between the predicted disaster region and the observed disaster region as *a proportion of* the area of the predicted disaster region.¹⁵²

If one chooses to embrace this particular simplification—if only to more easily communicate the experimental design—then one might lean toward adopting a model that generates social networks where nodes are uniformly distributed. As this approach approximates ratios of people requiring/not requiring shelter, some loss in accuracy could occur. One may not want to compound this loss by selecting a model that is knowingly inferior to others just because nodes are uniformly distributed. If the criteria for model selection leads to nodes being non-uniformly distributed, one could also remap these nodes onto a target spatial layout, i.e., make them uniformly distributed while attempting to minimise deviations in the distance between node pairs during the remapping process (see Appendix H).

Specific to the evacuation context, this research focuses on socio-spatial networks not to generate more realistic social networks but to select more realistic induced subgraphs. While induced subgraphs owe a great deal of realism to their original graphs (also called supergraphs), how one selects nodes that comprise subgraphs is also a factor. With socio-spatial networks, as network-theoretic neighbours are predominately spatial neighbours, whenever nodes are selected from contiguous disaster regions, one should expect highly connected induced subgraphs. This holds true whether nodes are uniformly or non-uniformly distributed; however, if nodes are organised into spatially distinct clusters, then whether nodes fall within (or outside

¹⁵² One can illustrate this concept via a Monte Carlo simulation. If one wants to estimate the value of π , for example, one can draw a circle inscribed in a square and then randomly place nodes in the square. The ratio of nodes inside the circle to the total number of nodes (inside the square) will approximately equal $\pi/4$. One then simply multiplies each side of the equation by 4 to find π . In this simulation, if nodes are non-uniformly distributed, then the approximation for π will be poor. Additionally, the greater the number of nodes, the better the approximation, i.e., the more decimal places of π one can report accurately. Inversely, taking into account these conditions, if one knows the value of π , then one can use the ratio between the area of a given circle and square (e.g., $\pi/4$) to estimate the ratio of nodes placed within these shapes.

of) disaster regions is influenced by which side of the boundary their spatial cluster predominately lies. Compared to nodes uniformly distributed, one would find a greater number of social connections within these induced subgraphs, an outcome that would track with population densities varying in the real world.

Hypothetically speaking, if uniformly distributed nodes generate more realistic social networks, but non-uniformly distributed nodes lend credence to the selection of induced subgraphs, then one might ask which of these spatial distributions results in the most realistic induced subgraphs. Alternatively, one could bypass this analysis and spatially remap the nodes, but this time from a uniform to a non-uniform distribution.¹⁵³ Please note that to justify using one spatial distribution over another, one might still need to remap nodes. Indeed, to compare subgraphs induced from networks where nodes are either uniformly or non-uniformly distributed (where uniformly distributed nodes have more realistic network-theoretic attributes), what is really being asked is which of these two sets of subgraphs is most *similar* to a set of theoretically most realistic subgraphs, namely those induced from spatially remapped networks of uniformly distributed nodes. Whether the process of remapping is applied post hoc to network construction (when applicable) or used strictly for analytical purposes, either way, this begs the question of how well one can define and solve this remapping problem.

When nodes are uniformly distributed, this research lays out two paths: one toward embracing simplicity (i.e., calculating prediction accuracy without counting nodes) and one toward greater accuracy (i.e., spatially remapping nodes). In the pursuit of accuracy, while one could draw a distinction between the role space plays in social network construction and the role space plays in facilitating disaster-household interactions and then resolve this distinction by remapping nodes in space, one should consider investing accuracy into the initial spatial construction of socio-spatial networks, as the desired result of creating social networks with non-uniformly distributed nodes would emerge through intuitive mechanisms. Please recall that one can place value not only in the accuracy of outcome measures but also in the accuracy of representing mechanism schemes that bring about social networks, i.e., as a means to reproduce social phenomena whether or not they are ultimately measurable.

As presented thus far, the virtue of accuracy is diametrically opposed to simplicity. Indeed, simple models are often cast aside for complicated ones, a decision “motivated by the

¹⁵³ As a starting point, regarding clusters identified within social networks, one would want *intra-cluster* distances to decrease and *inter-cluster* distances to increase. To visualise this relationship, one can (re)draw social networks in Gephi (Bastian et al., 2009) using “ForceAtlas 2” with “LinLog” enabled. This layout is essentially a visual representation of modularity (see Noack, 2009). One would need to take additional considerations into account for the layout to resemble real-world cities.

wish to capture more aspects of reality” (Frenken, 2006). However, complicated models can also be familiar and, in this sense, utilised with simplicity. This concept resonates with a particular KISS strategy (see above) referred to as TAPAS (“Take a Previous Model and Add Something”). As best described by its author (Frenken, 2006),

Too often, models start from scratch with many ‘idiosyncratic’ elements, which take a lot of time to construct and which are hard to communicate. In contrast, models that extend existing ‘core models’ are faster to build and more easily understood by other people. This should, of course, not be taken to mean that experimentation with new models is to be discouraged, but rather that one can take advantage of existing core models to formulate a new robust model in a relatively short amount of time and with a larger degree of understanding by others.

Building on the TAPAS concept, one can appropriate and extend not only models but their previously implemented parameter configurations. These are the configurations analysed and discussed when a model was validated. If one departs from using these well-understood configurations, then one should consider (when possible) re-validating the model. This is particularly important if interactions between “idiosyncratic elements” give rise to difficult-to-predict phenomena. Furthermore, when the goal of extending models is not to improve them but to perform subsequent operations on them, one would find that replicating model parameter configurations makes for succinct experimental design, allowing one to quickly and confidently advance new research.

The *simplicity* associated with selecting readily extensible social network models, which this research understands to include validated parameter configurations, and the *accuracy* associated with selecting induced subgraphs both arise as virtues within this research because social network-disaster interactions, via household locations, are subsequently simulated. Ideally, both simplicity and accuracy coexist in the experimental design, which means one has identified a readily extensible model featuring non-uniformly distributed nodes. Another possibility is that simplicity and accuracy are diametrically opposed, which means one has identified a readily extensible model featuring uniformly distributed nodes. In the latter case, one can pursue accuracy—for example, by spatially remapping nodes, building a new model or re-validating an existing model—or one can embrace the relative simplicity of the existing model.

“How one builds, checks, validates and interprets a model depends on its ‘purpose’” (Edmonds et al., 2019). In this research, constructing the social network model is a descriptive endeavour, and then the purpose becomes illustrative when simulating a disaster on it. The

disaster itself is not empirically descriptive nor, for that matter, explanatory or predictive (see Edmonds et al., 2019); the disaster illustrates, in a very controlled manner, different percentages of people than predicted requiring shelter. While the spatial organisation of people, represented as nodes, *could* play a role in social network construction, this research has sought out socio-spatial networks to specifically facilitate this illustrative purpose. With this purpose benefitting from strategies like KISS (Edmonds et al., 2019), if confronted with the choice to make a uniform distribution of nodes more accurate or keep it simple, this research would side with the latter.

In conclusion, the above discussion introduces the fact that after socio-spatial networks are generated, one must then select induced subgraphs from these networks, which become the data used in the research experiments. Having to select induced subgraphs is why this research seeks to introduce socio-spatial networks in the first place. Furthermore, this research maintains that the illustrative purpose of these induced subgraphs should have some influence on how the spatial component of these socio-spatial networks is selected/implemented, i.e., prioritising model accuracy subject to model simplicity, where the model can be readily extended for controlled disaster simulations that produce different induced subgraphs. Toward this purpose, one should not lose sight of other considerations influencing the selection of a socio-spatial model. When selecting a model from those discussed in the literature, one should review the network-theoretic outcome measures and attribute value to those measures based on their validation and contextual relevance. One could further draw confidence from the generative process, as Conte and Paolucci (2014) write, “Causal claims without an account of the underlying mechanisms are possible and in principle fully legitimate, but knowledge of a mechanism makes them much more secure.” Additionally, one would gain assurance from a model that is deeply rooted in the literature, supported by a history of replication and extension as well as evaluation from multiple angles.

Candidate Models

Taking a closer look at several candidate models, although constructing networks with realistic socio-spatial dimensions is commonplace when modelling large-scale, synthetic populations (Butts, 2002), when the goal is to specifically generate social networks using a graph or network generator (see Drobysheskiy & Turdakov, 2019), spatial realism is not often part of model design. This absence resounds in surveys covering scale-free network generators, the most recent being Penschuck et al. (2020), as well as those featuring spatial networks (Barthélemy, 2011, 2018; Hayashi, 2006; see also Boccaletti et al., 2006) and, more

specifically, navigation in spatial networks (Huang et al., 2014; Kleinberg, 2006).¹⁵⁴ Whenever models incorporate population densities, they are typically driven to replicate large-scale networks, where a wealth of empirical data is used to fine-tune the model parameters. These models embrace complexity over simplicity, producing highly “stylised” networks that are not often generalisable. Although reconstructing the most salient, socio-spatial features of these networks would be useful for “toy model” simulations, such an undertaking is beyond the purview of many studies. Notable exceptions include network models proposed by Frasco et al. (2014) and Alizadeh et al. (2016). The former was extended by Wickramasinghe et al. (2018). This model integrates Zipf’s Law for the distribution of city populations with Kleinberg’s optimised distance distribution between nodes, along with a procedure to simulate migration, to create geographically distributed social networks. Setting aside the excellent performance of this model (albeit with some minor caveats),¹⁵⁵ the authors conducted experiments by generating networks with over 50,000 nodes and 300,000 edges, which is arguably larger than necessary for the type of experiments presented within this research. How well their model generates social networks at different scales is not featured in their analysis.

As for network generators featuring a uniform (or random) spatial distribution of nodes,¹⁵⁶ one should consider a host of suitable models beyond those already cited within this research (e.g., Barthélemy & Flammini, 2006; ben-Avraham et al., 2003; Kaiser & Hilgetag, 2004; Kosmidis et al., 2008; Lewis & Rinzel, 2000; Manna & Parongama, 2002; Masuda et al., 2006; Ozik et al., 2003; Penrose, 2003; Rozenfeld et al., 2002; Warren et al., 2002; Waxman, 1988), including those from the ABM literature (e.g., Bouadjio-Boulic et al., 2017; Zachara & Piskor-Ignatowicz, 2016). Two models in this category stand out as particularly noteworthy: the first is proposed by Hamill and Gilbert (2009) in their article, “Social Circles: A Simple Structure for Agent-Based Social Network Models” (herein referred to as the “Social

¹⁵⁴ Other than the Kleinberg model, many other models intrinsically generate navigable, small-world networks (Duchon et al., 2006) or can be modified to do so (Achlioptas & Siminelakis, 2015).

¹⁵⁵ When experimenting with the generated networks, Wickramasinghe et al. (2018) were unable to replicate Milgram’s message-passing experiment. While the networks are navigable, they are not navigable to the same degree as those produced by Kleinberg’s lattice-based model. The authors contend that “[a] more realistic approach would probably still rely mostly on geography, at least until the message reaches the target’s city. Once inside the city the additional clues of occupation, gender, ethnicity, social status, and so on provide effective means for finding shorter paths.” That said, the addition of demographic information would preclude its use as a simple “toy model.”

¹⁵⁶ One should note that in between a uniform and random distribution is a quasi-random distribution (i.e., a low-discrepancy sequence, such as a two-dimensional Hammersley point set). Rarely are networks generated from a quasi-random distribution. Notable exceptions are found in Aldous and Shun (2009) and Butts et al. (2012). Along a trajectory from uniform to random distributions, one should witness the formation of subtle clusters that result in Poisson clumping. The clusters become apparent when evaluating spatial layouts using the Hopkins Statistic (Hopkins & Skellam, 1954).

Circles” model) and the second is proposed by Antonioni et al. (2014) in their article, “REDS: An Energy-Constrained Spatial Social Network Model” (herein referred to as the “REDS” model).

Selecting a Model

While Social Circles describes the spatial formation of social networks through a sociological lens and then translates this description into a mathematical model, REDS describes a spatial network model—what is known within the mathematical literature as a random plane network (Gilbert, 1961) or, more commonly, a random geometric graph (RGG)—and then imbues this model with a sociological interpretation. Both Social Circles and REDS undertake a cross-disciplinary shift, from sociology to mathematics and vice-versa, and while they end in a similar place, they begin with citing different literature: whereas Social Circles draws inspiration from sociology, particularly from the writing of McFarland and Brown (1973), REDS predominately owes its mathematical heritage to continuum percolation theory (Dall & Christensen, 2002; Penrose, 2003). As for methods, Social Circles identifies with ABM and is created using dedicated ABM software, NetLogo (version 5.2).¹⁵⁷ Although REDS does not mention ABM, upon examining a predecessor model (zu Erbach-Schoenberg et al., 2013), one finds not only REDS’ sociological origin but also a citation to Hamill and Gilbert’s (2009) Social Circles as well as a model description that captures the spirit of ABM functioning at a complex level, i.e., when ABM incorporates the cognitive feedback cycle of agents:

[W]e explicitly model the dynamic change of the network as a result of mutual, coevolutionary feedback between the network topology and individuals’ decisions and actions. The model’s behavioural rules are designed such that they reflect certain aspects of human social behaviour. This allows us to understand how individual behavioural tendencies lead to macro-level topology and which factors of this behaviour are important for creating structure observed in the real-world. (zu Erbach-Schoenberg, Bullock & Brailsford, 2013)

Toward another point of comparison, the authors of Social Circles and REDS share an interest in what constitutes realistic social networks. This sentiment, which echoes in the

¹⁵⁷ As described by Hamill and Gilbert (2009), NetLogo is a perfectly suitable software for generating social networks. Another good option would be Repast, which has a library dedicated to social network analysis (Holzhauer, 2010). As for REDS, this model uses the Python package NetworkX, along with other imported packages (namely matplotlib, matplotlib.pyplot, random, math, numpy, and scipy). One can improve the scalability of REDS by implementing a faster version of its RGG algorithm (see Funke et al. 2019).

adjacent literature (e.g., Barnett, Di Paolo & Bullock, 2007; Hamill & Gilbert, 2010), manifests in notable extensions to their respective models. Beginning with REDS, Antonioni et al. (2015) introduce a post-hoc, random rewiring procedure, adapted from Watts and Strogatz (1998), to create networks with a desirable small-world effect. Extending Social Circles, Pfeffer and Carley (2011) also introduce a post-hoc, random rewiring procedure; however, their procedure creates networks with integrated small-world effect (Watts & Strogatz, 1998) and scale-free properties (Barabási & Albert, 1999), effectively decreasing the average path length and increasing the skewness of networks produced by the Social Circles model.¹⁵⁸

One should also examine how these extended models are evaluated. Although both extended versions of Social Circles and REDS employ sensitivity analysis and report pertinent output measures, the authors who extended Social Circles, Pfeffer and Carley (2011), further conducted a side-by-side, quantitative comparison of their model against several other well-cited models. As neither REDS nor its extension underwent a comparative study, one cannot readily position them within the greater literature based on their performance. Given that the extended version of Social Circles can generate spatial networks with multiple, realistic social attributes and does so demonstrably better than other predominate models, such as Watts and Strogatz (1998) and Barabási and Albert (1999), this research comfortably adopts Pfeffer and Carley's (2011) model into the experimental design.

Parameterising the Model

To reconstruct Hamill and Gilbert's (2009) Social Circles, 1,000 nodes are distributed randomly in a unit square. Each node is assigned a "social reach," which is depicted as a circle emanating from each node. From this description, one can proceed to explain edge formation: by way of example, if the circle emanating from node *A* reaches node *B*, and reciprocally, the circle emanating from node *B* reaches node *A*, then an edge is drawn connecting nodes *A* and *B*. As for assigning nodes different social reaches, Pfeffer and Carley (2011) specifically adopt what Hamill and Gilbert (2009) term the "elitist" configuration. This configuration involves dividing the 1,000 nodes into three groups, where 700 nodes are assigned a small social reach, 200 nodes are assigned a medium social reach, and 100 nodes (the elite) are assigned a large social reach. More specifically, Pfeffer and Carley (2011) assign the small, medium and large social reach groups a radius of 0.04, 0.07 and 0.12 respectively.¹⁵⁹

¹⁵⁸ Skewness is most pronounced in the scale-free, preferential attachment model proposed by Barabási and Albert (1999).

¹⁵⁹ This deviates from the approximate values of 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 used by Hamill and Gilbert (2009).

The NetLogo code used by Hamill and Gilbert (2009) is freely available for download as supplemental material for their later book, *Agent-Based Modelling in Economics* (Hamill & Gilbert, 2016).¹⁶⁰ After downloading the code, specifically the “GeneralModel.nlogo” file from Chapter 4, it was then modified to include a third social reach group (the provided code includes only two groups) and the social reaches were subsequently adjusted to reflect the values prescribed by Pfeffer and Carley (2011).

A rewiring procedure was then introduced—one that favours high-degree nodes as the target of rewired edges. Following Pfeffer and Carley (2011), “The number of times a node k is in the urn is a power function of the degree d_k ”:

$$f(d_k) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } d_k \leq \bar{d} \\ (d_k - \bar{d} + 1)^x & \text{for } d_k > \bar{d} \end{cases}$$

Lastly, one should note that unlike in Hamill and Gilbert (2009), where the model space is a torus (i.e., the default NetLogo setting), the model space in Pfeffer and Carley (2011) does not have a cyclic boundary, which is preferable for this research. When overlaying a disaster that can shift and magnify across the spatial landscape but not wrap around it, so too should the affected underlying network abide by the same spatial logic.

Modelling Who Requires Shelter

Each shelter assignment strategy employed within Chapter 5 uses different data. This includes (1) predicted probabilities of people requiring shelter (used by the static prediction strategy) and (2) streaming binary “yes” or “no” labels that indicate whether people require shelter (used by the real-time batch strategy and the dynamic prediction strategy). When comparing strategies, their relative effectiveness might depend upon how well these different types of data, i.e., those representing predictions and those representing observations, correspond by the end of an evacuation.

For purposes of conducting experiments, one can create observed data from predicted data via an urn model. Balls representing “yes” and “no” labels are placed within urns in a ratio proportional to each person’s probability of requiring shelter. One then randomly draws once from each urn. Applying this method to a great number of people and/or repeating an experiment multiple times ensures that observations are on average good approximations of

¹⁶⁰ As noted in the book’s copyright notice, “Some of the material on social circles presented in Chapter 4 was previously published in 2010 in the journal *Emergence: Complexity and Emergence* by Institute for the Study of Coherence and Emergence and remains their copyright.” This is referring to Hamill and Gilbert (2010). The supplemental code is found here: <https://cress.soc.surrey.ac.uk/web/publications/books/agent-based-modelling-economics/more-information>.

predictions. To simulate cases where observations deviate from predictions, one could skew the ratio of balls representing “yes” and “no” labels within urns by different percentages. As people requiring shelter are part of a social network, how one skews the ratio of balls within urns—whether people are more or less likely to require shelter and whether this skew affects people equally—will have a bearing on the social composition of induced subgraphs. For this reason, one must further specify and evaluate different ways predictions could go awry.

As noted above, predicted probabilities are used as direct input for the static prediction strategy. To simulate different ways predictions could go awry, this research alters these predicted probabilities. The new probabilities are no longer predictions and are not intended for use by the static prediction strategy—this strategy is “static” and not revisable. The new probabilities serve as an intermediary construct from which binary labels for the real-time batch strategy and dynamic prediction strategy are derived. These binary labels are then streamed, so strategies using these labels are said to operate in real time or dynamically.

The concept of prediction accuracy used by this research is also tied to the above-mentioned relationship between predicted probabilities and new probabilities. Excluding those people who are outside the path of simulated disasters (whose probability never exceeds zero), this research measures accuracy as the percentage of people within the socio-spatial network whose predicted probability does not require reconsideration or revision.

Shifted Geographic Locations

One way to model a shift in the geographic location of a displacement area is to construct a simulated environment large enough to accommodate where a predicted displaced area is both present and absent. Within this simulated environment, one controls prediction accuracy by varying the geometric overlap/intersection between predicted and actual displaced areas. This is possible, as discussed earlier, because people are uniformly distributed. Although one could construct a model focusing on a cropped view of the geometric intersection, this research models the overall shift pattern, which better captures vector qualities (shift direction and magnitude) fundamental to describing a shift in geographic location. This approach also ensures that as this shift occurs, the number of people requiring shelter remains the same.

Furthermore, this research does not model the displaced area with a smooth gradient of probabilities. Alternatively, the displaced area is subdivided into three bands/regions, each representing a unique probability of people requiring shelter. Modelling the shift in geographic location is accomplished using a geometric translation, where the displaced area moves parallel

Figure D

Geographic Prediction and Accuracy *Rotational Shift*

100% Correct

Reduction in Predicted Displaced Area from *Rotational Shift*

80% Correct

60% Correct

40% Correct

20% Correct

to the direction of these bands. This allows the research to isolate and model a shift in location as opposed to a shift in magnitude.¹⁶¹

The model used to generate this data was constructed using the following steps. First, the research generated 50 networks, each containing 1,000 nodes randomly placed within a unit square. For each network, a circle was inscribed within the unit square, of which half (a semicircle) was designated as a displacement area (see Figure D). Within the semicircle, three concentric bands/regions were constructed whose arcs divided the radius of the semicircle into three equal segments. From the outermost semi-annular region inward, probabilities were set to 90%, 60%, and 30% displacement respectively.¹⁶² As these regions have rotational symmetry, the research simulated inaccuracy by noting the starting position of the semicircle (the prediction) and then proceeded to rotate the semicircle so that different percentages of the translated geometry overlapped this starting position. In this way, the research simulated 100%, 80%, 60%, 40%, 20%, and 0% prediction accuracy. After each translation, the urn model was applied to generate binary “yes” and “no” labels, and the streaming order was randomised. Of course, as discussed below, geometric translations are not the only way to simulate a prediction going awry.¹⁶³

Randomised Geographic Locations

While proximity to a disaster is a catalyst for displacement, with respect to the relationship between displaced people, what if this relationship is itself not characterised by

¹⁶¹ If the geometric translation is perpendicular to the three bands, then for every unit of distance shifted, not only would an exchange occur between those with a zero probability of displacement and those with some probability of displacement, but proportionately, given three geographic areas, twice this number of households would additionally switch between different probabilities (greater than zero) within these geographic areas. This seems more aligned with a change in magnitude.

¹⁶² As most people within the model are not within the displaced area, in order to simulate more people requiring shelter, the outermost and largest semi-annular region was set to 90% probability, the greatest of the three probabilities used in this research. By making the semicircle as large as possible, the number of people requiring shelter was also increased. Please note that although people close to the boundary (particularly close to the corners of the unit square) have fewer neighbours and thereby have a slightly different ego network than everyone else, no matter how the semicircle is rotated, the same number of people sharing the same boundary condition are enclosed. If one were to employ a linear translation instead of a rotational translation, then one would have to carefully describe boundary interactions and avoid the corners of the unit square by a set distance (greater than the large “social reach”).

¹⁶³ As for another geometric translation, one could simulate a change in magnitude. For example, given 1,000 people (nodes) randomly distributed within the unit square, divide this square into three regions/bands of equal size. People in each region are ascribed a probability of displacement: 50%, 30%, and 10% respectively. One can then simulate prediction inaccuracies in a stepwise fashion by increasing the total number of displaced people in each region by 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, and 100%. Alternatively, one can increase the total number of displaced people in each region by 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 people, i.e., increase displaced people by a given value (in this case by 20) instead of by a percentage. Depending upon which approach is used, although the total number of displaced people would be the same, the ratio of displaced people across the three geographic regions would differ.

socio-spatial proximity? In other words, if socio-spatial patterns of displacement exist, they may be obscure or unpredictable, or they may also simply not exist. One way to model a phenomenon that is (or appears) unpredictable is by randomising it (Eagle, 2005). Applied to the context at hand, this research thereby proposes simulating the dispersion of socio-spatial clusters. This research refers to this dispersion by the process used to generate it, i.e., “randomisation.”

For each of the 50 social networks (described above), divide the unit square into three equal-sized regions, and set the probability of displacement within the respective regions to 100%, 50%, and 0%. By way of example, this research simulated the above prediction being 80% accurate by randomly selecting 20% of the nodes and discarding their prediction. This prediction was then replaced with a 50% probability of displacement, i.e., the mean probability across all regions, which ensured that approximately the same number of people were displaced.

The research then simulated the prediction being 60% accurate by randomly selecting another 20% of the nodes (excluding those previously selected). Once again, their predicted probability was discarded and replaced with a 50% probability. This procedure was repeated three more times to simulate predictions being 40%, 20%, and 0% accurate. After the last round, the displaced area should appear completely random, meaning that one would flip a fair coin to determine each node’s binary “yes” and “no” labels for needing shelter. When node predictions are partially randomised, then as before, one draws from an urn to generate the binary labels.

Appendix E

Measures of Success

Developing Metrics

When graph or hypergraph partitioning is used to generate shelter assignments, how well do their associated metrics, edges cut (EC) and communication volume (CV), align with perceptions of success? Are other metrics or combinations of metrics better tailored to this unique context? Concerning people who become displaced, one might not only seek to understand their perceptions of success but also to elicit their participation in shaping the outcome. This begins with asking open-ended questions designed to reveal what is socially meaningful to people as individuals, family members, and members of society when confronted with different evacuation scenarios. In turn, these inquiries inform the registration process. More specifically, alongside registering social network connections, each registrant could also attribute value to one or more social objectives that have been incorporated into a partitioning function. As each disaster results in a different subset of registered people becoming displaced and requiring shelter, what is socially meaningful or valuable within emergency shelters is prone to change, i.e., depending upon which cultures and demographics are represented within shelters. The challenge becomes how to incorporate into an evacuation plan the unique views of displaced people alongside the views of other stakeholders, such as emergency management and host communities. Bearing on how to weigh these views, one might argue that displaced people are more likely to comply with recommendations that they themselves design or influence. Lending credence to this idea are collaboration-based research and design methodologies, namely *participatory design* and *action research* (Frauenberger et al., 2015), which have been successfully applied to studies and interventions involving vulnerable people, as exhibited in the context of forced migration (see Duarte et al., 2018).

Through this lens, the research posits several broad and guided questions into what defines and brings about a successful, socially oriented evacuation. This research further supports these questions by developing new metrics that would contribute to a more comprehensive analysis. With these new metrics, one can better evaluate the consequences of graph or hypergraph partitioning as well as reimagine what partitioning might become.

In what ways are displaced people benefiting? Apart from minimising the number of people separated across shelters, one might also want to minimise the number of communities separated across shelters. This research will take a closer look at developing a community metric. Emphasis is placed on steering clear of pitfalls that may accompany this metric within the partitioning context.

Are certain displaced people benefitting more than others? While encountering all of one's displaced social acquaintances at an emergency shelter might offer peace of mind, through the narrow lens of attempting to quantify emotional support, one might argue that for any given person, increasing his or her number of social acquaintances also leads to redundancy within that person's emotional support system. While redundancy of this kind would typically be viewed positively, one should ask whether this is occurring at the expense of other displaced people having little to no social acquaintances at emergency shelters. Shifting attention to those with the fewest connections, this research proposes an "aloneness" metric.

From displaced people's viewpoint, are they assigned to the best shelter? One should not overlook how success is perceived. While displaced people may not be privy to details used by emergency management to recommend shelter assignments, if wireless communication is intact, then displaced people might very quickly realise that a greater number of their social acquaintances are located at a different shelter and thereby conclude (all else being equal) that emergency management failed them. This could happen, for example, if the shelter assignment objective is to minimise the total number of edges cut—an optimal solution might require sacrificing edges of certain displaced people disproportionately to those of others. To capture this perspective of success, this research will introduce a "rather be somewhere else" (RBSE) metric.

How well can emergency management predict who will be together at a shelter? This is one of many questions related to prediction accuracy.¹⁶⁴ Apart from prediction quality being a retrospective indicator of one or more underlying procedural problems, if prediction quality can be assessed in near real time, and if a prediction strongly corresponds with what is actually unfolding, then perhaps emergency management can act upon this prediction. For example, if emergency management has confidence that certain groups of displaced people will arrive at shelters, then they can prepare and more quickly mobilise resources of particular value to those groups. This research therefore proposes a "predicted together" metric.

These new metrics are more thoroughly explored in the subsequent text, followed by how they can be incorporated into an experiment design. The appendix concludes with a discussion of research gaps and topics for future study.

¹⁶⁴ While asking how well emergency management can predict "who will attend a specific shelter" is generally the better question, asking "who is together at a specific shelter" is more aligned with the social orientation of this research.

Problems With Community Metrics

In the study of complex networks, detecting communities is a fundamental problem. The most recognised and widely cited method used to detect communities is known as modularity (Girvan & Newman, 2004; Newman, 2006b). Despite that modularity “has proven itself fairly reliable and largely in accordance with human intuition in the literature” (Bader et al., 2018), several shortcomings are documented. Modularity tends to either merge together small communities (Fortunato & Barthélemy, 2007) or otherwise split apart large ones (Lancichinetti & Fortunato, 2011; see also Lu et al., 2020). The literature refers to the former tendency as the resolution limit problem (Fortunato & Barthélemy, 2007). Additionally, studies indicate that certain types of graphs have arbitrarily inflated modularity scores, such as random graphs (Guimerà et al., 2008) and tree-like graphs (Bagrow, 2012), as well as sparse graphs (Good et al., 2010; Nadakuditi & Newman, 2012; Reichardt & Bornholdt, 2006a; see also Traag et al., 2013).¹⁶⁵

Modularity, as originally conceived, identifies non-overlapping or disjointed communities, whereas many real-world communities are overlapping. While many surveys feature community detection (e.g., Dao et al., 2020; Mkhitarian et al., 2019), which includes the overlapping variety (e.g., Jebabli et al., 2018; Xie et al., 2013), a survey conducted by Chakraborty et al. (2017) focuses specifically on metrics for community analysis. This is noteworthy as not all metrics have been integrated into community detection methods/algorithms and therefore may not appear in the aforementioned surveys. According to Chakraborty et al. (2017), the most promising overlapping community metric is known as Q_{ds}^{ov} (Chen, Kuzmin & Szymanski, 2014).¹⁶⁶ This is an overlapping version of another metric, modularity density (Chen, Nguyen & Szymanski, 2013, 2015), which significantly mitigates the resolution limit problem (see also Botta & del Genio, 2016; Chen et al., 2018), although

¹⁶⁵ Other shortcomings concerning networks are presented by Good et al. (2010). While certain shortcomings are explainable (see Riolo & Newman, 2019), many remain outstanding.

¹⁶⁶ While Chakraborty et al. (2017) refer to this metric as Q_{ov}^{MD} , the original authors, Chen, Kuzmin, and Szymanski (2014), refer to this metric as Q_{ds}^{ov} . This research adopts the latter nomenclature. To measure overlapping communities with Q_{ds}^{ov} , one must first detect overlapping communities. The authors of Q_{ds}^{ov} ran their social networks through SLPA (Xie & Szymanski, 2012). While this overlapping community detection algorithm is parameter-free and performs well (Xie et al., 2013; da Fonseca Vieira et al., 2020), SLPA also outputs values at 10 different resolution thresholds, which adds a layer of complexity when interpreting results. Taking a simpler approach, one could implement, for example, OSLOM2 with Infomap (Lancichinetti et al., 2011) and then pass a singular set of results (those generated at the lowest hierarchical level) into the Q_{ds}^{ov} algorithm. One might also consider a host of different algorithms to identify overlapping communities (e.g., Bandyopadhyay et al., 2015; Hou et al., 2016; Jin et al., 2016; Long & Liu, 2019; Whang et al., 2016).

shortcomings remain with certain network structures, such as tree-like graphs (Botta & del Genio, 2016) and sparse graphs (Botta & del Genio, 2016; Chen et al., 2018).¹⁶⁷

As overlapping community metrics are often extensions of non-overlapping community metrics, they likely subsume both the benefits and drawbacks (with the latter extended but not rectified) of their original formulations. As a result, one can typically gain additional insight into the performance of overlapping community metrics by drawing upon new research extending from their deeper, non-overlapping algorithmic roots. Following this tradition, metrics such as Surprise (Aldecoa & Marín, 2011, 2013), and Potts-based Hamiltonians (e.g., Ronhovde & Nussinov, 2009a, 2009b), have been extended to handle overlapping communities (see Lee et al., 2017; see also Darst et al., 2013).¹⁶⁸ While these overlapping community metrics improve upon modularity (at least in addressing the resolution limit problem), they also have their own limitations, traceable in part to emerging research concerning their predecessor metrics (see Xiang et al., 2018; see also Hu et al., 2011; Ronhovde & Nussinov, 2012). Another community metric that avoids the resolution limit problem, Conductance (Leskovec et al., 2010), also known as the normalised cut metric (Shi & Malik, 2000; see also Chakraborty et al., 2017), also has an overlapping version (Chen, Kuzmin & Szymanski, 2014), which likewise channels critique (see Bagrow, 2012). The metric, MaxPerm (Chakraborty et al., 2014, 2016b), which is touted as one of the better non-overlapping community metrics (Chakraborty et al., 2017), is yet another example of a metric extended to measure and detect overlapping communities (Chakraborty et al., 2016a). At the time of writing, perhaps the greatest limitation for all non-modularity-based metrics, with MaxPerm and its overlapping extension being an exemplar case, is that while modularity enjoys an impressive lineage of thoughtful permutations (see Chakraborty et al., 2017), not to mention being the *de facto* benchmark for new community metrics and shouldering the critique that accompanies this position (see Good et al., 2010), non-modularity-based community metrics are supported by significantly less literature reinforcing their benefits and exposing their shortcomings.

As a concluding remark, measuring communities requires not simply knowing what metrics perform well on average (see Chakraborty et al., 2017) but knowing which metrics rarely (if ever) perform poorly. Indeed, if community metrics are not robust to diverse network

¹⁶⁷ Modularity density also cannot resolve multiple cliques of unequal sizes. This problem is addressed in subsequent literature (Chen et al., 2018). Shortcomings with tree-like graphs and sparse graphs remain outstanding.

¹⁶⁸ Regarding Potts-based Hamiltonians, Darst et al. (2013) extend the absolute Potts model (APM). One should also note that other versions of Potts-based Hamiltonians exist, such as the “constant Potts model” (CPM; Traag et al., 2011) and the Reichardt-Bornholdt (RB) Potts model (Reichardt & Bornholdt, 2004, 2006a; see also Darst et al., 2013). From its conception, the RB Potts model accounts for overlapping communities.

conditions, then one might attempt to select metrics better suited to network conditions found in the application domain.¹⁶⁹ Otherwise, new metrics must be developed.

Problems With Community Metrics Applied to Emergency Shelters

In order to measure the presence of communities within emergency shelters, why should one develop new metrics? Indeed, the last section introduced multiple community metrics, all of which (notwithstanding their limitations) could be directly applied to the context at hand. Answering the above question is not so simple, although one might begin by asserting that research should explore more acute questions. Beyond asking whether communities are present within emergency shelters, one could ask, for example, whether communities are represented within shelters and/or whether communities are kept together within shelters. A more rudimentary answer, however, would qualify the premise not because the research warrants a deeper investigation but because the premise fundamentally misrepresents the research objectives—the goal is more precisely to measure the presence of *existing* communities within emergency shelters, and in this respect, one must acknowledge that current metrics are simply not designed to perform longitudinal comparisons and thereby should be extended.

If one attempts to measure existing communities directly within emergency shelters, then one must be aware that social connections found within emergency shelters are subsets of those that exist (i.e., one is operating under a limited view of the existing network). These subsets, although derived from a complex network, could manifest as simple network structures (e.g., complete graphs)¹⁷⁰ or as deeply fragmented network structures (e.g., nodes connected by a single edge). Despite these network structures potentially representing communities, they may not lend themselves to being identified as such. Thus, departing from how certain network structures might confound community metrics (see the previous section), this research will now detail how certain network structures become problematic when evaluated as a subset of a larger network. While the network structures under review are undeniably special cases, one must also recognise that evacuations are themselves unique circumstances, and as to be demonstrated, capable of bringing about these special-case network structures.

¹⁶⁹ For a parallel argument concerning community detection (instead of community metrics), please see Dao et al. (2020), Peel et al. (2017), and Schaub et al. (2017).

¹⁷⁰ Simple network structures are instances, strictly speaking, where “every node would be indistinguishable from any other node” (da Fontoura & Rodrigues, 2009). A complete graph is but one example.

Problems With Complete Graphs

When the sizes of nonoverlapping, displaced communities are approximately equal to the target occupancies of emergency shelters, graph partitioning (as a shelter assignment strategy) becomes a potent catalyst for the emergence of a unique scenario, one where all people within a shelter know each other. If this occurs, the resulting network structure is known as a complete graph or a single clique (or if using a conformal hypergraph, a single hyperedge). This structure is also indivisible (Newman, 2006b), i.e., the modularity matrix has no positive eigenvalues (see also Fasino & Tudisco, 2014).¹⁷¹

With modularity taking values in the interval, $[-1/2, 1]$ (Brandes et al., 2008) real-world social networks typically have a modularity score between 0.3 and 0.7, with higher scores being rare (Newman, 2006b; see also Arqué & Nettleton, 2012). The real-world social network, “karate club,” for example, has a modularity score of 0.419 (Newman, 2006b). When everyone knows each other within an emergency shelter (i.e., given a complete graph or single clique), one might expect an incredibly high community score, but to the contrary, modularity would return a trivial value of 0. In contrast, if three equal size groups/cliques of people are randomly assigned to one of three shelters, then on average the modularity score would be rather high—for k disjointed cliques of size n , the score would be $1 - 1/k$ (Brandes et al., 2008) or approximately 0.667. Knowing everyone within a shelter should result in a higher community score than knowing a third of the people; at least with modularity, however, this is not the case.

Assuming keeping communities intact is desirable, although a scenario where everyone knows each other is arguably not the absolute best outcome,¹⁷² such a scenario still features a potentially very large community being reunited, and at the very least, this community should be detectable. This research will now examine another network structure representing a community, one that is more subtly problematic but more credible and pervasive in its formation.

¹⁷¹ Newman (2006b) further contends that the absence of positive eigenvalues is a sufficient but not necessary condition for indivisibility. Another example of an indivisible network would be star graphs (Fasino & Tudisco, 2014; de Montgolfier et al., 2011). Unlike complete graphs or cliques, star graphs are not understood as communities.

¹⁷² For example, people within this shelter might have stronger affiliations with people within other shelters. Additionally, the successful preservation of communities within this shelter might have occurred at the expense of dissolving communities within other shelters.

Problem With Sparse Graphs

Social networks are typically sparse (del Genio & Bassler, 2011). As people within any given emergency shelter are a subset of the displaced population, and as this displaced population is a subset of the greater population, one has reason to believe that social networks within emergency shelters are likely sparser than those typically studied. More precisely, if people visit random shelters or even nearest shelters, then their social network would likely be dispersed across multiple shelters. Graph partitioned shelter assignments, on the other hand, tend to cut inter-community edges (as few as possible), leaving intra-community edges largely intact. Notwithstanding this intervention strategy, social networks are still prone to being exceptionally sparse, that is, as a function of people becoming displaced.

As networks become sparser, they undergo a phase transition, where communities that were once detectable (or recoverable) become undetectable (or unrecoverable). This phenomenon is observed when attempting to detect communities, for example, with modularity (Decelle et al., 2011; Nadakuditi & Newman, 2012; Reichardt & Leone, 2008), Surprise (Xiang et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2019) and Potts-based Hamiltonians (Reichardt & Bornholdt, 2006b). Regarding the latter, the literature further differentiates between easy and hard phases of community detection (Hu et al., 2011). Similarly, general stochastic block models (SBM), which are random graph models often employed to study communities, also exhibit a phase transition (Decelle et al., 2011). In this case, the literature distinguishes between exact and partial recovery of communities (Abbe, 2018; Abbe & Sandon, 2015). This vein of literature also introduces concepts such as minimum effective density (Vinayak et al., 2014b) and minimum relative density (Jalali et al., 2015, 2016), which are both largely defined by taking the product of the number n_i of people within each community and the probability p_i that these people are connected (Beckus & Atia, 2019). Keeping in mind that community sizes n_i within real-world social networks are heterogeneous with a distribution that tends to follow a power law (Arenas et al., 2004; Clauset et al., 2004; Guimerà et al., 2003; Radicchi et al., 2004), which in principle holds true for overlapping communities (Palla et al., 2005), one can reason that as social networks become sparser (or partially obfuscated; see Vinayak et al., 2014a), all else being equal, the smallest communities are most immediately prone to become undetectable. This occurrence does not mutually exclude larger cliques (albeit smaller than originally conceived) from individually occupying other shelters, which as previously discussed, are also undetectable community structures.

Toward a Solution

Against a backdrop where overly homogeneous and overly sparse network structures defy community detection, one might reassess the definition of community as it is commonly understood. Communities are intuitively defined as groups of nodes that are more densely connected with each other than with the rest of the network. Referencing this definition, Girvan and Newman (2004) designed modularity to measure the strength of division between groups of nodes. Other researchers, however, have argued “that the natural intuition for community does not necessarily imply increased link density” (Shang et al., 2020). Additionally, modularity can produce results inconsistent with its own definition of community, suggesting that a deeper mechanism is at play: “[C]ounter to our intuition, measures such as modularity, while ostensibly rewarding densely interconnected groups, can actually be optimised solely through the discovery of bottlenecks, and it is not necessary for the discovered groups to be internally dense” (Bagrow, 2012). Apart from whether the presented definition of community is contentious, or whether divergent formulations of community are subsumed (out of necessity or convenience) under an agreed-upon definition (see Reichardt & Bornholdt, 2006b), one should also recognise that oftentimes “communities are not defined at all, but are a byproduct of the [community detection] procedure” (Fortunato & Castellano, 2007; see also Darst et al., 2013).

If community detection algorithms measure the strength of the division between nodes, and complete graphs are indivisible network structures, then complete graphs should not be recognised as communities; however, as community detection algorithms implicitly (re)define what is meant by community, given the breadth of algorithms available (e.g., Dao et al., 2020; Fortunato & Castellano, 2007; Schaub et al., 2017), finding one conducive to identifying complete graphs as strong communities is not implausible. That said, pursuing a broader definition of community is overshadowed by what this approach cannot achieve: as networks become sparser, one possibility is that former communities are reduced to two nodes sharing a single edge, which as a network structure, does not (and should not) constitute a community by any definition.

Another way to approach the problem of measuring communities, and one that lays the groundwork for a more comprehensive solution, is to ask which communities are *absent* within any given emergency shelter. Without knowing which communities displaced people belong to on day-to-day basis—namely, by running a community detection algorithm on a representative sample of the greater population—one cannot evaluate which communities are absent within emergency shelters. In other words, if one includes not simply displaced people

within and across emergency shelters but also people (displaced and non-displaced) who register as potentially needing shelter as well as the acquaintances of those who register, then the generated network might begin to exhibit differentiation between groups of nodes, allowing for meaningful community detection. A relevant community metric might then capture the extent to which day-to-day communities are kept intact or split apart (i.e., are present or absent) within and across emergency shelters.

The goal here is not to detail a comprehensive solution but to add a cautionary note to the simple approach of measuring communities directly within emergency shelters. As with many contexts, reporting a high community score within emergency shelters remains desirable; however, one should also acknowledge that reporting a low community score is not necessarily undesirable because, as demonstrated, a low community score may not reflect communities that are in fact present.

Aloneness Metric

Considering various people's roles and the redundancy of these roles in a social support system, from a given person's perspective, every additional known person would likely increase his or her social support to some degree; however, the usefulness of this support might also not increase linearly but, alternatively, increase with diminishing returns. In other words, if one were to plot a usefulness score (in the y-axis) against the number of known people (in the x-axis), one might expect to see an increasing, concave-down function. Indeed, while increasing a person's friend count from 49 to 50 is useful for that person, increasing a different person's friend count by the same amount but from zero to one friend is from that individual's perspective much more useful. Without empirical evidence, the hypothetical concavity depicting this relationship is unknown, and even with evidence, the concavity is potentially context dependent. That said, introducing a generalised metric to understand collective edge quality in an unweighted social network is conceptually important, and if only acting as a placeholder until more research is conducted, it would nevertheless offer a much-needed counterpoint to the metrics proposed thus far. If the goal is to optimise for the greatest average quality of edges (not quantity of edges), then the metrics previously discussed are insufficient. In light of this gap, a new metric called "aloneness" is proposed as a useful measure to better understand the predicament of displaced people at emergency shelters.

In order to measure the collective quality of social edges, the following expression is proposed:

$$\frac{1}{(n + 1)^y}$$

where n is the number of adjacent neighbours with whom a node shares a connection, and y is an exponent used to fine-tune the concavity. Within each partition, one can then take the average score to understand the aloneness score within each partition and, subsequently, one can take the weighted average across these averaged partitions to generate a global aloneness score (where the weight is the number of nodes in a partition).

The decision to use $n + 1$ in the denominator is not only to resolve the problem presented by someone who has no connections (thus creating an illegal fraction), but it also avoids having someone with no connections overly skew the partition averages. That said, the y variable can reintroduce steepness within this function and, for that matter, decrease it as well.¹⁷³ By way of example, suppose that a subgroup of three people having arrived at two different shelters is analysed. In one shelter, person ID1 has three friends, person ID2 has three friends, and person ID3 has one friend. For simplicity, this can be represented using the following notation: [3 3 1]. The subgroup from the other shelter contains three people each having two connections, denoted [2 2 2]. Which shelter has a greater (worse) aloneness score? When $y = 1$, the score is the same for both shelters. When $y > 1$, more emphasis is placed on the smaller values, making shelter one “lonelier.” When $y < 1$, the opposite occurs, and shelter two becomes “lonelier.”¹⁷⁴

If the goal is to understand aloneness, then the above method should be employed as stated; however, if the goal is to measure model performance, then dividing the aloneness score after partitioning by the aloneness score before partitioning should be considered. Furthermore, if the aloneness score were used as an objective function, it would essentially replicate (particularly when y is set to a high value) a process that is both interesting in its own right and further clarifies the motivation for this score. That is, instead of greedily assigning people to the shelter with the largest number of people they know, which generally speaking is the most intuitive allocation approach, perhaps greedily assigning people to the shelter with the least number of people they know other than zero people is equally desirable. If this latter approach were realised, then more people at emergency shelters would at least know someone. Using the

¹⁷³ As a point of consideration, the $1/(n + 1)$ penalises someone having very few connections less steeply than having adopted say the natural logarithm in the form $n - e$. As for the y term, setting y to 1.2 seems to generate an aloneness score that aligns with intuition. Of course, more research is needed to better describe the concavity.

¹⁷⁴ Please note that upon introducing another shelter, where one of three people in the shelter has zero connections, then regardless of how many connections the other two people have, when y is greater than or equal to one, the aloneness score at this shelter will always surpass the score of those shelters with [3 3 1] and [2 2 2] connections.

aloneness score as an objective function evokes this process while allowing some trade-offs to occur via adjusting the y parameter. Substantiating an approach that in certain respects is diametrically opposed to the aforementioned edges cut metric, where both can be argued with equal fervour, calls attention to the great spectrum of plausible outcomes and the need for both ethical interpretation and practical experience in order to justify a best scoring metric.

Rather Be Somewhere Else Metric

Knowing who is at each shelter, would a displaced person rather be assigned to a different shelter? In other words, when optimising for displaced people as a whole, certain displaced people's connections might be sacrificed. This raises the distinct possibility that these displaced people might not only have many social acquaintances dispersed across other shelters but perhaps one or more of these other shelters would collectively offer them more social connections than their original shelter assignment. If this occurs, then not only would emergency management have failed those specific displaced people (to some degree), but those people would also perceive this loss.

Unlike aloneness, the Rather Be Somewhere Else (RBSE) measure is a Boolean function—either one has more social acquaintances at a different emergency shelter or not. Another difference is that RBSE derives its score by asking “what if” displaced people were assigned to different shelters, whereas aloneness is concerned with evaluating observable interactions within shelters.

Calculating the RBSE measure is straightforward. For each displaced person who is also acquainted with at least one other displaced person, pretend they are assigned to each of the shelters and calculate the number of connections formed. If the number of connections formed is greater at a shelter other than the one actually/originally assigned to them, then assign that displaced person a value of 1. Otherwise, assign that displaced person a value of 0. After repeating this process for each displaced person, one can then take the average score within each shelter (to compare scores across shelters), followed by taking the weighted average of these scores (where weights are the number of people in shelters) to create a global output measure.

Predicted Together Metric

If one can predict who is displaced and preemptively recommend best shelter assignments, and given that the prediction is incorrect to some degree, such as by

noncompliance or by suboptimal algorithm design, then to what extent are the same people together at shelters as were initially predicted?

To compare a set of people assigned to shelters against a set of people observed at shelters, one can implement the overlap coefficient, also known as the Szymkiewicz–Simpson coefficient (Vijaymeena & Kavitha, 2015). This similarity measure is related to the Sørensen–Dice coefficient (Dice, 1945; Sørensen, 1948; see also Gragera & Suppakitpaisarn, 2016) and the Jaccard index (Jaccard, 1901), which are both generalised by the Tversky index (Tversky, 1977; see also Tolia et al., 2001). The Sørensen–Dice coefficient is a semimetric version of the Jaccard Index, i.e., it does not satisfy the triangle inequality (Gragera & Suppakitpaisarn, 2016), and when applied to Boolean data, is the same as the popular F-score (Li et al., 2020).¹⁷⁵

The overlap coefficient (oc) is defined as the size of the intersection between two sets divided by the size of the smaller set:

$$oc(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{\min(|A|, |B|)}$$

The smaller set will typically be of people *observed at* shelters while the larger set will typically be of people *assigned to* shelters. The reason being, people are assigned to shelters based on their probability of displacement, which means shelter assignments include people who are both displaced and not displaced. A nice feature about the overlap coefficient is that if people observed at shelters are a subset of people assigned to shelters, then the overlap coefficient value is 1.¹⁷⁶

When an evacuation is underway and shelter assignments are potentially updating in real time, one possibility is that despite people being reassigned to different shelters, those same people might be reassigned together. Accounting for this possibility, one can generate a

¹⁷⁵ Two of the most popular similarity measures are F-score and normalised mutual information (NMI). The F-score (also known as the F_1 score or F-measure) is common to machine learning and information retrieval. It measures the harmonic mean of precision and recall (Van Rijsbergen, 1979; see also Powers, 2015). NMI originates from information theory. It measures the mutual dependence between two variables (Danon et al., 2005; Ghosh & Strehl, 2003). One can further define NMI by how it is normalised. For example, McDaid et al. (2011) and Esquivel and Rosvall (2012) advocate for dividing the mutual information by the maximum of entropies, as opposed to the sum of entropies (Rabbany & Zañane, 2017), the average of entropies (Lancichinetti et al., 2009), or the square-root of entropies (Ghosh & Strehl, 2003). Besides for F-score and NMI, other similarity measures include the adjusted Rand index (ARI; Rand, 2012), Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC; Mathews, 1975; see also Chicco & Jurman, 2020), Cohen’s Kappa (Cohen, 1960; see also Liu et al., 2019; Zhang, 2020), element-centric similarity (Gates et al., 2019), etc. Several of these have been modified to measure the similarity between overlapping clusters (see Lutov et al., 2019; Rabbany & Zañane, 2017). For this research, as people cannot simultaneously exist at more than one shelter, measuring the similarity between non-overlapping or disjointed sets is appropriate.

¹⁷⁶ Another way to achieve this “nice feature” is by using NMI (Danon et al., 2005; Ghosh & Strehl, 2003), where mutual information is normalised, more specifically, by dividing it by the minimum of entropies (see Estévez et al., 2009; Martin et al., 2005).

cost matrix that compares the similarity between each set of people observed at shelters and each set of people assigned to shelters. This matrix is then passed through a Hungarian (Kuhn–Munkres) algorithm (Kuhn, 1955; Munkres, 1957) to solve the linear sum assignment problem (LSAP).¹⁷⁷ As the Hungarian algorithm minimises the sum of weights instead of maximises them, one should adjust the similarity values using the matrix $A' = 1 - A$. Taking the one-to-one assignments from the Hungarian algorithm, one can then calculate their weighted average (with the weights corresponding to the number of people at each shelter). This approach is not without precedence. The literature predominantly features running the Hungarian algorithm with F-scores (e.g., Ochs et al., 2013; Samusik, 2016; Virpioja et al., 2011; Yang & Leskovec, 2015; see also Liu et al., 2019); however, one can use values generated from any similarity measure.

Accurately predicting who is displaced should lead to better “upon request” or “on demand” shelter assignments (via static graph partitioning) than receiving the same information dynamically and having to instantaneously generate shelter assignments (via streaming graph partitioning). That said, if the initial prediction is inaccurate—as determined using the above metric—then one might further investigate if not the cause, then the consequences of being inaccurate.¹⁷⁸

Benchmarking Graph Partitioning With Metrics

“When it comes to benchmarking algorithms for network analysis, typical measures of interest are solution quality and running time” (Bader et al., 2018). These measures are used to compare algorithms and ultimately identify which are state of the art for a given application. Whenever the goal is to fairly compare algorithms, one must ensure that (1) the input data, (2) the problem constraints, and (3) the output measures are identical. This research will refer to the collective specification of these variables as a “scenario.”

While one can test algorithm performance on novel scenarios, which entail acquiring or recreating existing algorithms for a comparison study, one can alternatively test algorithm

¹⁷⁷ This can also be solved using the Blossom algorithm (Edmonds, 1965).

¹⁷⁸ An investigation could reveal multiple ways in which predictions are inaccurate. For example, one might find fault with how the predictions are incorporated into a partitioning algorithm or determine that better prediction indicators are necessary. Alternatively, inaccurate predictions could reflect displaced people’s noncompliance with shelter recommendations. In this respect, perhaps a recommended shelter is inconveniently located or, more generally, unsuitable because of factors not considered by emergency management. Technological ease of use or application malfunctions might also result in people forgoing a shelter recommendation. Without knowing the exact cause of the problem, one can still employ corrective measures (as to be discussed) to blunt the consequences of a poor prediction.

performance on commonly cited scenarios, where the output scores (i.e., points of comparison) are already documented. As for establishing state-of-the-art graph partitioning algorithms, one can review and contribute to the “The Graph Partitioning Archive” repository (Walshaw, 2020). Similarly, one can draw upon scenarios and results from the “10th DIMACS Implementation Challenge on Graph Partitioning and Graph Clustering” (Bader et al., 2012) or from articles subsequently citing this repository to benchmark their own algorithms (Bader et al., 2018). Regarding the 10th DIMACS Implementation Challenge, metrics that define the success for graph partitioning include not only minimising edges cuts (EC) but also minimising communication volume (CV) as well as a Pareto scoring scheme that considers the trade-off between each quality metric (EC and CV) and computation work/efficiency (Bader et al., 2012). The 10th DIMACS Challenge also created a forum to benchmark community detection algorithms. Featured metrics include modularity and, referencing criticism with this metric (see Lancichinetti & Fortunato, 2011), a combination of several other objectives (Bader et al., 2012). Please note that community detection algorithms, not community metrics, are being tested and compared.

As underscored by the 10th DIMACS Implementation Challenge, graph partitioning and community detection optimise for different metrics. Research has yet to explore the impact that traditional graph partitioning has on community metrics, where detected communities are a byproduct of optimising for EC or CV. More fundamentally, research has also not explored graph partitioning optimised for community metrics (via tailoring the objective function to maximise community). In other words, while state-of-the-art graph partitioning algorithms certainly exist to measure and optimise for EC and CV,¹⁷⁹ they do not exist to measure and optimise for community or for any of the new metrics proposed within this research.

As graph partitioning necessarily degrades network structure, another upper bound point of reference is the state of a network prior to partitioning. One metric that accounts for this concept is fraction of edges cut, where the number of edges cut (EC) is divided by the total number of edges prior to partitioning. One can employ this same principle to develop a community metric (see above). On the other hand, metrics such as CV and RBSE only make sense in a partitioned context.

¹⁷⁹ The 10th DIMACS Implementation Challenge is concerned with static, not streaming, graph partitioning performance. Theoretically, static graph partitioning should outperform streaming graph partitioning, so one can benchmark how streaming graph partitioning performs relative to what is possible retrospectively (i.e., the EC and CV scores from the very best static graph partitioners). As for establishing benchmarks related to what is possible in real time, please see Appendix C for information on state-of-the-art streaming graph partitioners.

Two other benchmarks are also worth considering. First, one can assign displaced people to nearest shelters, followed by outputting scores associated with given metrics. These scores can then be compared against those derived from graph partitioning. One can simulate nearest shelter assignments with geospatially generated social networks; however, the location of shelters becomes another variable that influences results. Lastly, one can assign displaced people to random shelters, followed by once again outputting scores as a point of comparison. The significance of nearest shelter assignments and random shelter assignments are discussed in the Portland study (see Chapter 2).

Discussion

This research is specifically an intervention study, not an observational study. The presented metrics are therefore designed not only to record what happens during a simulated experiment, which is useful for analysing model performance but also to provoke a forward-thinking discussion, one that takes place before any experiment is conducted, into the imagined outcomes of intervention and how they then shape the intervention itself.

The chapter opens with several questions that if answered would inform better shelter assignments. Toward answering each question, this research identifies but a single factor or perspective, one of many that would contribute to a comprehensive answer, and details how to represent or begin thinking about it as a measurable phenomenon that can be further incorporated into experimental studies. The proposed metrics, in turn, lay a foundation for a more productive discussion of what constitutes successful shelter assignments. Indeed, the proposed metrics speak to challenges regarding, for example, how to formulate a metric (see community metrics) and how to resolve compatibility issues between metrics (see aloneness metric), not to mention challenges regarding how metrics are interpreted, as they may have multiple implications (see RBSE metric) or be explainable in multiple ways (see predicted together metric). What follows are the takeaway points of the proposed metrics, with an emphasis on what is unresolved. This gives way to metrics not yet discussed within this research.

Beyond the confines of preserving social network structure, one can measure social interactions within shelters (e.g., interpersonal trust and cooperative behaviour) as well as what is observed in the absence of social network structure (e.g., anti-modularity). One can additionally consider measuring social resources as distributed through social connections. The discussion then raises ethical considerations that should factor into determining success, including whether the objective function actively promotes self-segregation and whether (or to

what extent) the outcome facilitates deductive disclosure of social preferences, not simply upon displaced people reading a publication about their own evacuation (see Kaiser, 2009; Tolich, 2004) but upon displaced people encountering each other at shelters. Apart from directing attention to metrics that are missing or not fully considered, one can additionally take issue with independently evaluating metrics, which primes a discussion into multi-objective functions. Lastly, research can better define successful metrics by reaching out to multiple actors with surveys and semi-structured interviews, both pre- and post-intervention.

To revisit the metrics already introduced, beginning with community metrics, apart from the hardness of the problem justifying a heuristic approach, with modularity being *NP*-Complete in the strong sense (Brandes et al., 2006a, 2006b), the research expounds upon why community metrics require further development within the graph partitioning context. The research then introduces an aloneness metric, which unlike the community metrics, is not designed to complement but, more pointedly, rebuke the EC metric. To avoid displaced people being alone at shelters, the objective function essentially assigns displaced people to shelters with the least number of people they know (other than to shelters with zero acquaintances). The simple-to-formulate metric, rather be somewhere else (RBSE), stokes its own discord: whether to promote the greatest good or the least harm, and whether to promote success objectively or perceptually.¹⁸⁰ Garnering support for an evacuation protocol might rest upon not only positive but also negative feedback and results, potentially asymmetrically weighed. Lastly, the predicted together metric measures the disconnect between who is expected together and who is actually together at emergency shelters. Having to explain this disconnect moves the discussion beyond algorithmic design. Indeed, even if the gears of optimisation are proficient, a crudely understood and conceived user experience may hinder success.

The metrics presented represent different ways to physically reunify people who have existing relationships. What is not discussed are metrics concerned with making sense of interactions between potentially “unimagined” compositions of people, who even if acquainted have never coexisted at the same time and place. Two additional metrics seem relevant in this respect: measuring interpersonal trust and cooperative behaviour within emergency shelters. While measuring trust is often associated with graph-theoretic modelling (Sherchan et al., 2013), where trust is known to propagate or diffuse through social networks (Ziegler & Lausen, 2005), one might also consider studying trust, alongside cooperative behaviour, using game-theoretic modelling (e.g., Macy & Skvoretz, 1998; Sutcliffe & Wang, 2012), where interactive

¹⁸⁰ RBSE is situated at the intersection of these two ideas.

games are embedded and simulated within social networks.¹⁸¹ A closer look into measuring trust and cooperative behaviour might be particularly relevant in cases where displaced people endure a long stay at emergency shelters or in cases where emergency management provides little to no oversight.¹⁸²

What is also not explored is the concept of keeping people apart at shelters. Using only network structure, one can measure and optimise for “anti-communities” or “anti-modularity” (Chen, Yu & Chen, 2014; Fasino & Tudisco, 2018; Kumar & Dohare, 2020; Lackner et al., 2018; Newman, 2006a; Zhu et al., 2017). Anti-communities are characterised by people who have an opportunity to form a meaningful connection with each other but avoid doing so. The issue becomes whether to minimise anti-communities within shelters. Taking pause to examine a complicating factor, research on the concept of propinquity, beginning with Festinger et al. (1950), has shown that people who often have close encounters with each other generally also have shared experiences, not to mention exposure to similar content and ideas, which makes them more likely to become friends and have common interests. Addressing the above issue, one might first ask whether the reasons for people not forming connections with each other are greater than the effects of propinquity. If histories of past negative interactions were made explicit, such as by introducing negative edge weights with which people could specify others to avoid at shelters, then perhaps one could gain more clarity into interpreting anti-community metrics.

Drawing attention to yet another interesting and untouched dimension of success, one could measure different types of resources embedded within social networks as a function of both their *accessibility* and *relevance* to displaced people at emergency shelters. This research contends that displaced people sharing a shelter have increased accessibility to one another, where intra-shelter encounters become an opportune conduit for the transfer of social resources. While people at emergency shelters are themselves potential providers of social resources—capable of offering emotional support, instrumental support and/or social companionship to others (Agneessens et al., 2006; van der Poel, 1993)—accessibility to less generic and more

¹⁸¹ Graph theory and game theory offer different ways to think about social interactions, such as trust and cooperative behaviour. That said, creating a reliable and predictive model of social interactions using these techniques (or any other techniques for that matter) requires a greater defence than this research is willing to provide. Measuring phenomena that “play out” in emergency shelters for the first time (which is a unique context) is quite different from measuring phenomena that have already played out in people’s everyday lives and then are brought to emergency shelters, e.g., individual connections, community affiliations, etc.

¹⁸² Long-term displacement with little oversight is not the subject of this study. If it were, one might investigate how cooperative behaviour can become productive behaviour, allowing displaced people to collectively accomplish some task or offer some service within emergency shelters. The team formation problem might play a role here (see Lappas et al., 2009; Rangapuram et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2016).

personalised depths of emotional support, accompanied by a willingness of “providers” to mobilise their instrumental resources (see Flap, 2004; Lin, 1999), is not simply a question of who is at emergency shelters but also who is connected at emergency shelters. One can further qualify the value of these connections by distinguishing between accessibility to people and accessibility to resources through people. Just as the aloneness metric redirects the conversation from maximising the total number of social connections to maximising the utility of social connections (as measured across all displaced people), so too are these underlying principles at work in the context of social resources. A shift to maximise the utility of social resources finds voice in Van der Gaag and Snijders (2004):

[M]any alters will give access to the same resources, and although similar resources available from several alters could be seen as a form of help ‘insurance’, usually one alter suffices to solve a certain problem. For cases where multiple alters are useful in providing resources, diminishing marginal returns can be expected from additional alters. It is therefore more critical to assess whether at least one alter is available to provide some given form of resources, than the total amount of alters doing so.

Applying a different lens to these ideas, independent of asking whether any one social connection plays a certain role or has particular significance, one can also ask whether social connections have a collective quality. On this matter, the above quotation implicitly supports access to diverse social resources. While Van der Gaag and Snijders (2004) emphasise that “usually one alter suffices to solve a certain problem,” different social resources could merit greater redundancy, for example, due to their importance or protracted need. Additionally, accessibility to individual or diverse social resources might be reinforced or stifled in the presence of community formation at emergency shelters.

As for determining which social resources are relevant, while a person’s closest friends and family are an invaluable source of support, Granovetter (1973) draws attention to the distinct value of “weak ties.” According to Burt (2001), weak ties are non-redundant social connections that can act as bridges to diverse social resources. The value of weak ties garners further support from a somewhat counterintuitive finding:

[R]ather than consistently rely on their “strong ties,” people often take pains to avoid close friends and family, because these are too fraught with complex expectations. People often confide in “weak ties,” as their fear that their trust could be misplaced is overcome by their need for one who understands. (Small, 2017)

Instead of viewing weak ties as a secondary objective, as connections that potentially emerge at shelters as a byproduct of reuniting strong ties, one might alternatively design for their

emergence. To this end, following Putnam's (2000) recasting of strong and weak ties as respective attributes of bonding (within-group) and bridging (between-group) social capital,¹⁸³ the literature proceeds to demonstrate how one can use network structure to measure these two forms of social capital, either as independent measures (Barnes-Mauthe et al., 2015; see also Lakon, et al., 2008)¹⁸⁴ or as a single, interpolated measure (Ghaffar & Hurley, 2020). This lays a foundation to optimise for displaced people having access to a combination of bonding and bridging social capital at emergency shelters.

A looming concern, however, is that the measured strength of bonding and bridging social capital may belie the value of social resources associated with them. As noted by Granovetter (1973), "Treating only the strength of ties ignores, for instance, all the important issues involving their content." This overreliance on network structure is echoed by Lin (1999) who writes, "[M]y own view is that if it is assumed that social capital attempts to capture valued resources in social relations, network locations should facilitate, but not necessarily determine, access to better embedded resources." Moreover, even if one could point to where social resources are located within a social network, one should avoid generalising which social resources are contextually relevant (c.f., Van der Gaag & Snijders, 2004); for example, specific to evacuations, one might forgo reuniting people at shelters whose social resources are better accessed virtually, or one might reevaluate the effectiveness of particular forms of support when people are exposed to common stressors (see Gottlieb & Wagner, 1991). Indeed, what is missing from this research is identifying contextually relevant social resources,¹⁸⁵ followed by evaluating each person's access to these resources, which is information that could ultimately improve shelter assignments.

¹⁸³ As pointed out by Agnitsch (2003), this dichotomy also surfaces in Woolcock (1998), who distinguished between embeddedness and autonomy, as well as in Paxton (1999), who distinguishes between within-group and between-group social capital.

¹⁸⁴ Specific to bridging social capital, see also Everett and Valente (2016).

¹⁸⁵ For each person registering for an emergency shelter recommendation, one might compile a list of people acting as their strongest bridges (also known as brokers) and ask whether such people would be valuable to them at an emergency shelter. Alternatively, one might compile a list of social resources and ask each person to associate those resources with people in their social network. For the sake of argument (as these are not mutually exclusive lines of inquiry), whereas the former approach is blind to the content of social resources, the latter approach would allow one to represent social resources as node labels or node attributes within a social network. Undoubtedly, people within the same social network may disagree with how people are labelled. That said, if certain people are consistently labelled the same way (i.e., a trend is established), or if certain social resources have a resounding quality, then these labels could fill in missing data and simplify the registration process. Likewise, if a social resource belongs not to an individual but to a community, and a person is specified as representing a community, then one can use label propagation (Zhu & Ghahramani, 2002) or other approaches that solve the node classification problem (Bhagat et al., 2011) to identify other community members as potential sources of social capital. One can also compensate for incomplete data by augmenting networks with latent features (e.g., Hong et al., 2017).

As for overarching ethical issues, bringing together people at an emergency shelter because they identify with a common label—such as a particular religious belief, ethnicity, race, class, gender, political opinion, etc.—is a form of segregation. Within ethical guidelines of not discriminating against anyone seeking shelter (including those who are already homeless), one can debate whether exceptions are merited, such as providing a space for single women, single men, families with children, elderly people, disabled people, people with special needs, etc. As a cautionary note, apart from people identifying with a label and being grouped together as a result, excluding people from a group because they do not “fit” a label is contentious and, at the very least, requires one to further delineate and assess the impact of discriminatory practices. Additionally, self-segregation is often apparent both at the core and periphery of people’s social networks (DiPrete et al., 2011). Whether self-segregation is understood positively or negatively, if displaced people are brought together for the first time because of a label, then shelter assignments are not simply holding up a mirror to the practice of self-segregation; they are actively promoting it. This research is careful to focus on reunification, specifically on maintaining network structures that have an established history.¹⁸⁶

Turning to the serious issue of deductive disclosure, one should thoroughly analyse the repercussions of emergency shelter assignments being traceable by displaced people to a particular metric. More specifically, given the transparency of the metric or combination of metrics selected or selectable, and under the assumption that the underlying algorithm is proficient, would displaced people’s friendships and/or community affiliations not be questioned or harmed if certain people are assigned to separate shelters? To avoid replacing one form of trauma with another, answering this question demands one’s utmost attention and deserves a contemplative study, beyond and independent of this research, at the intersection of psychology and ethics. Findings would further guide which metric or metrics define success. One factor related to traceability is the complexity of the objective function, which this research will now address.

Who ultimately defines successful placement? Having people answer for themselves is different from having people answer on behalf of others. This raises an interesting possibility, that communities instead of individuals or families decide what constitutes a successful evacuation. In turn, how does one resolve trade-offs, if any, between individual, family and communal values during an evacuation? Beginning with each individual balancing his or her

¹⁸⁶ Albeit challenging, as certain demographics might be more prone to requesting a shelter assignment, one can measure self-segregation (Bojanowski & Corten, 2014; Rodriguez-Moral & Vorsatz, 2016) before and after people visit an emergency shelter.

own objectives and compounded by a potential need to accommodate conflicting views of multiple people, one might further consider multiple criteria decision-making (MCDM) using multi-objective optimisation (see Klamroth et al., 2018). This goes beyond an individual assessment of metrics as above presented. For example, one might look to principal component analysis (PCA) to understand the relationship between metrics. One might eventually ascribe different weights to selected metrics or find they are best incorporated sequentially.¹⁸⁷ Furthermore, if upon running a shelter assignment algorithm that produces ill-suited or detrimental results, then one might consider activating a secondary objective function that optimises for a different metric. In other words, one might prioritise metrics.

Lastly, from a position of theorising about untested metrics, what researchers think are effective shelter compositions at emergency shelters may not coincide with what is actually experienced. Indeed, the discussion thus far is largely an evaluative response to anticipated positions, one that leverages basic theorising tools, such as abduction, abstraction and analogy (Swedberg, 2017), and one that is locked into discourse with existing literature, where metrics predominately from SNA are reviewed both to support and give shape to different evacuation objectives. What is not informing effective shelter compositions is the greater feedback cycle between research and practice as bridged by retrospective analysis. This awaits yet another feedback cycle: metrics informed by those who have first-hand experience of displacement at an emergency shelter.¹⁸⁸

While this research could focus entirely on developing metrics, the motivation to proceed at a greater depth is arguably contingent upon demonstrating that one can design a real-time emergency shelter assignment algorithm to optimise for a single (and eventually replaceable) metric. What is presented here is a first look at the technical and ethical challenges of developing metrics, which spans both research and practice.

¹⁸⁷ The latter approach, for example, could incentivise people to evacuate before an impending disaster by first maximizing for community and, following community formation (which is the incentive), then optimizing for a different objective function, such as minimising aloneness. This sequential use of metrics is included here as an example, not a recommendation.

¹⁸⁸ One could pose the following question, particularly to those who have experienced displacement and visited an emergency shelter in the past: Who would you like to encounter at an emergency shelter? The answer could be guided, for example, by presenting different compositions of people (each composed of individuals and/or groups known to a respondent) and asking which composition is preferable. Another line of inquiry could involve asking how satisfied people would be if assigned to emergency shelters with certain people. Notwithstanding the many methodological hurdles, one must foremost consider the ethics of surveying people who have experienced trauma (see Newman et al., 2006; Legerski & Bunnell, 2010; Seedat et al., 2004), specifically post-disaster (see Browne & Peek, 2014; Bruno & Haar 2020; Ferreira et al., 2015, 2018; Mezinska et al., 2016; Van Brown, 2020).

Appendix F

Friends-of-Friends

This research proposes a “friends-of-friends” (FOF) shelter assignment algorithm. As connections within a social network extend far beyond anyone requiring shelter, the name speaks to establishing a boundary in the social network, one that includes not only displaced people’s friends (1-hop neighbours) but also their friends’ friends (2-hop neighbours). Upon qualifying which social connections are prioritised, one can bring into focus the details of this shelter assignment algorithm and what motivates its design.

Algorithm Design Considerations

With uncertainty regarding whether the intermediary friends of people already at shelters will eventually require shelter, one must decide how aggressively to incorporate these intermediary friends into a shelter assignment algorithm. As pertains to assigning a batch of people to shelters, this research proposes to not to forfeit opportunities to directly connect these people to their 1-hop neighbours already at shelters, i.e., to avoid creating “gaps” within shelters using 2-hop neighbours (which may never be filled) when 1-hop neighbours are available. More precisely, after running restreaming FENNEL with displaced people and their 1-hop neighbours already at shelters (with the latter treated as fixed vertices), the algorithm could identify any displaced people who are alone and attempt to reassign them based on their 2-hop neighbours at shelters using a second pass of restreaming FENNEL.¹⁸⁹ Please note that the first pass of restreaming FENNEL should include displaced people who are alone. If one were to remove them prior to the first pass, then one would be left with a smaller batch of displaced people subject to a tighter partitioning imbalance constraint, which would compromise the fraction of edges cut for 1-hop neighbours at shelters and violate the decision to utmost prioritise them.

Turning to the 2-hop neighbour component of this algorithm, a qualification worth considering is that the algorithm does not generate shelter assignments using all of a displaced person’s 2-hop neighbours but only those 2-hop neighbours already at shelters. The motivation for this decision is twofold. First, upon applying this strategy, the likelihood that a displaced person assigned to a shelter will eventually know someone increases. Indeed, in every instance where the algorithm creates a gap in the social network, the person who would potentially fill

¹⁸⁹ For clarity, displaced people who are alone have neither a connection with someone previously assigned to a shelter nor a connection with someone currently being assigned within a batch to a shelter.

this gap is acquainted with *at least* two people requiring shelter.¹⁹⁰ While merely a provisional hypothesis, the more friends one has requiring shelter, the more likely one will require shelter as well.

The second motivation concerns any displaced person who would like to improve their prospect of connecting with a friend. By assigning this person to a shelter with a 2-hop neighbour, while the assumption is that these two people are not acquainted,¹⁹¹ this pairing becomes mutually advantageous as now their assigned shelter, relative to other shelters, has more influence/pull in attracting their awaited friend.

As for another design consideration, one must decide whether to include connections between the intermediary people who may or may not require shelter. If these connections are both included and influential, and if these people later require shelter, then the generated assignments should improve.¹⁹² More realistically, however, not all these people will likely require shelter. Furthermore, the gaps in the social network at shelters might become dependent on multiple people filling them. In such cases, one would have to consider the joint probability distribution of people requiring shelter to fill these gaps, and in this respect, improved shelter assignments could be marred by a decreased likelihood that these improvements come to fruition.¹⁹³ By combining network structure with real-time information, such as people reporting whether or not they require shelter, one could in theory more accurately identify people with a high probability of requiring shelter and include them (along with their connections to each other) within each batch assigned to shelters, i.e., until these people themselves report needing shelter and receive a shelter assignment. Without such insight—*informed by, for example, additional spatial analysis (e.g., the dynamic prediction strategy), demographic analysis (e.g., factor analysis) or social network analysis (e.g., collective classification and/or centrality analysis)*¹⁹⁴—this research would hesitate to propose including

¹⁹⁰ In comparison, for people who would potentially fill the gap created by a 3-hop neighbour strategy, one can only guarantee that these people will be directly acquainted with one person requiring shelter.

¹⁹¹ This research does not speculate whether they should be acquainted, as would concern the link prediction problem (Kumar et al., 2020).

¹⁹² Displaced people without a direct shelter connection, through a chain of intra-batch connections, could indirectly have a shelter preference. Alternatively, intra-batch connections might not be grounded to a particular shelter, but at least these people are more likely to be assigned together.

¹⁹³ These gaps would grow larger in size, for example, if one were to connect not only intermediary people that form 2-hop connections within the currently assigned batch but also intermediary people that form 2-hop connections within previously assigned batches. In turn, the adverse relationship between how much shelter assignments can improve and how likely they are to improve would likely become more pronounced.

¹⁹⁴ For more information on collective classification in social networks, please see Jaafar and Birregah (2017) and Kazienko and Kajdanowicz (2012). As this research has presented methods to partition social networks that represent people's probability of requiring shelter, one can experiment not only with "hard" but "soft" label classification (Galstyan & Cohen, 2007; Zhu & Ghahramani, 2002; cf., McDowell et al., 2009). For more information on networks that are soft or probabilistic, such as those associated with a Markov random field (MRF),

fully weighted connections between people who potentially require shelter during the assignment process. Moreover, one can only identify connections between people who potentially require shelter if these people grant permission to access their social network data (see Chapter 5).

One should additionally understand the implications of prioritising 1-hop neighbours over 2-hop neighbours when that prioritisation categorically changes as a function of time. For the sake of argument, suppose that the algorithm incorporates fully weighted connections between intermediary friends of 2-hop neighbours. In the case, when generating a batch of shelter assignments using these intermediary friends, if results are presumed optimal, then the subsequent batch of shelter assignments must consist of *all* and *only* these intermediary friends. Assuming such conditions are met, the intermediary friends, whose status has subsequently changed from potentially to actually requiring shelter, will form the same subnetwork of connections as they did when they potentially required shelter, which means their shelter assignments will remain unaltered. On the other hand, if these people do not require shelter simultaneously but sequentially, then the subnetwork at any moment in time will look different. As a result, shelter assignments attributed to people before they are actually displaced are subject to being overwritten. The real consequence here is that previous batches of shelter assignments are based on outcomes prone to alteration and, in this respect, these shelter assignments should be presumed sub-optimal. That said, sub-optimal results should not be confused with ineffective results.

Another inherent challenge is that generating shelter assignments using intermediary friends, particularly those with high uncertainty of requiring shelter, could lead to unacceptable variance in partitioning imbalance. This concern is somewhat mitigated when intermediary friends exist temporarily within the algorithm; they could facilitate attracting displaced people who otherwise have no social connections to shelters prior to being removed. The partitioning imbalance is thereby confined to those who actually require shelter but whose assignments are now potentially off-kilter due in large part to this removal. One should not overlook the

please see Farasat et al. (2015). As for centrality measures, one might ask the following question: Can one identify certain people in a social network who if upon requiring shelter would signal that other people are likely to require shelter as well? In the circumstance where people rely on acquaintances to host them in times of crisis (which is not necessarily common), one might examine the role of Bonacich's power-based centrality measure (Bonacich, 1987). Accordingly, from a network perspective, a person in a position of power has acquaintances who in turn have few connections with others. In other words, a person in power has acquaintances who are highly dependent upon them. Therefore, if people in power start becoming displaced and require shelter, then these people would no longer be able to host acquaintances who are highly dependent upon them, which might indicate that these acquaintances are more likely to require shelter as well. Research has yet to explore the role centrality measures can play in identifying people with a high probability of requiring shelter.

downstream consequences: when assigning a subsequent batch of people to shelters, the partitioning imbalance constraint would potentially need to compensate for the previously created asymmetries, which in turn would negatively affect the fractions of edges cut. The question becomes whether one can design a shelter assignment algorithm where hedging future connections outweighs the cost associated with this corrective mechanism.

Proposed Method

Pass each batch of displaced people through restreaming FENNEL. For displaced people with at least one connection, report their shelter assignments. In preparation for influencing the next batch of displaced people, treat these assignments as fixed vertices. For all displaced people with no connections, discard their shelter assignment.¹⁹⁵ Generate a list of their friends and keep only those friends who are acquainted with someone at a shelter. Create an edge connecting each displaced person to their respective friends.

Within each shelter, create a virtual node. One can now create an edge connecting each friend to each virtual node, the weight of which corresponds to the number of people each friend is acquainted with at a shelter. As restreaming FENNEL requires an alpha value, which is formulated using the total number of nodes and edges, one should update the total number of edges to include the sum of all weighted edges to virtual nodes. This update will help keep partitions balanced. One can now run restreaming FENNEL for a second time and report the new assignments. Prior to analysing outcome measures, remove all intermediary nodes, virtual nodes and all edges created for this second pass of restreaming FENNEL.

Proposed Analysis

If the fraction of edges cut improves, one would have to demonstrate that what is responsible for the improvement is not simply a relaxation of the balancing constraint but, moreover, the integration of a FOF shelter assignment algorithm. As a control, one should run the same experiment with the FOF algorithm disabled but with the imbalance set as if the FOF algorithm is enabled.

¹⁹⁵ If using the untempered version of restreaming FENNEL, then one could skip this step and not discard these shelter assignments (see Chapter 4), which might subsequently reduce the number of iterations needed for convergence to equilibrium. This step is included here to future-proof the code, allowing one to eventually add tempering without breaking the functionality of the proposed algorithm.

Conclusion

A fairly conservative method is proposed for this FOF shelter assignment algorithm. A more aggressive approach might identify circumstances where bypassing 1-hop for 2-hop neighbour assignments becomes advantageous in the long run. More conservatively, one could introduce 2-hop neighbours as a tie-breaking strategy for when 1-hop neighbour assignments are equivalent.

If the FOF shelter assignment algorithm proves beneficial, one might find that it also complements another strategy, that of “tempering” across shelters. If imbalance is measured as the difference in percentage between the ideal and actual number of people within each shelter, then one should find the algorithm less accommodating of preserving connections early in the evacuation. A tempering strategy would involve relaxing the balancing constraint early in the evacuation and then tightening it as the evacuation progresses. One can accomplish this with the FOF shelter assignment algorithm.

Appendix G

Additional Results Comparing Node Orderings

Table G1

Node Orderings Ranked By Edges Cut 1 Stream		Dunn's Test, Control = Random	
EC	Node Ordering	Node Ordering	p
88	Leverage centrality HL*	" Local clustering coefficients HL	
94	MCC centrality HL	" Local clustering coefficients LH	
96	Degree centrality HL	" Semi local centrality HL	
"	Load centrality HL*	" Subgraph HL	119
"	Network centrality HL	106 ClusterRank HL	" Community centrality LH
"	Shortest path degree HL	" Communicability betweenness centrality HL	120 DMNC centrality LH
"	Strength (weighted vertex degree) HL	" Current flow closeness centrality HL	" Stress centrality LH
97	Centroid centrality HL	" Current flow closeness centrality HL	121 Average distance HL
"	Effectiveness centrality HL*	" Eigenvector HL	" Barycenter centrality LH
99	Community centrality HL	" Information centrality HL	" Closeness (Freeman) LH
"	MNC centrality HL	" Kleinbergs centrality (HITS) HL	" Closeness (Variant/Latora) LH
"	Topological coefficient LH	" Local assortativity HL	" Effectiveness centrality LH
100	LAC HL	107 Bridging centrality HL	" Geodesic K-path centrality LH
"	Lobby index HL	" Dangkalchev closeness centrality HL	" Lin centrality LH
101	Random	" Decay centrality HL	" Radiality centrality LH
"	Betweenness HL	" DMNC centrality HL	" Shortest path closeness LH
"	Eccentricity LH	" EPC HL	122 Degree centrality LH
"	Laplacian centrality HL	108 Alpha LH	" Laplacian centrality LH
"	Network fragmentation HL	" ClusterRank LH	" MCC centrality LH
"	Shortest path betweenness HL	109 Entropy centrality HL	" Network centrality LH
102	Barycenter centrality HL	111 LAC LH	" Semi local centrality LH
"	BottleNeck centrality HL	112 Political independence index HL	" Shortest path degree LH
"	Closeness (Freeman) HL	113 Topological coefficient HL	" Strength (weighted vertex degree) LH
"	Cross clique connectivity HL	114 Average distance LH	123 Centroid centrality LH
"	K-core decomposition HL	" Markov centrality LH	" Flow betweenness centrality LH
"	Lin centrality HL	" Random walk closeness LH	" K-core decomposition LH
"	Radiality centrality HL	115 Closeness (Variant/Latora) HL	" Political independence index LH
"	Random walk betweenness HL	" Current flow closeness centrality LH	124 Eccentricity HL
"	Shortest path closeness HL	" Information centrality LH	" Subgraph LH
"	Stress centrality HL	" Local assortativity LH	126 Diffusion degree LH
103	Flow betweenness centrality HL	" Network fragmentation LH	127 Communicability betweenness centrality LH
"	Markov centrality HL	116 Alpha HL	" Network fragmentation geodesic distance weighted HL
"	Network fragmentation geodesic distance weighted HL	" Eigenvector LH	128 Betweenness LH
"	Random walk closeness HL	" Kleinbergs centrality (HITS) LH	" Shortest path betweenness LH
104	Bridging centrality LH	117 Dangkalchev closeness centrality LH	129 EPC LH
"	Diffusion degree HL	" Decay centrality LH	130 Load centrality LH
"	Entropy centrality LH	118 Cross clique centrality LH	" SALSA LH
"	Neighborhood connectivity LH	" Leverage centrality LH	133 MNC centrality LH
105	Geodesic K-path centrality HL		

Note. A lower median number of edges cut (EC) is preferable. According to Dunn's Test, three node orderings perform significantly better than random.

Figure G

Node Orderings Compared to Random

Note. The left-most box plot represents a random node ordering. Its median line extends across the figure as a point of reference.

continued

Node Orderings Compared to Random

continued

Node Orderings Compared to Random

Appendix H

Remapping Social Networks Uniformly in Space

One could generate a spatial layout using a graph or network visualiser. The most widely used visualisation techniques draw upon a physical analogy, one of finding minimal energy in a system. According to Hu and Shi (2015), these techniques divide into two categories: the spring-electric model and the stress model. The problem with the former is that “[w]hile the spring-electrical model can be made scalable, it does have the limitation of not encoding edge length explicitly in the model” (Hu & Shi, 2015). To the contrary, real-world, geospatial distances between people in a social network/graph, where distances are defined at a certain time or activity location, could be principally represented using the stress model.

Popularised by Kamada and Kawai (1989), the stress model dates back to Kruskal and Seery (1980). A notable extension was presented by Gansner et al. (2004); their algorithm, Neato, remained state-of-the-art for the better part of a decade (Zheng et al., 2019). Drawing upon multidimensional scaling (MDS),¹⁹⁶ Gansner et al. (2004) introduced a method to visualise pairwise node distances utilising a global, *stress majorisation strategy*. The loss or cost function, *stress*, is a residual sum of squares (Buja et al., 2007), and *majorisation* is an optimisation procedure that “iteratively improves the drawing by considering a sequence of quadratic forms that bound the goal (or stress) function from above” (Dwyer et al., 2009). As MDS requires the construction of a full dissimilarity matrix, distances are derived not simply from an adjacency list but from calculating the shortest weighted distance between node pairs.¹⁹⁷ Since these calculations are computationally expensive, Gansner et al. (2004) further introduced the concept of *sparse stress*, where only a fraction of all pairwise distances are considered. Speaking to this latter concept through the extended methodology, Gansner et al. (2012) added an entropy term to the stress function. In this way, given pairwise node distances from an adjacency list, any node pair with degrees of freedom (i.e., nodes comprising a non-rigid graph structure) are positioned according to maximum entropy, which is optimised when nodes are evenly dispersed subject to edge length constraints. Much of the ensuing literature concerns sparse stress and focuses on reducing computational overhead (Meyerhenke et al., 2015; Ortmann et al., 2016; Zheng et al., 2019). An alternative approach is to approximate a *full stress* solution (Khoury et al., 2012). One should note that social networks tend to exhibit a high clustering coefficient (Newman, 2003; Newman et al., 2002), which in topological terms

¹⁹⁶ For a general overview of MDS, see Buja et al. (2007).

¹⁹⁷ Shortest path distances almost always overestimate the actual distances. As a result, this approach increases the stress, leading to some distortion in the graph layout.

signifies a high density of triangles and thus rigid structures. These structures would be present even in a sparse stress model. When graphs are rigid, one cannot simply introduce another distance criterion (for example, to create a uniform layout) without compromising the encoded pairwise distances.

Literature on graph drawing also includes methods to cope with irregular spatial layouts. For example, graphs can be mapped onto regular grids (Lyu et al., 2019), a process particularly useful for convolution neural network (CNN) implementation (Edwards & Xie, 2016). In a similar vein, Batini et al. (1986) proposed topology-shape-metrics (TSM) as a method to orthogonalise graph layouts. As summarised by Battista et al. (1997), this method has three phases: “The first phase, *planarisation*, determines the topology of the drawing. The second phase, *orthogonalisation*, computes an orthogonal shape for the drawing. The third phase, *compaction*, produces the final drawing.” Although such a method ensures node alignment, the nodes are not uniformly distributed in the unit square. With an emphasis on the final compaction phase of TSM, Yoghourdjian et al. (2016) engage with what one might call a graph “packing problem,”¹⁹⁸ where they independently use optimal techniques and metaheuristics to generate ultra-compact, grid-like graph layouts. Regarding the optimal solution, the problem is formulated as a constrained optimisation problem, where the objective function minimises not only the stress (as discussed in relation to multidimensional scaling) but also the compactness of grouped nodes¹⁹⁹ as well as the aspect ratio (i.e., the proportions of a rectangle containing the layout). While the literature points to other examples of graph drawing techniques that emphasise a uniform distribution of nodes (Davidson & Harel, 1996; Kermarrec & Moin, 2013; Koren & Çivril, 2009), the objective function proposed by Yoghourdjian et al. (2016) additionally attempts to preserve pairwise node distances.

¹⁹⁸ Yoghourdjian et al. (2016) compare their optimisation problem, and specifically the NP-hardness, to that of the rectangle packing problem. Similarly, Freivalds et al. (2001) proposed a packing method for disconnected graphs; however, in this latter case, individual graphs are drawn beforehand and cannot be transformed, including rotated, when packed together in a manner that minimises their collective bounding box.

¹⁹⁹ Following Dwyer, Riche, et al. (2013), the authors use edge compression techniques to form modules, i.e., groups of nodes, as well as new edges between modules that represent aggregated edge connectivity. These techniques simplify a graph without any loss of information. For a closer look at the specific edge compression technique used, see Dwyer, Mears, et al. (2013).

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